

Decolonising Algeria: Domestic Tourism Experiences and Postcolonial Identity.

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid identity is a prominent identifying characteristic in postcolonial literature that focuses on informing and (re)establishing a narrative of historically colonised communities. Colonial influence and assimilation policies play major roles in shifting and altering how identity is perceived and (re)presented by colonised subjects. This alteration is said to lead to the emergence of a newer identity; an identity that carries socio-cultural features from both the colonial regime and the colonised people, however unidentifiable to any of them. The case of Algeria is a significant environment for studying identity (re)presentation and interpretation, especially if investigated from a postcolonial tourism lens. The historical struggle to decolonise a century worth of colonial remnants has proven to be an interesting topic of discussion in the field of postcolonialism. With France's settler colonial presence for 130 years, the French and Algerian identities were in constant contact, which led to the emergence of a new form of identity adopted by Algerians in postcolonial times. Today, 61 years after the Independence Referendum, Algerian identity still displays a form of *Hybridity* and lacks proper (re)presentation throughout Algeria. Tourism, however, has been a chosen outlet to commemorate this hybrid identity by engaging in domestic mobility, and tourists are seeking outlets to learn what makes them Algerians.

This thesis critically examines the colonial and postcolonial (and even decolonial) influences on tourists' behaviour and experiences through the practice of domestic tourism in uncovering and (re)shaping postcolonial identity. While this study is informed by Bhabha's theory of *Third Space* and *Hybridity*, I present a detailed interpretation of tourists' experiences in their pursuit of understanding their Algerian postcolonial national identity. Through a qualitative inductive methodology, this study found that tourists go through the process of locating and reshaping their national identity by engaging in tourism activities at the domestic level. Additionally, this study found that the digital practices performed by travel agencies and travel content creators significantly lead the narrative to decolonise tourism by highlighting the cultural characteristics of the Algerian identity through branding Algeria on social platforms. In turn, tourism is found to act as a medium for Algerian nationals to (re)shape and (re)locate their *hybrid* identity set within a *Third Space* and transcribed through postcolonial underpinnings to brand a decolonised identity.

DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to my parents.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

A PhD thesis is individualising. You write the thesis alone, you gather and analyse data alone, you defend the thesis alone. Yet, claiming that this journey was a solitary achievement would be disingenuous. Along the lines of the analogy of “it takes a village,” I also must say that writing a PhD thesis truly takes a village. While the weight of this thesis was not something I shouldered alone, I would like to acknowledge every person who contributed to this research journey and express my appreciation for their presence.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

PEI	Photo-Elicitation Interviews
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
TA	Thematic Analysis
UNWTO	United Nations World Tourism Organisation
UNWHO	United Nation World Health Organisation
GDP	Gross Domestic Production
WoM	Word-of-Mouth
eWoM	electronic Word-of-Mouth
MENA	Middle East and North Africa
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
ONAT	Office National Algérien de Tourisme
SEC	School Ethics Committee
DMO	Destination Marketing Organisation
MTA	Ministère de Tourisme et d'Artisanat
SDAT	Schéma Directeur d'Aménagement Touristique
SNAT	Schéma National d'Aménagement Touristique

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

French Empire subjected Algeria to 132 years of settler colonialism. The lengthy colonialism sparked sociocultural and political issues within the Algerian community, influencing the Algerian identity to shift from Arab Islamic nationalist characteristics to an identity that carries pre-colonial and colonial cultural identifiers. Due to the continuous contact between different identities - the Arab Islamic and Amazigh identity in North Africa with the French cultural identity - it became difficult to describe and locate the Algerian identity that symbolises the Algerian population. The postcolonial era specifically witnessed a turbulent stage of Algeria's historical development as the Arab Islamic identity collided with the Amazigh identity without properly addressing the colonial remnants of the French assimilated identity, leading to the emergence of a hybrid identity, and causing more disorientation for the Algerian people to understand their identity. The turmoil to identity was sought through a postcolonial Arabisation policy imposed by the Algerian post-independence government and continued the escalation of proper representation of the identity, the culture, and the sociocultural markers of Algeria.

Algeria's post-colonial tourism field sought a great interest in reflecting the national and cultural identity of its people as a way to restore pre-colonial heritage and Algerian community's socio-cultural constituents. Through strategic processes to renovate and promote the tourism sector, there seems to be a significant focus on displaying the Algerians' cultural characteristics and reflecting their uniqueness to attract tourists. One example would be Algerian tourism stakeholders and policy makers prioritising activities where tourists would engage and participate with the host community to learn about local cultural traditions such as making traditional crafts.

With such focus from the tourism sector, it was significantly important to reflect the identity of Algerians for an accurate (re)presentation of what Algeria has to offer. However, there has been little regard from an academic standpoint to investigate the Algerian postcolonial identity within the realm of tourism studies, especially from the tourist angle and their perception and interpretation of identity. Therefore, this thesis addresses the complexities that Algerian tourists face in their quest to uncover, understand, and interpret their hybrid identity through tourism practices and how it is (re)presented on social platforms as an attempt to

decolonise tourism. For Algerians, the issue of identity is closely tied with the socio-political consequences that date back to the period of French settler colonialism in Algeria and the ardent desire for self-determination and decolonisation of the society's (re)presentation. Hence, this research intends to examine the colonial and postcolonial influences on Algeria's current domestic tourism trends and how tourists' experiences are (re)shaped to uncover their national identity.

1.1. Autobiographical Influences and Positionality; An Algerian Female Researcher of Postcolonial Studies

In the present thesis, I am drawing from personal experiences to investigate the inter-influential relationship between Algerian tourists' experiences and national identity awareness and understanding. As an Algerian researcher willing to conceptualise and contribute to Algerian tourism literature, I face complexity in defining and narrating my culture, speaking about what characterises my identity without including colonial alteration to who I am and how I think "what makes me an Algerian". What makes it even harder to know who I am is the fact that my lineage is a mixture of different culturally and socially distanced regions. When asked about my origin, I have always responded that *I am an African, a North African hybrid with roots in Morocco and Algeria*, simply because I cannot articulate what makes me who I am. I always acknowledge my North African roots and the exoticness of my culture without attempting to locate my identity into a specific ethnic, cultural, or national group.

Nonetheless, my background has always triggered questioning my identity and where I belong or if I should belong to a place. Of course, my identity is the outcome of where I grew up, my social interaction with my community, and the social norms I have been exposed to during my upbringing. It is also an inherited façade from French colonial times, deeply intertwined with the French lifestyle. When reading about pre-colonial Algeria, I am amazed by this proud North African community that preached and voiced its identity as a Muslim community under Ottoman rule and its strong position in the Mediterranean basin. It was a golden age for Algeria that was later undermined by the French empire, ensuring to alienate the Algerian community from its societal characteristics and forcibly endorse French customs and lifestyles.

Growing up with my parents, who were subject to French educational training, was further complicating my understanding of identity. My parents are more accustomed to the French lifestyle and were keen to reinforce the French language and customs for my siblings and me. I was too critical of their approach and wanted to break this never-ending colonial cycle. However, there was no escape from the French colonial presence around me in my day-to-day interaction, the language I speak, food etiquette, architecture, and interior design. I started travelling to different cities in Algeria, with distinct cultural norms and customs, hoping to understand my identity and culture. As a domestic tourist consumer, I viewed how tourism is shaped, how local communities interact, and how colonial symbolism and French heritage exist in an independent country. My constant attempts to depict my culture and identity when venturing into novel places brought attention to how France's culture is predominant and deeply rooted. My way to escape this 'colonialism-stained' environment was through a French-free academic path. I studied English language and civilisation at the Djilali Liabes University in Sidi Bel Abbes, Algeria, and got my BA. I later enrolled in an MA course in linguistics and language dynamics at the same university. I learned more about Algeria's linguistic portfolio, the Algerian society's code-switching/mixing patterns, semantics, and visual language. My MA course helped me understand my speech and the frequency of switching from Algerian Arabic to French. I also became more interested in studying visual and linguistic symbols and signs to create meaning. During this time in 2017, I visited the SIAHA International Tourism Exhibition in its eighth edition in the city of Oran, Algeria, as I was willing to visit a new domestic destination. The exhibition welcomed DMOs and tourism experts, displaying their offers in visual panels and brochures to consumers interested in both domestic and international destinations. Upon viewing their domestic offers, I noticed the cultural inclusivity and cultural heritage display as an advertising tool to attract consumers to domestic cultural destinations. As a curious consumer, I desired to understand how other consumers view these destinations, their perception of culture, and how they identify themselves through this symbolism from a postcolonial perspective.

By the end of my MA course in 2017, I was awarded a fully funded scholarship by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research of Algeria to enrol in a PhD programme at a UK university. I conducted a 6-months academic skills course at the Canterbury Christ Church University, where I started my postgraduate journey abroad. When drafting my research proposal, I reflected on my experience in the SIAHA exhibition and my position as a

postcolonial tourist interested in understanding postcolonial domestic tourism trends in Algeria. Diving into the realm of postcolonial tourism studies was a new and exciting academic path, especially for someone with a linguistic background. I gradually started learning about tourism literature, postcolonial theories, and the collision of both fields in enriching literature and bringing more awareness to the Global South studies. As an Algerian researcher, I desired to shed some light on the domestic tourism trends in my country and tourists' firsthand experiences in embracing identity and culture in a postcolonial setting, along with the effects of colonial/postcolonial discourses in the postcolonial national identity (re)construction.

Researching postcoloniality and national identity was triggering, especially as a member of the Global South community in constant pursuit of figuring out and accepting my identity's continuous transformation. However, I find it crucial to investigate tourism trends in a postcolonial setting to demonstrate how colonial influence impacts and shapes the Algerian tourism of today in terms of embracing the act of travelling. The French colonial influence on Indigenous Algerians impacted gender discourse and women's (re)presentation within the community as well. The colonial/postcolonial misogynistic implications of female voices and presence in various societal roles altered Islamic values and fractured the religious beliefs and understanding of gender (re)presentation (Brown, 2018). Such fallacies defied female presence to exercise basic rights such as travelling, which challenged my opinions and experiences as a female tourist and a postcolonial tourism researcher. When conducting this study, I acknowledge gender influence on my perception of tourism within my society and my views as a consumer and a researcher. However, my study carries a broader focus on current tourism trends among domestic tourists without allowing my presumptions and experiences as a female tourist to affect the trajectory of my discussion with the participants. I mainly approach this investigation as an Algerian researcher willing to study domestic tourist and national identity within a postcolonial society that features signs of *Hybridity* and *Otherness* in its meaning-making process.

1.2. Researching Identity and Postcoloniality

A nation; a named human population sharing an historic territory, common myths and historical memories, a mass, public culture, a common economy and common legal rights and duties for all members (Smith, 1991, p.14). The classical definition of a nation embodies the core collective constituents of a population's identity. A nation is commonly identified with a

shared cultural inheritance and a mode of life, something that is reflected through national identities (Moran, 2011). A nation's identity is also reinforced by institutions and educational systems that support and continuously protect its legacy. Myths and memories, in particular, are historically inherited; these components reflect the historical, collective events and experiences that shaped the identity of the nation's members.

What characterises a nation's identity is often looked at as the constituents that form the nation's image. The debate about constructing a nation's image has become the focus of many scholars, such as Anholt (2007), Fill (2009), and Percy (2008), to reform and reflect an awareness of the nation's significance and heritage in a globalised world. The image of a nation is an essential element when evaluating a country's influence and weight in modern-day society. However, evaluating societies that had a challenging past with imperialist colonialism is rather debatable. The historical aspect of a national identity reflects a complex ideology of inherited features and can intertwine with the consequences of colonialism. Postcolonial nations are convoluted environments to study and understand their national identity (Bhambra, 2014; Maddison, 2012). In a paper about Australian Indigenous people and their national identity's construction, Madisson (2012) presents an interesting notion that the implications of the historical struggle with identity resulted in historical guilt, which in turn creates a profound obstacle in diminishing the systemic racism that keeps marginalising Indigenous people worldwide.

The historical collective guilt witnessed among postcolonial nations is amplified due to colonialism, resulting in challenges to address the social psychological barriers and historical injustice (Maddison, 2012). For this, many scholars from the Global South were invested in discussing the characteristics and challenges to postcolonial national identity (Said, 1978; Bhabha, 1994, Spivak, 2004). The analytical focus provided by texts such as Frantz Fanon's *The Wretched of the Earth* (1961), Edward Said's *Orientalism* (1978), Homi Bhabha's *The Location of Culture* (1994), and Gayatri Spivak's *Can the Subaltern Speak* (1988) were foundational theoretical assets to examine and understand colonial, postcolonial, and anticolonial structures on various levels; societal, ethnic, linguistic, cultural, and political markers. These texts were also serving as challenging discussions directed towards the British and French imperial practices in Africa and Asia and aimed to rewrite colonial and postcolonial struggles narrated by the colonised subjects.

1.3. Researching *Hybridity, Otherness, and the Third Space*

Melange, hotchpotch, a bit of this and a bit of that is how newness enters the world
(Rushdie, 1991, p.394)

Scholars from the Global South often voice the concerns of postcolonial nations and their identity's reconstruction in postcolonial times. Said's work *Orientalism* presented a pivotal interest in postcolonial studies and pioneered how postcolonial nations' matters and concerns are discussed and narrated. In his scholarship, Said argued that the Western narrative of the Orient dominates how the world perceives the latter. In a clearer definition, Said (1978, p.7) explains Orientalism as "a created body of theory and practice" which is directed by the West to illustrate the Orient. The Orient is constructed on the basis of exoticness, femininity, weakness, and vulnerability, while the West defines itself as powerful, masculine, and rational. This binary juxtaposition gave the upper hand to the West to be dominant over the Orient and its related epistemology, which in turn led to mistaken perceptions of the Orient and Global South societies. Western epistemology on the Orient stretches back to nineteenth-century imperialist British and French empires and their dominance as colonisers and scholars to shape how the Global South is supposed to be constructed. With Napoleon's expedition in Egypt, and the French invasion of Algiers in 1830, writers and artists began documenting what they perceived as foreign and exotic to Western literature and knowledge. As a result, they introduced the terminology of Oriental identity and culture, as in the case of the painter Jean-Léon Gérôme whose journeys in North Africa, Constantinople and the Near East significantly inspired his work of drawing the Orient.

Due to Said's work on postcolonial societies' literature, scholars, especially from the Global South, were encouraged to discuss what they viewed as problematic and considered misleading in Western knowledge about their identities and cultures. Homi Bhabha, a postcolonial theorist and writer from the Global South, initiated the discussion about the issue of identity within postcolonial societies. Bhabha brought the theory of *Hybridity* and the *Third Space* (1994), which indicates that the postcolonial society is othered and endures a form of identity crisis. Such crisis reflects the clashing contact between their Indigenous identity and the coloniser's, bringing to life a newer, hybrid identity combining characteristics from both identities and evolving through time. The notions of *Hybridity* and *Third Space* are crucial theories in postcolonial literature as they allow curiosity and interest in exploring postcolonial

societies and their members' identities. Both concepts are interestingly dedicated to educating about the struggles and identity crises that postcolonial nations endure throughout their lives and how they cope with such hybrid identities to (re)present themselves.

From a much-nuanced perspective, national identity in postcolonial societies reflects how fluid and flexible identity is when it comes in contact with an opposing/imposed identity. This fluidity is also noticed with the emergence of globalisation and ease of mobility across the world. However, the colonial legacy of assimilation and identity alienation concludes the emergence of a hybrid identity that the colonised nation must carry forcefully and unequivocally. The hybrid identity is also viewed as a birth of new societal and cultural norms to the colonised society, with the loss of pre-colonial ties to cultural and national identifications and a continuous growth of newer forms of self-expression. This all ties back to Bhabha's theory and its crucial role in identifying the characteristics of the studied postcolonial society and a social approach to voice their concerns and struggles with identity interpretation and constructive discussions.

1.4. Algeria: A socio-historical background

In order to understand the parameters of *Hybridity* and *Third Space* and how they are displayed, manifested, and perceived within the Algerian community, it is important to look at the socio-historical background of the country. In this section, I will provide a general framework of Algeria's socio-historical background to contextualise the participants' interpretations of identity discussed in Chapters 6 and 7. I include a brief description of Algeria's geographical blueprint, as well as ethnic, cultural, religious, and linguistic background as they are related to several constructs discussed in this thesis and a focus on the tourism sector and ethnic identities.

Geographically speaking, Algeria has more than 1200km of Mediterranean coastal line. With a total area of 2.381.741 square kilometres (919.595 square miles), Algeria is the tenth-largest country in the world, the world's largest Arab country, and the largest in Africa and the Mediterranean Basin (UNSD, 2021). The massive territory is enriched with climate and geographical diversity. The Northern part is separated from the Sahara by two large mountain chains: the Tell Atlas, which stretches from Morocco to Tunisia by over 1500km, and the Saharan Atlas, located in the East region (Metz, 1994). The North is rich with a variety of

natural assets, namely eight national parks: Belezma, Chrea, Djurdjura, El Kala, Gouraya, Taza, Theniet El Had, and Tlemcen National Park (Cherfaoui, 2015; Achi, 2005). Also, eight national museums of art, archaeology and prehistory (Economic and Social Guide. National Office of Publication: Algiers, 1985). Three Roman Catholic Cathedrals dating back to the 1800s, and six famous mosques, a recently constructed one called Djamaâ El Djazaïr (The Mosque of Algeria). The mosque is regarded as the third largest in the world in terms of area after the Great Mosque of Mecca in Mecca and Al-Masjid an-Nabawi Mosque in Medina in Saudi Arabia (Belakehal et al. 2015). There are also five World Heritage Sites preserved by UNESCO in this area, namely: Beni Hammad Fort, Djemila and Timgad (preserved ruins of Roman cities), Casbah of Algiers (a walled citadel), and Tipasa (a Colonia; Roman outpost established in conquered territory to secure it).

Figure 1.1. UNESCO World Heritage Sites in Algeria

The South territory consists of an approximately 2 million square kilometres area of desert (Boufelih, 2010), three UNESCO heritage sites, namely Tassili n'Ajjar; a slowly eroded sandstone rock formation in which prehistoric engravings exist to narrate climatic change and human life evolution since 7000 BC and covers an area of over 72.000 square kilometres (Campbell & Coulson, 2010). Another site called M'Zab Valley is a natural region with the

presence of Tifinagh letters and symbols engraved around the valley (Tifinagh is the system or codes used to write the Tamazight language). The third site is called the Hoggar Mountains, a highland region in Central Sahara covering an area of approximately 550,000 square kilometres (Scheffel & Wernet, 1980) and displaying prehistoric paintings that date back to 6000 BC. (Haggett, 2001).

The history of the geopolitical area of Algeria is one of continuous and consecutive invasions and settlements (Barkley et al., 2018). Its strategic location in North Africa and its largest coastline facing Europe, many foreign waves of ethnicities contributed to the local communities' ethnic, cultural, and linguistic portfolio that consequently influenced their identity and culture. The French presence being the latest colonial power to govern Algeria lasted over a century – from 1830 to 1962. During this period, several policies were implemented to fit French imperialist desires. With French people making Algeria their new home, it was essential to limit the Algerian cultural, religious, and linguistic parameters from growing. Hence France alienated the Arab-Islamic identity of Algerians and assimilated the French culture within the Algerian society. As a result, Algerians implemented French into their dialect and constructed a code-switching pattern within their day-to-day conversations, French architecture was combined with the Neo-Moorish style and became a standard to architectural and building plans, and identity reflects a combination of French, Arabic and Ottoman characteristics that are displayed across Algeria and among Algerians.

Algeria's postcolonial profile is one example of how the colonial past is intertwined with how national identity is displayed, (re)presented, and discussed. The Algerian postcolonial national identity forged collective characteristics inspired and inherited from past civilisations that were located in North Africa at a certain point in history. Some of these civilisations- such as the Roman Empire, the Vandals, the Ottomans, the Arabs, and the French- were so influential that their presence still notably exists in today's Algeria. The ethnic groups coexisting in Algeria also contribute to the blurred lines of identity representation. The major ethnic groups in Algeria are Arabs and Berbers. Arabs arrived in Algeria in the 7th Century to spread Islam and Arabic in North Africa and peacefully continued settling within the region. Berbers are a minority group who are believed to be the Indigenous people of North Africa, including Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia. Berbers share common cultural identifiers with Arabs as they coexisted since the Arabs' arrival, which restricted the cultural gap between both

ethnic groups. However, with France's policy of *divide and conquer*¹, conflicts began to rise between Arabs and Berbers, leading to nationalist arousal in the post-independence stage and ethnic conflicts for the right of indigeneity in Algeria. This postcolonial conflict between Arabs and Berbers was, to some extent, enflamed with the Arabisation policy introduced by the Algerian government. The Arabisation policy was introduced in the 1960s as an attempt to regain the pre-colonial societal pillars and cultural identity, and was induced through Abdelhamid Ibn Badis'² slogan *Islam is our religion, Algeria is our homeland, and Arabic is our language*. The enforced policy was faced with national turmoil as Berbers were against these practices, which caused their identity to be derogated and unrecognised as a minority within the country. With this, a lasting conflict would cause more turbulence to the Algerian national identity and difficulties in properly setting a clear definition of the Algerian national identity.

1.5. Research Rationale

This research stems from investigating the phenomenon of postcolonial identity perception and (re)presentation among Algerians through tourism practices. With postcolonial underpinnings, I focus on reflecting the postcolonial tourists' viewpoints regarding identity and their experiences. Looking at how the Algerian national identity is displayed through tourism practices instigated this research to review these practices performed by tourists, travel agencies, and travel content creators and attempt to interpret how the postcolonial identity is perceived, (re)shaped, and (re)presented.

Tourism in Algeria is an unprioritised field compared to other highly profitable sectors, such as the hydrocarbon industry. Algeria's economy depends largely on the hydrocarbon production for its economy with \$43.3 billion in revenue from hydrocarbon exports in 2021 (OPEC, 2022), while tourism contributed only \$7.2 billion to Algeria's GDP in the same year (Galal, 2023). Despite the sector's weakness in accommodating international tourists, domestic

¹ *Divide and conquer* was a strategy employed by France to weaken the native resistance to foreign domination. It was brought to reduce the chances for future anti-colonial revolutions and nationalist demands.

² Abdelhamid Ibn Badis is an Algerian educator, an Islamic reformer, and a prominent figure of cultural nationalism. He founded the Association of Algerian Muslim Ulema (1931) which influenced the Algerian Muslim politics and the Algerian War of Independence.

tourism witnessed significant growth (Euromonitor, 2020). Algeria's domestic tourism is widely sought by Algerians for multiple reasons, varying from sun, sea, and sand (Ghodbani et al., 2016), Sahara Desert (Benaissa et al., 2022), and the need to seek cultural satisfaction (Boulhila et al., 2022). Culture is one of the components of the Algerian national identity, and many Algerian tourists conduct cultural trips as a way to learn more about their national identity (Bouadam, 2011; Kadri, 2021; Boulhila et al., 2022).

In the literature on Algeria's tourism, major emphasis is placed on investigating certain angles of tourism, namely tourism development perspectives and consumers' demands (Zeraib et al., 2022; Taibi, 2016; Louardi et al., 2018; Meftah et al., 2022); postcolonial heritage management and decision-making process to maintain sustainable tourism policies (Coslett, 2020; Aouchal et al., 2022); and cultural heritage sites' protection and sustainability (Rahal et al., 2020; Pirzada, 2019; Berbache & Hadjab, 2020). However, the impact of Algeria's colonial history and postcolonial consequences on tourists' perceptions of their national identity lacks investigation. The interdisciplinarity of postcolonialism and tourists' pursuits for national identity within the domestic realm holds the scope for wider discussions regarding the perception and communication of identity and experiences associated with understanding the said identity with the influence of digital practices on social platforms.

My interest in pursuing this investigation reflects my experiences as an Algerian female traveller, interested in learning about my national identity through tourism and curious to depict and articulate the influence of colonial history on my current worldviews on the Algerian postcolonial national identity. In this study, I chose to reflect on the concepts of *Hybridity* and *Third Space* as key features when dissecting Algeria's historical discourse and colonial/postcolonial challenges and influence on the tourism agenda. The French colonial rule in Algeria focused on alienation and assimilation policies to divert the indigenous community from their socio-cultural identity (re)presentation, resulting in the loss of links to precolonial constituents, "othering" the indigenous people, and degrading their value as human beings (Ladjal & Bensaid, 2012; Berque, 1956; Brown, 2018). The postcolonial and decolonial pursuits instigate the indigenous' desire and the government's motivation for a change (Ghodbani et al., 2016), unknowingly disregarding the notion of *Hybridity* and the significant alteration to the indigenous identity that was influenced by Western foreign culture during the assimilation procedure. Bhabha's *Hybridity* notion recognises the complexity of historical

transformation to identity (Bhabha, 1994). Such transformation indicates the culture's fluidity and performance exchange between diverse cultures, signifying a flexible and dynamic option for tourism operators to represent their culture (Amoamo, 2007). I specifically focused on the notions of *Hybridity* and *Third Space* in the Algerian context, given the long extensive French reforms to culture, identity, and lifestyle, resulting in an Indigenous community detached from its socio-cultural (re)presentations and norms (Ladjal & Bensaid, 2012). The postcolonial Algerian society went through a period of identity loss and struggled to define itself with cultural norms and identity parameters, especially during the government's decolonisation reforms to sectors. However, reconstructing tourism and Algeria's branding image with an undefined, massively French-influenced identity was challenging as cultural identity is an important segment in destination branding. For this, I set the following research questions for this study:

- To what extent is the postcolonial identity of Algerian tourists influencing their experiences in domestic tourism practices?
- How are domestic tourism trends featured and communicated on digital platforms to influence and (re)shape the postcolonial Algerian tourists' experiences and their postcolonial identity?

To address the research questions, I conducted an in-depth thematic analysis of tourists' experiences in retelling their tourism practices and perception of digital cultural representations that help them uncover and understand their postcolonial national identity. To achieve this, this study aims to critically understand the colonial and postcolonial influences on Algeria's current domestic tourism trends and how tourists' experiences are (re)shaped to uncover their national identity. This study also explores the implications of digital practices performed by travel agencies and travel content creators in the colonial/decolonial discourse to the Algerians' national identity.

The study was constructed through a postcolonial theoretical approach to investigate the notions of *Hybridity* and *Third Space* within the Algerian identity. I specifically focused on how Algerians describe their experiences as domestic tourists and how the national identity manifests and is interpreted to reflect their hybrid positioning as a postcolonial construct. Additionally, the study attempts to mirror the role of travel agencies and content creators in decolonising tourism through digital practices that may be influential to tourists' experiences and their perception of their national identity. My investigation, thus, explores the complexities

and interrelatedness of the collaboration between the consumer (the Algerian tourist) and the product's provider (travel agencies and travel content creators) as they are both providing and constructing knowledge, consequently leading to the essential role of these interactions in conducting research (Goodson & Phillimore, 2004). Examining and analysing the discourse and practices of tourists, travel agencies, and content creators aims to provide an in-depth, useful insight into how postcolonial national identity and tourists' experiences contribute to and benefit from digital practices they constantly interact with. The study's objectives are summarised as follows:

- To critically analyse the colonial and postcolonial influence on the national identity of Algerian tourists today;
- To critically review the implications of *Hybridity* and *Otherness* on Algerians' postcolonial national identity through tourism practices;
- To interpret Algerian tourists' experiences with understanding their identity through tourism practices;
- To evaluate the implications of digital practices to tourism on endorsing colonial legacy or decolonising national identity

1.6. Terminology used in this Thesis

Throughout this thesis, I referred to several terms and concepts related to Algeria, the Algerian culture, and ethnic groups. I chose to use footnotes instead of a separate glossary to explain what these terms mean briefly and translate non-English terms to facilitate understanding for the reader. These terms are mostly Algerian Arabic words used within the Algerian community and may not have a direct equivalent in English. For example, I referred to the Algerian traditional costume *Caftan* (See footnote on page 141) and explained its significance and denotation as a cultural asset for Algerians acquired from the Ottoman presence in Algeria. I also discussed the Algerian ethnic groups using their terminology, such as *Amazigh*, *Berber*, *Chaoui*, and *Tergui*, as they are combined in the compound ethnic presence in Algeria. However, in my writing, I choose to use the term *Algerian* when referring to any individual residing in Algeria, with no differentiation that can be perceived as an ethnic discriminatory act. All participants in this research are referred to as Algerians with no reference to their ethnicity unless stated otherwise or have significance to the discussion held.

Another term that I would like to address is the use of “Indigenous” and “Indigenous people” throughout this investigation. The term “Indigenous” is often used when referring to

people native to a specific region (Butler & Hinch, 2007). There is a plethora of discrepancies when it comes to defining the term. The term is meant to be used to lessen barriers between minorities and the rest of the world, while some Indigenous communities do not desire to be labelled with a definition (Stoll & von Hahn, 2004). The complexity of the term led to the difficulty of establishing a proper definition of it by the United Nations (UN); however, there are few criteria set by Jose Martinez Cobo (1986), the UN's Special Rapporteur of the Sub-Commission on Prevention of Discrimination and Protection of Minorities stating the following:

Unique traditions, they retain social, cultural, economic, and political characteristics that are distinct from those of the dominant societies in which they live. They strive for their identities, their ways of life and their right to traditional lands, territories, and natural resources but lack of political representation and participation especially related to the protection of their rights.

Additionally, Stoll and van Hahn (2004) summarised Cobo's report of Indigenous peoples' criteria that should be taken into consideration when defining the term "Indigenous" and listed the following criteria:

- A historical continuity with pre-invasion and pre-colonial societies,
- Occupation of ancestral lands or at least part of them,
- Common ancestry with the original occupants of the lands,
- They consider themselves distinct from other sectors of the societies now prevailing in their territories,
- They form, at present non-dominant sectors of society,
- They are determined to preserve, develop, and transmit to future generations their ancestral territories and ethnic identity, as the basis of their continued existence as peoples, in accordance with their own cultural patterns, social institutions, and legal systems.

In Algeria's case, the French colonial presence set societal boundaries between the settlers (French and Europeans living in French Algeria) and the Algerians through an orientalist lens of "us" and "other" (Steele, 2017). These boundaries constructed the terminology of referring to Algerians as the "Indigenous people," combining all ethnic groups that existed in pre-French Algeria within one construct to differentiate them from Western people; the Europeans. However, this imperialist construct halted societal issues of indigeneity in postcolonial Algeria. The rise of nationalist movements in independent Algeria caused an ethnic conflict between Arabs and Berber, with both parties claiming their ethnic indigenous

rights in the geopolitical area of Algeria. The blurred lines to define what “Indigenous people” mean and refer to, encouraged the Berber population to assert their indigeneity as the first population to exist in Algeria, while Arabs continued to reject the Berber’s calls for recognition. With this in mind, I choose not to assert the political standpoint of the Arab-Berber conflict within my analysis and discussion, and I will be referring to all Algerians who participated in this study as Indigenous as, according to Cobo (1986), they all share a historical continuity with pre-invasion and pre-colonial societies.

Another important idea to note is that this study investigates postcolonial settings and realms of tourism and identity. “Postcolonialism” and “post-colonialism” are often used separately and differently in literature and texts. The use of “post-colonial” signifies a reference to the period that comes chronologically after the end of colonialism, whereas “postcolonial” is indicative of the continuous consequences of colonialism across time and regions and serves as a comparative framework to comprehend the resistance to colonial impacts (Ashcroft et al., 2006). This study is situated within a postcolonial framework as it investigates the persisting impact of colonialism on the perception and (re)presentation of Algerian identity through tourism practices. Hence, I will be using the term “postcolonialism” and “postcolonial” throughout this study without limiting my focus to a periodic construct that denotes the period after colonialism (McLeod, 1994).

1.7. Thesis Structure

This thesis consists of eight chapters. **Chapter One** is an introduction in which I present the study with a brief overview of this research and autobiographical influences and positionality. I briefly discuss postcolonial identity and postcolonial theories that are significant to this study. I present a socio-historical background of Algeria to locate this research within a postcolonial framework. I also present the research rationale, the terminology used in this research and the thesis structure. **Chapter Two** examines the key concepts in the literature regarding postcolonial theory, and postcolonial tourism. I discuss the major postcolonial theories and the field’s interdisciplinarity with tourism studies, along with an empirical review of Algeria’s tourism sector and its post-colonial development plans. **Chapter Three** is concerned with reviewing literature regarding the postcolonial national identity and the nationalist movements that emerged in colonial and postcolonial Algeria. In **Chapter Four**, I present this study’s theoretical framework that is shaping the trajectory of this investigation

and aims to answer my research questions. In this chapter, I explore concepts of *Hybridity*, *Otherness*, and identity in postcolonial theory. I also illustrate the theoretical framework that is used in this study.

Chapter Five outlines the research methodology I used to collect data and report my findings. First, I discuss social constructionism as my epistemological and ontological positioning. Then I reflect on my qualitative methodological approach to conducting the study. I follow with an outline of the data collection and analysis procedures and conclude with ethical considerations and limitations of the methodology. **Chapter Six** is concerned with the discussion of my key findings. I discussed the Algerian tourists' experiences in Algerian destinations and their processes in uncovering their hybrid postcolonial identity. In this chapter, I aimed to interpret and explain tourists' experiences in domestic destinations and how these experiences manifested in uncovering and understanding the characteristics of the Algerian collective identity that is hybrid in the sense of revealing the colonial aftermath. For this, it was important to show how tourists sought tourism as an approach to reveal who they are and what being an Algerian consists of, despite the complex barriers that arose in shaping their experiences and worldviews to tourism activities. In **Chapter Seven**, I report on the thematic analysis of the digital practices in promoting domestic tourism, whether conducted by travel agencies, travel content creators, or both. In this chapter, I implemented an inductive approach to interpret and understand the travel agencies' and travel content creators' digital input to promote domestic destinations and how content consumers respond to such practices. I also focus on reflecting on how Algeria's image is conceptualised and (re)presented digitally to serve and attract domestic tourists, in addition to (re)defining the Algerian identity with hybrid postcolonial constituents. The last chapter, **Chapter Eight**, is dedicated to the study's conclusions in which I re-evaluate and summarise my key findings and report on how my investigation will aid in understanding the socially constructed phenomenon of tourists' experiences and postcoloniality. I also discuss my study's contribution to the postcolonial tourism field in Algeria from theoretical and practical stances. Additionally, I address certain implications of this study to the advancement in the literature on Algeria's case and state certain recommendations for future studies along with a personal reflection.

CHAPTER TWO: POSTCOLONIALISM and DECOLONIAL THEORY IN TOURISM; AN INTERDISCIPLINARY REALM

2.1.Introduction

Postcolonial tourism is a field of study that investigates and addresses the complexities of tourism and the decolonisation processes initiated by developing countries. Postcolonial tourism has allowed marginalised and previously colonised communities to shift the narrative about their cultures, usually produced by Western thinkers and theorists, and allow them to voice their concerns with literature. Theories of postcoloniality and discussion surrounding postcolonial matters highlighted the importance of postcolonial subjects in narrating their cultures, identities, and socioeconomic issues from their own lens and personal reflections and acquisition. Many theorists such as Edward Said, Homi Bhabha, Gayatri Spivak, and Frantz Fanon were pioneers in delivering literature on postcolonial struggle, colonial consequences on the Global South's socio-political development and cultural representation.

This chapter aims to address concepts of postcolonial theories and decolonisation of tourism. In this chapter, I review the literature about the postcolonialism field of study and the related theories that discuss Western epistemological literature about the Global South, focusing on the theories of *Hybridity*, *Third Space*, and *Otherness*. Additionally, I discuss literature regarding tourism, tourist profiles including tourist experience and motivation, and cultural tourism, and I discuss the postcolonial tourism interdisciplinary field. Then, I review the case of Algeria and present its post-colonial tourism endeavours to improve the tourism sector.

2.2.Postcolonialism

The concept of postcolonialism emerged as a framework to defy knowledge about past colonised nations and support their pursuit to regain their identity and position in a Western-dominant world. Postcolonial theorists have long been pursuing a change in literature by highlighting cultural constructions and allowing Indigenous nations to speak about their identity (Said, 1978; Lester, 1998; Ashcroft & Ahluwalia, 2001). Said's seminal text

"Orientalism" (1978) presented a foundation for postcolonial studies as reflecting historical, political, and anthropological views of the East and how the West created a mythological discourse about "the Orient". According to Said (1978), the discussion about the Orient was established to allow the West to control the narrative and set up a superior position over the marginalised and colonised societies. He stated that "in a quite constant way, Orientalism depends for its strategy on this flexible positional superiority, which puts the Westerner in a whole series of a possible relationship with the Orient without ever losing him the relative upper hand" (Said, 1978, p.38). Such a relationship between the West and the Orient offers the former the power to dominate the narrative, consequently disregarding the latter's cultural, historical, and social assets worth greater description than the way Western literature narrates. Said also critiques the West's colonial ideology of exchanging power and dominance for understanding and co-existing with different cultures. Such colonialist ideology relied heavily on radical differentiation and the importance of colonising and exploiting non-European territories as they considered non-Europeans inferior beings (Donze, 2017). Accordingly, a fundamental power imbalance has been established between the Western and Eastern sites of knowledge and remains present today (ElMarsafy et al., 2013).

Rukundwa and Van Aarde (2007) articulated that the postcolonial theory can be viewed from two opposite angles, based on what one reads and from the perspectives of political, religious, and literary studies. On the one hand, postcolonialism is viewed as challenging the discriminative and exploitative practices of the Global South, regardless of time and space. On the other hand, postcolonial theory can be regarded as problematic, ambiguous, and superstitious due to its lack of clarity and consensus (Rukundwa & Van Aarde, 2007). Slemon (1995) believes that the theory's lack of clarity and fluidity reflects a deep inability to understand it, specifically with the emergence of new forms of social collectivity. Hence, such forms have challenged theorists to obtain an intact definition of postcolonial theory while constant and rapid changes happen.

Postcolonial studies heavily address how the Western narrative generated a certain ideology about the Global South's cultural heritage and identity (Starck & Luyt, 2019; Chambers & Buzinde, 2015). Postcolonial studies also aim to alter colonialists' perception, understanding, and knowledge of the world by disempowering the colonised intellectual, linguistic, social, and economic theories (Ashcroft et al., 2000). As a result, postcolonialism

opened intellectual spaces for the subalterns (Spivak, 1988) to voice their cultural and philosophical discourse, their language, and economic and societal issues to balance the imbalanced binary power relationship of "us and them" (Ashcroft et al., 2000).

Critics from the Global South, namely Edward Said (1978), Homi M. Bhabha (1994), and Gayatri Spivak (1988), were some of the first and prominent scholars to discuss the issues of postcolonialism, the decolonisation processes, and the Western epistemology of the other to reflect Western dominance and its consequences on the Global South (Chambers & Buzinde, 2015; Nkomo, 2011). The scholars' criticism of postcolonial and imperialist systems was first introduced in the West and intended to tackle the Indigenous minorities and immigrants in a liberal-capitalist context while not giving voice to the subaltern subjects (Chakraborty, 2016; Spivak, 1988). The postcolonial theory transformed the Western epistemological beliefs regarding the South, specifically within Western academia (Mignolo, 2010; 2007). In contrast, the decolonisation theory is a more inclusive aim that pursues changes and development to multiple epistemic beliefs rather than seeking a change in a Western imperialist context (Grosfoguel, 2007).

2.2.1. Edward Said's Orientalism Theory

Orientalism, in its wider sense, is a discipline, a scholarly discourse, and a manifestation directed to the growing public interest in the East's culture and literature that were stereotypically supported by the views of the British Empire (Burney, 2012; Mawby, 2010). With much scrutiny, Orientalism sought wider interest in the mid-twentieth century when many scholars started analysing how Western and Eastern cultures interacted (Braginsky, 1997; Bhabha, 1994; Said, 1978). The postcolonial era and WWII effects on the Middle East intensified the complex geopolitical relationships between the West and the East, evidently putting the East under a critical analysis lens. Scholars from the East who witnessed the direct consequences of colonialism started questioning and criticising the Western stereotypical views on their culture and literature (Watkin, 2021).

Edward Said is one of the pioneers in postcolonial studies and critics of the Orientalism concept. Said's book entitled *Orientalism* (1978) is the foundation of postcolonial theory in which he challenged and discussed the artificial Western construction of boundaries, stereotypes linked to the Orient, and the concepts of "us" and "other". Said's work is driven

and adapted from Foucault's idea of discourse and the relationship between knowledge and power. He mentioned that "Orientalism has more often been thought of as a testimonial to subaltern status -the wretched of the earth talking back- than as a multicultural critique of power using knowledge to advance itself" (Said, 1978, p.336). With Said's background in English and Comparative literature and applying critical literary methodology to textual representations, he introduced new realms to modern critical studies and epistemological validation methods (Watkin, 2021). In this regard, Said (2003, pp340-341) stated "my project has been to describe a particular system of ideas, not by any means to displace the system with a new one" and "I meant to cast some light on their -Orientalists'- positions to make other humanists aware of one field's particular procedures and genealogy".

Effectively, Said's work focused primarily on the literature delivered by "poets, novelists, philosophers, political theorists, economists and imperial administrators" (Said, 2003, p.2) to disintegrate the epistemological and ontological differences between the Orient and the Occident. Accordingly, he ensured the importance of texts in delivering and imposing reality and said that "texts create not only knowledge but also the very reality they appear to describe" (Said, 2003, p.94). With Foucauldian theory of discourse, Said claims:

Without examining Orientalism as a discourse, one cannot possibly understand the enormous systematic discipline by which European culture was able to manage -and even produce- the Orient politically, sociologically, militarily, ideologically, and imaginatively during the post-Enlightenment period. (Said, 2003, p.3)

His focus on literature produced by theorists and novelists does not exclude other forms of defining the Orient. Orientalists in academia and research also share the responsibility of instilling Western epistemology about the Orient, including Arab and Muslim writers who did not join Said's critique of Western description of their cultures, which eventually endorsed these descriptions even further had they not collectively refuted (Varisco, 2017). Said also pointed to the political methods used to control the Orient, especially when he wrote about the Palestinian struggle and the anti-Islam stereotypes of the Middle East. Said states:

Orientalism can be discussed and analysed as the corporate institution for dealing with the Orient – dealing with it by making statements about it, authorising views of it, describing it, by teaching it, settling it, ruling over it: in short, Orientalism as a Western style for dominating restructuring, and having authority over the Orient. (Said, 2003, p.3)

What can be understood from Said's critique of Orientalism is that, similarly to any scholar from the Middle East or the Orient, Said's experiences as a Palestinian living in the West shaped his beliefs on how the narrative about the Orient should be told in the West. Despite that, his critique did not reflect or adequately represent the reality of Muslim countries; instead, he focused on criticising literature and practices of the Occident towards the Orient. It arguably challenged Western epistemology and assumptions and provided new tools for other researchers to address the concept of postcoloniality from a newer, more nuanced perspective that allows scholars from the Orient to narrate their reality and cultures. To this, Said brought three qualifications to the Orientalism discipline. First, he emphasised that Orientalism deals with "the internal consistency of Orientalism and its ideas about the Orient despite or beyond any correspondence, or lack thereof, with the 'real' Orient" (Said, 2003. p.5). Second, he highlighted the power that is driven by knowledge and description by saying, "ideas, culture, and histories cannot seriously be understood or studied without their force, or more precisely their configuration of power, being studied" and that the relationship between the Orient and Orientalism is "of power, of domination, of varying degrees of a complex hegemony" (Said, 2003, p.5). Third, he projected the geopolitical influence on Orientalism assumptions and how "Orientalism is more particular valuable as a sign of European-Atlantic power over the Orient than it is as a veridic discourse about the Orient (which is what in its academic or scholarly form, it claims to be)" (Said, 2003, p.6). In addition to Said, many theorists prevailed, especially from the Global South, to support Said's claims and contribute to the Orientalist theory. One theorist who revolutionised the concepts of understanding postcolonial identity is Bhabha with his theory of *Hybridity*.

2.2.2. Homi Bhabha's *Hybridity* and *Third Space* Theory

Another prominent theory in postcolonial studies pertain to the critical theorist Homi Bhabha. Bhabha provided a critical yet important intervention when he identified a limitation in Said's *Orientalism*, mainly that "there is always ... the suggestion that colonial power and discourse is possessed entirely by the coloniser" (Bhabha, 1983, p.200). To this, Bhabha suggested that the orientalisising mission ought to fail as the colonial subject is constructed in "a repertoire of conflictual positions" that render him/her "the site of both fixity and fantasy" (ibid, p.204). For Bhabha, the common ground to comprehend the colonial subjects' "in-betweenness" position is the *Hybridity* of a *Third Space* (Bhabha, 1994). The *Third Space*

represents a space of belonging to both yet neither cultures: their own pre-existing indigenous culture and identity and the coloniser's "being inside yet outside but through *hybridity* always incorporating the new" (ibid, p.4).

Bhabha theorised that there is a hybrid space, which he named *Third Space*, that exists within postcolonial societies. The hybrid *Third Space* emerges from adopting characteristics from the Western coloniser's culture and the Eastern colonised community. These characteristics intertwine and produce a newer, nuanced, and complex environment, interrupting the concrete awareness of the indigenous culture of the postcolonial society. DaCosta (2018) mentions how Bhabha's theory can offer possibilities for investigating how people live with and through differences that exist around them. These possibilities assert the *Third Space* as a space of agency and cultural translation within postcolonial communities. Also, Bhabha adds that the *Third Space* allows the cultural borders to be removed to create a new hybrid culture combining their features and balancing their differences (Milostivaya et al., 2017; 2018).

Bhabha's scholarship concerning cultural *Hybridity* resides in the core of postcolonial discourse. Hoogvelt (1997, p.158) commented that the concept of *Hybridity* "is celebrated and privileged as a kind of superior cultural intelligence owing to the advantage of in-betweenness, the straddling of two cultures and the consequent ability to negotiate the difference". *Hybridity* studies and describes how culture and identity are developed within postcolonial settings of inequality, inequity, and antagonism (Garcia-Morena & Pfeiffer, 1996; Bhabha, 1994). Bhabha also explained that *Hybridity* refers to the process undertaken by the coloniser to translate the identity of the colonised to fit a universal framework. However, this process later fails and generates a newer identity for the *Other* (Modood & Werbner, 1997). The postcolonial discourse asserts the unlikelihood of pure culture and identity (Ashcroft et al., 2005), to which Bhabha agreed that cultures, despite their forms, are in a constant process of *Hybridity* and generating *third spaces* (Rutherford, 1990).

Third Space has revolutionised the postcolonial realm of studies, presenting a new model to articulate, describe and address a productive space that instigates new possibilities (Meredith, 1998; Bhabha, 1994; Rutherford, 1990). This space is 'interruptive, interrogative, and enunciative' in generating "new signs of identity and innovative sites of collaboration and contestation" (Bhabha, 1994, p.2). Hence, the space is unfixed, symbolic in its active state of

production through discursive position (Roy, 2017). However, there has been a plethora of criticism to Bhabha's theory that sparked a wide array of imbalance in applying such theory in practice. One prominent critique is that Bhabha's theory tend to romanticise and oversimplify the complexities of cultural interaction and identity formation in colonial and postcolonial contexts. Critics (such as Huddart, 2006; Meredith, 1998) argue that the concept of *Third Space* as a place of hybridity and negotiation between cultures suggests a false sense of equality and agency, which fails to resolve the power imbalances and structural inequalities within the coloniser/colonised relationship. Similarly, Dirlik (1997) and Young (2005) suggest how the concept of *Hybridity* masks the continued marginalisation and oppression of the colonised communities. Along these lines, they pointed out that Bhabha's theory is heavily focusing on the 'in-betweenness' and liminal spaces without subjectively addressing the material and historical patterns of colonial dominance.

The *Hybridity* theory was used in a collection of tourism research to investigate various case studies. Amoamo's (2011) work on the Indigenous Māori community examines how Māori tourism operators are utilising hybridisation to (re)negotiate Indigenous identity and create subjectivity. Similarly, Kraidy (2002) reviews the dynamic of *Hybridity* and its interdisciplinarity through which Kraidy proposes the need to articulate *Hybridity* along with hegemony to comprehend global cultural dynamics. From another angle, Meethan's (2003) works on mobile cultures and cultural change critique the static models of cultural change in tourism and call for transforming how *Hybridity* and cultural change should be addressed in postcolonial tourism contexts. These investigations on the *Hybridity* notion among postcolonial communities are useful in discussing the sociocultural contexts of identity construction within tourism and can be a starting point to broaden this focus to other communities, such as Algeria. The complexity of the hybrid identity in the tourism context emphasises that identities are personal and collective and that "they are important bases from which people create new activities, new worlds, and new ways of being" (Holland et al., 1998, p.5).

Similarly, the *Third Space* can support Spivak's *Subaltern* theory since they are both investigating the *Otherness* of postcolonial nations, and their exclusion in literature as subjects belonging to a space further from the Western narrative.

2.2.3. Gayatri Spivak's Subaltern/Othering Theory

With growing interest from educators of the Orient to voice their concerns with how their culture is described and stereotyped, Spivak's work came to critique the Western models of class-consciousness, subjectivity, and feminist role in subalterning women from colonised nations. In a collection of series following her translation to English of Derrida's *de la Grammatologie* (1967), Spivak implied the lack of women's voices in evolving Derrida's deconstruction theory and the need to focus on women's historicity. With her criticism towards imperialist and Marxist historical interpretation, she explicitly accused Western women of enabling the oppression and exploitation of women from developing countries by complying with capitalism (Spivak, 1988). In this sense, the enabling behaviour provoked a reaction to how the Western culture investigates and describes other cultures.

Spivak's book entitled *Can the Subaltern Speak?* (1988) primarily addresses Western theorists, namely Marx, Foucault, Deleuze and Derrida and how their theories merely support Western economic interests over accurate representation of the "Other" cultures and societies (Spivak, 1988). Spivak attests that knowledge is always used to serve its producers. In this sense, knowledge is used as a commodity for any form of gain, be it economic or political. She states in this regard that "Subalternity is the name I borrow for the space out of any serious touch with the logic of capitalism or socialism. Please do not confuse it with unorganized labor, women as such, the proletarian, the colonized, migrant labor, political refugees etc. Nothing useful comes out of this confusion" (Spivak, 1995, p.115).

It is worth noting that Spivak focused on how the Third World subject can and must be studied without the colonial agenda's influence. In her book, she reflected on the reality of coloniality of research dominated by Western epistemology, especially when defining "the Other". Thakur and Thakur (2016, p.2) simplified Spivak's study and said, "We are talking about white men speaking to white men about colored men/women", and this has been causing a notable limitation to studying and understanding cultures from the Global South/the Orient/the East. In this sense, Crous-Costa (2022) presents a study on how *Otherness* shapes travel and tourism literature. It also provides an interdisciplinary methodology to relate tourism literature with postcolonial and decolonial studies. Crous-Costa's work (2022) is a semiotic study that addresses the representation of *Otherness* in advertising and travel posters in the case of China. Throughout this study, Spivak's *Otherness* and Said's *Orientalism* understanding are

implemented to semiotically comprehend the postcolonial imagery and reflection of identity through Chinese travel posters and recommended for DMOs to familiarise themselves with studies of *Otherness* to better align their campaigns with a broader spectrum of political and socio-economic goals.

2.2.4. Decolonisation and Postcolonial Identity Contention

In postcolonial studies, there has been a vast interest in investigating the legacy of European colonial rule and its impact on the formerly colonised societies. This sparked the emergence of decolonial thinking which, along with postcolonial literature, aims at critiquing colonial power structures, exposing, and challenging the underlying power dynamics of colonialism (Said, 1978; Fanon, 1961). Postcolonialism and decolonisation theory are both concerned with the ways in which colonial domination has shaped identities, cultures, and modes of representation of the colonised societies, and seek to reclaim and valorise their voices and agency (Bhabha, 1994; Spivak, 1988). This stems from the desire of resistance and liberation; a central theme in both theories to investigate the struggle for political, cultural, and economic liberation from colonial rule.

While postcolonialism and decolonisation theory share a common concern with the legacy of colonialism, the former adopt a more theoretical and conceptual stance in addressing colonial impact, while the latter is more focused on the practical and political struggles for liberation and self-determination. Postcolonialism is viewed as an examination of cultural, economic, and political legacies that persist in the post-colonial era (Said, 1978; Bhabha, 1994). The approach often adopts a more global and comparative interdisciplinary perspective when analysing the consequences of colonialism (Young, 2001; Dirlik, 1994). Decolonisation theory, on the other hand, is more focused on the historical processes and struggles for political independence (Fanon, 1961). Its scope lies within the specific experiences and contexts of individual colonised nations, and the primary focus towards achieving self-determination (Memmi, 2006).

Decolonisation refers to the process colonies proceed to gain political independence from their coloniser (Oelofsen, 2015). Such a process might take a gradual route to break from the colonial powers, for instance, in some British colonies, but for the other European colonies,

the decolonisation was in some cases violent and fuelled by nationalism and the need for rebellion to gain freedom (Cooper, 2019; Winchester, 2013).

The end of World War II, along with the stand of the Soviet Union and the US against colonialism, were factors that adhered to Europe's inability to suppress the colonies rising revolutions, especially with the lack of financial and political support of former European colonisers (Nwaubani, 2003; Rao, 2000). As a result, colonies began breaking apart from the coloniser, and it was during this period that scholars started generating literature on the subject of decolonisation. During the 1960s, the decolonisation process was evolving rapidly and became a hot topic to examine nationalism (Betts, 2004). Scholars like Roger Louis and Prosser Gifford started organising international conferences, specifically in Africa, to provide a reflective analysis of colonial power and regime in the African continent and shed more light on the continent's struggle in its nations' pursuits of independence (Cooper, 1989). In 1961, Frantz Fanon wrote the most provocative and critical study of decolonisation entitled "*The Wretched of the Earth*". The book is a manifesto for dismantling French West Africa and the violent resistance and revolution conducted by the National Liberation Front (FLN) in Algeria. Fanon's position towards decolonisation was largely recognised and sometimes criticised because of his stark statement, "Decolonisation is always a violent phenomenon" (1961, p.1). His views on the therapeutic value of violence were influenced by the French writer Georges Sorel (1908), who encouraged his beliefs in violence's cleansing effect to gain authority and dignity restricted by the colonial powers. His advocacy for violent resistance to colonialism was met with major criticism as the repercussions of such advocacy may lead to potential political and societal impacts; nonetheless, his points can be interpreted as violence is sometimes necessary for response to oppression and inhumane treatment of the oppressor on the oppressed.

In 1971, Rudolf von Albertini presented one of the first studies of the colonial world, entitled "*Decolonization; The Administrative and Future of the Colonies, 1919-1960*". In his study, Rudolf analyses the European colonisers, notably Britain and France, towards their colonies and how colonial administration had to be re-oriented to construct new relationships between the colonial power and their former colonies. The book was exclusively focused on examining European history and arguing the factors that led to the decolonisation movements and revolutions across colonies. However, investigating the phenomenon of decolonisation

requires looking at those who have been oppressed as seeking freedom. Decolonisation remains a reaction to oppression, violence, and the desire to have power over one's identity and land. It aims to gain political, cultural, and economic independence from the colonial regime. Political independence was pioneered with the world being politically reformed into a global economic dominance and the popularity of using "modernisation" and "underdevelopment" terms (Berger, 2003; Reyes, 2001). During these times, an academic interest emerged with the disparity of wealth and living standards between the former colonisers and the colonised regions (Betts, 1998). A Guyanese scholar, Walter Rodney, investigated the coloniser/colonised relationship and referred to it as a 'one-armed bandit' mainly exploiting indigenous populations with limited benefits (Rodney, 1974). Rodney (1974, p.14) also defined underdevelopment as "a product of capitalist, imperialist and colonialist exploitation".

According to Yansané (1980), political decolonisation had a limited gain for former colonies' populations if none. The middle class of the Indigenous populations collaborated and gave transnational enterprises access to control local economies, justifying it with globalisation (Yansané, 1980). In his book *"The Wretched of the Earth"* (1961), Fanon also mentioned the middle-class contribution to decolonisation struggles by calling the "underdeveloped middle-class" who lead the corporations to act in an intermediary position "between the nation and the former capitalist coloniser which today puts the masque of neo-colonialism" (Fanon, 1966, p.124).

To many advocates, the decolonisation process should not solely be achieved with national independence but also with regaining political power, which was not the case for most former colonies and the lost cultures before colonisation (Betts, 1998; Ngũgĩ, 1986). Former colonisers' imperialist beliefs wielded a destructive weapon daily unleashed upon the exploited populations. Ngugi called the weapon 'the cultural bomb', which destroyed the oppressed cultures and colonial powers, imposing their cultural system to colonise the minds. He asserted that language with all its uses is "central to a people's definition of themselves" (Ngũgĩ, 1986, p.4) and that the communication system must align with the population's identity, not with the imposed culture of the colonial regime. Ngũgĩ (1986) anti-imperialist beliefs encouraged reforming the literature department at the University of Nairobi and replacing English with African languages. In this regard, he declared that things should be viewed from the African perspective. Ashcroft et al. (1989) extended Ngugi's statements into postcolonial realms and

pointed out their concern with the instrument of writing rather than the language used. In this respect, Ashcroft et al. (1989, p.82) mentioned that "in many postcolonial societies, it was not the English language which had the greatest effect but writing itself". Their views emphasise the importance of seizing the means of communication and the written language when seeking independence from a colonial power. However, Eldred Jones, a professor of English literature, insisted in his paper 'The Decolonisation of African Literature' that the choice of language should not be important as long as the writing reflects the author's imagination and delivers authenticity (Jones, 1968).

The former colonies' urge to gain cultural independence had led to forging a postcolonial identity distinguishing them from the Western power and classifying them as "the other" or "the subaltern" in the binary power-relationship system (Spivak, 1988; Said, 1978). According to Ashcroft et al. (1989), more than three-quarters of the world's population have their lives shaped because of colonialism. Changes in these developing nations are apparent as cultural and economic dilemmas, where confusion occurs about their culture and identity. These cultural and ethnic dilemmas resulted from a long process of redefining their constant disposition between margin and centre at the spatial, social, and metaphorical levels and the continuous reinterpretation of their history (Marinescu, 2007). The struggles justify the coloniser's attempts to inflict power and cultural control over the colonised people. However, with the resistance of the colonised nations to preserve their identity once they gained independence and the coloniser's cultural transformation of their colonies, a conflicting identity crisis emerged and reflected the former colonies' desire to confirm their independence (Dizayi, 2015).

The concept of identity is a controversial issue among postcolonial societies and one of the most crucial elements in postcolonial literature due to its common complexity among all former colonies (Azada-Palacios, 2022). Following World War II, nations under colonial occupation sought nationalist movements and revolutions to decolonise their people. Decolonisation significantly showcased a fight for people's liberation, their culture, economy, and art to restore and recapture their lost identity in the remnants of the coloniser's power (Dizayi, 2015; Hargreaves, 2014; Memmi, 2006).

The national identity constructed in postcolonial nations is presumably unfixed and unstable within the environment and culture because of transfer and sovereignty, leading to

more confusion about one's identity (Chan, 2006). According to Hall (1989, p.10), "identity emerges as a kind of unsettled space or an unresolved question in space, between several intersecting discourses". Accordingly, colonialism's aftermath was multi-dimensional across the colony, leading to identity emerging in different forms and shapes (Dizayi, 2015). As governmental, societal, and individual decolonisation took place, identity became a chosen constituent and was actively used by the colonised nations to resist the coloniser's former societal and cultural policies and refute the dominant representation of "others" (Goldberg, 1996).

Postcolonial theory asserts that colonised societies develop a postcolonial identity built on their existing heritage and, in most cases, assigned in varying degrees to the coloniser's social power and preserved heritage on the colonised land (Sinamai, 2020). In postcolonial literature, the narrative depicts the resistance of the subaltern colonial societies to the coloniser's culture. Additionally, the cultural resistance led to failure in establishing a colonial society, but simultaneously employed the binary power relationship and encouraged referring to non-Western societies as "the other" (Spivak, 2015). The subaltern's resistance in this matter led the Western imperialist regime to shift to a neo-colonialist practice of economically, culturally, and globally influencing countries to create dependence, subservience, and financial obligation towards imperial nations (Prashad, 2007).

2.3.Tourism

Before discussing the interdisciplinary juncture of postcolonial theory and tourism, it is important to review the literature about the tourism and the tourist experience to frame a picture of this thesis and facilitate the narrative for the reader. Global mobility and tourism are one of the most critical activities and visible manifestations of globalisation; the improvement can be seen in every dimension of economic, social, cultural, and even political processes (Čerović et al., 2015). The study of tourism has been seen more often on the periphery of the social sciences, whereas the mobilities paradigm places tourism at the centre of social and cultural life (Hannam et al., 2013; Coles & Hall, 2006).

One of the most cited phases in the history of tourism and mobility is "The Grand Tour", which was undertaken mainly, but not exclusively, by wealthy British elites seeking education, culture, arts, and pleasure in the seventeenth century (Colletta, 2015; Chaney, 2013; Buzard,

2002). Primarily, The Grand Tour centred on France, Italy, Germany, Switzerland, and the Low Countries (Belgium, The Netherlands and Luxembourg). Various opinions are related to its origins; they vary from the break of the Roman Catholic Church in 1534, which resulted in the change of spiritual pilgrims into secular tourists, to the mid-seventeenth century (Howard, 1914) or early eighteenth century (Ford, 1981). The decline of the Grand Tour is speculated to have been caused by the French Revolutionary and Napoleonic wars from the 1790s to 1814, which imposed restrictions on time and movements and resulted in failure to regain the old patterns of the tour (Hutton, 1937). However, by the 1840s, railroad constructions and steamboat manufacturing during the Industrial Revolution facilitated transportation and mobility for the wider population, especially among the middle-class groups, and changed the cultural attitude towards travelling that was exclusive to the elites and lengthy to circuit the European continent (Colletta, 2015; Brand, 2011).

Tourism mobility is now more advanced, well-integrated, and extensively studied. It is primarily because of the contribution of globalisation in easing the travel process due to the advances in technology, the efficiency and growth of travellers' transportation, open borders, and the increase in the number of people who can afford to take vacations outside the national borders. Those factors have strengthened international over domestic tourism (Nedeljković et al., 2013). Additionally, people are now able to live 'geographically independent' lifestyles, which "allow more and more individuals to be free to live where they want and travel as much as they want" (Makimoto & Manners, 1997, p.6). Some studies brought attention to investigating how new mobile and social technologies, including smartphones, mobile applications, tablets, and social media, expand the perimeters of tourism research (Molz, 2012; Tussyadiah & Fesenmaier, 2008; Mascheroni, 2007; White & White, 2007). Green (2002) points out that new technologies are reconfiguring time and space for users and becoming an inescapable part of daily life. Tourists often expand their daily practices into digital spaces by replicating their performativities and sociabilities and maintaining their co-presence on social networks as part of the travel experience (White and White, 2007).

2.3.1. The Tourist Profile

The term "tourist" is believed to be firstly used by Stendhal (1838) in McCabe's "Memoires d'un touriste" (2009). The term "tourist" was first defined as "people on temporary trips away from home who also spend money derived from their home area and not from the

place being visited” (Shaw & Williams, 1994, p.68). Such definition primarily refers to international tourists who are categorised based on time frame limitations and distance from their home, and it excludes people who are considered students, people who travel to work, and anyone who exceeds 24 hours in their destination.

The UNWTO published the “Technical Handbook on the Collection and Presentation of Domestic and International Tourism Statistics” (1981) and defined the international visitor as “an individual entering a country that is not his usual place of residence”, which was a clearer definition than how it was previously set, but still excluded a category of people such as expatriates, refugees, and foreign workers. In 2014, UNWTO developed this definition to include more clarity to this concept and took into consideration the mobility, duration, and purpose of travel. Accordingly, a tourist is:

“A traveler taking a trip to a main destination outside his/her usual environment, for less than a year, for any main purpose (business, leisure, or other personal purpose) other than to be employed by a resident entity in the country or place visited. A visitor (domestic, inbound, or outbound) is classified as a tourist (or overnight visitor) if his/her trip includes an overnight stay, or as a same-day visitor (or excursionist) otherwise”. (UNWTO, 2014, p.13).

2.3.1.1. Tourist Experience

Prior to discussing tourism and tourist experience, I should provide a brief explanation of the term 'experience' by referring to the Collins Paperback English Dictionary, which defines experience as "direct personal participation or observation of something; a particular incident, feeling etc., that a person has undergone" (Sinclair, 1999).

When implemented within the tourism context, the experience can refer to two types of phenomena. The first type concerns the nature of a tourist's activity during their trip, such as consuming host communities' cuisine or visiting a museum. This type has been investigated by Light (2000) and Stewart et al. (1998) when they examined the variable of tourist experience by studying the tourists' use of heritage sites and interpretative media. The second type is merely concerned with the psychological and emotional effects tourism activities induce within the tourist. This includes feelings of fulfilment, happiness, dissatisfaction, or sadness. Brown (1992) focuses on investigating the psychological and emotional impact of tourism activities and states that "tourism is an encounter, an interaction with the environment in a state of

heightened consciousness" (Wearing & Wearing, 1996, p.238). Similarly, Mannell and Larson (1988, p.291) claim that the tourism and leisure experience "has been conceptualised as similar to a variety of highly involving psychological states".

From the perspective of evaluating the tourist experience, it is important to look at the process of constructing the said experience. Tung and Ritchie (2011, p.1369) view the tourist experience as "an individual's subjective evaluation and undergoing (i.e., affective, cognitive, and behavioural) of events related to his/her tourist activities which begin before (i.e., planning and preparation), during (i.e., at the destination), and after the trip (i.e., recollection)". The general consensus is that the experience's core element lies within the 'during' stage. This does not suggest that the 'before' and 'after' stages are unimportant; rather, it emphasises that the tourist is more engaged intellectually and emotionally in the on-site experience (Ebejer, 2015). This was also supported by scholars considering the psycho-emotional part important during the experience (e.g., Holloway, 1989; Urry, 1990; Voase, 1995).

Theories on tourist experience were widely stemming from a focus on the psycho-emotional perspective, especially in investigating and evaluating the tourist's satisfaction with tourism activities and products. Clawson and Knetsch (1966) were the first to introduce a theory on tourism experience through researching recreational tourism. Their study found that the tourism experience comprises the following stages: the anticipation stage, travel to site stage, on-site activity stage, return travel and a recollection stage. In Kelly's thesis (2000), the anticipation stage is the period in which the tourist forms a perception of the destination based on memory, past experiences, or images and formulates certain expectations of what he/she will experience in the destination. The recollection stage includes a reflection and comparison of their initial expectations with the experience, in which the tourist evaluates the merits of the total experience. Since Clawson and Knetsch (1966) support the psycho-emotional approach to the tourist's experience, their theory views the on-site activity and travel to and from the destination stages as parts of the overall experience and have little impact on tourism motivation and experience.

Similarly, van Raaij (1987) and Hughes (1991) implemented the satisfaction parameter to the tourist experience. Vittersø et al. (2000, p.433) report that tourism satisfaction can be "the result of comparative process, between expectations and actual performance". As for Eagly and Chaiken's expectancy-value theory (1993), the tourist satisfaction parameter is determined

based on the tourist's process of assessing the quality of the tourism product in terms of meeting their expectations. This can also be linked to the idea of how tourist motivation plays an important role in the overall experience of the tourist, as motivation can be part of the tourist expectancy and anticipation stage and a driving force to pursue a tourism product.

When reviewing tourist experience literature, the notion of embodiment appeared as a closely related concept when investigating experiences. The concept of embodiment refers to the idea that our bodily experiences and sensations are integral to how we perceive and interact with the world around us. In tourism context, the embodied nature of the tourist experience has been a subject of ongoing discussion and research. One of the key ways in which tourist experience and embodiment are related is through the role of the senses. As tourists, we engage with our surroundings through our sight, sound, smell, taste, and touch. The sensory experiences help in shaping our perceptions and interpretations of the places we visit, and they contribute to our overall embodied nature of the tourist experience.

According to Urry and Larsen (2011); “the tourist gaze is not just visual, but involves all the senses -smell, touch, hearing” (p.17). They argued that the tourist experience is not simply a passive observation of a destination, rather an active and continuous engagement with the surroundings through the body. This interaction can lead to a deeper understanding and appreciation of the local culture and way of life. Crouch (2008) also highlights the importance of the body in the tourist experience, stating that “the body is a central part of tourism, not just as a vehicle for travel, but as a means of engaging with and experiencing the world” (p.210). This suggests that the construction of meaning and knowledge within tourism landscape is heavily influenced by the tourist’s bodily movements, sensations, and gestures. Interestingly, the notion of embodiment is closely linked to the concept of place and place-making in tourism. It is noticed that tourists engage and experience a particular place through their bodies which shape their understanding and perception of their destination (Edensor, 1998). This adds a defining layer to conceptualising the importance of embodied relationship with place in forming meaningful tourist experiences which lead tourists to be motivated for travel.

2.3.1.2. Tourist Motivation

Motivation can be simply defined as “derived from the word ‘motivate’ which means to cause (a person) to act in a certain way or to stimulate interest” (Cooper et al., 1993, p.21).

Vukonic (1996, p.42) supported this definition by stating that “the essence of every human motivation is the need to satisfy a deficiency”. When projecting motivation upon the tourism practice, the concept reflects a “global integrating network of biological and cultural forces which give value and direction to travel choices, behaviour and experience” (Pearce, 1993, p.116). As such, tourism motivation encapsulates the tourist’s urges, needs and stimuli, encouraging an individual to partake in tourism practices.

Across the scope of tourism motivation theories, it is agreed among scholars that tourism motivation can be investigated through three main categories: internally stimulated motivation, socially or culturally based motivation, and multi-faceted motivation. The first theoretical category indicates an intrinsic state that encourages an individual to undertake the activity to gain internal benefit (Goodall, 1991). In contrast, Ingham (1986, p.259) defines socially or culturally based motivation as “the driving force behind activities for which some obvious external reward or sanction is associated (e.g., money, social approval, punishment)”. The multi-faceted motivation theory encapsulates internally stimulated and socially/culturally based motivations. Ingham (1987) and Vukonic (1996) indicate that it is widely common among tourists to have internal and socially/culturally based motives to partake in a tourism activity, which can be very difficult to evaluate each motivator and to which category the tourist fits.

In a much broader sense, internal motivation plays a critical role in determining the success of an individual’s trip (Deci & Ryan, 2000). This internal desire to explore new cultures, meet new people, and learn new things increases the likelihood of the tourist having a fulfilling and enriched travel experience (Gnoth, 1997). Arguably, internally stimulated motivation is “generally based around the inherent states of personality, homeostasis, anxiety, and the personal perception of one’s everyday environment” (Kelly, 2000, p.49). This indicated that tourists are mostly motivated by internal factors classified as push and pull and desire to escape. Kelly (2000, p.49) also added that tourists could be motivated to take part in a tourism activity because “they feel pushed to escape from an everyday environment which is causing an imbalance in their inner equilibrium (i.e., stress/boredom/fatigue)”.

When looking at tourism motivation that is based on social and cultural influences, it is argued that these factors are the strongest determinants of tourist behaviour, specifically as “most social action is intrinsically motivated, in that people account for and explain their

choices and actions with reference to judgement by others” (Pearce, 1993, p.121). In support of this, Goodall (1991) attests that tourists are motivated through social factors and cultural pressures from their environment. This can reflect that family background involves a level of mindlessness or unconsciousness in a tourist’s leisure decisions (Ryan and Glendon, 1998), and a habitual behaviour created during socialisation processes in early childhood also influences a tourist’s adult leisure decisions (Iso-Ahola, 1983). In essence, the social and cultural factors are majorly driven by the tourist’s socialisation and familiarity with the place to visit; tourists are more likely to decide on travelling to a destination because, according to Merriman (1989), a familiar destination is “unconsciously” more attractive and desirable than having to deal with the dilemma of feeling anxious and uncomfortable in visiting an unfamiliar destination. However, it is argued by theorists that tourist typology is also a contributing factor when disseminating motivations to travel since each tourist is socially, culturally, personality-oriented, and internally exerting certain desires to fit within a category of tourists (Cohen, 1984; Pearce, 1993).

2.3.1.3. Tourist Typologies

When categorising the tourist, it is worth reviewing Cohen’s tourist typology (1972), which is considered a fundamental model for the classification of tourists. The sociologist Erik Cohen was the first to propose that there are different types of tourists. In his 1972 paper *Towards a Sociology of International Tourism*, Cohen set four categories of tourists within a range of institutionalised and non-institutionalised characteristics. These categories are described as 1) the organised mass tourist, 2) the individual mass tourist, 3) the explorer, and 4) the drifter. This categorisation of tourists is set “according to whether or not they wish to exist in familiar environmental bubble ... those who seek the shelter of the familiar environmental bubble are the institutionalised travellers (e.g., the mass/individual mass tourist); while those who venture outside are non-institutionalised types such as the ‘drifters’ and ‘explorers’” (Goodall, 1991, p.61).

The four types of tourists can be placed in a motivational continuum that streams from the unfamiliarity and novelty boundary to the familiar and security boundary. The “drifter” and the “explorer” are tourists who are driven by their desire to “discover and search out exotic, novel or unfamiliar environments” (Page, 1995, p.27). These types of tourists are interested and focused on participating in various leisure activities and “consciously” seek new

destinations. In contrast, the “mass individual tourist” and the “mass-organised tourist” always seek familiarity and security and often search for relaxation and restful activities in familiar destinations. Their desires are also defined through their personal characteristics of “anxiousness, self-inhibition and adventurousness” (Burton, 1995, p.64). Additionally, while taking into consideration the tourists’ motivation based on their individual personality traits, it is also argued that cultural influence may greatly contribute to the destination choice and tourists’ desires to venture their personal traits and channel them through interacting with their destination’s culture. For this, reviewing culture and evaluating how it provides certain connections and familiarity/unfamiliarity-driven motivations is important.

2.3.2. Culture

The term culture can be difficult to define, and this complexity in eliciting one clear view of the concept has raised various debates among scholars (Malinowski, 1931; Meade & Whittaker, 1967; Geertz, 1973; D’Andrade, 1995; Richerson & Boyd, 2005). One of the reasons is how individuals interpret it on a personal scale and differently than others; every person has a unique way of doing things. Therefore, it would be best to define individual cultures’ beliefs based on what most people follow rather than looking at it from a general viewpoint and neglecting the element of individuality. In this respect, Schwartz (1989, p.324) defined culture as follows:

Culture consists of the derivatives of experience, more or less organised, learned or created by the individuals of a population, including those images or encodements and their interpretations (meanings) transmitted from past generations, from contemporaries, or formed by individuals themselves.

According to Schein (1993), culture is manifested in three layers of depth: observable artefacts, values, and basic underlying assumptions. The observable or visible artefacts include everything from the physical layout, the dress code, the way people address each other, the smell and sensation of the place and its emotional intensity, to the more permanent archival manifestations such as products, philosophy statements, company records and annual reports (Schein, 1993). The components proposed by Schein (1993) could be easily approached to collect data. However, it is challenging to analyse them. The challenge can be referred to as the difficulty of interpreting the reason behind people’s behaviour in such manners rather than questioning the system their environment is constructed from (Spencer-Oatey, 2012). The

analysis of peoples' behaviour should be based on the values that govern their behaviour. However, such values are not observed directly; they generally espouse justifications such as conscious strategies, goals, and philosophies (Schein, 1993). Detecting them through interviews with key group members or analysing artefacts such as documents and charters is often mandatory.

A society's culture consists of various elements essential for the nation's recognition and acceptance at the national and international levels. Heritage, as one component, gained much interest from scholars as it is considered a tangible asset to retell history (Brett, 1997; Graburn & Barthel-Bouchier, 2001; Graham et al., 2016; Timothy & Boyd, 2003). Heritage, a distinctive component of society, is accepted as an element from the past. It represents a sort of inheritance of cultural traditions and physical artefacts to be passed down to current and future generations (Jones & Hardy, 1988) and a useful tool a society wishes to keep (Fladmark, 1998; Graham et al., 2016; Hall & McArthur, 1993).

Culture and heritage have become essential to almost 40% of all international trips (UNWTO, 2015). Many destinations started to realise the potential beneath selling and retelling the past and branding it (Timothy & Boyd, 2003). Heritage has ascribed absolute value to places, objects, and practices and led to an objectifying plan around them, from performance and display to preservation and tourism (Porter & Salazar, 2005). As a result, culture became one of the most significant motivators of tourists in choosing a particular destination (Correia et al., 2013); it triggers the individuals' desire to travel to learn about other countries, their people, their heritage, art, and literature (Raina & Agarwal, 2004). In other words, tourists decide on a destination based on internal factors and motivations related to their emotional and internal desires, such as self-actualisation, rest, leisure, or social interaction, besides a set of external destination attributes that enhance their desire to visit such as landscape, climate, hospitality, facility, and culture (Yoon & Uysal, 2005).

2.3.2.1. Cultural Tourism

Richards (2001) noted that cultural tourism, heritage tourism, ethnic tourism and arts tourism are mostly interchangeable in their usage, making it complicated to distinguish whether or not people are discussing the same thing. Richards (2001) clarified the link between these types and claimed that culture comprises processes such as ideas and people's way of life and

their outcomes such as buildings, art, artefacts, and customs. Therefore, cultural tourism encompasses heritage and artefacts of the past and art tourism related to contemporary cultural production (Hall & Zeppel, 1990).

Cultural tourism emerged as a social phenomenon and became an object of academic study since post-World War II as incomes and consumption started to rise in Europe (Richards, 2018). By the 1980s, the increased number of international visitors to main sites and attractions in Europe brought attention to cultural tourism as a new niche market (Richards, 2018). Interest in cultural tourism continued to grow throughout the 1980s and 1990s, driven by the growth in both international and domestic travel and the identification of cultural tourism as a definite form of tourism that would eventually help to preserve the culture and stimulate the economy (Richards, 2001; Hewison, 2023). The early 1990s was a remarkable transformation of cultural tourism to pave its way to developing the orientation toward the mass market. Since then, cultural tourism has encouraged researchers to increase academic research about the 'new' market and has led to being regarded as a well-established phenomenon in many tourism destinations (Smith & Richards, 2017; Ivanovic, 2008).

UNWTO considers cultural tourism an area of significant potential growth for the next century (UNWTO, 1998) and a pedagogic instrument that allows new identities to emerge as a significant role in world events (Lanfant et al., 1995). Richards (1999, p.7) suggests that cultural tourism covers:

Not just the consumption of the cultural products of the past but also of contemporary culture or the 'way of life' of a people or region. Cultural tourism can, therefore, be seen as covering both 'heritage tourism' (related to artefacts of the past) and 'arts tourism' (related to contemporary cultural production).

Various definitions are given to the concept of cultural tourism, as culture varies depending on the scope that is looked at and the elements of the society (McKercher & DuCros, 2003). It is remotely challenging to establish a universally valid definition of cultural tourism since it could be easy to use other terms to describe it, such as 'heritage tourism,' 'arts tourism,' 'ethnic tourism,' or 'indigenous tourism' interchangeably (Smith, 2003). In 1997, ICOMOS (International Scientific Committee on Cultural Tourism) suggested that:

Cultural tourism can be defined as that activity which enables people to experience the different ways of life of other people, thereby gaining at first hand an understanding of their costumes, traditions, the physical environment,

the intellectual ideas, and those places of architectural, historical, archaeological or other cultural significance which remain from earlier times. Cultural tourism differs from recreational tourism in that it seeks to gain an understanding or appreciation of the nature of the place being visited. (ICOMOS, 1997, in Csapo, 2012, p.204)

This form of tourism is the desire to explore a particular society's culture and environment by people who do not belong to the visited area. Richards (1996), in this respect, suggests that cultural tourism is merely the movement of persons to cultural attractions away from their usual place of residence to gather new information and experiences to satisfy their social needs. Such experience lay mostly in visiting cultural heritage sites, architectural memorials and monuments, libraries, and theatres and experiencing local art and literature. Cultural heritage is the main reason for encouraging people to such tourism. In 2005, the Council of Europe defined cultural tourism as:

A group of resources inherited from the past which people identify, independently from ownership, as a reflection and expression of their constantly evolving values, beliefs, knowledge, and traditions. It includes all aspects of the environment resulting from the interaction between people and places through time. (Innocenti, 2014, p.6)

The broadness of the previously mentioned definitions merely implies that cultural tourists are interested in the more experiential aspects of culture (Smith, 2003). In indigenous or ethnic tourism situations, for example, the central focus of the tourist is the society's way of life and the direct authentic contact with the people whose cultural and ethnic backgrounds are different from their own. However, it could be a mistake to combine all cultural tourists under the same umbrella and assume they all merely travel for cultural purposes and experiences.

Kotler et al. (1999) indicate that every market consists of groups or segments of customers with different needs, motives, behaviours, and reactions towards the activities provided. Both conceptual and empirical studies showed that different people would engage in culture-related attractions at different levels under different factors such as their interests, their knowledge about the services, and the time arranged to devote to the destination (Stebbins, 1996; Timothy, 1997; Kerstetter et al., 1998; Prentice et al., 1998).

To identify the differences between cultural tourists, researchers such as Richards (1996), Blackwell (1997), and Miller (1997) mentioned that the emphasis should be only on socio-demographic variables due to the absence of other discriminating conditions to set the

differences. From the opposite view, some authors proposed the use of benefit segmentation - the process of dividing the market based on quality, performance, customer service, and specific features a customer perceives from a product or service (Prentice et al., 1998; Frochot & Morrison, 2000). Such segmentation is more reliable and accurate in detecting types of cultural tourists since tourism is more about the tourist's experience. Hence, several typologies were suggested to clarify the classification of cultural tourists depending on various criteria, mainly the cultural motive and choice. The Irish Tourist Board (1988) suggested a typology that divides tourists into two main categories; "specific" and "general" cultural tourists. The former refers to tourists who choose a destination only to acquire cultural knowledge. At the same time, the latter denotes that tourists are more likely to have a superficial interest in culture. The classification was not accurate or detailed as it was based more on the tourists' degree of cultural motive without considering any other circumstances that might affect the consumer's decision.

Bywater (1993), on the one hand, gives a more accurate classification and divides cultural tourists into three main types: culturally interested tourists who do not plan to consume cultural attractions but participate in some activities. On the other hand, culturally motivated tourists consider culture a significant reason for their holiday experience. Nevertheless, their destination choice may not be entirely based on specific cultural activities and attractions. The third type Bywater (1993) proposes is called culturally inspired tourists; this category's primary goal is culture; they are ready to travel long distances to obtain cultural experiences and learn about the destination's culture and practices.

To a large extent, research on cultural tourism typologies is based on the fact that this market is undifferentiated, with an implicit assumption being that all cultural tourists signify the prototypical deep cultural tourists. Accordingly, a cultural tourist is a highly motivated person willing to travel for mere cultural reasons and to acquire a profound experience; hence, the emphasis was only on socio-demographic variables (Bowen, 1998; Prentice et al., 1998). McKercher and DuCros (2003) deny previous claims and assert that the importance or centrality of cultural motives in choosing a destination significantly differs among tourists. Culture could signify the main reason to travel for some. In contrast, for others, it is a secondary reason for a destination visit and involvement in cultural activity and might play no role or influence in the choice of destination (Silberberg, 1995; Richards, 1996; Shifflet, 1999;

McKercher, 2002). Studies on the centrality of cultural tourism as a motive for travelling indicate that it significantly influences the number and type of activities pursued (McKercher, 2002) and awareness levels about the destination as pre-trip research undertaken (Shifflet, 1999) and various trip factors. Different people will be involved in cultural tourism attractions relying on their interests, knowledge level about the destination, time availability, and their company, from a conceptual (Stebbins, 1996; Timothy, 1997) and empirical level (Kerstetter et al., 1998; Prentice et al., 1998)

For a better understanding of cultural tourists, McKercher and DuCros (2003) state that the classification should be based on two interconnected variables: the centrality or motivation to travel and the depth of cultural experience. They propose a more detailed typology which divides cultural tourists into five types;

a) Purposeful cultural tourist: Cultural tourism is the primary motive for this category of people to visit a destination. The tourists will gain a deep cultural experience.

b) Sightseeing cultural tourists: Cultural tourism of this type is also the primary motive for travel, yet the tourist's experience is not deep and more entertainment-oriented.

c) Serendipitous (opportune) cultural tourist: The tourist does not travel for cultural reasons, but once they participate in a culture-related event or activity, they will gain an in-depth cultural experience.

d) Casual cultural tourist: Cultural tourism is a weak reason for this type of tourist and plays a limited role in choosing a destination. As a result, the tourist's experience is shallow and narrow.

e) Incidental cultural tourist: The tourist, in this case, does not travel for any cultural reasons, yet they participate in some activities and acquire a shallow experience.

McKercher and DuCros' model (2003) was tested on a sample of cultural tourists visiting Hong Kong. Their study tested the typology set against various tips, demographics, awareness, and motivational and experiential variables to ensure a full investigation of the types. As a result, the study shows different shades of cultural tourists. They range from recreational/pleasure tourists who participate in cultural tourism activities to supplement their trip experience to tourists who travel primarily or exclusively to pursue cultural tourism activities and experiences. The findings suggest that the model reflects more profound motives that shape and distinguish the tourists' experience and cultural tourism behaviour. The

classification of cultural tourists reflects the implementation of factors that encourage tourists to travel in the first place and the experience they seek to endeavour at a destination. For instance, incidental tourists are not superficial consumers of culture; they consider travel a refreshment and pursue experiences to achieve their goals.

Cultural tourists' motivation and centrality will be evaluated during the pre-purchase stage. Potential cultural tourists commit to a research period in which they browse online and check a destination's aesthetically beautiful images and cultural offers provided in that area. This stage is essential as it signifies a person's search for a destination. Since the era of social media as a widely spread platform for communication, advertising destinations to attract consumers have become very popular and increasingly relevant (Hudson & Thal, 2013). On the other hand, "the post-purchase stage" or "post-purchase evaluation" (Pizam et al., 2001) is also crucial, especially for tourism marketers wishing to promote their destination and attract new consumers (Jenkins, 2003). It indicates the sense of satisfaction with the chosen destination and results in an evaluation by consumers to express their satisfaction level, service quality and recommendation (Dube-Rioux et al., 1989). These notes will also be reflected when analysing data that covers the participating tourists' motivations, experiences, and cultural typologies upon dissecting how their experiences are shaped in a postcolonial setting. In this context, I will address the interdisciplinarity of tourism and the postcolonial theory, influences, and setting in the next section to locate this study's framework.

2.4. Tourism and Postcolonial Theory

The imperialist narrative of the Global South's cultural (re)presentation is visible across most disciplines. It has been a point of interest to tourism researchers in their attempts to decolonise literature (Chambers & Buzinde, 2015). Former colonial regimes governed and produced tourism knowledge, overshadowing and negating cultural diversity and indigenous heritage (Chambers & Buzinde, 2015; Platenkamp & Botterill, 2013; Teo & Leong, 2006; Hollinshead, 1992). The Western epistemology of tourism was fundamentally developed to sustain colonialism and create an entangled exploitative relationship with former colonies. Pritchard and Morgan (2007) claim that there is a need to decolonise academic knowledge by learning knowledge traditions from indigenous people worldwide, especially from the South, to allow a fair demonstration of their way of thinking, being, and viewing things.

The relationship between tourism and postcolonialism emerged in the last twenty years to discuss the identity dilemma and re-presentation of marginalised groups and decolonising tourism terminologies within a critical framework (Hollinshead, 2011; Phillips, 2008; Hall & Tucker, 2004; Hinch & Prentice, 2004; Duval, 2004). Pairing tourism studies with the critical structures of postcolonial research offers a lens to uncover the nuances and complexities of tourism embedded within the developing countries' decolonisation processes. In this sense, postcolonialism helps accentuate "the pervasiveness of the legacies of colonialism in tourism, and how tourism might act as a medium for offering postcolonial counter-narrative of resistance to those colonial relationships" (Tucker & Akama, 2009, p.504). Pritchard and Morgan (2007) highlight the crucial step of decolonising tourism literature and state the relevance of learning from all knowledge traditions worldwide to create new unbiased tourism knowledge. Chambers and Buzinde (2015) attest to how colonial thinking is predominant in tourism literature and how important it is to seek insights from the indigenous peoples to expand knowledge and conceptualise theories through co-creating epistemic literature with the Global South. Alternatively, most postcolonial theorists originating from the Global South, such as Edward Said (1978), Homi Bhabha (1983), and Gayatri Spivak (1988), drew their theoretical frameworks based on Western epistemologies of post-structural theorists, namely Michel Foucault, Jacques Lacan, and Jacques Derrida, respectively. Nonetheless, postcolonial theorists arguably contributed to literature to pivot the course of "Western cultural criticism away from its historically parochial confines" (Majid, 1996, p.9) and opened a path for newer conceptual frameworks and critiques of colonial practices. Their contribution to literature offered comprehensive insights into tourism phenomena to deconstruct neo-colonial knowledge and shape and use colonial heritage and postcolonial conditions as a tourism marketing strategy (Chambers & Buzinde, 2015; Hall & Tucker, 2004; Amoamo, 2007; Morgan et al., 2003).

2.5. Tourism in Algeria; Historical background and Postcolonial Development Plans

Algeria became a member of the UNWTO in 1976 as a plan to boost and enhance its tourism assets and performance. However, Algeria's results were not encouraging since it welcomed only 2.6 million foreign tourists in 2018 in comparison to its neighbouring countries, Morocco and Tunisia, whose statistics indicate the arrival of 12 million and 8.3 million inbounds, respectively, and its GDP is estimated 6.8% of the total contribution of Travel and

Tourism to GDP in 2017 (WTTC Report, 2018). The stagnant tourism industry of Algeria is due to various reasons, namely the Black Decade's Terrorism in the 1990s, which led to safety and security issues that were immensely difficult to overcome, mainly because the notion of terrorism was associated with Algeria's image for years (Sabi, 2015). In addition, the Algerian government ignored the tourism sector and its supporting division because of the significant dependency on the oil and gas industry that flourished the national income, hence the remaining fields' negligence. On top of that, Algeria lacks destination promotion and a transparent communication strategy (Nasi, 2015). Building a destination's image through social media is crucial to creating a cloud of comfort for its potential visitors. Tourists will not travel to a destination without promotion in their countries, and its image is linked to safety issues. Unfortunately, this is not the case for Algeria, as its government and sectors' websites are rarely updated and lack coordination and long-term visions for a prosperous future of the nation (Sabi, 2015).

Algeria was a French colony for 132 years (1830-1962) and was under a massive cultural and social displacement by the French coloniser to erase the Algerian identity, language, religion, and culture. During the colonised period, the ruling party was under French authority, with all sectors administered as an integral part of France and followed the French constitution with no inclusivity of Algerian educators and politicians (Bell, 2000).

In 1897, France established "The Algerian Winter Committee", dedicated to advertising organised trips to the Algerian Sahara and discovering landscapes and historical monuments (Aouinane, 2013). The Committee gained considerable interest, leading the French authority to create tourism associations in Oran, Constantine and other cities starting in 1914 (Drideche, 2017). The newly established associations became under the supervision of the Tourism Federalism in 1919. They encouraged the authority to grant loans to French investors in the tourism field to establish hotels and touristic sites (Aouinane, 2013). Consequently, authorities established the Algerian Office of Economic and Tourism Activities in 1931 to develop the tourism sector. It was later renamed the "Tourism Development Centre" and continued its activities even after its Independence in 1962 (Drideche, 2017). The foreign inbound arrivals reached 150,000 tourists in 1950, prompting the French authority to establish more hotels, create leisure stations, and set strategic plans to host more tourists in the coming years, especially in the capital Algiers (Heddir, 2006).

After the independence in 1962, Algerian revolution forces gained power over the entire sector and founded the “People’s Democratic Republic of Algeria”. By then, it was necessary to establish new reforms to improve the nation and restore national identity. The policy pursued after independence focused mainly on renovating the industrial, agricultural, health and educational sectors as the main pillars of society, indicating significant negligence of the rest of the sectors, including tourism, due to the lack of financial resources and possibilities as a newly independent state (Aouinane, 2013). Though the tourism sector did not receive much attention at this time, a programme was drawn between 1962 and 1966 aiming to renovate the remnants of France’s tourism efforts. The first step taken was the creation of the National Office of Algerian Tourism (ONAT) as the main office for refurbishing the sector (Drیدهche, 2017). It was followed by establishing the Tourism Ministry in 1963 to be the first office combining the ONAT (Aouinane, 2013), the 1965 Management Committee for Hotels and Restaurants inherited from France’s pre-independence policy, and the Algerian Tourism Agency as part of the ONAT dedicated for hosting and planning organised trips across the national territory (Heddir, 2006). The Ministry founded the Tourism Charter in 1966, devoted to setting tourism valuation and development programmes, protecting tourist sites and renovating them, providing jobs, and welcoming foreign investments to introduce Algeria to the international market (Ouazani, 2012). Additionally, various expansion and renovation attempts were taking place to protect Algeria’s cultural and historical diversity, provide accommodations and mobility routes, facilitate administrative and monetary regulations, open tour operators, and ensure political and social stability for tourists’ safety (Aouinane, 2013).

The Algerian authorities kept setting plans and strategies consistently between 1966 and 1989 to refurbish the tourism sector with several reforms and investments, mainly in the coastal line and urban cities, to create more hotels, with few contributions in the country's Southern region: the Sahara. However, their strategies failed due to unstructured planning and a lack of long-term vision for the sector (Aouinane, 2013).

Following the failure of the previously discussed plans and the beginning of the Civil War in 1989 that prevented any foreign investments from reaching completion, the Algerian authorities sought to transition from a centralised planned economy to a market economy by adopting a privatisation strategy for tourism. The process of privatisation consists of the partial or complete transformation of public institutions into the private sector with the benefit of

assets selling, the development of the market laws, and liberalisation of trade, along with raising cash to reduce government debt and broaden the base of participation in the economy (Heddir, 2006; Kastarlak & Barber, 2013). The process started with classifying hotel establishments according to their financial and commercial situation, productivity, location, and equipment status (Madouche, 2003). They later offered to sell hotel projects that were partially or fully completed to private investors (Rebhi, 2013). One of the current contracts is with the well-known French complex “ACCOR”, which signed a management contract with the Tourism Management Corporation to administer the SOFITEL Hotel in 1992 and Algiers Airport Hotel MERCURE in 2000 (ibid.).

With the arrival of former president Abdelaziz Bouteflika to rule in 1999, he faced countless political issues that led the country to complete isolation from the world. The president launched an aggressive diplomatic reform to achieve two primary objectives: restoring the country’s image abroad and attracting foreign investments (Thieux, 2020). Consequently, he established the “Civil Concord”, a peace initiative that ended the terrorism era and domestic security and stability (International Crisis Group Report, 2001). With Bouteflika’s considerable assets of his long experience as a diplomat in the 1960s to 1980s and his contacts abroad, the country gained international recognition, and its foreign policy started to expand in Africa and around the world, attracting more investments in all sectors, including tourism (Hamadouche & Zoubir, 2009).

Following the peace contract that brought political stability, the Algerian tourism ministry worked effortlessly to place the tourism sector at the core of the economic development policies. It recalled the importance of tourism statistics for future development and further enhancements (UNWTO, 2017). During the UNWTO 1st Regional Capacity Building Programme on Tourism Statistics, the Minister of Tourism, Mr AbdulOuahab Nouri, declared that “Algeria is truly committed to creating a more competitive and sustainable tourism, a sector that can become one of the pillars of Algeria’s economy and a tool for diversification and inclusive growth” (2017). For this reason, the national plan for tourism development was established, creating a state policy based on the involvement of all institutions elaborating on developing tourism products and activities (Bouadam, 2011). The plan was introduced to set up a sustainable framework to guide, coordinate, and monitor tourism development until 2025. Tourism specialists and authorities decided to set a plan in

2008 named “Horizon 2025” to cover all issues hindering the tourism sector from reaching noticeable success in the Mediterranean basin with their suggested long-term solutions.

Horizon 2025 was set in 2008 following strategic planning and Algerian tourism experts to promote Algeria’s image in the global market and eliminate the stereotypical internal and external associations (Terki & Yahiaoui, 2019). The plan aims to develop the sector as part of the economic diversification strategy set by the government, allowing more sectors to contribute to the nation’s development, as tourism is a horizontal sector requiring the contribution of transport, culture, agriculture and so forth for complete development of services (Bouadam, 2011). Such economic diversification will lower the pressure on the hydrocarbon industry, considered the main financial income since 1962, consequently leading to various investments in all sectors and creating more job opportunities. The plan also reflects the state’s will to evaluate the historical, cultural, and natural potential to reach a Euro-Mediterranean success and develop human resources for planning appropriate infrastructure for tourism activities by providing international-levelled hotels and expanding the railway network to tourism sites (Aouinane, 2013; Bouadam, 2011). Horizon 2025 is the result and culmination of a long process of research, investigation, surveys, studies and wider consultation with national, local public and private institutions (Bouadam, 2011). Their evaluation of previous strategies detected failure points to be reconsidered and covered properly and suggested a necessary enhancement in dependent industries like handicrafts, environment, culture, and transportation (Terki & Yahiaoui, 2019). The master plan was divided into two major steps: a short-term process set between 2008 and 2015 in which authorities plan and authorise the commencement of priority programmes such as accommodation expansion and touristic villages and parks (BenTalbi et al., 2018). During this stage, major collaborations with foreign investments took place mainly in the coastal cities (Oran, Algiers, Tipasa, Tlemcen, Bejaia), neglecting immensely the South, which was assigned to have few projects to construct, although the massive territory (Amara, 2018).

According to the plan drawn in collaboration with the French Committee (ODIT France), they assembled five major steps to analyse the current tourism situation and elaborate a successful plan divided into two main periods to test validity and accomplishments (Ait Bara, 2022). They started with a long-term diagnosis of global trends, problematics, and potentials to see how to fit Algeria in the international market. They drew the strategic directions and

guidelines with follow-up programmes for completion of diagnosis and evaluation (Sahraoui, 2017). As part of the Horizon 2025 plan, it was important to consider the construction of new spatial experiences to shape the overall image of Algeria as a desirable destination (Hannam et al., 2013). Sabi (2015) argued that the destination image of Algeria is an intricate angle that should be optimised if the desire is to attract new consumers on the domestic and international scale, which is what the development plan was created for in terms of travel ease, infrastructure modernisation and extension. Statistically speaking, MTA reported that accommodation capacity was increased with an additional 58 new hotel establishments in the coastal region; adding a total of over 100,000 beds in 14 cities (APS, 2022).

Algeria, overall, is well equipped concerning general infrastructure; it has 53 airports, of which 18 are international, in addition to a railway network of over 4.500 km serviced by 200 already operating commercial stations and 13 ports across the coastal line (BenTalbi et al., 2018). These transportation assets, in conjunction with the cultural and historical heritage, the affordability of services and products, and the diversity of landscape and natural sites, contribute fully to the opportunities for the strategy to reach recognisable success (Bouadam, 2011). However, some challenges might be faced while endorsing the government's master plan to elevate the tourism sector. The tourism sector endures multiple constraints, necessitating serious reforms. Such limitations are the visa's lengthy process, the limited accommodation capacity to host tourists compared to Morocco and Tunisia, the necessity to create direct and indirect jobs which require a massive investment the country could not afford, and the lack of tourism culture among Algerians as hosting foreigners is ambiguous and new for the society resulting in foreign tourists to avoid Algeria as a destination (Boukhris & Peyvel, 2019; Bouadam, 2011; Terki & Yahiaoui, 2019; Aouinane, 2013).

2.6. Summary

This chapter provided scholarship about the postcolonial theories and their interdisciplinarity with the field of tourism. Literature about postcolonial theory provides the lens through which this study is constructed. The presentation of prominent postcolonial theories, namely Orientalism, Hybridity, and Subaltern, offers a canvas that shapes the whole study as it progresses and aims to uncover tourists' experiences and postcolonial national identity. This chapter also provided an understanding of the decolonisation processes and pursuits of colonised societies aiming for freedom from imperialist economic and political ties

with their former colonisers. I also provided literature on Algeria's post-colonial development plans to its tourism sector.

The following chapter will review the literature regarding postcolonial national identity and the nationalist movements that emerged in colonial and postcolonial Algeria. Later, I will present Algeria's ethnic and cultural contention between the Arab and Berber populations and the socio-political issues that arose during these conflicts from 1988 onwards, collectively contributing to the investigation of the Algerians' postcolonial hybrid identity and sociological state.

CHAPTER THREE: NATIONALISING THE SELF; NATIONALISM AS AN IDENTITY IN POSTCOLONIAL ALGERIA

3.1. Introduction

The postcolonial national identity is imperative in Bhabha's and Spivak's theories. The identity of a previously colonised nation has a certain dynamic that locates it within its own space, a *Third Space*, where the identity is adapting characteristics from the coloniser and merging them with the Indigenous socio-cultural norms. The present chapter will be a review of literature in regard to the postcolonial identity contention from the perspective of Algeria. First, to understand national identity and nationalism, it is important to look back at the history of Algeria as a first step to learning about the historical events that led to nationalist movements in twentieth-century Algeria during and after colonialism.

The points of contention in the study of postcolonial identity will be discussed in this chapter as I review the literature regarding cultural and national identity. I also discuss literature about nationalism movements in Algeria during and after French colonialism, namely the Arab and the Berber movements in twentieth-century Algeria. Additionally, I will provide a literature review on the identity contention in a form of an Arab-Berber dichotomy where I dive into the ethnic-cultural conflict and socio-economic issues that consequently emerged.

3.2. Nationalism Ideology; Origins and the Theory of Self-determination in Postcolonial Studies

The concept of nationalism can be used in various forms. It can be implied either to describe an ideology or a form of behaviour. Halpern (1963, p.207) explains nationalism ideology as "nationalism can assert itself without the same time demanding loyalty to any particular form of government or society, economic organization or values, or any particular religious beliefs. No other ideology presents as cheap as bargain". Accordingly, the main feature of the nationalism ideology is the belief in the nation's supreme value and the subjective judgement of the nationalists in presenting the content of their nation. Nationalism can also refer to specific organisations seeking specified goals. In this context, activities lacking

articulation and formal organisation are covered under the “nationalism” label. Also, nationalism can be used as a label for the spheres that lack in-depth definitions, such as politics, culture, religion, or economy (Humphrey, 1976).

Nationalism is mostly viewed as a European philosophy. Kedourie (1960, p.1) argues that “nationalism is a doctrine invented in Europe at the beginning of the 19th century”, whereas Hutchinson and Smith (1994) state that historians trace the origin of nationalism as a discourse and ideology back to the 17th and 18th centuries in Western Europe and North America, and later in Latin America. The initial references to the emergence of nationalism include the 1772 First Partition of Poland (Perkins, 1896), the 1776 American Declaration of Independence (Hutchinson & Smith, 1994), and the 1789 French Revolution (Smith, 2005). By the 19th century, nationalism grew to be a general European movement that, later in the 20th century, was regarded as the most explosive political philosophy ruling the world today. With European epistemology, the projection of nationalism on the Third World, especially from a colonial perspective, is angled from the top bottom. The problems arising revolve around the consequences of the colony’s nation-to-be on the politics of the coloniser. However, nationalism can also emerge within the Global South without colonial literature influences. Bhandari’s work on Nepali nationalism (2017) is a great example of the emergence of national identity as a form of boundary to serve differentiation from outsiders, specifically Chinese and Indian identities. Bhandari (2017) also debates the intricacy of political influence on the construction of national identity in his example of Nepal, reflecting the defying importance of self-determination and differentiation from others.

Nationalism and self-determination are closely related ideologies as they both prioritise the importance of identity to nations, especially those seeking independence from liberal colonialism and ownership of their governments. Self-determination has roots within revolutionary nationalism, through which politically driven movements were raised to defy the established order set by the colonial powers (Wilson, 1970). Revolutionary nationalism was a point of contention among the American stand on the African American community and the unbalanced opportunities between blacks and whites. Wilson (1970, p.46) states that “the revolutionary nationalists maintain that their primary task is to promote effective revolution in order to alter existing social and power arrangements between blacks and whites, hence improving the status of black people”. This statement indicates the given society’s rejection of

the imposed social order that is hindering their prosperity and sovereignty as a free community within their society. Among the prerequisite factors to revolutionary nationalism, cultural representation is considered necessary, as Huey P. Newton (1968, p.4) mentions in his interview with *The Movement* that:

Revolutionary nationalism is first dependent upon a people's revolution with the end goal being the people in power. Therefore, to be a revolutionary nationalist, you would by necessity have to be a socialist... cultural nationalism ... is basically reaction instead of responding to political oppression.

The African American community's struggle for self-determination clearly shows people's desire for self-governance and rights to freedom and sovereignty. In the same interview about revolutionary nationalism, Newton gave the example of the revolution in Algeria and how it demonstrates an exact definition of revolutionary nationalism is; a socialist-driven revolution that prioritises the people's importance in the power roles. However, Algeria's revolutionary nationalism was set through an Arab Islamic basis nationalism, stemmed from the Middle East region and incorporated within Algeria's revolt against the French settler.

3.2.1. Cultural and National identity

To Ashmore et al. (2001), national identity is the combination of multiple traits of a nation that makes a member experience a sense of belonging to that nation. It represents distinctive traditions, language, ancestry, history, education, commitment to place, and morals that do not necessarily make it a uniformed entity, but rather the whole individual representations of the sense of nationism and nationalism while interacting with others (Kiely et al. 2001; Thompson & Fevre, 2001).

From an anthropological perspective, a nation is defined as "an imagined political community and imagined as both inherently limited and sovereign" (Anderson, 1991, p.6). Anderson (1991) considers the nation imagined as members sharing the same image of their communion even if they do not practically know each other. Therefore, it refers to the comradeship, solidarity and fraternity that gather people to have a sense of belonging. Its limit relies on the fact that every nation has confined boundaries that separate and distinguish it from other nations. According to the Western model of the territorial nation, Smith (1991) asserts that a nation is a cultural community whose members share a historic territory, common myths

and historical memories, a mass, a shared economy and legal rights and duties for all its members (Smith, 1991). National identity combines attributes and characteristics shared by those who belong to a particular nation. The shared history, culture, territory, and project for the future while claiming the right to self-determination (Berdún, 1996) aid in defining a nation and differentiate it through a set of dimensions, namely psychological, cultural, territorial, historical, and political (Berdún, 2007).

From a psychological perspective, national identity arises from the consciousness of forming a group based on subjectivity and feelings that generate a sense of belonging (Smith, 2002) — Sharing national identity results in an emotional bond and closeness among nationals, which is seen fundamentally psychological and non-rational (Connor, 1994). In Connor's view, a nation is "the largest group that can command a person's loyalty because of felt kinship ties" (Connor, 1994, p.202). However, this loyalty excludes the historical ties that are not factual due to the assumption that nearly all nationals originate from mixing various ethnicities. Therefore, what matters the most is the sentient and felt history rather than the factual or chronological sequence of events of the nation (Berdún, 2007).

The cultural dimension is based more on the values, beliefs, languages, habits, and practices inherently transmitted to new members who receive a given nation's culture. Identifying the "self" with a specific culture proceeds with a substantial emotional investment, consequently constructing solidarity bonds among the community's members. Such bond will allow them to recognise each other as fellow nationals (Gellner, 1983) and imagine their community as distinct from other nations (Anderson, 1983), and lead to the members' tendency to internalise their nation's symbols, values, and customs as part of forming their identity (Berdún, 2007).

The historical dimension revolves around the nation's antiquity and relevance as a legitimate source for its culture. It binds people to a past that stretches throughout their lives and their ancestors (Smith, 1991). Accordingly, the continuity and preservation of the ancestors' heritage are one of the main identity elements that antiquity stresses. Acknowledging and preserving cultural antiquity contributes to nations' realisation of their history's worth and reassurance of their ancestors' deeds in enriching their lineage (Guibernau, 2004). Consequently, nationals tend to consider their roots as resilient elements of identity and a legacy to revive (Berdún, 2007); for instance, the case of Greeks contemplating their glorious

legacy of art, philosophy, the introduction of democracy and the Olympic Games, regardless of their current status as a nation.

Smith (1985) argues the significance of the nation's geographical root and homeland when emphasising the territorial dimension of the identity. He points to the tendency of the nation's members to feel proud of their ancient roots, which is interpreted as a sign of resilience, strength, and even superiority compared to other nations that do not have a rich past and history (Smith, 1985; Anderson, 1983). Nationalists, in this respect, assert that gaining control over the nation's destiny to fulfil it correctly will be accessible through taking control over a geographical place with ancestral roots (Bradshaw, 1997). Furthermore, a territory has traditionally been the people's primary nourishment source, essential to their wealth and historical prosperity. The land embodies the nation's traditions, history, and culture with its ancestors and is considered a heritage for future generations (Berdún, 2007).

From a political dimension, national identity is understood from its relation to the modern nation-state (Berdún, 2007). In this respect, a nation-state consists of the homogenisation of three pillars of a nation; sovereignty, unified people, and attachment to the territory (Tuladhar-Douglas & Tuladhar-Douglas, 2018). It aims to combine the nation's dominant cultural and linguistic aspects within its territory to create unity and a single nation out of the various existing nations in the territory. This dimension focuses mostly on the actions constructed by a nation to build a cohesive society. These actions are strategies meant to create a homogenous citizenry on both cultural and linguistic levels (Guibernau, 2001). On this note, it is crucial to create an adequate national education system to introduce ancestors' heritage to new generations, construct national media to spread knowledge about one's nation and promote the commonly dominant culture and language among its members (Berdún, 2007). In the case of Algeria, the national identity ought to be unpacked by looking back at the historical background of the geo-political territory of Algeria, the successive invasions and settler colonialism in the 1830s. Understanding Algeria's historical background is essential to understanding the emergence of nationalist movements in twentieth-century Algeria and demystifying the myths around the Arab-Berber identity contentions, which lead to more understanding of the cultural and national identity of the Algerian people.

3.2.2. Algeria: A Historical Succession of Cultural and National Identities

The state of Algeria was historically a witness to a succession of invaders and settlers arriving in this North African territory. The ancient kingdom of Numidia, located in northwest Africa, was one of the first major states in the history of Algeria. The Numidians, also known as Berbers, are considered the Indigenous nation of northwest Africa, which explains the presence of the Berber language and dialects within today's Algerian society.

The history of Algeria can be traced back approximately 1.8 million years, with the discovery of prehistoric stone tools found in the region of Ain Hanech in 1992 (Sahnouni, 1998). The early North African civilisations were mostly depicted in paintings throughout the caves and mountains of Tassili n'Ajjer in the Southern city of Tamanrasset, Algeria, reflecting early life practices from prehistoric Maghreb until the classical period. During the classical period, North Africa witnessed the arrival of Phoenicians from the Levant region. Phoenician traders settled and established Carthage (known today as Tunisia) around 900 B.C. and later acquired Tipasa (an Eastern town of Cherchell, Algeria) around 600 B.C. The city of Carthage was prominently the centre of power and ruler of North African territory. Carthaginians began expansions by establishing towns, or as they were called, *emporion* along the coastal line to serve as marketplaces (e.g., the towns of Hippo Regius, current Annaba, and Rusicase; current Skikda in East Algeria).

Aside from the Carthaginians and Phoenicians, the North African territory was also occupied by a population that is said to be native to this land: the Berbers. With their lack of written language and linguistic attributes, the Berbers were marginalised by incoming settlers and often referred to as a barbaric tribe lacking discipline and proper manners (Metz, 1994). The Berber civilisation was prominently prosperous in its agricultural and manufacturing trades that grew links with Carthaginians. However, conflicts arose between Carthage and the Romans that led to Carthage's defeat and the Berbers obtaining control over the city of Carthage, announcing its destruction in 146 B.C. (Slimani-Direche, 1997). The Berber population belongs to the ancient kingdom of Numidia and occupied what is known today as Algeria, Tunisia, Libya, and parts of Morocco (Markowitz, 2021).

The Roman Empire, the Vandal Kingdom, and the Byzantine Empire were all present in Algeria at a certain time to either spread Christianity, seek trade relations with the indigenous

people, or seize and settle in the land. Arab colonisation commenced in the 7th C with the arrival of the Umayyads from the Arabian Peninsula to introduce Islam. Arabs' presence in North Africa had significant impacts on the region. The indigenous population accepted Islam as their religion and fostered Arabic as their official language to this day (Benrabah, 2014). By the 16th. Century, Algeria became a state under the rule of the Ottoman Empire. Amidst conflicts and Spain's Christian conquests, Algiers' leading citizens wrote a letter on behalf of the whole population of the city to the ruler of the Ottoman Empire, Sultan Selim I, stating, "We had fallen ... in these troubled times from difficulty into difficulty ... in an unhappy situation of weakness on the edge of misfortune". In response to this pleading letter, Khayr al-Din Barbarossa was sent to the North African city of Algiers and announced his devotion and faithfulness to be the head of Algiers state under the Ottoman protectorate (McDougall, 2017). The Ottomans joined Algiers to their empire as an independent state, autonomous of its decisions and subject to influence, albeit required to join any political conflicts and the Ottomans' army (Hutt, 2019). Throughout the Ottoman presence in Algeria, the Indigenous people's identity was merged with that of the Ottomans, and they fostered amicable relations with a continuous thriving in the Mediterranean region until 1830, when France took over Algiers, and the rest of the territory under a settler colonial policy.

The French colonisation of Algeria lasted for 132 years, through which Algerians witnessed displacement and were treated as second-class citizens (Prunty, 2021). Additionally, Algerians' identity was targeted and degraded for a long time, making it difficult to reconstruct the culture. The colonisation of Algeria did not only seek economic exploitation and political domination; France's calculated assimilation and alienation policies emphasised identity cleansing and cultural loss (Mann, 2009; Gallois, 2008). These policies caused a significantly high illiteracy rate, displacement of the indigenous population, loss of identity, and utter change to material and non-material culture (Barclay et al., 2018; Prunty, 2021; Legg, 2021). However, the period of World War I witnessed the emergence of Arab nationalist movements across Egypt, the Levantine region, and Algeria. Arab nationalism was a movement that called for a unified Arab identity among all Arab countries and was a leadership that inspired Algerian nationals to form a similar movement that emphasised the Algerians' socio-cultural attributes, land, religion, and language.

3.3. Arab Nationalism

With the emergence of postcolonial studies in the 1980s, the anticolonial and revolutionary nationalist movements were on the verge of ending as major colonial powers were diminishing. During this time, capitalism was globally expanding as the new successor to further developments in critical theory (Hobsbawm, 1992; Lazarus, 2004). Ernest Gellner (1983, p.55) explains the nationalism ideology as “it is nationalism which engenders nations, and not the other way round”. In this sense, nationalism does not refer to reviving an old dormant concept, despite that is how nationalism presents itself. In fact, it utilises some aspects of pre-existing cultures and knowledge that transform throughout the process to what is sought to project.

In colonial settings, nationalist movements hold a different epistemology to what they aimed to achieve. The 20th century saw the emergence of nationalism in colonised countries, which differed from the European version. Arab nationalism, for example, was one of the movements that sparked a different ideology than the Europeans, and it emerged right after the First World War (Haim, 1962). Arab’s ideology of nationalism is defined as:

Consciousness among Arabs of their complete social existence, a consciousness that is internal and not merely external objective knowledge so that the image of the Arab community as a spiritual and living complex is ever present in Arabs’ conscience” (Haim, 1962, p.120).

Arabs’ claims for a well-defined and clear territorial and geographical existence were of great cause to establish and promote a common Arab/Islamic identity within the Arab countries. The origin of Arab nationalism is assumed to be during Muhammad Ali Pasha’s (also known as Mehemed Ali) ruling of Egypt under Ottoman protectorate from 1805 to 1848 (Aziz, 2009; Azra, 2016). After his contribution to ending Napoleon’s invasion of Egypt in 1901, Muhammad Ali Pasha grew interest in the Arab world and developed, along with his son Ibrahim, “the vision of an Arab empire and the ambition to be its architects” (Antonius, 1946, p.23). However, the goal of an Arab empire was quick to diminish as Arab nationalism was at its earlier stages and would interfere with the Ottoman Empire’s ruling in the MENA region (McKay, 1946). In fact, the British Foreign Secretary, Lord Palmerston, wrote a letter to the British Minister at Naples stating that:

His (Mehemed Ali's) real design is to establish an Arabian kingdom including all the countries in which Arabic is the language. There might be no harm in such a thing in itself, but as it would imply the dismemberment of Turkey, we could not agree to it. Besides, Turkey is as good an occupier of the road to India as an active Arabian sovereign would be. (quoted in Antonius, 1946, p.38)

The Arab nationalist movement was later passed to Syria and Lebanon, where Christian Arabs taught at the American University of Beirut and began enriching the contemporary Arabic literature with the Arabic dictionary in 1867, an Arabic Encyclopaedia in 1870, and publishing newspapers written in Arabic (Aziz, 2009). During this time, various nations, such as the Balkans' independence from the Ottoman Empire and Japan's from Russia, gained liberation. These nations' experiences encouraged the birth of the Arab National Committee in an attempt to be recognised as free Arab nations without the protectorate and governance of Ottoman rule (Khalidi, 1991; Aziz, 2009). Additionally, the Ottoman Empire's overpowering control and hold on the roads towards the Far East was a disservice to France and Britain's commercial and colonial pursuits, encouraging the colonial powers to support Arab elites' pursuits for Arab nationalism (Kurun, 2017; Khalidi, 1991). The Western support for Arabs' rebellion against the Ottoman Empire was primarily the result of Arab elites' Western educational training and secular lifestyle during WWI and their (Arabs') dire desire for self-determination and governance under an Arabian identity (Kurun, 2017).

3.3.1. Arab Nationalism in Algeria

Arab nationalism is viewed as an attempt to recover of what has been lost during the Ottoman protectorate. With implications of anticolonialism and decolonisation to the Arab movement, Arab nations were breaking ties from foreign domination and opening a space for national evolution (McDougal, 2006). In the case of Algeria, the Arab nationalist movement between the 1920s and the 1950s was a significant contributor to setting foundational and concrete principles for the postcolonial independent state (Fois, 2017). During this period, discourse about autonomy and independence started to define the Algerian identity, resulting in the founding of Algerian Arab nationalism and its core perception of the right to freedom. Nationalism in Algeria differed from what it was established in the Middle East and Gulf area. McDougall (2006) argues that Algerian Arab nationalism sought to identify which aspects of modernity, politics, and culture Algerians were willing to attest as national identity constituents. In his book *History and the Culture of Nationalism in Algeria*, McDougall (2006,

p.87) grants Tawfiq al-Madani the title of the pioneer of Algeria's nationalism with his articulate discussion about Algeria's position and its nationalist direction and attests that "the conflict among nationalists and collaborationists was over the meaning of Algeria itself". In the same book, McDougall (2006) emphasises that colonial alienation policies were key factors in directing nationalists' beliefs that Algerians are Muslims and should unite under the Arab-Islamic uniform to defeat colonialism.

Throughout the colonial era, Algerian activists were on a mission to liberate the country. Their core purpose next to independence was to decolonise the national identity. Algerians' national identity has been Arab/Islamic at its core since the arrival of the Arabs to North Africa in the 7th century. However, France's alienation and assimilation policies targeted the Algerian identity and isolated it at best to facilitate the process of full control over the land (Salhi, 2007). With international influence, the Algerian nationalist movement believed in the principle of self-determination and was fuelled by the popular renunciation of colonial control and the *raison d'être*³.

ElAmir Abdelkader is one of Algeria's well-known nationalists, military, and religious leaders during French colonialism (Mezhoud, 2020). With his established state in Western Algeria, he slowly spread the concept of independence and nationality to his people. His teachings and political endeavours were of exceptional moral grounds that paved the way for the anticolonial nationalist movements and, later, the 1954 War of Revolution to continue the fight for the nation's liberation, sovereignty, and Algerian identity (McDougall, 2006; Perkins, 2007). Farhat Abbas, an advocate for France's assimilation policy and its potential for cultural promotion, established the *Federation des elus musulman*⁴ in 1927. Additionally, Abbas believes that the Algerian nation and identity does not exist. He states, as cited in Collot and Henry (1978, p.65):

If I had been able to discover the 'Algerian nation', I would be a nationalist, and I would not be ashamed of such a crime. Then men who died for the national ideal are honoured and respected every day. My life is not worth more than theirs. And nevertheless, I will not commit this sacrifice. Algeria as a country

³ French for reason for being, reason to be.

⁴ French for Federation of Muslim Elites

is a myth. I have not discovered it. I questioned the story, I questioned the living and the dead, I visited cemeteries, and no one told me about it.

Abbas' French-schooled beliefs and his stance that assimilation is the only viable option for Algerians, along with his denial of the existence of an Algerian nation (Abbas, 1931), were strongly opposed by AbdelHamid Bin Badis, who eventually established the *Association des Ulama Réformistes*⁵ in 1931 (Fois, 2017). Bin Badis was a highly regarded advocate of Islam and education in the Maghreb region and firmly believed that religion is the source of Algerian identity. As a response to Abbas' claims on Algerian national identity, Bin Badis states, as cited in Julien (1952, pp.114-115) and Collot and Henry (1978, pp.67-69):

We searched in the past and present, and we noted that an Algerian Muslim nation was created and continues to exist. We discovered how nations were formed, and that there are nations all across the world. The Algerian Muslim nation has its own history, marked by great deeds; it has its religious and linguistic unit; it has its own culture, its traditions, and its specific characteristics [... we] affirm that this Algerian nation is not France, cannot be France and does not want to be France. It is impossible that it will be France, even if it wanted to assimilate. It has determined that its territory is Algeria with its current borders.

Bin Badis, along with the Ulama, were strongly advocating for founding the nationalist movement on the grounds of Islam and Arabism and were constantly hailing the slogan *Algeria is my country, Arabic is my language, Islam is my religion*, which reflects the main constituents of the Algerian nations; the land, language, and religion (Fois, 2017). Bin Badis' association is regarded as the birthplace of nationalism in Algeria, especially as it was founded with strong ties with religious and Arab scholars and cultural circles from Tunisia and Syria (ibid.). With the continuous evolution of the Algerian nationalist movement, Algerian pioneers and scholars were keen on ensuring their political stance to self-determination and recognition of the Algerian national identity. The nationalist associations were also intrigued by staying updated with the inner and outer political sphere that in the 1940s, Algerian nationalism reached a political maturation when all nationalist parties joined as a force to advocate their anticolonial position (Julien, 1952).

⁵ French for Association of Algerian Muslim Scientists

With the growing interest in the concept of independence and anticolonial pursuits, the Arab League was founded in Cairo in 1945 to support and facilitate Arab nations' independence, which Algeria became more encouraged to liberate from French governance and joined once independence was granted in 1962 (Ennaji, 2014). The Algerian resolution from the French empire was later a motive for Algerian elites to strengthen their Arab nationalist position in the MENA region and aim for a singularity of Algerian identity, refuting the existence of Amazigh indigenous people and their right for recognition as Algerians as well (Fois, 2017). Such undermining of Berber identity emerged after the independence referendum and was voiced as a new era of nationalism in Algeria: The Berber Nationalism.

3.4. Berber Nationalism

The Berber nationalism movement did not emerge solely because postcolonial Algerians oppressed their identity. In actuality, the Berber movement began with the arrival of Arabs to the North African region, when mountainous tribes were resistant to the Arabs and refused to convert to Islam and learn the Arabic language (Forstag, 2009). Additionally, the movement prevailed across Algeria and Morocco as both countries were home to most Amazigh people. Algerian and Moroccan state leaders argued that the Amazigh identity as a whole is solely a modern invention and an artificial temporal belief. In contrast, members of the Amazigh movement strongly held to the recognition of their centuries' worth of historical presence and identity as the indigenous inhabitants of North Africa (Chafik, 2005). Berber movements in Morocco and Algeria were both substantially sensationalised in the post-colonial times after France left the territories. In Morocco, it was more a matter of multicultural and societal recognition, whereas in Algeria, it presented a fierce desire to end the oppressive regime that was attempting to enforce the Arab identity and neglect the minorities living within the Algerian society (AlKroud, 2018; Fois, 2017; Layachi, 2005).

3.4.1. Berber Nationalism in Algeria

Before discussing the Berber Nationalism movement and its diaspora across Algeria, it is worthwhile first to explain who the Berber people, or Amazigh people, are from an anthropological, historical, and linguistic perspective.

The Amazigh (plural of Imazighen) are believed to be the Indigenous people of North Africa (Morgan, 2004). The Indigenous group is often said to have mythical origins or immigrated from Yemen, Syria/Lebanon, or Nigeria (Maddy-Weitzman, 2011). Often referred to by the terms *Berber* or *Kabylans*⁶, the ethnic minority is divided into four major tribal groups residing across Algeria. The most influential and vocal Berber tribe is the Kabylans, who reside in the Northeast of Algiers across three provinces: Tizi-Ouzou (referred to as the Great Kabylia), Bejaia (the Small Kabylia), and Bouira. The Kabylans, according to Maddy-Weitzman (2011), are the backbone of Berber political activism, especially due to their close contact with mainstream Algerian society and the outside world. The remaining tribes are the Chaouias in the Aures Mountains, the Mzabites of central Algeria, and Sahara's Tuareg nomads, whose political involvement and activism are less noticeable and voiced (Forstag, 2009). With the largest population out of all four tribes, their higher education rates, and perceived oppression and discrimination by Arab nationalists, especially after the independence, the Kabylans shifted the focus of Berber politics studies to be primarily the study of Kabylan activism and nationalism (Forstag, 2009).

Historically speaking, the Berbers quickly adopted Islam as their faith during the Arab conquest in the 8th century. While Arabs settled in North Africa, they recognised the Berbers as a distinct ethnic group. Forstag (2009, p.86) claims that "Berber culture could best be described as a hybrid variant of the dominant Arab culture". This indicates that the Berbers shared common cultural identifiers with the Arabs. By adopting Sunni Islam as their faith and the growing number of inter-ethnic marriages, they mitigated the cultural distinction between the two ethnic groups. They restricted the cultural gap solely to be distinct regarding rural Berbers and retaining their traditional dialect/language, *Tamazight*.

Prior to French settler colonialism in Algeria, Berber culture was accepted and recognised as an integral part of the Maghreb Islamic region. Nevertheless, French arrival quickly emphasised and maximised the ethnic and cultural differences between the Arabs and the Berbers. In Forstag's (2009, p.87) paper about Berber Identity and Algerian Nationalism, it is stated that France used "a *divide and conquer* strategy to weaken native resistance to foreign

⁶ Kabylans are the residents of the region of Kabylia. The term is derived from the Arabic word [Qabilah] which means a tribe.

domination" and would lead to a lesser chance for anti-colonial revolutions by indigenous Algerians. Additionally, France's *mission civilisatrice*⁷ focused primarily on the Berber community in Kabylia. Brett and Fentress (1996, p.185) discuss that the colonial *mission civilisatrice* policy was framed by "the thesis of a [Berber] country and its people wrenched away from Europe by waves of invaders from the East", leading to theories that the Berber population was the indigenous and stemming from pre-Arab Christian ancestry, and France was on a mission to reinforce the Berbers' European civilisation roots.

Along with France's *divide-and-conquer* policy, separate cultural and legal institutions were created for the Berbers (Brett & Fentress, 1996). The Berbers were also granted access to education, which gave them a disproportionate advantage in the colonial state compared to Arabs, whose Quranic schools⁸ and mosques were destroyed to prevent them from religious education (Forstag, 2009). The creation of unequal opportunities, especially in terms of intellect, advanced the Berber population by decades compared to Arabs, leading to modern Berber elites and highly skilled workers, educators, and servants (Favret, 1972; Prochaska, 1990). In retrospect, France's favouritism of the Berber people was not well sought as the latter maintained a strong stand of anti-colonial nationalism. It was during the 1950s when, according to Maddy-Weitzman (2011, p.37), "Berbers held commanding positions or were disproportionately represented in nearly every political and military grouping involved in the struggle against French rule". As for Arabs, they were accepting of the French construction of Arab/Berber cultural gaps. It was reported that Arab elites were conditioned to believe that the Berber culture was impure due to foreign influence, which made it anti-Arab (Forstag, 2009). Arabs, especially Islamic nationalists, were accusatory of the Berbers due to the colonial regime's disproportionate and favouritism treatment. Maddy-Wietzman (2011) states in this regard that the favouritism of Berbers led the Arabs to question the former's nationalist and Islamic motives. These internal conflicts between Berbers and Arabs were exceedingly exacerbated after the 1962 independence referendum and postcolonial Algeria's new reconstruction era.

⁷ French for the civilisation mission.

⁸ Quranic schools were small institutions within mosques in which Islamic rules and religious bases were taught to children and young adults.

With the rise of Arab nationalism after the independence and the enforcement of the Arabisation policy across all sectors, the Amazigh were quick to revolt for their rights as an ethnic and Indigenous minority in Algeria. Berber nationalism emerged as a political and cultural movement opposing Arabisation and the pan-Arabist political ideology. It was during the 1980s that the Amazigh began rioting for cultural recognition and officialisation of their dialect after the government banned the traditional Kabyle poetry conference in Tizi-Ouzou (Moore, 2008). The postcolonial Algerian slogan remained: *Islam is our religion, Algeria is our country, Arabic is our language* and was the pillar in the reconstructive era of the postcolonial nation. As for Berbers, they only met two out of the three prerequisites: their faith and the geo-political area of residency. Berber's use of *Tamazight* language and their non-Arab culture eliminated them from the generic Algerian nationalist movement (Forstag, 2009). As a result, Algerian authorities put restrictive measures against the Berber people to reinforce the Arab identity upon all Algerian nationals. Among these measures, radio stations dedicated to the Berbers were restricted to 4 hours of programming, using Berber names was considered illegal and punishable by law, and the authorities firmly disapproved of public expression of Berber culture. With such restricted initiatives towards the Berber population, the message authorities were willing to transmit was to ignore the country's cultural diversity and linguistic composition (Benrabah, 2004).

The Berber nationalism was primarily cultural to legitimise and reinforce their presence as an ethnic minority within the Algerian society. The Amazigh demands promoting the Berber language and culture and officially recognising their existence in the national Algerian identity (Greene, 2017; Gonzalez, 2020). Amazigh activists attempt to achieve political gains through their cultural demands, especially as they have long been calling for the political integration of the Amazigh, the consolidation of their identity, social justice, and gender equity (Ennaji, 2005, 2014; Cornwell & Atia, 2012).

3.5. The Arab-Berber Dichotomy; Ethnic-Cultural Conflicts and Socio-Economic Issues

With the rise of nationalist movements in Algeria, the conflict between Berber and Arab identity grew exponentially, causing a division between both ethnicities. Many scholars focused on The Arab-Berber dichotomy to investigate core issues, causes, and solutions to

satisfy both parties. Additionally, the said dichotomy can be better understood when reviewing the major postcolonial events that surfaced within Algerian society and the socio-economic issues that faced the postcolonial state. As previously stated in Section 3.4., the independence of Algeria began with introducing the Arabisation policy to achieve Arab nationalism pursuits of an Arab Islamic identity of the Algerian people and decolonise the society from the colonial French remnants, especially language. During the early phases of postcolonial Algeria, the Berber community passively accepted the said policy. However, it was temporal. The Arabisation policy began slowly politicising and radicalising the Berber community's identity (Benrabah, 2004; 2014). It was on the verge of oppressing the Berber's cultural and national identity that "... once the state moved from 'Algerian' to 'Arab', the ethnic question could not be avoided" (Brett & Fentress, 1996, p.274).

For over 25 years, the Berber community failed to achieve their goal of recognition and awareness of the multicultural and multiethnic state. By the 1980s, it was more challenging for the minority as a new radical Islamic political movement emerged, with its increased demand for enforced Arabisation and Islamisation of the Algerian community (Quandt, 2001). With the birth of the radical Islamic movement, the Algerian state restricted any political participation of the said conservative movement but, in turn, passed a new constitution to confirm and maintain Arabic as the only language of the state and the people (Benrabah, 2014). With the rise of conflict between the state and the Islamic movement, "the Berbers of Algeria stand somewhat apart, opposed not only to the Islamist who seek to affirm the Islamic identity of the nation but also the creed of the army and the FLN" (Brett & Fentress, 1996, p.199). The Arab nationalists were unnecessarily uncomprehensive and unfair to the Berbers, whose stand with Arabs was historically noticeable. Forstag (2009) reiterates that the Berbers did not seek to challenge the Algerian state or question its geopolitical legitimacy. However, the inclusion of the Berber identity comes opposing to the state's fundamental albeit undermining aims. Benrabah (2004, p.63) adds that the state was leading a dictatorship form of nationalism:

Inheriting a multicultural country with arbitrarily drawn borders, elites used Arab nationalism - particularly Arabic language policy- to justify the new Algerian state. In this environment, rival languages and alternative cultural identities cannot be tolerated as they undermine the fundamental legitimacy of the state. (Benrabah, 2004, p.63)

The conflict between the Algerian state and the Islamist movement was quick to escalate in the 1990s when the FIS (Islamic Salvation Front) won the elections against the FLN (National Liberation Front) and consequently evoked a ten-year civil war characterised by brutality and violence by not an outsider, but the 'Algerian brother' eliciting a new ideology (Daoudi, 2018). The FIS aims were to replace the FLN's state with a divine, religious-based order named *Hikimiyaat el-Allah* (God's Wisdom) as an attempt to legitimise their extremist political and religious ideologies (Tibi, 2009). The extreme and radical order set by the FIS was detrimental in inflicting torturous acts upon whoever opposes their ideology (Mellah, 2004). They imposed rules such as banning smoking, teaching the French language, reading newspapers, forcing young men to join the forces or face execution with their families, and many radical actions justified by imposing an Islamic extremist state.

The FIS justification for their brutal actions was to set Islam as the fundamental religion of the state, from which political and cultural views are drawn. However, they misinterpreted and misrepresented Islam. Islam and Islamism are two different concepts with different systems. Islam is a faith, a cultural system with a democratic set of rules, while Islamism is drawn from political and non-democratic standpoints (Tibi, 2009). Hedges (2015, p.1) explains that "Islamism often denotes a political form of Islam, which sees 'religious' aspects being extended into areas of statecraft, law, and the public sphere. In some respects, this misunderstands what 'religion' and 'Islam' are".

The misinterpretation of Islam's laws and the radical extent to which the FIS reached has led to a fatality estimated between 44,000 and 200,000 deaths, including children, women, and the elderly (Hagelstein, 2008). The ten-year period instilled fear within the Algerian society not only from the foreigners but also from their own. Consequently, fear, trauma, and withdrawal have significantly (re)shaped the society's identity and altered what was previously perceived as freedom and postcolonial societal and political growth.

Immediately after the 1962 independence referendum, Algeria sought tremendous reforms in various governmental sectors (Laframboise et al., 1998; Abadeer & Noh, 2018) The newly elected state initially focussed on health, agriculture, education, and economy, arguing the importance of these sectors in the nation's initial rebuilding processes. Culture and identity were at the core of Algeria's reforms as they are considered an essential component of what constitutes the Algerian society. With that, the education sector was strengthened with

educators from the Middle East leading a mission to protect the Arabic language, instil Islamic values, and (re)introduce Algerians to their country's heritage, culture, and diverse societal composition.

The continuous nationalist efforts pushed to decolonise the nation encouraged sustainability within the society and ensured comfort and gradual improvement to the quality of life. However, the Civil War, also called *The Black Decade*, caused social, political, and psychological devastations. Thomas (2022) commented that the ultimate reason for the war was primarily the ill-equipped Algerians to self-govern, and "this was the inevitable corollary of the coloniser's development of the exclusionism and prejudices that prevented their development".

3.6. Summary

This chapter presents a conceptual background to address and unpack the case of Algeria as a postcolonial nation. The literature regarding the nationalist movements that emerged in Algeria during the colonial and postcolonial eras helps accentuate the recurring struggle of locating the governing identity of the Algerian people. Additionally, the consequences of such movements and other socio-economic issues offer a glimpse of the current state of the Algerian society, striving to (re)locate and clearly define its national identity and socio-cultural constituents as an independent state.

The following chapter will address the theoretical framework that directs this thesis to investigate national identity and tourists' experiences. In Chapter Four, the discussion will be more focused on identity in the postcolonial theory, the relevance of *Hybridity* and *Otherness* in postcolonial tourism studies, and to the case of Algeria.

CHAPTER FOUR: INVESTIGATING *THIRD SPACE AND OTHERNESS* IN TOURISM SETTINGS; A POSTCOLONIAL PERSPECTIVE TO ALGERIA'S CASE

4.1. Introduction

The concept of identity holds an important weight in the postcolonial studies. Said (1978) and Bhabha (1994) discussed this concept extensively in an attempt to shed light on the issues associated with the Global South and the difficulties of narrating and highlighting their identity in a world where Western epistemology is prevailing to describe the Orient's societies.

In this chapter, I conceptualise and locate the concept of identity in the postcolonial studies and tourism literature. *Otherness* and *Hybridity* hold a significant role in my research on the national identity of Algeria and tourists' experiences. I also explore the realm of branding a postcolonial identity and the theoretical underpinnings that govern and direct how branding is approached in postcolonial nations.

4.2. Identity in Postcolonial Theory; Denoting and Reflecting the Concepts of *Hybridity* and *Otherness*

Identity refers to how we respond to questions along the lines of "Who are you?", "Who are we?" and "Who am I?". These questions often indicate personal, social, or both ties to how we perceive a person's identity (Vignoles et al., 2011). A response to "Who are you?" involves a large array of social and psychological processes, notably:

The choices we make, goals we pursue, our emotional experiences, relationship with others, friendly or hostile treatment of different groups of people, and thus ultimately our own and others' psychological and physical well-being. (Vignoles, 2017, p.1)

Research on identity has been integrated within many disciplines to be widely conceptualised beyond the constraints of personal and psychological confines. In philosophy, Appiah (2005) approached the study of identity through the notion of autonomy and the

importance of individuality on the basis of finding one's place through various forms of political identity, ethnicity, politicised religion, and nationality. As for Noonan (2019), his work is more narrowed to comprehending the most fundamental bases of personal identity and answering philosophically to questions regarding problems of personal identity as debated by many 18th-century scholars such as John Locke, Thomas Reid' and David Hume. In the field of sociology, we find the works of Giddens (1991) and Woodward (2002) to be of value to the research on identity. Both of their works focus more on demystifying and exploring identity from a modern dynamism and social constructs to self, providing sociological flexibility and fluidity in understanding belonging. However, research on identity started to be integrated from a postcolonial theoretical perspective to investigate postcolonial nations' identity and representation.

Historically speaking, decolonisation has been a dominating ideology since WWII among colonised societies in Asia, Africa, and Latin America (Nasser, 2019). Nationalism prevailed in former colonised nations as an approach to decolonisation and was viewed as a cure for their issues with the coloniser. For this, nationalism was vastly associated with democracy, freedom, and socialism (Walzer, 1995). This association highlighted identity as an integral part of decolonisation efforts and aimed to pursue freedom by strengthening the sense of belonging to the land and the indigenous people's identity.

Scholars, especially from the Global South, were keen to discuss identity from a postcolonial perspective (Said, 1978; Bhabha, 1994, 2004; Kuortti & Nyman, 2007; Barker & Murray, 2010; Dizayi, 2019). Interestingly, identity holds a crucial role within the postcolonial literature and epistemology. Dizayi (2019) revealed in his paper *Locating Identity Crisis in Postcolonial Theory: Fanon and Said* that self-determination and representation are core issues within the literature about postcolonial narrative. In the same paper, Dizayi (2019) emphasises how the postcolonial theory is mostly concerned with the aftermath of colonialism without precise recognition of the colonial encounters and significant impact on identity. The significance of identity in postcolonial theory relies on investigating the social behaviour of the colonised community. Olsson (2010) states that the previously colonised societies are more likely to feel inferior to others and despise anything belonging to them. In order to overcome this sense of inferiority, they tend to mimic and adapt the habits of the Western coloniser;

however, this behaviour renders the colonised society a hybrid and results in the loss of their true identity (Bhabha, 1993).

The postcolonial literature has shown that an identity crisis is inevitable within a society that has endured colonialism (Dizayi, 2015; 2019). Such crisis continuously manifests in reflecting how postcolonial societies attempt to understand their relationship with their land and each other. Hall (1997, p.3) argues that “identities are about questions of using resources of history, language and culture in the process of becoming rather than being” and that:

Identities are always created in relation to their distinctions, the Other without which they could not exist, and thus the building of social identity becomes the question of power, what is involved or excluded. (Goleš, 2020, p.91)

The identity of a social group becomes unstable and in constant development; it justifies the importance of relationships, diversity, and differences for an identity to remain an existing component within a society. Additionally, such development in the identity asserts’ Said’s statement regarding the role of cultural resistance and development in constructing the Other (Said, 1999). To this, the process of constructing the identity justifies the means to which the construction of the Other is essential, consequently leading to creating a form of the newer spectrum to identity that is in-between the binary ‘us/them’; a hybrid space, also referred to by *Hybridity* (Bhabha, 1994).

In the traditional essentialist view, identity is considered unified, unchanging, and acquired by virtue of birth (Bucholtz, 2003, p.400). The variables that embody identity were strictly limited to social class, ethnicity, age, religion, and others, which are considered fixed and strained with time and space. However, social constructionists argued this limiting view on identity and asserted that identity should be reconstructed as fluid, emergent, multiple, and constructed through communication and discourse (Block, 2006; Giddens, 1991; Miller & Kubota, 2013).

Block (2006) underlines the importance of the social world and the common features that people share with their society’s members in shaping and forming their identity, which generally occurs through interacting with others. As a result, Jenkins (2014) suggests that identity formation is initiated as soon as the earliest socialisation process begins in people’s lives. As time goes on, this process continues along with acquiring experiences and knowledge

that construct new identities. In that way, these identities become multi-layered and multidimensional and are subject to co-existing. According to Block (2007), acquiring new identities does not imply abandoning existing ones; constructing identity is “not a half-and-half proposition whereby the individual becomes half of what he/she was and half of what he/she has been exposed to” (Block, 2007, p.21). In these circumstances, people develop a hybrid identity in a *Third Space* (Bhabha, 1994). The hybrid identity takes characteristics and features from various existing identities, whether they were old or opposing, and allows people to navigate differences between all forms of the existing identities (Block, 2007; Bhabha, 1994; Papastergiadis, 2013).

Kuortti and Nyman (2007) referred to *Hybridity* as an “intercultural transfer, ” meaning that it reflects how two cultures engage in interchangeable characteristics that produce a new identity from different cultural roots. Historically, the term “hybrid” was mostly used in biological literature and research referring to the intrarelationship between two different botanical or animal species (Kuortti & Nyman, 2007). It was later used as a derogatory term by white colonial powers, indicating a negative connotation of something to be impure and inferior. In the social science literature, the hybrid identity is widely investigated, specifically in postcolonial studies (e.g., Bhabha, 1994; Sylvester, 1999; Singh & Schmidt, 2000; Chakraborty, 2016). Bhabha’s work (1994) provides a rich reflexivity on the importance of understanding how a national identity is experienced, specifically from a postcolonial perspective, in determining the characteristics of a postcolonial identity. To this, Bhabha (1994) identifies *liminality* and *splitting* as the main components of a postcolonial identity. The experience of liminality and *in-betweenness* is prominently prevailing among colonial subjects and postcolonial writers as they attempt to articulate their identity. As for splitting, Bhabha (1994) argues that colonial subjects have been instilled with a desire to be different from who they truly are, and due to the coloniser’s alienation policies and treatment, colonised subjects are dissatisfied with their own identity, and as a result, this desire creates a tension that Bhabha named as *splitting* (p.44).

Upon reviewing Frantz Fanon’s work, Bhabha mentions:

‘Black skin, white mask’ is not a neat division; it is a doubling, dissembling image of being in at least two places at once that makes it impossible for the devalued, insatiable évolué ... to accept the colonizer’s invitation to identity: ‘You are a doctor, a writer, a student, you are different, you are one of us.’ It is

precisely in that ambivalent use of ‘different’ -to be different from those that are different makes you the same- that the Unconscious speaks of the form of otherness, the tethered shadow of deferral and displacement. (Bhabha, 1994, pp.44-45)

In this excerpt, Bhabha goes beyond explaining how colonised subjects face the difficulty of locating themselves, perhaps even unintentionally othering the self due to the coloniser’s assimilation policies. Additionally, Bhabha emphasises the widely foreseen instability of identity that continues to be a part of the postcolonial experience of the community. To this, Bhabha (1994, pp.46-47) comments on the work of the migrant poet named Adil Jussawalla and says:

What these repeated negations of identity dramatize, in their elision of the seeing eye that must contemplate what is missing or invisible, is the impossibility of claiming an origin for the Self (or Other) within a tradition of representation that conceives of identity as the satisfaction of a totalizing, platitudinous object of vision. By disrupting the stability of invisibility of which the migrant poet speaks changes the very terms of our recognition of the person. (Bhabha, 1994, pp.46-47)

As prescribed by Bhabha, the postcolonial experience of identity and its association with negative feelings about one’s identity are considered prevalent themes in literature discussing marginalised and oppressed people, particularly within indigenous communities that struggle to recognise and understand their identities. In tourism literature, it is widely investigated that such negative feelings within the hybrid identity can influence the overall tourist experience. A few examples can be mentioned, such as the work of Stephenson and Hughes (2005) on the UK Black Caribbean community and the work of Wearing, Stevenson, and Young (2009) on the hybrid travel cultures’ influence on the tourist experience.

4.3. The Hybrid Identity in Tourism

In tourism literature, the hybrid identity is mostly implied within a postcolonial framework to understand all influencing factors on identity, with a certain focus on colonial consequences instead of postcolonial policies to decolonise such identities. Zhang, L’Espoir Decosta, and Mckercher (2015) presented an analytical study on how postcolonial Hong Kong relies on myths that are embedded within the sociocultural and political heritage of the nation in an attempt to convey the nation’s hybrid identity that is separate and different from China’s. Through this study, the authors delivered an interesting result of how Hong Kong exploits its

colonial past by creating a hybrid identity by enhancing the characteristics of “local Chineseeness” without being constantly confused with China’s identity. The ethnographic study on Sarawakian-Chinese experiences with identity formation when visiting China (Tie et al., 2015) also contributes to the literature on hybrid identities from a tourism perspective. This study was significant in drawing clear lines of the role of visiting the homeland in forging new hybrid identities outside of the homeland. It attests to the vitality of identity formation in tourism contexts and tourist experiences with locating and (re)constructing their identity.

The idea of exploring identities, especially among diasporic groups and previously colonised communities, is more embedded in the literature investigating education, religion, and language. Tourism and its relationship with hybrid identities (re)construction is seemingly an overshadowed focus in the existing literature (Timothy & Olsen, 2006; Tie et al., 2015). Visiting the homeland, whether from the perspective of domestic or international tourism, may play a significant role in building a cultural connection with the past and place and “reflect on the perennial questions of diasporic existence and the individual’s relationship to place” (Kelner, 2010, p.3). A case study that is closer in proximity to my thesis focus was conducted by Zineb Charai in Morocco. Charai (2014) investigated tourism's effects on Morocco's cultural identity, with a narrowed interest in the old Medina of Fez. In her work, Charai (2014) focused on evaluating the interrelationship between tourism and intercultural attributes and their role in mitigating and/or strengthening the cultural identity of Moroccans. Through this study, Charai shed light on the impact of tourism on the cultural identity of the old Medina of Fez and highlighted the attribute of *Otherness* in shaping the identity and heritage. Another interesting study concerning national identity was by Zhang, Fong, Li, and Ly (2019). Zhang et al. (2019) focused on investigating the social and political role cultural festivals in Macao play in celebrating the postcolonial hybrid identities. This study was quite interesting as it reflects a postcolonial theoretical framework of *Hybridity* to illustrate the characteristics of the Macao identity in cultural festivals and the political desire to strengthen the hybrid identity in postcolonial Macao.

There seems to be a commonality among postcolonial literature emphasising the notion of celebrating the hybrid identity. This ideology reflects how culture and identity have been perceived, and the focus was turned “towards investigation of the real phenomenon of individuals interacting with one another with their natural environments” (Sahlins, 1976, p.95).

culture and identity are now a flexible and fluid realm of “communal thought in which people of a given society participate” (Hollinshead, 1998, p.122). The national identity’s fluidity and consequential interaction with the coloniser’s identity was the centre of attention for Bhabha and his work *The Location of Culture* (1994). Bhabha’s thesis is centred around acknowledging that people’s identifications are extensively directed through a Eurocentric, gendered, and colonised rhetoric, especially in Western epistemology. For this, Bhabha attests that those new areas of conflictual articulation of meaning and place in which the colonised subject is within a contested category are to be celebrated. However, Hollinshead (1998) argues that tourism politics cannot be highly relevant and accommodating to the constant changes to identity in ensuring proper representation of such hybrid characteristics to celebrate them. Arguably, I find that the domestic tourism market may be a suitable environment to answer Hollinshead’s questions concerning the relevance and adequate representation of the said hybrid identities. Within the domestic market, marketers and tourism scholars are well aware of their own hybrid identity and can ensure proper (re)presentation to reflect their identity’s *Hybridity* and uniqueness. This trend is widely noticed among scholars investigating postcolonial cases such as Hong Kong’s Chineseness (Zhang et al., 2015), the Sarawakian identity (Tie et al., 2015), the Māori identity (Amoamo, 2008), and the Southeast Asian identities (Hitchcock et al., 2010). Despite not all scholars explicitly demonstrating their desire to celebrate the hybrid identity of previously colonised communities, they are clearer in presenting such identities to shift the Western colonial narrative and be the voice of their identities. However, one might wonder: Could this interest in celebrating the hybrid identity be an outcome of colonialism? Or is it the new approach to decolonise the self and deliberately and consciously come to terms with the sociocultural interactions that gave birth to such *Hybridity*?

4.4. Investigating *Third Space* and *Otherness* in Algeria’s Postcolonial Tourism

When reviewing the case of Algeria, the aftermath of the long settler colonialism by the French significantly impacted the Algerian identity. Scholarship focusing on the case of Algeria lacks an in-depth analysis of the recurring patterns within the Algerian societal behaviour reflecting the postcolonial identity. For this reason, the theoretical framework of this study was established to investigate a gap in the literature concerning the Algerian tourists’ behaviour and experiences upon locating and understanding their national hybrid identity. Literature on Algeria’s tourism has been mostly narrowed down to studying the sector’s

planning policies, strategies, and ways to advance the field from a top-bottom perspective. Algerian scholars widely focus on discussing the Tourism development plan Horizon 2030 with its subsidiary schemes SDAT 2025⁹ and SNAT 2025¹⁰. The work of Abada and Foura (2019) focuses on the government's objectives to create a sustainable tourism culture through the tourism development plan SDAT 2025 and SNAT 2025. The work of Sadaoui and Kheniche (2019) approaches the study of tourism from the perspective of focusing on heritage protection and its importance to the overall tourism sector in Algeria. Other angles that Algerian tourism scholars focused on, especially in recent years, are tourism development perspectives and consumers' demands (Zeraib et al., 2022; Taibi, 2016; Louardi et al., 2018; Meftah et al., 2022); postcolonial heritage management and decision-making process to maintain sustainable tourism policies (Coslett, 2020; Aouchal et al., 2022); and cultural heritage sites' protection and sustainability (Rahal et al., 2020; Pirzada, 2019; Berbache & Hadjab, 2020). However, little has been done regarding the tourist experience, specifically the tourist's postcolonial identity (re)construction and understanding. In this study, I attempt to establish a clearer understanding and an emphasis on the tourist's perspective, their postcolonial identity recognition, and (re)construction through domestic tourism. Additionally, this study's theoretical framework indulges within the interdisciplinary field of postcolonial tourism in mirroring Bhabha's *Third Space* and *Otherness* theory.

In this study, the notions of *Hybridity* and *Otherness* are highly prioritised. As a case study, Algeria presents a unique interrelated representation of a hybrid identity. With a background denoting settler colonialism and self-determination pursuits, a hybrid identity was brought to light to serve as a *Third Space* to belong to for the Algerian society. My views on hybrid identity in Algeria are drawn from personal experiences; for this, I attempt to construct a way to approach how I am willing to investigate tourism and *Hybridity*. The Algerian tourist experience can be shaped by many influences that dictate the outcome of the travel experience. With Algerians' quest to identify and locate identity and the postcolonial implications causing

⁹ SDAT; an acronym of "le Schéma de Développement et d'Aménagement de Tourisme". SDAT refers to the tourism development plan initiated by Algeria's tourism sector as part of the Horizon 2030 scheme.

¹⁰ SNAT; an acronym of "le Schéma National d'Aménagement de Tourisme". SNAT refers to the tourism development plan to improve the national infrastructure for tourism development as part of the Horizon 2030 scheme.

the emergence of a *Hybridity* phenomenon, I understand that approaching the interpretation of the postcolonial hybrid identity is best done through reviewing and interpreting the colonial/decolonial discourse that is communicated through digital branding. Through reviewing the digital constructs of postcolonial identity portrayed in tourism, I analyse the interrelationship between the consumer (the Algerian tourist) and the provider (travel agencies and content creators) in (re)shaping and endorsing decolonised narratives to identity, tourist experiences, and tourism practices. For this, I developed a diagram illustrating the process to which I am undertaking this research within postcolonial *Hybridity* framework. Figure 4.1 below illustrates how colonial legacy and national identity are presented as the predominant tourism narratives in Algerian digital platforms. These narratives are closely related to constructing and shaping the tourist experience outcome, and while the postcolonial identity is (re)shaped through colonial legacy and indigenous culture, the identity is existing in a *Third Space* that can be viewed as a *Hybrid* space uncovered through tourist's experiences. In Figure 4.1, I present the interrelation between tourism narrative and tourist experience. The tourism narrative is the discussion and the representation of the Algerian culture's legacy, from the time of Arab-Islamic and Amazigh peaceful coexistence to the colonial period of the French presence in Algeria (1830-1962). This cultural legacy has reshaped how Algerians perceive and acknowledge their current post-colonial identity, and as a result, my investigation is focused on exploring how these Algerians' experiences as domestic tourists help in uncovering, understanding, and (re)presenting the manifestation of their post-colonial hybrid identity.

Figure 4.1. The theoretical framework shaping this study

4.5. Summary

This chapter serves as a theoretical framework to shape the orientation of this research and set a plan for conducting the methodology afterwards. The chapter merely focused on key prominent theories in framing this research. *Hybridity*, *Otherness*, and *Identity* significantly factors in investigating the Algerian tourists' behaviour and experiences, shaping how national identity is perceived, discovered, and (re)constructed. I aim to investigate how Algerian tourists' experiences are related to and (re)constructing the postcolonial hybrid identity. This focus on identity (re)construction requires a postcolonial framework that highlights Bhabha's theories that are orientalised and serve a complex structure to identity understanding by tourists. This prompted this chapter to lay the theoretical underpinnings governing this investigation, focusing on Bhabha's *Hybridity* guided through Said's orientalist guidelines.

In the following chapter, I will present the research methodology used to approach this research, a detailed breakdown of the data collection and analysis processes and the ethical considerations.

CHAPTER FIVE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1. Introduction

This chapter aims to identify and explain the methodology I adopted for my study. My research dives within the realms of postcolonial theory and instigates data collected through a qualitative methodological approach to understand and interpret Algerian tourists' experiences and postcolonial identity in domestic cultural destinations. The interconnection of the tourist experience and postcolonial identity has been a contentious topic, especially within postcolonial investigations, as it requires a careful approach to interpreting tourists' worldviews regarding *Hybridity*.

In this chapter, I first present my ontological and epistemological positioning in a social constructionist paradigm. In section 5.3., I discuss the qualitative methodology I followed for this research and outlined my research approach and design. Section 5.4. covers the procedure of data collection in which I explain participants' recruitment and profile, research methods used, and data translation. Section 5.5. is dedicated to the data analysis procedure in which I discuss how thematic analysis is used to analyse interviews, focus group discussions, and images. And lastly, I provide an overview of ethical considerations, limitations to the methodology, and a summary of the chapter.

5.2. Ontological and epistemological positioning; Social Constructionism

My study reflects a focus through a postcolonial lens to examine Algerian tourists' experiences with domestic destinations and identity (re)presentation and colonial/postcolonial discourse within digital practices to promote Algeria. My research leads to investigating different analogies, mentalities, experiences, and opinions, which indicates a complex and multi-layered dimension in conducting the study (Dammak, 2015). It requires interaction and involvement with individuals to understand the phenomenon exactly how it is occurring and through their eyes rather than the researcher's (Cohen et al., 2007).

At the start of my research, my objective stemmed from a marketing perspective, in which I aimed to explore travel agencies' role in (re)shaping tourism trends and consumers' experiences with the agencies' offers. As my research was developing, my research questions

were constantly changing, and I shifted how I approached domestic tourism to be more aligned with tourists' experiences and identity discovery through digital tourism practices and within postcolonial settings. This adds certain constructionist elements when dealing with experiences that are socially developed, allowing the phenomenon to align properly within a qualitative approach. The social constructionist paradigm influences such idea as I am reflecting on how tourists' experiences are constructed to interpret their national identity.

When employing a social constructionist philosophy to research, I am acknowledging that "reality and science are socially constructed, researchers are part of the research setting" (Holliday, 2016, p.16), and that it is important to value the participants' views, perspectives, and interpretations of their realities (Cohen et al., 2007). In the present study, I approach participants' responses in the focus group discussions and interviews, visual representation of Algerian identity and culture, and my observations of the tourist's practices as a reality constructed by the participants, reflecting the value delivered through distinctive experiences and worldviews. Additionally, my observations and interpretation of the participants' experiences position me as an insider taking part in the investigation I am conducting. For this, I attest to the value of flexibility the constructionist paradigm offers when collecting data and constructing themes in the data analysis process.

Social constructionism, or the social construction of reality, is society's theory of knowledge and examination of communication (Galbin, 2014). It sheds light on the perspective of human existence based on social and interpersonal influences (Gergen, 1985). Social constructionists believe knowledge arises from human relationships and interactions (Gergen, 2011), and environmental factors influence relationships, creating reality (Vinney et al., 2019). The social constructionist perspective can be defined as "locating meaning in an understanding of how ideas and attitudes are developed over time within a social, community context" (Dickerson & Zimmerman, 1996, p.80).

The social constructionist theory acquired aspects from post-positivism and interpretivism (Levers, 2013). Social constructionism resembles post-positivism in terms of ontological understanding of reality. It implies a critical realist ontology in its need for logical reasoning and attention to the empirical evidence (Crossan, 2003). Social constructionism is also characterised by epistemological subjectivism. Meaning-making interaction is influenced by the phenomena and society constructing such meaning (Levers, 2013). Hence, the acquired

knowledge demands subjective conceptualisation and understanding of its constituents and underlying meaning that is accessible through involving my worldviews, concepts, and background to the investigation.

In tourism studies, constructionism is often used interchangeably with the term constructivism. The inconsistency in terminology led Crotty (1998) to propose a defying explanation for both terms. Crotty suggested that constructivism pertains to epistemological considerations to analyse the meaning-making process of the individual mind, whereas constructionism dictates the study of the collective creation of meaning. More often, the term "social" is coined with constructionism to reflect the understanding of how meaning is most commonly created out of collectiveness and transmission; hence, the social stance is embedded within the epistemology (Hacking, 2001). Nonetheless, the adjective "social" does not reduce constructionism to a less social investigation. However, it emphasises the social origin of meaning and the importance of the social generation of ideas and thoughts in the individual's mind (Pernecky, 2012). To this, I will be using constructionism and social constructionism interchangeably as my research aim is about the combined meaning-making through my participants' individual experiences to construct what they consider their reality in Algerian society.

Various tourism scholars introduced social constructionism/constructivism practices to the tourism literature, defying the traditional approaches to studying social sciences with a positivist lens (Hollinshead, 2006; Ayikoru, 2009; Chambers, 2007; Jamal & Hollinshead, 2001). The use of social constructionism in tourism studies varies and can be depicted as a paradigm (Denzin & Lincoln, 2000; 2003; 2018; Guba & Lincoln, 1989; 2004; 2005). Some scholars use it as a technique (Williams & Irving, 1998), while others approach it as an epistemology (Crotty, 1998). Hollinshead (2006), for instance, opens the debate in his publication *The Shift to Constructivism in Social Inquiry: Some Pointers for Tourism Studies*, and presents ten shifts in the interpretative investigation of tourism studies, including perspectivity/intersubjective understanding, relativism, situated research, and justification through science. Crotty's (1998) belief of constructionism as an epistemology insinuates that research involving human experiences and performance indicates that these experiences construct meaning and contribute to the overall worldviews and interpretations of phenomena. Constructionism as an epistemology is what drives this research to understand postcolonial

tourists' experiences. Employing Crotty's social constructionism as an epistemology (1998) in a tourism study where participants are to be sharing their experiences, worldview's reality that is uniquely theirs, and their contribution to establishing a collective reality constructed based on their individual experiences will certainly reflect the binary relationship between the subject (the tourist in this research) and the object (the act of tourism) and the importance of such interaction in constructing the reality of the studied phenomenon.

On the same note, conducting a tourism investigation through a constructionist epistemology requires establishing the methodology based on the epistemic underpinnings. Crotty (1998) argues that an investigation should follow a certain order that consists of (1) establishing the epistemology of the research, (2) considering the theoretical perspective that is about to be covered, (3) choosing the methodology based on the epistemological underpinnings, and finally (4) identifying the data collection tools to be used in the study. According to Crotty (1998), such order will be an intellectual indication to establish a qualitative methodological basis.

5.3. Research Approach

The choice of research methodology approach is a critical decision that significantly shapes and directs the process and outcome of any scholarly research. The main approaches used in research are inductive and deductive approach. Deductive approach is a theory-driven model that is more used in quantitative research. While inductive approach follows a rigorous process of specific observations and empirical data to develop a broader conceptualisations and theoretical explanations. In this study, I used the inductive approach to investigate the complex phenomenon of postcolonial tourist identity, and shed light on the lived experiences, perspectives, and meaning-making processes to reveal insights that may challenge the dominant narratives (Wearing et al., 2009).

The inductive approach begins with the systematic collection and analysis of data, from which patterns, themes, and possible explanations can emerge organically (Bryman, 2012; Gioia et al., 2013). This is opposed to the deductive approach which starts with a pre-conceived hypothesis and theoretical framework that is later tested through empirical investigation. One main feature of the inductive approach is that conclusions and theories are to be derived from the data; this allows the researchers to engage in an open-ended, exploratory process to produce

newer insights and conceptualisation from their observations and analyses (Saunders et al., 2019).

When using an inductive approach, the researcher will notice the approach's openness to novel insights and its suitability to new or under-researched topics to uncover unexpected findings that may challenge existing assumptions (Patton, 2015). This is valuable when investigating the complexity of postcolonial identity in tourism context which prompts challenging pre-existing knowledge about identity in the Western epistemology. Additionally, the approach provides detailed, contextual understandings of the phenomena under investigation as it is frequently paired with qualitative methods that ensure nuanced data and richer interpretations (Yin, 2018). This also leads to the development of newer theories and improving the explanatory relevance of the resulting theoretical framework, with the flexibility in enabling organic and adaptive approach (Suddaby, 2006; Eisenhardt, 1989).

With all this being said, the researcher should consider the limitations of the inductive approach and attempt to address them while developing the study. One weakness that can be located, especially in postcolonial tourism studies, is the limited generalisability of the findings. As the focus of inductive approach is on depth rather than breadth, there might be few restrictions to generalising the findings beyond the scope of the research (Ateljevic & Doorne, 2002). This also poses a challenge to replicating the research design and findings and limit the ability to validate or extend insights on studies with different variables, contexts, and settings (Golafshani, 2003). Another weakness is the researcher bias that is prompted by the exploratory nature of the inductive approach. The open-ended characteristic of the approach, although helpful in broadening the findings of a study, can be vulnerable to researcher bias in the data collection, analysis, and interpretation stages (Braun & Clarke, 2006). This is crucial to be aware of so that researchers can acknowledge and mitigate their positionality when conducting the investigation. One way of mitigating such limitations would be triangulation, reflexivity, and the articulation of clear boundaries around the scope and context of the study.

Through the use of inductive approach in postcolonial tourism context, along with qualitative research methods, I will be able to gain richer, contextual understandings of how postcolonial tourists navigate and construct their identities through tourism practices. This will prompt the development of novel theoretical models that better capture the nuanced, flexible nature of postcolonial identity, and shed light on Algerian landscape which has been lacking

extensive research. Additionally, due to the flexible nature of inductive approach, I am allowed to remain responsive to unexpected findings, enabling the exploration of novel dimensions that may have been overlooked or unexplored in previous studies (Eisenhardt, 1989).

5.4. Research Design

In every study that focuses on exploring a new phenomenon, understanding its intricacy, explaining it through theory, qualitative research is ideal to address such points (Ellis & Levy, 2009). As I previously mentioned all throughout this chapter, my investigation is exploratory in nature, seeking to understand postcolonial tourist interpretations of their hybrid identity, and the decolonial efforts in (re)presenting the national/cultural identity. Therefore, a qualitative research design is more suitable to address my research questions. According to Creswell and Poth (2018, p.8 citing Creswell, 2013, p44):

Qualitative research begins with assumptions and the use of interpretive/theoretical frameworks that inform the study of research problems addressing the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. To study this problem, qualitative researchers use an emerging qualitative approach to inquiry, the collection of data in a natural setting sensitive to the people and places under study, and data analysis that is both inductive and deductive and establishes patterns or themes. The final written report or presentation includes the voices of participants, the reflexivity of the researcher, a complex description and interpretation of the problem, and its contribution to the literature or a call for change.

This definition reflects how qualitative research is fundamentally rooted in a social constructionist worldview, where the focus is on understanding how individuals interpret and make meaning of their lived experiences (Denzin & Lincoln, 2000, Merriam, 1998). It also attests to the choice of a qualitative approach that is deeply tied to the researcher's underlying ontological, epistemological, and methodological beliefs and assumptions. Within an interpretive paradigm, qualitative researchers seek to uncover the subjective realities and perspectives of their participants, reorganising that reality is not separate from the researcher, but rather co-constructed through their interactions and engagements (Lincoln, 2013). Ultimately, the choice of a qualitative design signals the researcher's commitment to prioritising participants' voices, exploring the complexities of human experience, and addressing issues of social justice and equity within the research process (Denzin & Lincoln, 2000).

In postcolonial tourism studies, qualitative research design allows to delve deeper into the subjective experiences, perceptions, and sociocultural contexts that shape the identities of tourists. In a sense, the qualitative design provides insights to capture nuanced and complex nature of postcolonial investigations. When using qualitative methods, such as in-depth interviews, observations, and focus group discussions, a rich and contextual understanding is gained about how postcolonial tourists navigate and negotiate their identities through postcolonial legacy (Mkono, 2016). As Hollinshead (2004) suggests, postcolonial tourism is a site of ongoing negotiations, where tourists engage in complex identity-making processes. Qualitative methods, such as focus group discussions and interviews, can capture these nuanced and evolving identity constructions, providing valuable insights for understanding the fluid and multifaceted nature of postcolonial tourist identity (Tucker, 2016).

Having established my methodological approach and design, the research questions are:

- To what extent is the postcolonial identity of Algerian tourists influencing their experiences in domestic tourism practices?
- How are domestic tourism trends featured and communicated on digital platforms to influence and (re)shape the Algerian tourists' experiences and their postcolonial identity?

Research questions	Theoretical framework	Data collection method	Sample	Analysis procedure
To what extent is the postcolonial identity of Algerian tourists influencing their experiences in domestic tourism practices?	<i>Hybridity</i> and <i>Otherness</i> theories are employed in prescribing the longitudinal effects of colonialism on postcolonial tourists' experiences	Focus group discussions; follow-up semi-structured interviews	Algerian domestic tourists	

<p>How are domestic tourism trends featured and communicated on digital platforms to influence and (re)shape the Algerian tourists' experiences and their postcolonial identity?</p>	<p><i>Hybridity</i> and <i>Ottherness</i> theories are employed in prescribing the longitudinal effects of colonialism on postcolonial tourists' experiences</p>	<p>Semi-structured interviews; images: videos, posters, social media</p>	<p>Travel agencies; Algerian travel influencers</p>	<p>Thematic Analysis</p>
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Table 5-1 Overview of the methodological plan

5.5.Procedure of Data Collection

In June 2020, I got ethical approval from the University of the West of Scotland's Ethics Committee, allowing me to begin conducting my data collection. As the data collection procedure was to be conducted online, I anticipated gaining a richer insight into the phenomenon of domestic tourism. This was primarily because while collecting data online, I could recruit participants from different regions of Algeria, which evidently led to a wider and more diverse sample to support my investigation, as opposed to having a sample of participants that belong to the same regional attribute. The online data collection presents the opportunity to recruit participants and discuss different experiences shaped and directed by different backgrounds, traditions, and age/social groups. Adding to that, my background as an Algerian female who has also been a domestic tourist helps build rapport with the participants as we share the same historical and sociocultural knowledge in terms of interest in domestic tourism, the linguistic ability to communicate in Algerian dialectal Arabic, and comfort when talking to someone from their society to discuss opinions and experiences. The rapport positioned me in an insider perspective to facilitate data collection for myself as a member of the participants' community and allow participants to discuss their experiences comfortably.

When investigating domestic tourism from a postcolonial perspective, using different research tools to match my inductive approach was important. In this research, I used the following qualitative methods to answer my research questions: (1) focus group discussions,

(2) semi-structured interviews, and (3) visuals. When employing these qualitative methods, I had to follow a specific plan to select my participants to collect and analyse my data. Below, I detail the process I followed during this investigation.

Reflecting on the research journey, I believe the data collection process began at the start of my PhD programme when I followed domestic tourism influencers and travel agencies on social media (Facebook and Instagram). The main reasons for using these platforms were (1) to stay up to date with their latest activities and posts related to domestic tourism (their upcoming trips to domestic destinations, their collaborations with travel agencies/ associations, and current travel offers to domestic destinations), and (2) because both platforms are the most used by Algerians (Statista, 2022) which allowed me to reflect on their audiences' perception of domestic tourism on these posts.

The data collection process was unique in its characteristics as it was modified due to the global pandemic of Covid-19. Initially, I planned to conduct focus group discussions in Sidi Bel Abbes and Oran in Algeria, where I pre-booked conference rooms to hold the discussions in person. I also planned on visiting the International Tourism Exhibition -SIAHA- in Oran in February 2021 to conduct semi-structured interviews with travel agencies exhibiting their domestic destination offers at the event and attend conferences held by the organising committee and tourism officials. However, due to travel restrictions and a ban on gatherings across Algeria, in addition to the exhibition being cancelled until further notice, I had to reconsider the data collection process to be held online while in the UK. For this, I divided my data collection process into three stages (see Table below); stage one was dedicated to collecting data through focus group discussions. I contacted Algerian tourists by posting a request on a popular Facebook page dedicated to Algerian tourism destinations and contacted travel content creators through Instagram to arrange focus group discussions via Zoom. I also gathered images and posters from Instagram accounts of Algerian content creators and Algerian travel agencies respectively. Stage two was dedicated to recruiting travel agencies' representatives to arrange semi-structured interviews via Zoom. These representatives were members of a Facebook group named "Offre & Demande Touristique"¹¹, in which travel

¹¹ French for Offer and Tourism Request [available in: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/282875262711913/>]

agencies and tourists are joined for the purpose of advertising and purchasing offers. Stage Three emerged after I started the data analysis process. During the thematic analysis of the data collected through the focus group discussions, I uncovered the emergence of various themes, namely the concept of identity crisis, postcolonial impact, and postcolonial Algerian identity. These themes necessitated more data to accurately represent the Algerian tourists' perception and attitude toward domestic tourism. For this, I contacted my participants through Facebook and requested their consent to conduct one-to-one interviews to answer and discuss more questions. In so doing, **eight** participants agreed to one-to-one interviews conducted online via Zoom. Table 5.2. Below is the procedure of data collection that I conducted for this thesis:

Data Collection Stages	Procedure
Stage 1 - Focus Group Discussion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Posted a request form in a popular Facebook page to recruit participants; • Recruited 34 tourist-participants; • Gathered consent forms from participants; • Conducted four focus group discussions.
Stage 2 – Semi Structured Interviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Posted a request form in a Facebook group dedicated for travel agencies; • Recruited 7 travel agencies; • Gathered consent forms from participants; • Conducted semi-structured interviews.
Stage 3 – Follow-up interviews with tourist-participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contacted tourist-participants via Facebook Messenger for interview recruitment; • Recruited 8 tourist-participants; • Gathered consent forms from tourist-participants; • Conducted follow-up interviews.

Table 5-2 The data collection procedure

5.5.1. Qualitative Methods

This investigation is qualitative and employs the combination of three different qualitative methods to ensure providing answers to the study. Below, I discuss each qualitative method I used in this study.

5.5.1.1. Focus group discussions

Using focus group discussion as a qualitative research tool provides the opportunity to understand the social phenomenon of postcolonial tourism trends in Algeria among domestic tourists. Throughout this research method, I acquired in-depth evidence to explore participants' ideas, understanding, experiences, and perceptions of the study in an interactive means (Nyumba et al., 2018; Strielkowski et al., 2012). I am also permitted to ask about specific points that might arise during the discussion and gain more insight into additional information, especially with a complex historical/colonial background like Algerians. In addition, it facilitates engagement between the participants and encourages debates with richer explanatory answers. Mack et al. (2005) propose that focus groups proved effective in allowing participants to freely express their thoughts with others interested in the discussed topic and attentively listen to their opinions, which might not happen more often in their daily lives. The non-directiveness of the focus group method also allows us to understand better and discover people's experiences (Weeden, 2005) as the participants are engaged in the topic and eliciting opinions and beliefs that will help develop the topic in question (Halcomb et al., 2007).

The focus group discussion method is used as a qualitative approach to obtain an in-depth understanding of a social issue and investigation. Morgan (1996, p.129) defines focus group discussion as "a research technique that collects data through group interaction on a topic determined by the researcher". While Albanesi (2014, p.2310) provides a general definition of the focus group method:

A qualitative research technique based on the idea that the group interaction facilitates the production of original information: through group discussion, people have the opportunity to express their ideas but also to form and modify them as the discussion develops, similarly to what happens in natural conversational settings.

The use of focus group discussion as a qualitative method started in the 1930s when scholars had a growing doubt regarding the accuracy of traditional data collection tools; thus, they started implementing focus groups (Krueger & Casey, 2000; Strielkowski et al., 2012). The method was widely used among social scientists, especially during WWII, to investigate the psychology and experiences of U.S. Army veterans (Strielkowski et al., 2012). However, it was later implemented by marketing researchers as they were seeking to understand consumers' preferences and products' attractiveness (Morgan, 1996). Arguably, focus group discussion became widely popular among qualitative researchers due to its advantages compared to interviews and observation. Krueger (1994, p.19) states that since focus group provides a more natural environment than individual interviews, focus group participants "are influencing and influenced by others – just as they are in real life". Additionally, the natural environment provided contributes to less control of the interviewer over the discussion and allows the participants to engage in a debate among themselves to discuss their opinions, experiences, and worldviews (Litosseliti, 2003).

The planning process for the focus group discussion method requires an attentive and thorough schedule to cover participants' number to be recruited, how many groups to be held, and the meeting location to meet participants' convenience. Focus group discussions generally include six to eight participants, with an over-recruitment of 10-25% (Krueger & Casey, 2000; Rabiee, 2004; Powell & Single, 1996). Hence, I recruited ten participants for each of the four discussion groups to avoid disorganisation, challenges in managing the group, and the possibility of some participants failing to attend (See data collection procedure).

Between October 3rd, and October 28th, 2020, I carried out four focus group discussions via Zoom with 34 participants in total. Each focus group included participants from different societal, educational background, as well as different indigeneity and geographical locations. Group A was totalled to seven participants, Group B was totalled to eight participants, Group C was totalled to 10 participants, while Group D was totalled to nine participants. The four focus groups were held online via Zoom video calls. Zoom was selected due to my inability to conduct my fieldwork in person during the Covid-19 pandemic. Despite the fieldwork being conducted online through a video conferencing tool, I could take notes of the participants' mannerisms, facial expressions, and natural pauses, which reflected a similar setting to direct in-person communication. The discussion was later transcribed from the Algerian Arabic

dialect to English, verbatim, to be forwarded to a third party to verify transcription authenticity and accuracy. On average, each focus group discussion lasted 90 minutes, and video recordings and transcripts were stored in a password-protected file on my computer. Participants were also asked to maintain communication via Facebook and Gmail for potential withdrawal of data or additional questions for the study.

5.5.1.2. Semi-structured Interviews

Interviews were the second research method I selected for my data collection procedure. I conducted semi-structured interviews with travel agencies' representatives to understand their role in promoting and endorsing the current tourism trends in Algeria and depicting their opinions regarding the postcolonial tourism agenda and Horizon 2030. The purpose of using interviews with travel agencies is to understand how they contribute to colonial/postcolonial discourse and the decolonisation of Algeria's tourism, meaning whether travel agencies are reinforcing the colonial legacy or decolonising the tourism sector.

As a research tool, the interview is generally used one-on-one with participants to collect qualitative data about their experiences, beliefs, and views of a phenomenon (Lambert & Loiselle, 2008). The interview can be formed in various designs, depending on the study's aims and the desired data to be collected. The three main types of qualitative interviews identified by Babbie et al. (2007) are 1) the standardised interview, 2) the semi-standardised interview, and 3) the unstandardised interview. The standardised or structured interview follows a strict schedule of formulating and wording the questions for open-ended answers, offering no room for participants to deviate from the topic (Turner, 2010; Ryan et al., 2009). One feature of the standardised interviews, which I find too rigid and similar to a questionnaire survey, is that all participants are asked identical questions in the same order, offering the researcher limited responses for comparability (Berg, 2009). Semi-standardised or semi-structured interviews provide more flexibility to the interview process, allowing more space for unanticipated answers and the emergence of new angles to the studied phenomenon (Tod, 2006; Ryan et al., 2009). Such flexibility allows the researcher to gather data about the general areas of the study from all participants (McNamara, 2009) whilst getting richer and more textured data (Ryan et al., 2009). Unstandardised or unstructured interviews are predominantly casual and can be seen as informal conversational interviews. This type allows the researcher to generate the questions spontaneously (Gall et al., 2003) and engage in a non-directive natural

interaction with the interviewee with broad themes rather than questions to contribute to a fieldwork observation (Ryan et al., 2009).

Between February and March 2021, I conducted seven semi-structured interviews via online platform Zoom with travel agencies' representatives. These travel agencies were selected based on their role as exhibitors in the SIAHA tourism fair in Algeria, and as promoters of domestic tourism through their offers. Interviewing travel agencies was for the purpose of seeking an answer to understanding their role in reshaping the domestic tourism trends in Algeria. Their contribution to national fairs and exhibitions, and online, highlighted how the postcolonial national identity is used in promoting domestic tourism for Algerian tourists. During the interviews, participants shared their offers in images to illustrate how they conduct and construct promotional offers online. These images are added to the data collection process for visual content analysis.

The interviews' semi-structured form allowed the participants to be as detailed and elaborative as they pleased. Purposefully wording the questions in "how" and "why" offered freedom to expand their ideas and prompted access to their experiences regarding how trends are shaped in postcolonial settings. The interview questions were designed to acquire information about the following attributes:

1. The agency offers in terms of tourism;
2. The agency's approach to developing offers and selecting destinations;
3. The agency's marketing processes;
4. The agency's networking processes with other DMOs and consumers through exhibitions and fairs;
5. How culture and national identity are embedded within Algeria's brand image development;
6. The prospects sought in terms of domestic tourism;
7. The inclusion of postcolonial national identity in their offers.

5.5.1.3. Visual research methods; photo-elicitation interviewing

Images are a useful tool to explore and interpret representations. Dealing with images is an important constituent of semiotics; the study of signs and meaning aims to give images a sense, an interpretation, and wide representations to the observer. Bryman (2012, p.565) defined semiotics as:

...invariably referred to as the “science of signs”. It is an approach to analysis of symbols in everyday life and as such can be employed in relation not only to documentary sources but also to all kinds of other data because of its commitment to treating phenomena as texts ... semiotics is concerned to uncover the hidden meanings that reside in texts as broadly defined.

Semiotics is often coined with the work of Roland Barthes (1973), a French theorist who studied the formulation “people, places and things” depicted in images and the approach to follow to make sense of these components in interpreting the image in its entirety. Barthes (1973) states that the image represents an “imitative art” that only carries a copy of reality. Van Leeuwen (2011, p.4) comments that:

Perceiving photographs is closely analogous to perceiving reality because photographs provide a point-by-point correspondence to what was in front of the camera, even though they reduce this reality in size, flatten it and, in the case of black and white, drain it of colour”. In a sense, images (or visuals) do not provide evidence of the “now” rather it reflects the “then”; it delivers the message of the past form of reality while presenting a newer reality of “having been there.

Barthian visual semiotics constitutes a layering of the meaning with connotative and denotative interpretation. The layer of denotation reflects the immediate, fixed, and abstract message obtained of ‘what/who is being depicted in the image?’. Barthes refers to denotation as a message with “a universal symbolic order” in which the interpretation of what is seen is constituted by recognising who/what is depicted, what is done, and what is seen (Barthes, 1977, p.18). The connotation layer, on the other hand, is flexible with broader concepts, ideas and values that justify what the message stands for. The message is often attributed to cultural associations about the “people, place and things”. Accordingly, Barthes (1977, p.27) defines connotations as:

... neither ‘natural’ nor ‘artificial’ but historical, or if it be preferred, ‘cultural’. Its signs are gestures, attitudes, expressions, colours, or effects, endowed with certain meanings by virtue of the practice of a certain society: the links between signifier and signified remains if not unmotivated, at least entirely historical.

Semiotics presents an approach to studying and interpreting signs, of which visuals and culture are part of (Pashaki et al., 2016). Barthes’ ideology of culture being a given currency shared by people and accentuated by the style and content of images, it is fairly suitable to implement his visual semiotics approach in investigating the domestic tourism trends depicted on social media and their influence on tourists’ experiences. It answers the questions ‘What

ideas and values do people, places, and things represented in images stand for?’ and ‘How do these interpretations redirect patterns to tourists’ experiences?’.

Images were first introduced as a qualitative tool in the mid-19th century in studies of social and cultural anthropology, ethnology, and folklore (Harper, 1988; Schnettler & Raab, 2009). It was significantly used as a methodology in studying Indigenous communities, such as Franz Boas’ work on Kwakiutl Indians in British Columbia, Canada (1894), Alfred Haddon’s work on the Torres Straits in Australia and Papua New Guinea (1898), Malinowski’s fieldwork on the Trobriand Islanders in Papua New Guinea (1915). The emergence of Cultural Studies in the 1960s and Media Studies in the 1980s refocused on the use of visuals within the field of sociology (Murdock & Pink, 2005). Images, especially in ethnographic studies, were implemented within many disciplines, including “... health studies, sports studies, ethnology, tourism studies, organisation studies, and art therapy” (Pink, 2009, p.15).

Images in research can be used in two ways: to gather data while investigating a social phenomenon and to analyse what was found within the studied community (Pink, 2013). According to Harper (1988, p.55), “Some sociologists take photographs to study the social world, whereas others analyze the photographs others have taken in institutionalized occupational settings or in their family lives”. Visuals, more specifically images, are classified into three categories: images as ‘writing’, ‘found’ images, and creative use of images (O’Reilly, 2005). Images as ‘writing’ is similar in role to that of a text as it elicits clear meaning without the need to elaborate or write something in it. It can also be presented as a supportive element to a text or to make an argument. ‘Found’ participants or members of the studied community capture images. At the same time, creative use of images refers to images used as expressive in forms of art.

The use of images and creative methods in qualitative studies increased in social science research, specifically psychology studies (Reid et al., 2018). Images were used in combination with interviews to investigate various topics to create a stimulus to elicit more data and enrich the findings (Reid et al., 2018; Folkestad, 2000). Folkestad’s work on using images in interviews provided a concrete starting point for interviewing people with intellectual disabilities (2000). In her small pilot study conducted with people with intellectual disabilities living in their homes or grouped homes, participants were asked to take pictures of themselves in daily encounters. These images were later used as a discussion tool with the participants,

providing a helpful, familiar topic of conversation to express their viewpoints and assist in understanding participants' language use. Folkestad's study (2000, p.18) concluded that photographs "provide a more concrete base for our conversations than verbally formulated questions would do".

Clark-Ibáñez (2004) also investigated the social world using Photo-Elicitation Interviews (PEI) as a supplement to ethnography. PEI is a qualitative method in which the researcher introduces photographs in interviews (Collier & Collier, 1986; Harper, 2002). Photographs can be produced by either the researcher or the participant, and in this study, participants were responsible for taking photographs to be discussed during the interviews. According to Clark-Ibáñez (2004, p.1512), "researchers can use photographs as a tool to expand on questions and simultaneously, participants can use photographs to provide a unique way to communicate dimensions of their lives".

Throughout this study, I selected seven images posted on social media, mainly on Instagram, which were captured by either the participants or any member of the Algerian community. The images I selected from Instagram's public profiles were used to elicit data through the representation and meaning of the images. The images (see Appendix 8) were presented during the focus group discussions for the participants to elicit conversation about domestic tourism, cultural significance, national identity, and their decision-making processes upon observing places and interpreting images. The use of Photo-Elicitation Interviewing was crucial in encouraging participants to converse into in-depth dialogue about their thoughts and interpretations of visuals, in addition to it being an approach to obtain further data that would not be gathered through questions only. As a researcher, PEI was important in facilitating rapport with the participants, and enhancing the process to interact smoothly (Meo, 2010), especially as online data collection was only popular and commonly used since the Covid-19 pandemic.

Since images elicit personal narratives and experiences, especially when presented in a group setting, as in focus group discussions (Schwartz, 1989), the selected images were incorporated in two different ways throughout this study. On the one hand, I introduced the images as a Photo-Elicitation interview approach (Clark-Ibáñez, 2004) to obtain in-depth data from participants and a richer engagement during the interviews and FGD processes. On the other hand, I used images from the participating travel agencies to briefly describe and analyse

how they are promoting domestic destinations, and reflect their work on the ground in relation to the discussions we had during the interviews.

5.5.2. Participants' recruitment

Once the research methods were established for this study, it was important to prepare, plan, and conduct the process of participants' recruitment. In a qualitative methodology, researchers are often challenged with defining the sample size for their investigation. With concerns as to whether there is an optimum number of participants to reach for the sample to be accurately representative of the studied population, there is no clear cut to it (Cohen et al., 2018). The challenging issue of sample size is often linked to the idea that qualitative research is more concerned with answering "why" and "how" questions, which is opposed to quantitative research, which relies on a larger sample to conform reliability (Cohen et al., 2018).

The sample size of a qualitative methodology is commonly smaller, with fewer participants that are asked open-ended questions, compared to the quantitative methodology, which often requires a larger sample size. These questions often include "how" and "why", allowing the participants to elaborate and provide in-depth data about the studied phenomenon. To this, Morse (2000, p.3-4) proposed five components to consider when deciding the sample size;

- (1) The scope of the study should be narrowed to avoid a lengthy process of reaching a saturation point.
- (2) The nature of the topic determines how many participants are needed. In other words, the more the topic is clear and straightforward, the fewer participants are required and the more data you can obtain.
- (3) Data quality plays an important role, especially when participants are well-engaged in the discussion and have experience and insight into the study's scope.
- (4) The study design is significantly impactful when factoring the investigation's duration, as in some instances with longitudinal studies, and there is repeated data collection that can be lengthy.
- (5) Shadowed data refers to participants drawing and referring to their experiences as similar to or different to others. This data type provides clues to enhance and facilitate the analysis of duration to go through data.

Accordingly, the sample size in a qualitative methodology cannot be pre-estimated but relies more on the quality of the collected data. The sample size cannot and should not be majorly prioritised in data collection as long as this data is richer and insightful in covering all aspects of the investigation and provides important answers drawn from the participants' experiences.

In this study, I used non-probability convenience sampling to recruit participants (Teeroovengadam & Nunkoo, 2018). The sampling technique aims to create a sample from participants who showed interest in partaking in the study and are qualified to participate based on certain conditions set by the researcher (Murairwa, 2015). To reach the desired sample, I prepared a request to recruit participants for focus group discussions in which I mentioned the study's aim and specific set of criteria for a participant to be recruited in this investigation (see Appendix.1). The criteria for inclusion are as follow: (1) the participant must have travelled to a domestic destination, (2) the participant is interested in visiting cultural sites, (3) the participant must provide an email address to be contacted for further communication and confirmation. The request was posted on a popular Facebook page named *Discovery of Algeria*. With an estimated 81,000 followers (as of December 2020), the Facebook page was selected as it portrays Algerian destinations' photographs and promotes domestic tourism. Fifty potential participants replied to the request to participate in the study. These participants were sent a participant information sheet (see Appendix.2) and a consent form (see Appendix.3) to read and sign, and later be sent a Zoom link to partake in the study. In total, 34 participants were part of the focus group discussions. As for the interviews, the same sampling strategy was used to recruit participants with the following criteria: (1) they have offers for domestic destinations, (2) they have a social media presence, especially on Instagram, (3) they previously visited/exhibited in SIAHA's previous editions. In so doing, I recruited seven travel agencies representatives for interviews. The recruitment process for the interviews was also conducted on Facebook; however, I did not post a survey. Instead, I contacted travel agencies that have been active on the "Offre & Demande Touristique" Facebook group. I sent a message to the travel agency via Messenger (see Appendix.4) in which I explained my research and asked if they were willing to participate in one-to-one interviews.

In this investigation, recruiting participants from different regions of Algeria was important to represent Algerian tourists accurately. As data collection was conducted online, it

was easier to approach and recruit participants with different societal backgrounds, varying from indigenous (Imazighen and Arab), social classes (rich, middle class, and impoverished), educational background and level (university and non-university level), and region (South, North). The virtue of conducting online data collection was significant in ensuring participants' inclusivity across Algeria. This demographic variation contributed largely to gathering in-depth data from participants who grew up in different environments and sets of cultural and religious attributes. For the focus group discussions, the participants' profile was as follow:

Socio-educational background	Variables	Number of participants in each variable	Total number
Region	North	24	34
	South	10	
Educational level	University (Bachelors, Masters, Doctoral)	28	
	Non-university/centre, or no degree	6	
Gender	Male	19	
	Female	15	
Indigenous group	Arab	27	
	Imazighen	7	

Table 5-3 Participants' Profile for Focus Group Discussions

Each focus group discussion was assigned a code (a letter) to easily identify and analyse data. The four focus group discussions were identified as follow:

Identifier	Gender	Educational level	Indigenous Group	Region
A1	M	Doctoral	Arab	Medea (North)
A2	M	Masters'	Arab	Algiers (North)
A3	F	No degree	Imazighen	Tizi Ouzou (North)

A4	M	No degree	Imazighen	Bejaia (North)
A5	F	Bachelors'	Arab	Adrar (South)
A6	F	Masters'	Arab	Adrar (South)
A7	M	No degree	Arab	Tlemcen (North-West)

Table 5-4 Focus Group Discussion – Group A

Identifier	Gender	Educational level	Indigenous group	Region
B1	M	Bachelors'	Arab	Adrar (South)
B2	F	Bachelors'	Arab	Bechar (South-West)
B3	M	Bachelors'	Arab	Sidi Bel Abbes (North-West)
B4	M	Masters'	Imazighen	Bejaia (North)
B5	M	Doctoral	Arab	Oran (North)
B6	M	centre diploma	Arab	Bechar (South-West)
B7	F	No degree	Imazighen	Tizi Ouzou (North)
B8	F	Masters'	Arab	Chlef (North-West)

Table 5-5 Focus Group Discussion – Group B

Identifier	Gender	Educational level	Indigenous group	Region
C1	F	Bachelors'	Arab	Bechar (South-West)
C2	M	Masters'	Arab	Tiaret (North-West)
C3	M	Bachelors'	Arab	Jijel (North-East)
C4	F	Bachelors'	Arab	Oued Souf (South-East)

C5	F	Bachelors'	Arab	Oran (North-West)
C6	M	Masters'	Arab	Sidi Bel Abbes (North-West)
C7	M	No degree	Arab	Ghardaïa (South)
C8	M	Centre diploma	Imazighen	Bejaia (North)
C9	F	Bachelors'	Arab	Sidi Bel Abbes (North-West)
C10	F	Masters'	Arab	Algiers (North)

Table 5-6 Focus Group Discussion – Group C

The fourth focus group discussion (Group D) was dedicated to collecting data from travel content creators. Participants for Group D were recruited after contacting them via Instagram. All participants have a social media presence and are considered content creators. Their content is predominantly about tourism destinations in Algeria, in which they share personal experiences, recommendations, and offers available for the advertised destination. The following table indicates the participants' profile for Group D;

Identifier	Gender	Educational level	Indigenous group	Region
D1	F	Masters	Arab	Algiers (North)
D2	M	Bachelors'	Imazighen	Algiers (North)
D3	M	Bachelors'	Arab	Ghardaïa (South)
D4	M	Bachelors'	Arab	Blida (North)
D5	F	Bachelors'	Imazighen	Algiers (North)
D6	F	Masters'	Arab	Blida (North)
D7	M	Masters'	Arab	Bouira (North)
D8	M	Bachelors'	Arab	Oran (North-West)
D9	F	Bachelors'	Arab	Oued Souf (South-East)

Table 5-7 Focus Group Discussion – Group D (travel content creators)

The profile of the participants in the interviews was based on the predetermined criteria I previously discussed. The participant must (1) own a travel agency recognised by the Ministry of Tourism, (2) have social media presence, whether on Facebook, Instagram, or both, (3) have domestic destinations' offers, and (4) participated in the SIAHA exhibition as an exhibitor, a visitor, or a conference speaker. The following table illustrates the profile of the recruited participants;

Agency	Social Media presence	Domestic destinations' offers	Participation in SIAHA
Agency 1	Facebook and Instagram	Yes	Exhibitor
Agency 2	Instagram	Yes	Exhibitor
Agency 3	Instagram	Yes	Visitor
Agency 4	Facebook	Yes	Exhibitor
Agency 5	Facebook and Instagram	Yes	Visitor
Agency 6	Instagram	Yes	Exhibitor
Agency 7	Instagram	Yes	Conference Speaker

Table 5-8 Participants' Profile for the Interviews

5.5.3. Translation

Once the data collection procedure was complete, it was important to translate the data into English. Algeria's official language is Modern Standard Arabic; however, Algerian dialectal Arabic (Derja) is the spoken version within Algerian society. Furthermore, French is considered the first foreign language, although used interchangeably with dialectal Arabic in Algerian everyday speech to serve a code-switching pattern. With English being the second foreign language (a third language for Arabs and a fourth for Imazighen), I was aware that it might cause some issues for participants to express their opinions properly and would cause

them to struggle to find the right words to deliver their ideas correctly and properly. Keeping that in mind, I made sure that my participants were allowed to speak in any language they felt comfortable using, and eventually agreed on using Derja from my part and theirs.

As we established that the chosen mode of speech is Derja, translation of transcripts was needed. I transcribed all the collected data into English to facilitate the analysis process and to allow understanding of the discussions by the non-speakers of this dialect. After transcribing my data, I forwarded the audio recordings and the transcripts' English version to a colleague who is a certified interpreter in Algeria to verify and confirm the integrity of the translation. Afterwards, I began the process of analysing my data.

5.6.Procedure of Data Analysis

After conducting the aforementioned qualitative methods, the following step was to analyse the data. At this stage, I used TA to understand Algerian tourists' experiences in postcolonial settings through generating and interpreting themes across the focus group discussions and semi-structured interviews and complemented it with the use of Photo-Elicitation Interviewing to review, construct, and interpret social media content that portrays Algeria's destinations and travel agencies' offers for Algerian tourists.

5.6.1. Thematic Analysis

To understand the colonial/postcolonial influence on today's domestic tourism trends and national identity in Algeria, I utilised Thematic Analysis (TA) as my approach to analyse, understand, and systematically interpret tourists' experiences and how they (re)construct their postcolonial national identity through tourism practices.

TA is an inductive and foundational approach to qualitative analysis. It is largely used to identify, analyse, and report patterns/themes within data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). TA equips the researcher with fundamental skills that will be useful in conducting any form of qualitative analysis, many of which are essentially thematic.

The flexibility of TA within a wide range of paradigms -compatible with both essentialist and constructionist paradigms- is one of the main benefits of this method as it allows for constructing rich analysis to data and manage complexities that could be found in

qualitative research. However, many researchers (Braun & Clarke, 2021; 2021a; 2021b; Thomas-Meyer et al., 2017; Forrester, 2010) insist that it is crucial to detail how the method has been used in order to justify choices and decisions during the whole process of analysing data and developing themes.

When conducting a thematic analysis, researchers must make several important decisions, as discussed by Braun and Clarke (2006). First, the researcher must define what constitutes a theme, which requires researcher judgement and flexibility. The emerging theme must capture an important point in relation to the research question(s). the researcher must also decide whether to take an inductive (bottom-up) or a deductive (top-down) approach to identifying themes. An inductive approach means themes are strongly linked to the data itself, without being driven by the researcher's theoretical interests or preconceptions (Patton, 2015). In contrast, a deductive approach is guided by the researcher's theoretical framework. Additionally, Braun and Clarke (2006) suggest that researchers should determine whether to identify themes at a semantic (explicit) or latent (underlying) level. A semantic approach focuses on the surface meanings in the data, while a latent approach examines the underlying assumptions, conceptualisations, and ideologies that shape the semantic content. In this study, I adopted a latent level of analysis.

From another perspective, TA is viewed as a valuable method especially when exploring understudied areas or examining perspectives that are not well understood (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Its strength lies in uncovering the meanings people ascribe to their social realities (Schutz, 1962). As TA is suitable for investigating unexplored phenomena and uncover novel viewpoints, the method is deemed appropriate to reach the aim of this study.

In conducting a TA, the process of analysing data can be complex and time-consuming that “evolves as the researcher navigates the different phases. This can lead to new interpretations of the data, which may in turn require further iterations of earlier phases” (Byrne, 2021, p.1398). Following this, the researcher's positionality is significantly embedded as the study requires immersing within the participants' experiences. As I went through the data collection and analysis stages, I reflected on personal experiences, especially being part of the studied community and sharing the same historical and sociocultural background. However, it was essential not to let the interpretation of my own experiences dictate how I interpret the participants' meaning-making processes. Hence, it was important to utilise the six-

phase framework developed by Braun and Clarke (2006) as a guideline that provides flexibility to fit the data and the research questions (Braun & Clarke, 2013; 2021) (See Table 5.9.)

In Braun and Clarke’s paper *Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology* (2006), TA requires certain steps to achieve a well-rounded analysis of datasets. These steps are often referred to as phases of thematic analysis, and they are classified as follows:

<i>Phase</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Familiarising yourself with the data	Transcribing the data, reading and re-reading the data, noting down initial ideas.
2. Generating initial codes	Coding interesting features of the data in a systematic fashion across the entire data set, collating data relevant to each code.
3. Searching for themes	Collating codes into potential themes, gathering all data relevant to each potential theme.
4. Reviewing themes	Checking if the themes work in relation to the coded extracts and the entire dataset, generating thematic “map” of the analysis.
5. Defining and naming themes	Ongoing analysis to refine the specifics of each theme, and the overall story the analysis tells, generating clear definitions and names for each theme.
6. Producing the report	The final opportunity for analysis. Selection of vivid, compelling extract examples, final analysis of selected extracts, relating back of the analysis to the research question and literature, producing a scholarly report of the analysis.

Table 5-9 Phases of Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006, p.12)

Braun and Clarke (2006) suggested that these phases do not need to be followed in a linear fashion as the researcher might need to move back and forth between steps to ensure coherence and reflect the method’s flexibility. Additionally, they highlighted that one of the limitations of using TA is that researchers do not describe in detail how the method is used, which allow the study to be scrutinised and may reduce its rigour (Nowell et al., 2017, Braun & Clarke, 2006).

The first phase consists of familiarising with the data. Braun and Clarke (2006, p.12) state that “you will develop a far more thorough understanding of your data through having transcribed it”. I started transcribing the focus group discussions and semi-structured

interviews without using a transcription software. This allowed an advantage in getting to know the data, re-reading the data to ensure accuracy of transcripts with the recordings, and noting down initial ideas, non-verbal expressions, and the settings of data collection. While doing the transcription, I began highlighting statements that are relevant to the research questions which prompted an understanding of the data (Braun & Clarke, 2021; Sullivan & Forrester, 2019).

The second phase consists of coding the data, previously called generating initial codes. In this phase, Braun and Clarke (2006, p.14) suggest that the researcher can code “by writing down notes on the texts you are analysing, by using highlighters or coloured pens to indicate potential patterns, or by using ‘post-it’ notes to identify segments of data”. As I conducted a manual analysis of data, I highlighted the important statements within my data and colour-coded each one in relation to each research question. I also gathered these highlighted statements in one Word document, printed it, and organised each code with its related statements to visualise my analysis plan that was influenced by my research questions, my constructionist positioning, and the literature I explored earlier in this study (Yardley, 2000).

The third phase consists of searching for themes. This phase was set with the idea that themes do not emerge from data, but are created through the researcher’s process of engaging and familiarising with the data (Braun & Clarke, 2021). In this phase, I re-read my transcripts and started collating codes into potential themes, and gathering all data that is relevant to each theme. This process ensured all transcripts are connected, and codes are organised into potential themes that reflect the research questions.

The fourth phase is called reviewing themes. In this phase, Braun and Clarke (2006, p.16) insist that “some candidate themes are not really themes ... while others might collapse into each other ... other themes might need to be broken down into separate themes”. At this stage, I started reviewing my themes by revisiting and reflecting on my transcripts. I found some themes to be too narrowed down to reflect the codes. Hence, I continued going back and forth throughout my transcripts and themes to re-form where needed and re-organise the content of some codes to reflect the story of my research.

The fifth phase consists of defining and naming the themes in which I reviewed each theme’s name to ensure it is properly reflecting the study’s aim and objectives. Braun and Clarke (2006, p.18) state that the names of themes must be “concise, punchy, and immediately

give the reader a sense of what the theme is about”. This process took a while as I was adamant in ensuring names of the themes I concluded were accurately reflecting the story my research is narrating. At this stage, I settled on the following themes: (1) encountering identity, (2) challenging postcolonial identity, (3) reconstructing cultural disparity, (4) decolonising identity, and (5) experiencing decolonised identity.

The sixth and final phase is producing the report. This phase is “where you bring the analysis to life for the reader” (Sullivan & Forrester, 2019, p.180). At this stage, the constructed themes can be discussed and elaborated in-depth to address the research questions and tell the overarching story of the findings. Braun and Clarke (2021; 2019) emphasise that themes can continue to evolve during the writing process itself. When writing my findings, I continued developing my themes and themes’ names to ensure proper reflection of my study’s core intent and the important points that construct my research story, and eventually settled on my themes that are detailed in Chapter Six and Seven.

5.7. Ethnocentrism, trustworthiness, and credibility in qualitative research

When conducting a qualitative research, researchers are ought to be aware about ethnocentrism that could influence the trajectory of their research, or reshape their perceptions of their own culture through their interpretations. Hammond and Axelrod (2006) suggest that ethnocentrism refers to the tendency of viewing one’s own culture or ethnic group as superior to others. It has direct links to the exploration of *Othering* this research is focusing on as a reflection of postcolonial subjects’ perceptions of self and other. From a certain perspective, ethnocentrism of researchers can cause issues in qualitative research if the researcher imposes their own cultural values and assumptions onto the research process, instead of understanding the participants’ perspective and interpretation (Madison, 2012). For this, it is crucial for researchers to be aware of their own biases and make efforts to ensure they are accurately and subjectively representing the perspectives and experiences of participants (Malterud, 2001). This can be in various forms such as engaging in ongoing self-reflection to surface hidden biases and assumptions, and establishing clear protocols for research process and navigating the complexities of the researcher’s positionality. Throughout the data analysis process, I sought external reviews and feedback from individuals outside of the investigated community to provide fresh perspectives that I may have taken for granted. This constituted of having

discussions with PhD colleagues who are unfamiliar with my study's case, and engaging with my supervisors to evaluate and be critical about the research findings.

In qualitative research, trustworthiness is the term used to refer to “the degree of confidence in data, interpretation, and methods used to ensure the quality of a study” (Connelly, 2016, p.435). Similarly, Heigham and Crocker (2009, p.264) proposed a definition of trustworthiness to be:

A set of standards that demonstrates that a research study has been conducted competently and ethically. Observing these standards convinces the reader that the study has merit and worth and that the results are credible and therefore potentially useful to guide further research and practice.

The criteria that are set for trustworthiness in qualitative research are different than those in quantitative studies. Instead of validity, objectivity, and reliability, it is agreed that trustworthiness is bound with credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability (Lincoln & Guba, 1985).

In this study, I aimed to address the criteria that constitute trustworthiness. Each criterion is explained below how it was addressed and reflected through my data collection and analysis:

Credibility: refers to the truthfulness of qualitative findings (Leung, 2015). This can be established by ensuring studies are conducted ethically, the findings represent participants' perspectives and not researcher biases, and conclusions are logically connected to the data (Elo et al., 2014). Maxwell (2020) suggests that building credibility can be achieved through providing rich examples from the data and accounting for negative/discrepant cases, in addition to detailed methods, transparency, and acknowledgment of limitations.

To ensure credibility in qualitative research, Heigham and Crocker (2009) propose few strategies that help maintaining research integrity. These include:

- Prolonged engagement or being there: As my study was conducted online, it was important to ensure prolonged engagement with the participants. This was done through asking open-ended questions that trigger participants to describe, explain and narrate an experience in a cultural destination in Algeria. Additionally, I presented images to elicit more discussions

and create rapport when talking about the places in the selected images. After the end of my data collection, I continued interacting with most participants through social media to keep them updated about my analysis of their views and interpretations, and to conduct follow-up interviews when further themes were emerging as I analyse the data.

- Triangulation: It was important to use different data collection methods for the purpose of covering “more than a small fraction of the complexity I seek to understand” (Heigham & Crocker, 2009, p.269). For this, I used focus group discussions with Algerian tourists, interviews with Algerian travel agencies promoting domestic destinations, and follow-up interviews with the same Algerian tourists to help establish further understanding of postcolonial identity.
- Participant validation: Follow-up interviews were conducted with Algerian tourists to elaborate and extend my initial analysis of the discussion we had in the focus groups.

Transferability: Refers to the applicability of the findings that can be transferred and generalised to other contexts and settings (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Korstjens & Moser, 2018). Since the focus of qualitative research is to study a phenomenon in depth within its context, the issue of generalisability is addressed differently than in quantitative research. Some points that could be focused on in transferability are the following:

- Creswell and Creswell (2018) found that the responsibility of the qualitative research is to provide rich and detailed descriptions of the context, setting, participants involved, and findings so that the reader can evaluate the potential transferability to their own settings. In the present study, I ensured that my analysis, interpretations, and discussions of the findings were context-based as I focused on reflecting the search for identity in a post-colonial context through the act of tourism. The study focus can be applicable to other settings through changing variables but remaining within the context of post-colonial influences on one’s identity.
- Thick description is another crucial point to support transferability. Leung (2015) states that the researcher is urged not to solely describe behaviours and experiences of participants, but also include their context so that similarities and differences can be discerned across settings. For this, I focused in my investigation on reflecting Algerian tourists and their quest in uncovering their postcolonial identity, and how they share similar characteristics (Algerian, interested in culture, previously conducted a domestic trip in

Algeria). Despite the small sample and narrowed variables, the study focused on interpreting tourists' diverse experiences and practices as they indulge in their visited destination, and their unique ways of uncovering their post-colonial identity instead of generalising them. Hence, throughout the development of this thesis, I aimed at providing in-depth description of the context, the place of data collection (online via Zoom), and the emerging themes through analysing the data, which in turns aligns with the principles of qualitative research and allow the findings to be transferable across different contexts (Lincoln & Guba, 2013).

- The sampling strategies in qualitative research aim at reflecting the diversity in a phenomenon rather than being statistically representative of a given population. Malterud (2001) states that the heterogenous and maximum variation sampling is crucial to reflect the study's transferability. In this thesis, I used non-probability convenience sampling to recruit participants (Teeroovengadum & Nunkoo, 2018). The sampling technique aims to create a sample from participants who showed interest in partaking in the study and are qualified to participate based on certain conditions set by the researcher (Murairwa, 2015). This sampling technique ensured a variety of participants from different socio-cultural, educational, and ethnic backgrounds, which reflects the diversity within the Algerian population.

Dependability: In qualitative research, dependability refers to the stability and consistency of the data over time and across researchers and analysis techniques (Lincoln & Guba, 1985; Connelly, 2016). With more fluidity and context-driven in qualitative research, the assessment of dependability is focused on the process and care taken in carrying out the study. This ranges from creating an audit trail to record decisions taken during the research (such as the study design, recruitment of participants, data collection and analysis choices), assessing the consistency of findings through comparing codes/themes, triangulation of research methods, and explicitly explaining changes that occurred in the study and the rationale for this, to reflect integrity of the research and involvement of attentiveness (Carcary, 2021; Bitsch, 2005; Moon et al., 2016; Korstjens & Moser, 2018). In this study, I kept an audit trail of every stage of the research process, and every change I made in the research plan. I also documented the data collection process and data analysis methods. This helped in staying on track all throughout the research and establishing dependability of my findings.

Confirmability: Refers to the degree to which research findings are shaped by the participants and inquiry process, instead of the researcher's biases and values. To achieve confirmability, it is important for the research to highlight their positionality and reflexivity for the purpose of externalising one's position and perspective (Korstjens & Moser, 2018). In this study, I incorporated my positionality as an Algerian researcher investigating post-colonial influences on tourists' perception and reflection of identity. My positionality was presented in my introductory chapter to reflect how I view my questions about identity to externalise my biases, in addition to a reflexivity section added to my conclusion chapter to summarise how this study has shaped my perception of identity from the perspective of other Algerian tourists, and the development of my thinking processes about post-colonial contexts and influences on identity.

5.8. Ethical Considerations

The investigation of tourists' perspectives and worldviews in regard to domestic tourism in postcolonial settings highlights a number of ethical issues. Emotions and past traumas are factored in any postcolonial investigation, and requires care and awareness of these attributes to dully collect data while respecting participants' privacy and autonomy. Discussing ethical protocols is a difficult task especially in participant-centred research. Fluehr-Lobban (2003, p.104) states that:

Unfortunately, discussions of ethics may prompt fear of accusation, blame, or shame, with the result that silence prevails rather than dialogue. An open and continuous conversation has the opposite effect, it put people at ease and prepares the ground for times when crises arise and requires a response.

In any research that involves human subjects, certain ethical guidelines and frameworks are to be upheld by the researcher. According to Cohen et al. (2011, p.77), conducting a study with human participants requires their approval to take part; "much social research necessitates obtaining the consent and cooperation of subjects who are to assist in investigations and of significant others in the institutions or organizations providing the research facilities". Adding to that, the research should provide certain requirements for the participants such as safety from risks and harm, confidentiality, and respect of privacy (Ritchie et al., 2013).

The University Ethics Committee Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship outline that the fundamental ethical principle is the respect for human dignity. In participant-centred research, a number of guiding moral principles are considered during the

ethical review. These principles are (1) autonomy, veracity, and informed consent; (2) privacy and confidentiality; (3) justice and inclusiveness; and (4) benefits and harms (University Ethics Committee, 2020). Individuals included in a study have the right to determine whether they approve to take part in the research or not. Autonomy requires the need for informed consent. The main elements to informed consent require the researcher to outline, explain, and sufficiently detail all aspects of the research in a participant information sheet to be handed to the participants. Additionally, participants should be informed about their right to withdraw their consent and their full ownership of their data, and that they will not be coerced to remain in the study if they choose to withdraw. And lastly, participants are given sufficient time to make an informed decision about the nature of the research, and their role as participants.

In participant-centred research, every individual is entitled to privacy and confidentiality. All information obtained from and related to a participant must adhere to confidentiality principle unless otherwise agreed in advance. For this, participants should be unidentifiable unless informed consent was given, and the study requires such information. Additionally, data should be stored securely in a password-locked file to protect participants' personal details. Participants must be informed that the research treats them in fairness and equity. The researcher describes a clear plan to address all needs that may arise during data collection, and must provide necessary obligations where vulnerable participants are recruited. And lastly, the researcher is ethically obliged to minimise any forms of harm to the participants. These forms of harm may be physical, cultural, and psychological.

The above-mentioned principles were taken into consideration when applying for ethical approval, and explicitly stated in the participant information sheet and the consent form. Prior to conducting the study, I followed the University of the West of Scotland standard guidelines. I kept in mind, from the planning stage for my data collection, that I must protect the participants' anonymity, preserve confidentiality and privacy, and ensure non-maleficence and non-traceability in the research. Most importantly, I also ensured to acquire the participants' consent by delivering an understandable and simplified consent form that was translated to Modern Standard Arabic. The majority of participants gave a verbal consent; however, I insisted on obtaining a written consent for ethical purposes.

During the stage of data collection and analysis, I aimed at adopting a flexible approach in case of any potential ethical issues. One example of the issues I anticipated facing is research

bias. When dealing with the social phenomenon of domestic tourism practices and experiences, I considered to a highest degree the wording of my questions, especially when it comes to discussing personal experiences and postcolonial identity. Participants' reaction may vary to each question that can be perceived as too personal and intrusive, offensive, or irritating. To address this issue, I primarily outlined the type of questions and general topics to be discussed during the focus group discussions and interviews, and confirmed the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. At the stage of reporting my findings, I deliberately established my discussion to evade any harm that might be threatening to the participants' wellbeing and their personal information.

5.9.Limitations

5.9.1. Limitations of Data Collection

Several issues arose during the process of the data collection process. One major limitation was the unprecedented timing of my plan to collect data with the start of the global pandemic of COVID-19. When I started my PhD, I set up a plan for my data collection process. It was scheduled to conduct in-person focus group discussions for which I prebooked two conference rooms in two different cities in Algeria, and I structured the process in which I will be recruiting participants. I also planned to travel to Algeria to attend the SIAHA tourism exhibition held annually in February of each year. The exhibition would have been an excellent opportunity to meet with Algerian travel agencies representatives from the Ministry of Tourism and the chance to attend tourism conferences held in the exhibition, which major leaders and operators in Algeria's tourism sector would be attending. Unfortunately, due to the pandemic, international travel was banned, and the ban on gatherings was in place, leading the exhibition event to be cancelled. Despite my inability to attend in person as a researcher, I was fortunate to attend the 2017 edition, have an idea of how the exhibition is run, and have the opportunity to reach out to exhibitors and see domestic destinations' offers.

Additionally, the unprecedented pandemic of COVID-19 shifted the way research is conducted. Doing online investigation became the new norm, especially with the availability of ICTs and the rising popularity of Zoom and Teams within education and academia; it was necessary to collect data online. For this Ph. D., I had to completely readjust my data collection and move to an online process that took longer than anticipated. Doing data collection online was challenging in the context of Algeria as a case study. The Algerian population is traditional

in the context of conducting research and delivery of education. When I recruited participants, I was questioned about the focus group discussion method and why I chose it instead of a survey, questionnaire, or one-to-one interviews, as these are the most common methods used among Algerian university students. I had to justify the advantages of using online focus group discussions as opposed to other methods and the importance of this qualitative method to my study. I also noticed a certain resistance from female participants regarding their presence on a video call with participants who are strangers to them. While I acknowledge their views on attending mixed-gender video calls and understand their perspective as I, too, can show certain resistance as a female Muslim in a call with the opposite gender, I offered them the opportunity not to turn on their camera and be present orally to share their experiences and opinions.

5.9.2. Limitations of the Data Analysis

The data analysis process was also faced with a few limitations. The first limitation was the inability to analyse the data through qualitative software such as NVivo. I acknowledge the importance of ICTs and software created to facilitate a researcher's work; however, I chose not to use software for various reasons. First, I realised that using the software requires learning its basics and how it operates to analyse my data successfully, and in doing so, I was aware of the time I would be dedicating to learn how to use NVivo. Second, I fully support analysing data in the traditional way. My justification for this is that a human analysis is more articulate and interpretative than a machine-based analysis. I view the traditional approach to analysis as more humane, realistic, and natural than the machine-based analysis and conclusions. Despite being viewed as limitations; the combination of these points was deliberately chosen as I am familiar with the traditional data analysis process and was approached from a time-efficient perspective.

5.10. Summary

This chapter has covered the methodology I used in my study to align with my research questions, aim, and objectives. I began by explaining how I used social constructionism to understand and interpret domestic tourists' experiences in a postcolonial setting. With a constructionist philosophy, I reflected on my position as to how I conducted a study of the socially constructed experiences and views on postcolonial identity and tourists' worldviews. Through a thematic analysis to data, I settled on five main themes that are further detailed and discussed in the following chapters. These themes are named as: (1) encountering identity, (2)

challenging postcolonial identity, (3) reconstructing cultural disparity, (4) decolonising identity, and (5) experiencing decolonised identity. Identity is crucially valued and constructed collectively in Algerian society, especially with the co-existing pattern of Arab and Amazigh cultures. In this sense, analysing and interpreting discourse related to Algerians' identity, postcolonial socio-cultural involvement, and tourism practices were valorised to understand tourists' experiences. These experiences provide a certain peculiarity in engaging postcolonial theory in interpreting the "hybrid" identity Algerians acquired post-colonialism, which also engages the notion of *Otherness* within postcolonial national identity and discourse. In the following two chapters, I will report on the findings and discuss both notions of *Hybridity* and *Otherness* emerging within the Algerian society as a direct consequence of colonialism, and present an extensive report on how tourists' experiences are (re)shaped within a postcolonial setting.

CHAPTER SIX: UNCOVERING IDENTITY; INTERPRETING/NEGOTIATING THE PRESENT SELF THROUGH TOURISM PRACTICES

6.1.Introduction

Postcolonial identity in Algeria reflects a combination of Western lifestyles embedded within the society through colonial policies and practices, with roots stemming from pre-colonial Arab-Islamic values. This melting pot of socio-cultural representation of identity may be a detrimental cause of confusion and loss of attachment to what makes Algerians who they are. Since their independence in 1962, Algerians have been susceptible to attempting to recover and reconstruct their national identity and culture to reflect their "Algérianisme"¹² and their relationship with their land and each other. However, it was deemed challenging as identity was and still difficult to allocate, describe, and interpret without inherited colonial influence.

The discussion provided in this chapter answers the first research question: "To what extent is the postcolonial identity of Algerian tourists influencing their experiences in domestic tourism practices?". The relationship between the postcolonial identity and tourists' experiences lies in that distinct features prevail to construct their views on their identity and help them uncover and embrace the decolonisation efforts to their existence. Throughout this chapter, I focused on discussing two main themes that were concluded in the thematic analysis of data; (1) encountering identity; which will be depicted throughout Section 6.2. and 6.3., and (2) challenging postcolonial identity which will be further explained in Section 6.4. and 6.5. I present and discuss the constituents and struggle of the Algerian national identity as narrated by the participants. I also reflect on Algerians' approach to understanding their postcolonial identity through tourism and domestic travel and how they cope with complexes such as

¹² Algérianisme: a movement emerged in 1911 among the descendants of European settlers -les Pieds Noirs- and the native Algerian population. It aimed to develop and celebrate the shared culture among the two populations (Calmein, 1975)

poverty, safety, and colonial trauma in shaping their tourist experience within a hybrid framework.

6.2. The Postcolonial Identity of Algerian Tourists

The concept of postcolonial identity has been widely discussed by academics, emphasising the diversity it entails through the fusion and collision of cultures (Goleš, 2020). Postcolonial theorists such as Edward Said and Homi Bhabha notably criticised the cultural diversity emerging from the fusion. They argued that the fusion of cultures sensationalises political correctness and puts the colonised subjects' voices under a dominant Eurocentric model, as their colonial past remoulded their perception of identity and way of thinking. However, it is quite impossible to overshadow the cultural interactions between opposed identities since it creates an integration rather than an assimilation of past colonisers (Goleš, 2020).

Postcolonial identity is commonly created based on the variances between colonisers and colonised. Goleš (2020) calls it the binary opposition of "self" and "other" that are not reciprocal in nature but rather hierarchical in which the coloniser is a superior power imposing and dictating the weak colonised society. When postcolonial theorists began investigating the concept of identity within postcolonial communities, they focused on providing more literature about these societies' characteristics and the influence colonialism had on shaping their identity representation. Fanon (1963) was one to argue about the devastating consequences of colonialism, such as societal ruin and mental impact on the colonised psyche, while Said (1978) focused through a Foucauldian lens to understand the ability to resist and recreate oneself against colonial and imperialist ideology. With his concept of a "*Third Space*", Bhabha (1994) desired to study the particular space between two separate cultures. Within this space, the intermixing and interchangeability of various cultural traits are allowed with no interference of prejudice or imposition (Bhabha, 1994).

When conducting the focus group discussions and follow-up interviews with Algerian tourists, I noted the concept of identity emerging as a persistent issue the society is dealing with. As a society with a colonial past, there are certain implications to the vagueness of the participants' postcolonial identity, which prompts the idea of the possibility of having a hybrid identity stemming from the fusion of pre-colonial Algerian culture with French's. This is also

apparent as I ask participants questions that signified certain difficulties in discussing one's identity. In a postcolonial society, the identity is unstable in definition and cannot reside in a fixed state (Hall, 1997; Glissant, 1969); hence, explaining its constituents and communicating them directly and in clear settings is challenging. With sequential phases of colonialism and conquests from different civilisations (See 2.53.2.2., where Algeria's historical background is detailed), the identity of the Indigenous Algerian community has been influenced and reshaped for centuries. Nonetheless, French colonialism has significantly damaged the society, culture, and, most importantly, identity perception and representation, causing an identity crisis in postcolonial Algeria (Croisy, 2008).

While reflecting on my identity crisis as an Algerian through my questions asked in the focus group discussions, I discerned the governance of such crisis among my participants, especially when I asked them how they view themselves and their identity in a postcolonial society. I noticed that participants faced difficulty articulating or defining their identity and were often confused in drawing differences between their identity and ethnicity. They mostly refer to themselves as Algerians, which is their identity and nationality; however, they also responded with their identity being Arab and Amazigh, which in retrospect are ethnicities and belonging to cultural ethnic groups existing in Algeria. When participants were asked, "What do you refer to yourself as a subject in postcolonial Algeria?" in an attempt to depict their worldviews and personal illustration of self within a postcolonial society, their answers commonly stemmed from the concepts of nationality and ethnicity. Participant B2 said, *"I refer to myself as an Arab, but can I truly be full Arab while being from an African country and the Arabic presence only lasted for a few centuries though a long time ago?"* (B2). Participant A4 also shared the same understanding of identity when responding: *"I do not know how to speak about myself; I, maybe, I should stick with an Algerian Arab; that sums it up, right? I guess"* (A4). Whereas participant A6 said, *"I do not know if I should refer to myself as an Arab, an Algerian, or an Amazigh, but I am all that; I can be all those, normally."* (A6). These responses reflect the colonial consequences impacting societal and cultural ties with the land and community, strengthening Bensaid and Ladjal's theory on France's long-lasting colonial reforms to identity and culture were impactful on past and today's Algerians (2012).

This inconsistency in drawing clear lines on one's identity separately from ethnicity was continuously stated by all tourists, not only as an issue of understanding oneself but as

confusion and loudly enunciating the misleading tactics of colonialism during the assimilation policy (Bensaid & Ladjal, 2012). As discussed in the introduction chapter (see autobiographical influences and positionality in 1.1), I continuously struggle to define myself as an Algerian citizen. My role as an insider within my research allowed me to understand the difficulties the participants are stating on a personal level; however, for anyone reading this work, it is one of many consequences of long-lasting colonialism and a defining aspect of the postcolonial identity crisis. This also attests to Bhabha's theory of *Third Space*, where colonised subjects face difficulties locating their identity within a specific and clear framework. The participants' difficulties in discussing their identity can indicate that they are in a state of in-betweenness (Bhabha, 1994), and their *Third Space* could potentially be an Algerian identity.

For example, participant B1 stated, "*I truly feel lost and not sure about my culture and identity ... I do not know whom to ask or if there are any books discussing our heritage or at least our identity before colonialism and after*". I see a reflection of frustration and scrutiny over the lack of knowledge, loss, and difficulties in comprehending who a person is. Meanwhile, there are compelling books written by prominent Algerian writers discussing different concepts of Algeria's national identity, cultural constructs, and revolutionary events that reflected the Algerian determination to fight for their land, culture, and religion. Benrabah's testimony (1999) reiterates how, after 1956, Algerian writers were prominently working around the themes of revolution and victory, independence and earning back their land. However, these writers, namely Kateb Yacine (1956), Mohammed Dib (1952, 1954, 1957), and Mouloud Mammeri (1965) were keen on (re)presenting Algeria's multiple battles for independence, identity, women's rights, and a variety of societal endeavours using French as the language of their writing to spread as much information and awareness to Francophones. The use of French was not popular among Algerians nor welcomed after the independence as it is the oppressor's language.

Additionally, alongside the postcolonial government's policies to 'Arabise' the people, the staggering ninety per cent illiteracy across Algeria resulted in Algerians refusing the colonial reformation and threat to their native culture (Bossut, 2016; Benrabah, 2013; Sahel, 2017). Nonetheless, novels from Algerian authors were commemorated and heroically greeted outside Algerian borders as they reflect testimonies of people's prolonged struggle and perseverance to regain what was righteously theirs. This also may indicate that the success of

such writings on an international level was not reflective of the same case for nationals living in Algeria. With the high illiteracy rate, learning about the Algerian identity may be unreachable and uncomprehensive for those who cannot read French, which could be a possible reason why today's Algerians were unaware of these writings.

Upon reading through Kateb Yacine's novel "Nedjma" (1956), which participant C1 brought to my attention, I realised it is a biography of Algeria; I found it beautifully narrates Algeria's quest for liberation and identity. Nedjma, a Franco-Algerian woman, is described as a symbol or a metaphor of love and suffrage in colonial Algeria, the incarnation of femininity and resistance to reflect an Algeria in constant search for self and (re)presentation. This writing approach about the society's struggle to recover their land and freedom brought me back to when my grandmother used to tell me stories of how hard life was during the last years of colonialism and how inaccessible and unattainable education and most basic human needs were. My grandmother is illiterate, and so are her siblings and cousins; their youth was spent worrying about life and death and whether they would survive seeing another day. During colonialism, schools provided a French curriculum to whoever chose to enrol, with the condition of not studying Arabic or attending Quranic schools for religious classes. She categorically refused to be part of the colonial agenda and chose illiteracy over French education because she was proud of her Islamic identity. However, when independence was granted, my grandmother dedicated her entire life to encouraging her children to be educated and obtain a formal education without French scrutiny in her land. My grandmother is one example of those voiced through the Algerians' novels and autobiographies. Novels like Nedjma offered her and all colonised Algerians an outlet to spread their stories and narrate their daily struggles with war, lacking rights, freedom, and their desperate need to exist.

Throughout the process of liberation and exploration of Algeria's national identity, there have been several burdens upon both the society and the government to set the ground for postcolonial Algeria. During the post-independence stage, the quest for recovering, or at least defining the national identity was complicated and challenging, especially since the newly elected government came facing the duty of ruling with no previous political expertise. Not only the political realm that was defying but also industrial and societal requirements to develop the nation. At that time, the war of revolution (1954-62) and the regime of President Ahmed Ben Bella (1962-65) gave rise to a socialist ruling approach and a nationalist

movement, which the latter was proclaimed by the Algerian scholar and forefront advocate of cultural nationalism Abdelhamid Ben Badis (Byrne, 2009; Kraiss, 2019). Ben Badis' Association of Algerian Muslim' Ulama¹³ (AUMA) was the first to link the concept of nationalism with the discovery of the forgotten Arab civilisation and Maghrebi culture, through which they pushed the narrative of Islamic reformism as a form of cultural nationalism (Kaddache, 1981; Kraiss, 2019).

The nationalism movement in colonial Algeria revolved around considering religion as a primary and crucial component of the national identity, according to Ibn Badis. Nationalism activists like Ibn Badis employed religious symbolism as a guiding force in their attempt to re-establish an Islamic state (Kraiss, 2019). Most prominently, the indigenous referred to themselves as Muslims, not Algerians or Arabs, which surprisingly reflects an opposite interpretation of identity that my participants provided during focus group discussions. The participants did not mention the term "Muslim" as their national identity but solely reiterated "Algerian", "Arab", and "Amazigh". Participant A7 said, *"I view myself as an Algerian Arab"*, while Participant C8 said, *"I am an Amazigh from Kabylia"*. During the nationalism movement, the Muslim identity in colonial Algeria prevailed amongst the colonised natives, and it overrode the national identity, especially when Christian European settlers and the indigenous Jews were withholding French citizenship. In a way, I view it as a way the indigenous Algerians were showcasing their difference from the settler and proudly declaring their belonging to Islam as Messali Hadj, an Algerian nationalist politician, purposely stated, "love of the homeland -or the country- is an act of faith" (Kraiss, 2019). Interestingly, opposing sentiments were displayed in post-colonial Algeria. The complex issue regarding pre-colonial identity has been debated as a redundant ideology that obscure the process of modernisation and nation-building. Fanon (1963) believes that the reclamation of the pre-colonial identities and traditions could hinder the development of unified national identity and the pursuit of modernisation. Similarly, some postcolonial scholars argued that the emphasis on pre-colonial identity can be a form of 'cultural essentialism', which fails to recognise the dynamic and hybrid nature of postcolonial societies (Bhabha, 1994). However, this ideology has been challenged by scholars and activists who believe in the importance of preserving and

¹³ Arabic translation of "scholar"

revitalising pre-colonial identities as an assertive form of cultural sovereignty. For example, Ngugi (1986) advocated for the centrality of the African languages and cultural traditions in the process of nation-building, stating that the 'decolonization of the mind' is a crucial step towards independence.

The Islamic identity remained a symbolic definition to indigenous Algerians for decades after the independence, especially when the Arabisation policy was introduced to bring back the Arabic language to administration and education and to reduce the illiteracy rate that was prominent within the Algerian society (Benrabah, 2008). However, the ambition of the Algerian nationalist party (FLN) to keep Algeria an Arab/Muslim country led to the inauguration of the Berber Academy of Exchange and Cultural Research (ABERC) to defend the Amazigh identity and minorities' struggle for recognition (Mahe, 2001; Goodman, 2004). The 1980s was the start of the Berber Spring and saw continuous demonstrations and strikes in Tizi-Ouzou, Bejaia and Algiers, challenging the authorities, the FLN, and the single-party system since independence. With the authorities violently suppressing the Berber Spring, a lasting contention remained between the Amazigh and the rest of the Algerians, causing countless issues to the national identity, mainly the Amazigh's demand to recognise their identity as the national identity of Algeria rather than the previously set national identity (Mahe, 2001). The Berber Spring consequently caused a fracture in the Algerians' perception and understanding of their national identity. Giving the previously stated excerpt from the follow-up interviews, participant A6 mentioned: *"I do not know if I should refer to myself as an Arab, an Algerian, or an Amazigh, but I am all that, I can be all those, normally."* This promptly shows how the FLN's Arabisation policy and the Amazigh's demands were detrimental to today's population. Both parties were bluntly trying to defend their policy as the sole approach to impose, leading to mass confusion among Algerians and difficulties in articulating what a national identity constitutes, which encouraged the quest for identity across different methods, one of them being through tourism and mobility.

From another perspective, a recurring theme within the data showed that the Amazigh participants proudly demonstrated that they identified themselves as Amazigh, not considering using the term "Algerian" as an identity. Participant D2 and Participant B7 frankly stated that they do not consider "Algerian" to be an identity, but rather "Amazigh" is the proper term to use for all citizens of Algeria; they stated respectively, *"I am an Amazigh, this is our identity,*

all Algerians' identity, and we should be proudly talking about it because we are the Indigenous people of this land"(D2), and *"the Berber identity is the Indigenous one, Arabs came later to settle here, and we just coexisted in this land, but that does not mean I should give up my identity to be part of the Arab population ... we all carry the Algerian nationality, but our identity is Amazigh"* (B7). As for the participants who identify themselves as Arab, they jointly used Algerian identity along with the "Arab" term, for example, *"I consider myself an Algerian Arab, Algerian national with Arab identity"* (B5), and *"we are all Algerians with Arab decent"* (C4). Given the historical struggle of the Berber community for recognition since the 1980s, it is understandably justified that their concern stems from their fear of losing what characterises them from the remainder of the Algerian population and their fear of marginalising them.

The Arab-Berber dichotomy reached its peak in postcolonial Algeria as the ruling elites emphasised legitimising the rejection of cultural and linguistic reality and concentrating solely on colonial nationalists' aims of Arabisation (Tilmatine, 2016). The consequences of such decisions led to minimising the Berber's demand for recognition as a minority with a socio-cultural value to Algeria as a whole (Boudraa & Krause, 2007; Hoffman, 2010). *"I feel the need to speak loudly about my Amazigh heritage because that is who I am and what I am proud of"*, said participant B4 when responding to the question about reasons to state your ethnicity as an identity. The participant's response is justified and accurately reflects what I discussed about identity contention in Algeria in Chapter Three. Additionally, the postcolonial policies to identity were negatively impacting the Amazigh ethnic groups as a minority that is said to be already struggling to be recognised (Aidi, 2016), which was also supported by Mateu's (2021) and Benrabah's work (2014) that support the idea that socio-linguistic crisis the Amazigh endures since the implementation of the Arabisation policy post-independence was detrimental to their identity and sociological perception of the *Other* Arabs. However, the post-colonial Arabisation policy did not initiate such ethnic tension. The colonial experience is also involved in imposing borders that did not fit with the pre-existing ethnic and cultural landscapes. Herbst (2000) states that the colonial powers drew borders that were not reflecting the realities of Indigenous people, and often separated ethnic groups while in other times joining disparate communities. The disregard for local Indigenous identities and the imposition of new political structures laid the foundation for ongoing tensions and convoluted post-colonial restoration experiences. Similarly in Algeria, ethnic and national identities were

divided and conspired against each other to cause societal disparity and loss that continued in post-colonial era. However, the separation is not solely a product of colonialism. In many countries, such as Ethiopia, the presence of diverse ethnic groups, historical marginalisation, and political dynamics have contributed to the challenge of building a strong national identity and overcoming ethnic divisions.

As previously discussed in Section 3.5, the Arab-Berber binary evokes the historically opposing ethno-racial systems that define Algeria's former sociological reality from Ibn Khaldun's encyclopaedia about Arab settlement in North Africa and the Berber presence to the French colonial era and contemporary political and academic discourses (McDougall, 2006; 2017; Silverstein & Crawford, 2004). Postcolonial Algeria was dedicated to restoring the pre-colonial Arab-Islamic identity and launched Arabisation missions to ensure this identity is generalised and implemented within the education, political, and cultural teachings. The Arab-Islamic nationalism pursuits are what Fenwick (2008, p.76) discussed: "In this modern 'official' history taught in schools and underpinning historical and archaeological research, the Berbers are consigned to a distant past or ignored entirely". The favouritism of the Arab-Islamic identity is rooted in a continuous conflict between Arab and Berber ethnicities in Algeria.

My data shows how Amazigh respondents are clutching tightly to what they perceive as identity out of fear of losing it. Despite the contention, both ethnic groups strongly and respectively argue that tourism and travel greatly contributed to knowing how identity is perceived across Algeria, and help represent their perception of identity to other Algerian communities. A study by Hitchcock (1999) found that tourism contributes to encouraging majority populations to re-evaluate their perception of minorities. I found that those who consider themselves as Arab are susceptible to being driven to learn about the Amazigh identity, as participant C9 said: "*I always wanted to know about the Amazigh culture, so I have visited Bejaia several times ... my first visit was significant because I was only exposed to the Amazigh culture on social media or television, but being among them was completely different ... I now appreciate the diversity in Algeria even more*". Such a statement reflects Hitchcock's conclusions on tourism's opportunity to explore new cultures and identities through interacting with the places and people.

6.3. Searching for One's Identity through Tourism

Tourism and mobility allowed people to explore new cultures and identities and learn about other nations. Burns and Novelli (2006) propose that tourism can be impactful in making culture and people parts of the tourism product. Tourism can also encourage the emergence of new expressions of culture, cultural practices, and identities, which collectively contribute to sustainable, richer forms of tourism development (Canavan, 2016). This ideology falls within the realm of the individual's experience in which the tourist is learning about the destination's cultural, social, and natural characteristics.

When conducting a cultural activity in a given destination, one may develop a form of connection to the host community and a certain degree of understanding, freedom, and respect for their cultural identity. Similarly, when travelling to a domestic destination, the tourist is exposed to newer facets of the national identity and how culture is manifested and (re)presented. For Algerians, travelling opened new opportunities to explore their country and regain freedom and peace by visiting different destinations, especially after 132 years of colonialism, decades of political, industrial, and cultural instabilities, and the 1990s Civil War.

Domestic travelling can be a learning experience for those looking to see and live the local cultural customs. It holds a much deeper level of understanding for tourists to learn more about their country's cultural components and the lifestyle of local communities. Taylor et al. (2012) explore this idea and conclude that domestic tours engage a set of emotions for the tourist who experiences dimensions of closeness and distance at once.

In the case of Algerian tourists, with a tumultuous historical background, they consider domestic destinations as their sole approach to understanding and engaging emotionally with their national identity. One of the concerns raised in the focus group discussions was concerning how a tourist attempts to learn about his/her national and cultural identity. Responses varied under each participant's experience as a domestic tourist. Some participants agreed that partaking in activities within the host community is a crucial behaviour to engage with and understand the identity. Arguably so, participants stated, *"see how they -host community- coexist and celebrate their cultural and social representations ... it benefits my pursuit of knowing myself and learning about the similarities and the few differences my own community shares with where I am."* (B4), and *"As Algerians, we are supposed to share the*

same identity; most of us share the same religion, cultural traits, customs and language, and the same goes for the identity, so the only way for me to understand our identity is to travel to local destinations to see the cultural manifestation and communicate with the host community." (C1), while participant D3 commented, *"I mainly travel to see how Algerians from different cities live and coexist in their small community; I get so much understanding of my own identity, our identity."* These testimonies of tourists' behaviour in host communities justify what Olsen (2012) refers to as travel being the exercise in identity-building through different forms of interaction with the host community. Despite Olsen's (2012) study merely focusing on religious tourism, it can be accurately mirrored in how tourists approach national identity through cultural practices. The strong tie between national identity and tourism behaviour can indicate a potential benefit to improve the destination brand, especially in cases of tourists searching for their identity through tourism.

The national identity/tourism binary attests to a learning exchange and testimony to the brand growth. In Falk's (2011) model of identity-related visit motivation, this construct offers important implications for improving tourism practices. Such implications can be reflected through push-pull factors emerging within tourists' desire to learn about their national and cultural identity and their pursuits of knowledge through partaking in travelling and communicating with the host community. While I acknowledge tourists' desire to learn more about their national identity as I participated in the same activities for the same purpose, I view identity as a personal concept that cannot be generalised to an entire nation. Of course, there are many similarities and differences between how I define myself and what I observe from integrating within the host communities. However, this dichotomy does not necessarily mean that a tourist must abide by and be a pedantic rule-follower. Instead, experiencing and learning more about the host community's national and cultural identity allows the tourists to construct a sense of who they are and how they fit in with their own and host communities. This notion reflects what Hibbert's (2013) study concluded: a tourist's identity plays a major part in travel decisions and behaviour within the host community. Additionally, it is important, especially for marketers and policymakers within the tourism sector, to give more emphasis on tourists' identity when attempting to establish better outcomes and experiences for tourists.

On another note, demanding a single unified national identity is undeniably unattainable, especially in terms of having a rich culture and multilinguistic community

alongside outside influences. Hence, identities are constantly reshaped through (re)collecting from the past and gaining inspiration from various outlets like symbols, languages, and foreign media (Clifford, 1988). In fact, the established link between identity and tourism is prominent for domestic tourists since it facilitates the process of making the connection between themselves and the nation, unlike an international tourist who would view the identity from an outsider's perspective and a distinctive characteristic of the destination (Lanfant et al., 1995). The interrelation between national identity and tourism manifests as a driving force to strengthen the destination image and contribute to the government's pursuit of boosting the economy through destination branding. However, in the case of a postcolonial country, the identity-tourism relationship can bring many challenges to the surface, which might lead to negative prospects if used for international destination branding.

6.4.The Postcolonial Tourist Experience

When investigating the experience of a tourist who shows signs of *Hybridity*, the narrative shifts to a more focus on the psychological and sociocultural attributes that shape how tourists see themselves and their identity, especially when being in a new destination. An Algerian individual is considered a hybrid entity, carrying Arab/Islamic features, Berber ethnic characteristics, and a Westernised French legacy instilled during the colonial period. To define a postcolonial tourist, there should be more emphasis on his/her identity and how this identity is manifested through tourism practices and activities. Arguably, tourists with postcolonial/hybrid identities may seek experiences that connect them with the destination and facilitate learning about their identity, such as visiting cultural sites or museums that showcase their ancestors' history and traditions (Urry, 1992; Urry & Larsen, 2011).

In the case of the Algerian tourists, data showed the influence of their postcolonial identity on the destination choice. Accordingly, participants indicated that every trip is different and unrelated to their travel patterns. Participant A7 said, "*I randomly choose my destination, and I sometimes just tag along with friends whenever they consider travelling, especially if the trip includes visiting a cultural site*", while B3 said, "*I do not travel at random, I spontaneously choose my next destination, and more often I travel to places where I know someone living there and can introduce me to traditions and cultural places*". These statements assert that the unpredictability of the tourist renders the investigation complex to carry, while attesting that they are commonly motivated by culture and seeking to interact with the host communities'

traditions. Tourists may have additional motivations when travelling; however, they confirmed that culture is the primary driver in shaping their individual experiences with uncovering their hybrid identity.

As a postcolonial society, violence was instilled within the Algerian colonised subjects (Fanon, 1963) and continued emerging despite gaining independence. Ait Hamou's report on gender-based violence in Algeria reflects the colonial legacy's continuous impact on the Algerian's perception of freedom and their desire to restrict and impose extremist views on women (2020). The instability in perceiving freedom brought certain gender inequalities and discrimination to the frontline, as female Algerians were susceptible to harassment in their daily encounters. In the tourism context, tourists are keen to have safe experiences in their destinations; however, female tourists are more attentive to the notion of safety and are adamant in ensuring their experiences are positive. According to the participants, harassment and violence against women are significantly high in the Algerian community, making women avoid solo travel and purchase travel agencies' offers. Female participants commented: *"I have never travelled alone ... I am concerned about my safety ... my friend and I always purchase travel packs from a travel agency ..."* (B8), *"I would never travel alone ... my family would never let me, and I get it; they are concerned about my safety"* (B2), while participant A6 shared a relative's experience with travel *"My sister had a 3-day conference in Oued Souf (an east Saharan state), and her husband was comforted with her leaving because her university granted safety... they sat a programme with an agency for her and her colleagues, and no safety issues occurred"* (A6)

The female participants' statements clarify that safety is the first motivator in their decision-making and overall experience. It is comprehensive to prioritise safety and well-being for a successful tourist experience; however, tourists consider it an essential factor, especially in a postcolonial society carrying the remnants of decades tarnished with suffrage and torture, causing physical and emotional pain that is generationally inherited. Hence, ensuring safety is crucial for Algerian tourists for a positive experience. Drawing from my experience as a female traveller in Algeria, I can reflect on and support participants' opinions regarding women's experiences as domestic travellers. Regardless of the destination and the experience that would be shaped, safety is primarily the first attribute I will ensure is met, especially in unfamiliar destinations. Looking back to 2018, when I got my Ph.D. scholarship, I had to travel to Algiers

for administrative purposes -with the intent to visit a few cultural sites. However, safety was a major concern to me as Algiers was a city I had never travelled to. I resorted to asking my father to accompany me, to which he agreed. My father's presence provided a feeling of safety and comfort during this trip and built my confidence to travel solely to Algiers again. Hence, growing up in a country with an alarming rise in gender-based violence and the Civil War's collective trauma, I comprehensively understand participants' discourse regarding gender-based violence and safety prerequisites when travelling.

In addition to safety and the desire to comfortably visit new destinations, satisfaction also contributes immensely to the tourist experience, adding an instrumental perspective to the product's quality. Swarbrooke (1995) defined the concept of quality as the combination of a product or service characteristics bearing on its ability to satisfy the customer's needs. Satisfaction is a cognitive state resulting from the product rather than its experience (Crompton & Love, 1995; Williams, 1989). According to Meng et al. (2008), tourists' satisfaction often combines importance, performance, and travel motivation attributes. When evaluating the pre-purchase and post-purchase stages, satisfaction is measured based on the expectation's reach to fulfilment or exceeding it. The participants' experiences were based on their needs to acquire satisfaction by ensuring comfort and flexibility attributes in their purchased offers. Male participants specifically emphasised that their satisfaction relies heavily on the comfort and flexibility attributes, especially regarding travel agencies' offers. In this regard, male participants responded with *"a burden for me to explore the area at ease ... I do not like the agencies' extensive programmes ..."*. (A4), and *"I would rather go on my own or ask an agency to provide a flexible programme for my group ... we were served what we needed and had a great experience at a cultural festival in the Sahara"*. (C8)

When reviewing the attribute of comfort among participants, it was important to look at their preferences when shaping their travel plans. Bravi and Gasca's (2014) study concluded that tourists preferred certain tour packages based on transport services rather than food services. In contrast, Knobloch et al. (2017) consider the importance of evaluating tourists' overall experience with well-being and quality of life. Participants' responses varied regarding what they wanted from their trip and how they chose to travel. They said in this regard: *"I am more likely to check reviews on Instagram and learn about the destination's culture and uniqueness on my own before going ... influencers helped me a lot in all my travels in the past"*

because they always portray that exotic side of the destination and reflect reasons why this place is worth visiting...." (A4), "I prefer travelling independently and setting my programme based on my liking." (A1), and "I travel alone because I want to have the flexibility in getting in touch with my destination's community; I want to freely explore and engage their culture." (C3). These excerpts from the discussion groups reflect the importance of comfort in constructing a tourist experience. Otto and Ritchie (1996) outline a framework that evaluates and interprets tourists' satisfaction at the level of cognition and affection perspectives. The study results reflect that the element of comfort falls within the dimension of peace of mind, which is closely linked to the elements of safety, relaxation, security, and assurance. According to Otto and Ritchie (1996), these elements are essential to investigate tourists' experiences and satisfaction reasonably and effectively with their travel.

From a postcolonial perspective, it is argued that the identity of postcolonial subjects may significantly influence their experiences and comfort while undertaking tourism activities (Willis & Yeoh, 2012). This also can pertain to the idea that the legacy of colonialism can create complex power dynamics and socio-cultural differences that may impact the tourist's perception and interaction with the local population and the land (Hall, 1989). Simply put, a tourist with a postcolonial identity may feel a sense of solidarity and connection to the host community with whom he/she shares a common colonial past. Additionally, postcolonial tourists with hybrid identities tend to search for authenticity and belonging within their individual experiences (Canavan & McCamley, 2021; Moore et al., 2021). It is their *hybridness* that encourages them to experience, negotiate, construct, and contest the authenticity within their tourism activities (Bhabha, 1994; Halewood & Hannam, 2001; Rickly-Boyd, 2013; Liu et al., 2015).

In contrast to what I discussed in the preceding paragraphs, I noticed that female travellers rely on achieving satisfaction through the travel agencies' offers and rely on an external party to structure their overall experience. On the contrary, most male participants seek comfort when independently structuring their trip throughout the three stages of a tourist experience: pre-experience, during the experience, and post-experience. Male participants identify and collectively refer to themselves as solo travellers wanting to experience "the opportunity to do what they want" (ABTA, 2016). Solo travellers' key motivational factors range from their desire to take risks when planning their itinerary (Hyde & Lawson, 2003),

exploring new cultures, and seeking authentic experiences (Moscardo, 2006; Paris & Teye, 2010), and their search for something new and expand their social network (Laesser et al., 2009). The travel motivator for solo travellers consists of push factors as they are urged to discover and experience feelings of independence (Demirovic et al., 2019). Thus, they are more likely to search for new destinations and check reviews of other travellers during their decision-making process.

Participants who classify themselves as solo travellers expressed their desire for freedom and getting away from society; *"I prefer travelling alone." (A1), "I am more likely to travel solo than with a group; it is more freeing and provides a sense of isolation." (C7)*. Their experiences are drawn from socio-economic factors, motivating them to travel independently. While these solo travellers are men, I depicted their main purpose of travel as independence, which is driven by their openness to adventure and risks more than women, whose main motivators lie within the realm of seeking cultural and educational experiences and safety (Torkington et al., 2020; Berdychevsky, 2016; Khan et al., 2017). Men's satisfactory evaluation attributes are comfort and flexibility; their decision-making process is based on eWOM (see 7.4). These travellers are more likely to trust credible electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) than traditional advertising (De Veirman et al., 2017), as the former is seamlessly endorsed within the influencer's daily life and experiences (Abidin, 2016) and grants a sense of familiarity and normality. To put it into perspective, male participants consider eWOM an essential outlet to verify prior to travelling to a new destination, especially as it helps the trajectory of their pre-planning and decision-making process. Hence, digital influence, or social media influencers, can be an intricate and beneficial attribute in aiding these travellers throughout their journey to a new destination. However, tourists' experiences are also drawn from various psychological complexes that direct their thinking to tourism preferences. Some of these complexes can directly result from colonial trauma, generational trauma, gender-based violence, and poverty.

From a postcolonial viewpoint, the eWOM can assert certain power dynamics that attempt to enforce colonial narratives and perpetuate unequal relationships with host communities (Kim, 2018; Lai et al., 2018; 2019). These power dynamics seem less impactful when the e-WOM is transmitted from fellow travellers or travel influencers whose intentions are primarily authentic and unbiased (Karacaoğlu, 2021). When the eWOM is quality-driven and endorses authentic experiences with host communities, tourists are more likely to engage

with their destination and are allowed to learn about the communities' culture and identity with whom they share a common colonial past. Hence, these experiences with eWOM and understanding identity are closely related to providing postcolonial tourists the opportunity to uncover and (re)shape their hybrid identity.

6.5. Complex Barriers and Plans to (R)constructing the Postcolonial Algerian Tourist's Experiences

Algeria endured processes of settler colonialism at the hands of the French state, followed by ten years of Civil War initiated by Islamic extremists who terrorised the population and instilled fear and trauma among the Algerian people. As discussed in section 3.2.1., colonialism consequences are still prominent in today's generation. Poverty is one of the consequences of the historical background and the government's failure to rebuild the nation. Algeria's population is relatively poor. The poverty rate is 5.5% as of the recent statistics conducted in 2011 (The World Bank, 2018). The poverty factor led Algerians to turn to one-day trips or to stay at an acquaintance's house. According to participants' responses, travel agencies' general offers are tailored to include hotels priced for the middle and upper class. Participants indicated that they are more likely to avoid hotels for financial reasons. They disagreed with hotels' staggering prices and demanded a revision considering the population's financial capacities. Participant C1 said in this regard, "*... prices of services are high for families' budget ... this might lead families to consider going abroad to a more affordable destination like Tunisia ... prices should be revised to accommodate all society's social ranks*". (C1) while participant B5 mentioned "*honestly, I can never understand how a month's salary can pay for five days stay in a hotel here, it is unreasonable to do so, and I would rather take a road trip or stay at a friend's or a family's house when necessary*".

I can fully understand the participants' frustration regarding their inability and unwillingness to spend their salary and savings for leisure purposes. It resonates with my circumstances as part of a middle-class family who struggled financially to afford a week of leisure in a domestic destination during summer. On the one hand, I can comprehend Algerian tourists' disappointment towards the authorities for limiting tourism investments and paying little attention to a fast-growing global industry, to some extent. Nevertheless, on the other hand, it is challenging for tourism providers to upgrade their services and encourage tourism competitiveness amid countless social and economic issues. Since independence, the

authorities' primary focus has been directed to the oil and hydrocarbon industry to generate rapid wealth, especially being a newly established country with a great need for financial growth. Algeria's oil and gas industry accounts for 20% of the annual GDP and 85% of its exports (OPEC, 2019). The nearly full dependency upon this industry would potentially lead to unreversed consequences to the nation's whole system. The government's focus on such an industry is unsustainable, especially when most developed countries consistently aim to shift to clean, renewable energy (Carfora et al., 2021; Karooni et al., 2015). Oil-dependent nations might not benefit from their natural resources in the future, or their reserves might end. Hence, the industry's unsustainability factor might lead to regretful outcomes, specifically when the remaining sectors are neglected.

With such neglect to improve the country's economy across all sectors, weaknesses emerge within the tourism sector, ranging from a lack of proficiency and marketing competence amongst the sector's workers (Aouinane, 2014). Tourism marketing is an important branding segment that Algerian travel agencies overlook. Participants agreed that agencies are not keen on establishing a solid communicative and persuasive base with potential clients. It is noticed that their services are either posted on social media groups without fully delivering the programme's structure or exhibited in annual local fairs and exhibitions for potential B2B deals (Benchabib, 2022). Such a burden in communication has led travellers to spare from agencies and decide based on other travellers' social media reviews. In this regard, participant B7 stated: *"I prefer looking for people's reviews than searching for an agency's offer ... I already know I will not be pleased with their unprofessionalism and lack of communication ... I want to know how to go to my destination and what to do there and would rather hear from travellers first ... if agencies were more open to advertising and attractively detailing their programmes and listening to us the consumers, I would opt for it"*. Participant B2 also added: *"I am interested in travel agencies' offers in terms of best places to go and activities to do in all their advertised destinations, but I do not prefer purchasing from them ... I do not think they can meet my needs and requirements"* (B2), while participant B1 said: *"it is rare to find an agency which gives further details about their offers in case the inquirer wants to go on their own"*.

During the early stages of this thesis, I was attentively observing travel agencies' digital presence. I noticed the agencies' attentive desire to respond to their audiences' public requests

and interact in the comments section to accommodate each question. To illustrate my observation, Figure 6.1 below is one example of an agency's post on Instagram, where an agency replies to people's comments regarding the destination offer to Ghardaïa city.

Figure 6.1. A travel agency's offer to Ghardaïa, Algeria

I also must mention that the travel agencies recruited in this study have a large audience following their accounts (for example, the agency in Figure 6.1. has over 250,000 followers on Instagram), which indicates that these agencies are conducting positive and approachable digital customer service. However, the participants mostly shared their experiences with travel agencies' offices and did not mention that they contacted an agency on social media. Additionally, most travel agencies dedicate their efforts to displaying their services at national exhibitions and fairs. In Figure 6.1, there is a display of images of popular activities included within the travel agency's offer to the city of Ghardaïa, Algeria. These images are all printed

on a large banner to display in the tourism exhibition SIAHA, according to Agency 5, quoting “most of the offers that we post on Instagram are provided in SIAHA fair ... as you can see in this post, we included a picture of camel ride, a picture of the traditional shop of local handmade rugs to be visited, and a picture of the hotel. When a client purchases this offer, he/she will visualise where he/she will stay and what activities he/she will pay for. We also add other activities such as visiting the Old Mosque, Old Medina, and visiting a local museum with a guide to narrate the city’s history and culture”. The travel agency’s offer provides an opportunity for clients to learn about Ghardaïa’s culture, traditions and history, and it is common among travel agencies to prioritise the culture of the advertised destination; as Agency 6 said, “based on my experience, people are more drawn to the culture and always seek to make their travel as educational as possible”, and Agency 2 said, “I always prioritise adding cultural activities because that is what I observed throughout the years”. This desire to explore the destination’s culture seems to support the idea that tourists attempt to learn about their postcolonial identity through interacting with the culture of the host community (Urry & Larsen, 2011), and they seek to construct authenticity to their experiences as tourists with postcolonial hybrid identity (Ricky-Boyd, 2013; Liu et al., 2015).

Alongside the digital advertising of destination offers, travel agencies are interested in pursuing a physical display of their offers in national exhibitions and fairs. During my interviews with travel agencies, they all confirmed the importance of exhibitions and fairs to promote their offers using traditional marketing methods as they help reach a demographic of people not active on social media. “These [national exhibitions] are a one-time event where I know there will be plenty of tourists willing to purchase domestic or international offers” (Agency 4), and “customers coming to my agency office have already decided on a destination and they come to request a prepared package ... in exhibitions, we [agencies] are visually displaying our offers in banners and flyers in our allocated stands, this is allowing tourists to view our selection of offers and decide on their next destination” (Agency 6). Based on these responses, I understood that national exhibitions and fairs provide a higher chance for agencies to sell their offers when they are visually displayed and authentically reflect cultural expectations of national identity. Additionally, agencies are more likely to create offers based on their returning customers’ requests. Agency 1, for example, said, “I have a service that I call ‘a la carte’ which allows customers to create customised offers to certain destinations. I usually tell my clients that we have a 7-day trip to Oued Souf, for example, and list to them the

cultural activities they can participate in while being there, and it is up to them to choose what they want the offer to consist of. I later promote the customised offer for other clients and arrange it for a limited time and group". The agency's statement reflects people's preference for human interaction in the age of ICTs and the satisfaction to be achieved when allowing the clients to create their package with the guidance and recommendations of the travel agency. van Rensburg (2014) proposed that in the era of ICTs and the internet, destination marketing plans should combine both online and traditional marketing tools to ensure relevance and protect the social one-to-one aspect of marketing. This also explains why the participating agencies ensure having a social media presence, along with their office and their participation in tourism exhibitions. This online and traditional marketing strategy contributes to visibility and reach and values digital marketing as an enabler of existing marketing strategies, with a central focus on the customer in the marketing plan (Prendergast et al., 2010; van Rensburg, 2014).

Online and traditional marketing strategies can be successful approaches for travel agencies, specifically if the services are properly delivered, and consumers' demands are fully met. To van Rensburg (2014, p.7):

No amount of advertising or low prices can make up for service failures, such as customers being unable to complete transactions, products not being delivered on time or at all, e-mails going unanswered, and desired information being inaccessible.

This also contributes to positive experiences for postcolonial tourists who seek authenticity, safety, and comfort when visiting a destination. van Rensburg proposed a five-step process for travel and consumption for a rewarding experience. The process consists of (1) dreaming, which refers to undertaking the necessary steps to ensure the client's desire or need to travel is realised; (2) planning, which involves proposing all travel options and destination selection when communicating with the client, (3) comparing and considering alternative destinations, services, or activities to select from, (4) consumptions; which indicates the physical travel experience, and (5) support for clients and required interventions to be considered or aware of during travelling.

When questioning the travel agencies regarding their process of constructing and marketing an offer, whether online or traditionally at their office level, I established the

presence of all the five steps indicated above. Algerian travel agencies emphasise achieving the dreaming and planning steps; as Agency 5 stated, “*every time I receive a client, I ask them where they would like to travel the most, and I must facilitate and ensure their desire is met*”, and Agency 3 “*I always propose to customers all travel options to the available destinations, and it is up to them to choose how they want their travel plan to be*”. Comparing and considering alternative destinations, services, or activities to select from is also considered by the travel agencies I interviewed; Agency 1 said:

“Planning for a trip is a process that I would like to go through with the customer on a step-by-step basis ... I have to lay down all options for the customer to choose what they are comfortable with purchasing, and that varies from the activities they want to undertake, for example, a trip to Taghit can include city tours, guided tour to oases in proximity, or any activity they are interested in ... I also provide options for accommodation, if they want to be closer to the city centre or old town if they want all-inclusive...”

The consumption step is also considered regarding accommodation, according to Agency 2: “*If a customer wants an all-inclusive for their hotel booking, I will ensure it is met ... but usually I propose traditional restaurants to taste local cuisine, which often is accepted by customers*”, while Agency 5 said, “*my proposition for accommodation varies between hotels and private hosts I collaborate with in different destinations, and the clients decide to choose which one they prefer*”. As for the fifth step of providing client support during travel, all agencies confirmed they hire a companion or an agency representative to serve as a guide and assistant for the tourists group at their destination. For example, Agency 4 said:

“In all groups I organise a trip for, I make sure a companion is representing the agency with the customers ... usually the companion we send is familiar with the destination and will provide aid and assistance to our clients “, while Agency 6 said: “in all the destination offers I sell, I make sure I know and trust someone there to be of an assistance to any customer travelling there, and I communicate this point with the customer to be aware of in case an emergency takes place”.

As I established the travel agencies’ steps to fulfil the tourist’s experience, it is worth mentioning that when it comes to a postcolonial society, tourists are more likely to prioritise certain attributes before their travel. Travel agencies are more reliable in ensuring two fundamental factors that postcolonial clients seek the most: safety and security. The participants in this study have witnessed atrocious events related to the 1990s Civil War and are surrounded by a generation that suffered traumas caused by French colonisation and the

Civil War (Zeraoulia, 2020). I previously discussed gender-based violence and female Algerians prioritising safety when travelling to a selected destination; however, male participants also reflect signs of fear and insecurity, especially when travelling alone to a new place. In this regard, male participants state, "*I avoid going out at night ... I do not feel safe ... I do not know the destination too well to wander at night ...*" (D3), and "*travelling alone can be scary, so I tend to be more cautious where I am at*" (B6). Such statements denote a rooted psychological problem integrated and transmitted from the old generations to new ones with no discrimination to gender, which could be labelled as a postcolonial outcome to challenge social freedom and rest. Every postcolonial society continuously faces unsolved issues like terrorism, environmental and societal damage, and cultural untranslatability (Ravi, 2011). In Algeria, the postcolonial era witnessed continuous and challenging trials to reconstruct and rebuild its crucial assets, namely industry, agriculture, education, and health sectors, while neglecting tourism (Aouinane, 2014). The socialist ideology of government reconstruction was deemed unsuccessful at its core as it led to a division between Algerian elites across the political platform and eventually failed in addressing social concerns and eliminating the sources of "unfreedom" like poverty, illiteracy and social unrest (Rocherieux, 2001; Ait-Chaalal, 2002). These failures affected tourism in the sense that poverty and social unrest are essential to address and solve prior to planning and developing Algeria as a desirable destination (Aouinane, 2014). On another note, these social concerns were also contributing factors to the perception of identity among Algerians, especially with the loss of ties with the pre-colonial Arab-Islamic identity and France's alienation policies, it became justified as to why a hybrid identity needed to emerge as a solution to belonging and desire to fit within a postcolonial and decolonised framework of self and identity.

6.6.Summary

The data discussing tourism in Algeria denotes and explicitly reflects the state's struggle to build its tourism sector, especially with a heavy historical background and colonialism's significant effect on societal constructs. These struggles caused the Algerian people to have a narrowed vision of what made them who they were. In a way, it alienated and *othered* them from their past national identity, the Muslim identity they once were inherently proud of voicing and presenting. Their struggle with identity disorientation relocated them to a new space where they can -and cannot- fit comfortably. For one, they proudly declare that they are

Arabs. At the same time, in other circumstances, they view themselves as Amazigh, but until when this disorientation lasts is the question to be asked and worked on a final and done answer. In fairness, it is difficult to establish a single national identity, especially with today's mobility and interracial exchange of cultures and social norms, along with the inability to keep one's identity in a box out of reach and beyond interference with the world. However, tourism can provide a positive outlet for tourists to explore and understand their own national identity, especially if mobility is exercised within local terms and among communities with whom there are grounds for mutual and interchangeable facets of the overall culture. The Algerians' approach to learning and exploring culture has significantly progressed in articulating and defining their shared national identity despite the recurring confusion between national identity, ethnicity, and nationality. Nonetheless, I cannot disagree with their approach to describing their heritage and culture. Evidently, it is to be a learning process in which, at a given time, the national identity will be set in stone once Algerians overcome and make peace with the past and move forward to building their future for future generations to live without complex barriers and to (re)shape and (re)form Algerian tourists' experiences.

In the following chapter, I will focus on the remaining three main themes that emerged from my thematic analysis; (1) reconstructing cultural disparity, (2) decolonising identity, and (3) experiencing decolonised identity. I present the data collected concerning the use of digital practices by travel agencies and content creators to position in the market of postcolonial Algerian tourism. The chapter will provide an analysis to how domestic tourism trends are featured and communicated on social media platforms to reshape tourists' experiences and mirror the postcolonial identity of Algerians. The concept of culture will be explored within the Algerian context and how it is viewed as a marketing tool for postcolonial Algeria. Additionally, I will review travel agencies and content creators' contributions to colonial/postcolonial discourse and how their decolonial input is implemented for the tourism sector to evolve sustainably.

CHAPTER SEVEN: GLORIFYING COLONIAL ERA OR DECOLONISING TOURISM? AN INTERPRETATIVE ANALYSIS OF DIGITAL PRACTICES IN ALGERIA

7.1. Introduction

Postcolonial Algeria developed numerous branding and tourism development strategies, such as Horizon 2030, to promote and construct a tourism sector able to compete internationally, especially in the Mediterranean region. One approach that is widely used in Algeria is digital advertising of domestic destinations, be it presented by travel agencies or travel content creators (Benghadbane & Khreis, 2019; Madoui & Bendjeroua, 2021; Azizi & Bouacha, 2019). The digital practices of advertising tourism focus more on presenting Algeria's culture and richness to attract people to visit the advertised destination. In this sense, culture is a sustainable tool for marketing gains, an essential component in a postcolonial country that lacks tourism infrastructure and weight within the region. Taking this into consideration, it is intriguing to comprehend how these digital practices are influencing and (re)shaping the perception of postcolonial identity among Algerian domestic tourists.

This chapter answers my research question: *How are domestic tourism trends featured and communicated on digital platforms to influence and (re)shape Algerian tourists' experiences with identity?* This chapter is concerned with discussing three main themes that emerged from my thematic analysis; (1) reconstructing cultural disparity, (2) decolonising identity, and (3) experiencing decolonised identity. I provide a detailed interpretation of travel agencies' and content creators' role in (re)constructing the Algerian culture to (re)shape the tourists' experiences and perceptions of the hybrid identity. Throughout this chapter, I report on the systematic approach used by tourism agents and digital travel content creators to promote culture, national identity, and diverse socio-cultural constructs of the Algerian community for Algerian tourists. Additionally, I approach digital practices with a colonial/postcolonial lens to review and identify how Algeria's domestic tourism is promoted to endorse a decolonised narrative to identity.

7.2. Postcolonial cultural divergence

Throughout the construction of digital marketing plans, culture is commonly a prioritised component for travel agencies and DMOs to attract customers. Culture is an important segment of the tourism sector and a significant motivator for tourists in their destination choice (Correia et al., 2013). Several studies show that Algeria's culture plays a crucial role in enriching the tourism sector and attracting tourists as it is deemed the identity's primary constituent and reflects the people's history and socio-cultural characteristics (Kherroubi, 2016; Karim, 2016; Fehit & Hedibi, 2020).

The country's brand image is constructed through the implication of cultural and societal norms, including its cultural diversity and geographical characteristics, to represent the richness and offers available to tourists. According to participating agencies, culture is vital in their destination offers that are advertised digitally or traditionally. They said in this regard:

“I view culture as a physical representation of who we are, and what better way to show the destinations' identity other than enjoying its culture? It is a mirror of the people's identity, and a reflection of their history and lives.” (Agency 6)

“I am more inclined to know the culture of a certain destination because it reflects a glimpse of who the people are and what characterises them from other places, and this is why I make sure all my offers have cultural activities.” (Agency 5)

According to these statements, Algerians consider their culture a defining representation of their livelihood. They thrive in showing what and how their culture symbolises their unity and long-awaited freedom. In fact, the shared colonial history strengthened their attachment to culture and identity even further for fear of losing what makes them Algerians (Saad Allah, 2009). One of France's motives for colonising Algeria was to eradicate and assimilate the Algerian identity into the French lifestyle (Merbah et al., 2020; Bensaid & Ladjal, 2012), and their adverse policies managed to reshape the Algerian culture, lifestyle, and way of speech. During my discussions with the participants, I noticed that the Algerian way of speaking constitutes a mixture of French and Algerian Arabic words. This code-switching paradigm is primarily considered a colonial consequence of French policies (Adder & Bagui, 2020). Despite my role as a facilitator within the discussions, I found myself joining the participants in using French terms, more specifically technical terms like colonialism, assimilation policy, and the Civil War, for the reason of not having a dialectal

equivalent to it in Algerian Arabic, and by the habit of using French in my day-to-day conversations.

On another note, I concluded that despite France's efforts in alienating and annihilating culture and identity, Algerians managed to hold tight to elements of their national identity. I must add that as cultural norms are continuously in close contact with the external world and face alteration in how they are (re)presented and (re)produced, the essence of the culture remains the same. Taking the example of the Caftan¹⁴, the pattern, fabric, and sewing process in Algeria's Western region differ significantly from the Eastern part due to the influence of the Moroccan and Tunisian cultures, respectively. However, the core of the Caftan, a cultural symbol of social class and celebrations, remains the same across the country. In this sense, the (re)branding and (re)presentation of Algerian culture signify the regional desire to include their take in altering cultural norms without (re)shaping Algeria's cultural identity, which in terms is enriching Algeria's brand image and offering a multidimensional façade to each cultural norm that will contribute to building a brand strategy (Aouinane, 2014; Hedir, 2016).

Going back to postcolonial theory, it is worth mentioning how the postcolonial Algerian culture reflects what Bhabha (1994) said about a *Third Space*. In the case of Algeria, the *Third Space* is the current status of the Algerian identity. In the example of language that was utilised during the data collection process, code-switching is prevalent in Algerian day-to-day conversation. This switching code pattern results from the fusion between Algerian and French contact for 132 years. As Ferguson (2003) stated, it is a phenomenon of language contact in multilingual settings that exist in Africa and worldwide. Algeria is a multilingual country. Most of the population speaks Arabic, French, and English, in addition to Tamazight for the Amazigh community. This linguistic profile is uniquely shaped and continuously switched between codes for successful communication. Alongside the language, the architecture is also taking part in the *Third Space*, reflecting a certain degree of fusion between French and Ottoman styles, as shown in the figure below.

¹⁴ The Caftan, or Kaftan, is a garment made with the finest silk and/or velvet textile, along with mosaic colours and intricate patterns to display social rank and wealth. It used to be worn by the wealthiest emperors and Sultans in the Middle East during the Ottoman empire ruling, and was brought to the North African region to later be worn by women in special occasions, such as weddings, cultural events, and celebrations.

Figure 7.1. French architecture in Oran, Algeria

Image in Figure 7.1, shown above, depicts a colonial building in Oran, Algeria, renovated as a preservation policy launched by the Ministry of Tourism (Mazouz, 2015). The building was constructed during the French colonial presence in Algeria in the early twentieth century. Historically speaking, the French systematic annexation of Algeria led to imperial investments to turn the region into a department that is part of France on the social, economic, political, and cultural levels (Djerbi & Safi, 2003). With assimilation policies intended to “civilise” Algeria and weaken the local culture and identity, urban improvements were quickly implemented (Ladjal & Bensaid, 2012; Djerbi & Safi, 2003). In addition, architects’ training and teaching in Algiers’ School of Fine Arts followed the French model, and it was not a viable sector to improve as France’s colonial interest was far from considering urbanism as a priority in their agenda. With the growth of urban centres in Algeria, along with an increased need to

build the colony, it was important for France to reconsider its colonial interests and include architecture as an economic activity to reflect its settler colonial gains. However, the field of urbanism was interesting to French practitioners rather than experts to preserve the existing cultural portrayal through architecture.

Deluz (1988, p.30) states that “the classical architecture of European affiliation was for seventy years the official architecture of the French empire in Algeria”. This reflects the growth of architecture and fine arts in Europe that was extended to France’s African colonies, especially in the Northern region. The beginning of the twentieth century was significant with the emergence of a humanistic approach aiming to reflect the traditional architecture with urban heritage and arabise the ‘built environment’ (Foura-Bouchair & Foura, 2011). This approach is called the “neo-Moorish” style of architecture. The neo-Moorish style is characterised by orientalist arts and architectural eclecticism seen in nineteenth-century Europe. Francois Beguin (1983, p.14) describes the neo-Moorish style as:

A protective style, invented to divert the attention of the colonized inhabitants and to remedy the uneasiness felt in front of the neo-classical style [of the victor] which invaded the landscape of the Algerian cities since the beginning of colonization.

The picturesque orientalist characteristics of Algeria’s colonial architecture were collectively inspired by the Andalusian-Maghrebian architecture, which was influenced by the Arab-Islamic civilisation (Chalabi & Lazri, 2021). The neo-Moorish style was characterised by white-coloured buildings, Ottoman designs and intricate calligraphy displayed on the outside front or inside walls and stairways, a dome or multiple domes on the roofs, and minarets as pillars of the building from the outside. The following images are descriptive examples of the neo-Moorish architecture still existing across Algeria.

Figure 7.2. Neo-Moorish architecture in buildings' interior in Algiers, Algeria

Figure 7.3. Neo-Moorish architecture in buildings' exterior in Algiers, Algeria

Chalabi and Lazri's paper (2021) about the *Image and Signification of the Neo-Moorish Architecture in Algeria Case Study: The Big Post Office in Algiers* was of significant

importance in highlighting how the neo-Moorish architectural style is depicted and appreciated by Algerians. In a passage, Chalabi and Lazri (2021, p.1249) state:

Despite its belonging to the colonial architectural legacy, the neo-Moorish architecture is accepted by the population it is even appreciated. Today, it has great importance in the collective memory of Algerians, who have an emotional attachment to its neo-Moorish buildings decorated with local references that have become landmarks of Algerian cities.

Along these lines, I presented the following images during my focus group discussions as an attempt to capture participants' opinions and interpretations of these significant tourism landmarks in Algiers. The first images I presented were of *La Grande Poste d'Alger*¹⁵.

Figure 7.4. La Grande Poste d'Alger in Algiers, Algeria

While showing these images to the participants, I received a collective agreement regarding the importance of the building to the Algerian culture and national heritage. Participant C10, who lives in Algiers, commented that *"to me, it is a regular building, it is a*

¹⁵ French for "The Grand Post Office of Algiers"

post office that is practical for my postal needs ... I have noticed that many people take pictures around it ... I admit it is a beautiful historical building that is very appreciated by people visiting Algiers". In contrast, participant B4 who lives in Bejaia, an Algerian eastern city, said that *"every time I visit Algiers, I have to go by La Grande Poste and have a cup of coffee in the coffeeshop facing it ... I am really fascinated with this type of architecture and its originality"*. I understood from their comments that the intricate design and calligraphy (shown in the image on the left, with golden Arabic writings) make this landmark distinctive from the other buildings around it. Although most colonial buildings in Algiers are white, the colour signifies a certain degree of uniqueness and originality that offers the building an opportunity to stand out as an important landmark, surrounded by coffee shops, a flower shop, and a few stores. However, the colour also justifies why Algiers is named *Alger la Blanche*¹⁶, as the building is a majestic landmark with plenty of buildings painted white, distinctively viewed as a colonial heritage acquired and accepted within Algerian heritage.

Despite many tourist landmarks in Algeria being built by the French, the artistic and aesthetic touch that combines modernity with orientalist thinking has shaped a hybrid product for Algerians to appreciate. In fact, Chalabi and Lazari's study (2021) concluded that there is some confusion regarding the architectural style of La Grande Poste d'Alger, varying between Ottoman, Islamic, and French, which ideally reflects the *Third Space* theory of the fusion between these civilisations in constructing what is known as the Algerian culture and identity. Additionally, the aesthetics of La Grande Poste d'Alger is interpreted as being closer to a mosque than a post office, and the white colour and golden calligraphy are interpreted as signifiers of purity and peace, and attractive and balanced. However, this study also emphasised that the landmark is considered a colonial product rather than an identity representation. However, this does not exclude their acceptance of such a landmark and its importance as a cultural heritage and a historical monument to be added to the many tourist landmarks across Algeria.

Other cultural identifiers, like religion, music, and traditional costumes, remained preserved throughout the colonial era. Algeria is a Muslim country, with 99% of the population

¹⁶ French for "Algiers the White City"

claiming Islam as their religion and a minority of Christians and Jews (Office of International Religious Freedom, 2022). Music also sustained its originality without French influence. One musical genre that originated in Algeria was Rai music, a form of Folk music that combines traditional characteristics of the society and narrates social struggles and cultural richness. However, Andalusian Music was imported from Al-Andalus¹⁷ and was adopted mostly by many older coastal towns, such as Al Casbah in Algiers (Farmer, 1978). Kabyle music is an urban folk musical variety that is popular and indigenous to the Amazigh community in the Kabyle region. The Kabyle music remained uninfluenced, narrating the Amazigh's struggle for recognition and identity acceptance (Blench, 2021). Costumes are inherently sustained as they narrate the shared historical outfit representing every area and are considered a cultural asset often promoted as part of the national identity.

7.3. (Re)defining the National Identity; Shifting to Domestic Promotion during Challenging Times

Using culture to attract tourists is, interestingly, a positive step toward reviving the sector (Butowski, 2018). Tourism in Algeria is a recent trend emerging after the 1990s Civil War (Hedir, 2016). As most regions are not widely explored, local travellers are becoming more interested in discovering cultural and geographical diversity (Cherfaoui, 2015; Achi, 2005; Shepard, 2013). Consequently, promoting the culture as a product can significantly affect consumer demand (Camilleri, 2017) and help increase the tourism sector's recognition and interest in culture and development.

The growing demand for Algerian destinations from domestic tourists was noticeable during the global pandemic of COVID-19 (Benchaib, 2022). Interestingly, during recent years, and especially since the surge of the pandemic, the tourism industry worldwide witnessed a drastic hit to its facilities and global presence as the industry noted a decline in the number of international tourists' arrivals by 84% between March and December 2020 (UNWTO, 2021). This sudden change to tourism dynamic limited tourists from exercising their desire to travel and explore new places and led to growing interest in "staycation" and domestic travelling. Algerians took part in domestic mobility and became intrigued to discover local destinations.

¹⁷ Former name of the Iberian Peninsula, currently Spain and Portugal

During the vast spread of the Coronavirus, many countries sought to ban international travel or impose stricter rules for travellers.

As the UNWHO announcement regarding the global pandemic in March 2020, Algeria's policy was to reinforce an international ban on any form of transportation. This policy forced people and travel enthusiasts to remain quarantined in their homes to contain the virus' spread within Algerian society. However, with fewer restrictions to regulations on the domestic level, Algerians began mobilising internally to satisfy their need to be in a new place and act as tourists. As a result, domestic tourism witnessed significant growth, especially within travel agencies' offers and demands. In this regard, Agency 4 states that

“Ever since Covid started, people began requesting domestic destinations ... I had few destinations that were not popular among Algerians because they always ask for international destinations or the generic one -the Sahara- but surprisingly, Covid revived the domestic market and encouraged me to arrange more offers with plenty of incentives and activities ... ”.

The agency's statement reflects how the global pandemic contributed to boosting the popularity of Algeria's domestic tourism among Algerians. Despite the monumental shift to the tourism industry at the global level and how the industry itself was put on hold during the pandemic outbreak, Algerian tourists shifted their attention to domestic destinations. This shift, primarily motivated by the international travel ban in March 2020, encouraged domestic tourism to be recognised and pushed travel agencies to provide for the high demand for Algerian destinations. In a sense, the global pandemic rescued -to some extent- Algeria's tourism sector, which has been neglected for decades, and contributed to marketers reconsidering their strategies to include more local destinations. A newspaper article by Ayache (2022) offered a glance at Algeria's tourism situation during and post-pandemic. Ayache (2022) asserts that the global pandemic caused an influx in accommodation capacity in almost all hotels across Algeria. In her interview with Said Boukhelifa, president of the National Union of Travel Agencies:

For the majority -of tourists- it is an adventure; they rent a coach, take a guide and head towards Tikjda and the Djurdjura -Mountainous regions in the Northeast of Algeria- or towards the south, especially to Taghit -Southwestern Saharan city.

Additionally, lifting the international ban has little impact on domestic tourism. As reported by Algeria's tourism ministry (MTA), the Algeria-Tunisia border's opening has, in fact, impacted Tunisia's tourism industry, with -50% of Algerians travelling to Tunisia for summer vacation, compared to the 2018 season (MTA, 2022).

The domestic market growth is also witnessed in Algeria during the nation's lockdown since the pandemic started, and the travel ban was imposed on air, land, and sea. Despite the travel ban policy, which was a protective measure to stop the spread of the pandemic, tourists were growing impatient, especially those who are frequent travellers passionate about always being on the road. By the summer of 2021, the travel ban eased to allow limited international travel, especially for expatriates and urgent medical care, while domestic mobility became significantly easier. The facilities opened for domestic travel allowed a great opportunity for both tourists to enjoy travelling again and for agencies to focus on the domestic market, especially since international travel was very limited and their businesses were on the verge of failure. As mentioned by Agency 1, *"I was about to shut my business down because of Covid; luckily, domestic travel was my only way to recover the losses of borders' closure of over a year"*. At the same time, Agency 4 said, *"I was not expecting such high demand for domestic destinations just when the restrictions were slightly lifted"*, and Agency 5 added, *"Offers to local destinations were not appealing until Covid hit and people did not find a way to travel but to go to a local city"*. With such interest in domestic destinations, agencies faced the growing demand to provide newer and richer offers to tourists. It was essential for these travel agencies to work with host communities and tourism offices in popular Algerian destinations to create programmes with various activities, accommodation, and transport facilities.

During my discussions with the agencies, I noted their views on how a global pandemic that affected and slowed down all economies and industries could benefit the Algerian domestic tourism market. These conclusions do not underestimate the pandemic's negative consequences on most economies and sectors. However, from a business perspective, and for a previously colonised country that struggled since the 1960s to recover and create a decent tourism industry, it fascinates me to view such progress and, most importantly, Algerians' interest in exploring their country and uncovering hidden and tourism-worthy places that we do not usually see advertised for. In this instance, I view the domestic tourism industry's potential, especially when the transportation links are stretched to connect all cities, and social

media aids in introducing Algeria to local Algerians and unveiling ways to improve the tourist experience. Adding to this, the sudden growth of domestic tourism encouraged policymakers and DMOs to reconsider exploring the domestic market's potential and the need to develop destination branding strategies.

The destination branding strategy sought a necessary step to be accomplished. The Algerian tourism office is on a mission to create a destination personality. Destination personality is a strategic approach to creating a distinctive and unique destination based on tourists' perceptions and experiences of destinations (Morgan et al., 2003; Caprara et al., 2001). The needs should primarily drive the destination development process, wishes and aspirations of the host communities and involve them in the construction strategy (Fernandes, 2013). The host communities' contribution to destination development stimulates the local economy and creates a value-added commercial road for their local products (ibid.). Meanwhile, the host community's sensory, affective, behavioural, and intellectual characteristics are important factors to be embedded in the development process to achieve a memorable destination experience (Barnes et al., 2014) and avoid affecting the host community's role in advertising (Jackson & Morpeth, 1999).

Kim et al. (2012) highlighted that the most distinguishing factor in the destination experience relies upon its memorability and tourist interest. A memorable destination experience should be based on various dimensions: involvement, pleasure, social interaction, meaningfulness, knowledge, personal relevance, and intellectual cultivation (Kim et al., 2012; Karayilan & Cetin, 2016). In Algeria's case, the emphasis of tourism promotion is mostly on the southern regions and providing the Saharan experience to local tourists (Karim, 2016). In this regard, one agent said, *"70% of my travel agency's offers are to Southern cultural destinations and Sahara's festivals, while 30% are to North-eastern destinations where Roman ruins and heritage is present"*. (Agent5). This reflects that for most travel agencies, the destination personality they seek to promote is the exoticness of the South.

The Sahara promotion revolves around the host community's cultural implementation and involvement in the offers by recruiting local guide tours and benefiting from cultural and religious festivals. The cultural aspects of Algeria's southern destinations have complied with travel agencies' offers to their customers, while we nearly notice complete neglect of the rest of the North's destinations. Participant D3 stated:

“The Casbah in Algiers, Tipaza’s Roman ruins, and Tlemcen’s national park are all incredible destinations to go to in the North but rarely advertised by agencies ... I visited those sites several times and never saw a travel agency’s group. It is always individuals visiting on their own, and I always found it odd because they are worth advertising and more recognition”.

According to the tourists and agencies, the focus on Southern destinations results from the customers’ demands and interest to visit and integrate within the host communities’ culture. Tourism offices work on meeting customers’ expectations; they creatively construct the offers based on the destination’s climatic conditions, natural environment, and diversity of attractions (Kastarlak & Barber, 2013). Kastarlak and Barber developed a tourism planning system based on the dynamics of multidisciplinary relations in the tourism industry. According to the system’s principles, Algeria’s southern destinations draw tourists’ attention to the attractions available while enhancing the facilities to serve them. Thus, tourists are more likely to visit for longer periods and meet their expectations in the presence of numerous good quality and diverse attractions in the destination (Kastarlak & Barber, 2013). Human-made attractions in the southern destinations vary from cultural festivals, desert skiing, and Safari rides (Kahoul, 2018; Karim, 2016). As described by one of the tourists, the festivals offer entertaining and *“different vibes for the Sahara visitors ... it is a completely different atmosphere than the life in the North ... it is more appealing to the eyes and vibrant” (E2).*

Upon interviewing the travel agencies, they collectively agreed on tourists’ demands and interest in Southern destinations’ offers. Agency 1 commented, *“My clients are always looking for something fun, entertaining, different from their city life.”* while Agency 2 stated: *“Tourists are drawn to the uniqueness of the Sahara and the welcoming of the communities there.”* Most agents agreed that consumers are more likely to request a Southern destination than a Northern one. They justified their statement by pointing at the difficulty of reaching the Sahara and tourists’ unfamiliarity with the place and host community, which takes us back to the safety and security notions I discussed previously in Section 6.4. Therefore, purchasing an agency’s offer is easier for tourists worried about safety to ensure satisfaction, comfort, and flexibility of their trip. Additionally, agents collectively agreed that the exoticness and uniqueness of the Southern destinations encouraged more tourists, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, to gravitate to local destinations as international travel was banned. Agencies currently structure their offers based on the selected destinations and the most popular activities. Using the example of Sahara’s destinations, all participating agents said they began

including sand skiing and desert bikes among the activities to be added to the purchased offer. At the same time, they try to accommodate all their customers and provide various cultural and leisure activities.

When reviewing travel agencies' offers posted on social media, I noticed the large commentary on offers of Southern destinations. A few examples of these offers are in the Figures 7.5 and 7.6 below;

Figure 7.5. A travel agency's offer to Bou Saada, Algeria, with replies from the agency to potential customers

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions

Figure 7.6. A travel agency's offer to Oued Souf

The image above presents an offer from a travel agency with 133,000 followers. The agency created a collage to show the activities that will be provided for consumers who choose to purchase this offer. The activities that are included are (1) camel and horse rides, (2) quad rides, (3) 4x4 safari, and (4) traditional dinners. When I interviewed the agency's representative, he ensured that their agency's goal is to deliver services and offers that are diverse and culturally rich for a positive tourist experience.

“Our aim in our agency is to provide positive services for our clients ... we usually run surveys on social media asking our followers what they want us to include in our offers, and we mostly consider their feedback to better our offers and positively impact their experiences in the promoted destination” (Agency 5).

The agency's digital strategy to lower the boundaries with their followers on Instagram is perceived as a positive approach to learning about what tourists want and how they can improve their clients' experiences.

Interestingly, with tourists demanding more cultural destinations and the inclusion of activities within the host community, I view it as a way for these tourists to reconnect with their

national identity and attempt to understand what links them all together to the land. The underlying reasoning for exploring one's roots and understanding the national and cultural identity is the past colonised way of leaving behind the preconditioned idea of the colonial power embedded deeply within the Algerian society and mind. As discussed in Chapter 3, nationalist movements within Algeria during and after colonialism fought relentlessly to protect the Algerian identity and the Arab Islamic values within the Algerian community. However, the difficulty in preserving the Arab Islamic identity that once prevailed and later overshadowed through alienation policies was reflected through the indigenous' understanding and communication of who they are and what makes them Algerians. This instance encouraged travel agencies to embed Islamic values within their promoted offers to help in the rhetoric of voicing the national identity and instil interest in one of the pillars of Algerian society. One example can be taken from my interviews with the agencies and upon reviewing their offers on social media is the presence of various activities implying religious acknowledgement, such as tours to the oldest mosques in the chosen destination and celebrations of the New Hijri Year;

"We have tours to visit Ketchaoua Mosque in Algiers, AlNakhla Mosque in Biskra, and so many ancient mosques across the country; we always attempt to reflect the conservative side of the destination, especially in Southern cities as they are more conservative than the North" (Agency 2);

"We always have certain plans for New Year's celebrations, usually an organised trip to Ghardaïa, Biskra, Djanet, and Tamanrasset, where locals have festivals and activities involving horse riding with armed shooting, bonfires and local music, traditional food ...etc." (Agency 4).

The growing interest in cultural characteristics being embedded as a tool for marketing purposes reflects how important it is to work with host communities (Zaei & Zaei, 2013; Soares et al., 2021). The implication of the host communities to the tourist experience is greatly appreciated and considered an essential part of tourists' satisfaction after visiting the destination. For this reason, many travel agencies and tour operators ensure the involvement of host communities in their offers' development and product reliability to provide what the tourist is looking for positively. Additionally, they began implementing digital practices in their destination marketing strategies to ensure a wider reach and delivery of their offers, and with the realisation of electronic Word-of-Mouth has input on redirecting tourists' decision on a destination.

7.4. Digital Practices in Promoting Postcolonial Identity

eWOM, or the information obtained from interpersonal sources, impacts the consumer's decision-making more than traditional marketing techniques (Goldsmith & Clark, 2008). It is viewed as a more credible and authentic message delivered by a fellow consumer who has already tested the product/service (De Veirman et al., 2017) and a powerful, persuasive tool than when provided by an advertiser. With the significant growth in social media popularity, having two billion active users on Instagram only (Statista, 2021), eWOM is widely recognised for exerting a considerate influence on consumers' decision-making (Boyd & Ellison, 2007; Knoll, 2016; Jansen et al., 2009). Some participants stated having social media accounts to share their personal experiences travelling within Algeria; *"Instagram is a great platform to share my travel and experiences with others"* (B2); *"I love to travel and have always looked for others' experiences to have an idea about certain destinations ... for this, I opened my Instagram account to help others deciding where to go, or at least learn something new about our country"* (A3).

Social media influencers, or so they are called content creators (De Veirman et al., 2017) and digital influencers (Kapitan & Silvera, 2016), have played a major role in promoting tourism. They represent a new type of independent endorsers capable of shaping their audience's attitudes through social media posts (Freberg et al., 2011). As opinion leaders, content creators use the information and deliver it to their audience persuasively (Jalilvand et al., 2017). Participants agreed that Algerian digital influencers' voice is widely recognised and trusted among their audience, especially since Algeria is at a stage of growth and prosperity and continuously enhancing hospitality services (Aouinane, 2014). Development in the public sector and hospitality services is witnessed in most Algerian cities: *"... in the last ten years, there has been a construction of multiple hotels and attraction sites which helped immensely in flourishing domestic tourism ... people now have places to go to ... they can easily find accommodation ..."* (D4); *"In my city [Setif] they built many hotels and one of the biggest malls in the country ... transportation links were also established to the preserved Roman ruins Djemila, which is a popular cultural heritage ...it was also nominated as the country's greenest city in 2019... now it is widely visited by people from different regions...."* (A4); and *"I have visited almost every city in Algeria ... hospitality services are widely available and accessible"* (C4).

With the significant growth in hospitality services and constant improvements in the Algerian tourism sector, the industry's workers attempt to deliver better offers to potential customers. One approach I notice being conducted by travel agencies in Algeria is promoting their offers through social media and providing their services to popular influencers for digital advertising. Travel agencies tend to select influential content creators who share their domestic tourists' experiences and influence their audience's decisions (Javed & Awan, 2022). Such a strategy ensures a larger reach of the promoted offers (De Veirman et al., 2017) and enables agencies to gain new customers via the influencers' social accounts. Based on the discussion with the participants identified as travel content creators, they confirmed the presence of work agreements with agencies based on certain criteria: the agencies' ethical background, online reputation, and offers' affordability for all social ranks. Participant D4 said, "*... I always check the agencies' activity on all social media platforms and people's responses in the comments ... if I accepted the offer, I would rate it based on the programme's timing, structure, and their ethics and customer service ...*"; while participant D6 stated, "*... I advocate for affordability and ability to travel at a low cost ... if the offer is expensive, I will not accept the collaboration*".

The collaborative work between agencies and the participating social media endorsers encouraged the latter to provide authenticity and trustworthiness and to ensure a positive consumer experience with the offers promoted by delivering novelty, uniqueness, competition, and interest to potential consumers (Királ'ová & Pavlíček, 2015). With a constant desire to use these attributes in the endorsers' favour, trust between the influencers and consumers resulted in continuous communication. Digital influencers aim to create attractiveness and casualty on their accounts. Participant D8 said, "*My goal has always been creating a safe environment for my followers where they can share their experiences with me and take my word and recommendations for any destination I previously posted about*". As a result, digital influencers collectively agreed that they gained positive feedback from their followers. Their experiences were always informative and confirmed achieving a successful marketing strategy, according to participant D5 who stated "*...I am thankful for the trust and positive environment I see towards my content whether publicly or privately ... I constantly receive messages from people that took my recommendations and visited a destination I previously went to ...*"; while participant D9 said "*... people are always respectful towards each other ... they help by answering each other's concerns, and I constantly learn new information about different destinations ... that is why I am doing it*". These statements align with what Guede et al. (2020)

found in their research concerning the relationship between the e-service quality provided by travel YouTubers and the e-relationship quality with the users. The field research was intended to measure the quality of the electronic relationship between users and Youtubers and identify the dimensions that form and direct the users' behaviour towards travel content. Guede et al. (2020) found that users' attitude is redirected to developing a positive eWoM interaction, in addition to the tendency to repeat the purchase. Measuring trust, satisfaction, and commitment indicated that the interrelationship between content creators and consumers represents an e-loyalty to the content and the potential to influence consumers' decision-making processes.

Additionally, agencies are more likely to advertise their offers through travel content creators. Agency 3 mentioned, *"I previously worked with a travel influencer to whom I offered an all-inclusive trip to Timimoun in exchange for advertising my agency on their social platform"*, while Agency 5 stated, *"I already have a social media account to advertise my offers, but I prefer working with influencers that have a unique way of narrating their travel experiences through their posts and pictures"*. It seems that travel agencies and content creators can provide more insights into travel destinations, especially the cultural aspect of Algerian destinations, as culture is viewed as a raw material in advertising Brand Algeria. The collaborative work between both parties is what Nanji (2017) demonstrated as the five main reasons for hiring influencers in marketing destinations (further reflected in 8.2.2). These five reasons are namely: (1) improve brand advocacy, (2) expand brand awareness, (3) reach targeted audience, (4) increase the share of voice, and (5) improve sales conversion.

The consumer-endorser relationship is built based on attractiveness, trustworthiness, and familiarity (Branchik & Chowdhury, 2017). Another study by Nielson (2013), as part of the Global Survey of Trust in Advertising, concluded that 68% of global respondents confirmed they trusted consumers' opinions and experiences posted online, while 84% of global respondents stated that they trust Word-of-Mouth suggestions from friends and families. Consequently, social media platforms are increasingly becoming trustworthy, especially for travellers, to adjust their decisions and intentions regarding a destination and aid in planning and experience formation. In the figure below, a travel content creator with an account exceeding 743,000 followers posted a picture of her trip to Oued Souf;

Figure 7.7. A travel content creator in Oued Souf, Algeria

Oued Souf is an Algerian Eastern city largely known for its Saharan characteristics and cultural richness. The content creator faces a tall, white building in the image above. The building is an ancient mosque depicting a neo-Moorish architectural style. The building is painted white, with minimal to no designs from the outside, and has several domes and a minaret stretching to several meters. A traditional cape worn by the content creator also reflects the traditional style of drawing and designing local costumes and outfits. With over 743,000 followers on Instagram, the travel content creator is advertising her hometown's culture and identity. In her post, she did not disclose whether she collaborated with a travel agency to advertise a tourism offer; however, that does not exclude the content creators' efforts in advertising domestic destinations lacking digital presence.

From a service provider's perspective, advertising messages delivered by an endorser are more likely to direct greater audience attention and appeal than the regular traditional advertising strategies (Sääksjärvi et al., 2016; Spry et al., 2011) and consequently shape the tourist destination image (Kracht & Wang, 2009). Social media influencers are expected to spread the word through their platforms and launch a campaign to introduce the offer to form

a brand image and influence their followers' intentions towards the destination (Tapinfluence, 2015). The travel content creators participating in focus group D talked about opportunities to visit and promote a few destinations. Their responses were:

"... I am invited to a tour organised in the ancient city of Al Casbah ... documenting the trip and introducing it to my audience is part of the deal ... it is a great opportunity for myself and my followers to learn about the city's history and cultural value ..." (D4);

"I received an invitation from a tour guide in the city of Ghardaïa ... they are trying to promote the destination as the portal of the Sahara, and they invited a few digital influencers to reach their goal. I am willing to share the trip on my social media platforms...." (D9)

Algerian host communities and tourism offices continue working on inviting digital influencers to the destination for marketing purposes, especially since social platforms are now seen as a powerful tool to influence consumers' decisions and the targeted environment to increase the destination's competitiveness and publicity (Királ'ová & Pavlíček, 2015). The strategy resulted in wider exposure to the promoted destinations. It spreads more information about the host community, leading local destinations to gain popularity in the domestic market and improve the tourism sector. Throughout my discussion with participants about content creators' work with travel agencies and host communities, I noticed how crucial their role is to deliver real-life experiences for their audience when advertising domestic destinations. Evidently, there is no other outlet that fits current society's needs than social media to learn about interesting destinations and activities. These destinations were once only popular among agencies' customers or the locals to the area; however, with social media, it has been much easier to know about new destinations, societal and cultural characteristics, and hospitality services available, which offered tourists the opportunity to structure their future travel plans based on recommendations and others' experiences.

7.5. Algerian Tourists' Experiences with Digital Branding of Algeria

As previously established in Chapter 6, the Algerian tourist experience is largely influenced by postcolonial consequences that affect how the tourist perceives his/her hybrid identity. Additionally, other tourists' experiences usually influence the tourist experience, feedback available on social media, and Word-of-Mouth. This understanding contributes to

establishing the question of what is included in the digital practices of travel agencies and content creators, contributing to tourists uncovering their identity.

With the complexities around the tourist experience from a postcolonial hybrid perspective, travel agencies and content creators are key players in dictating and (re)shaping the hybrid identity. This crucial role is driven by a desire to shift the narrative to what is best appropriate in a postcolonial context. In the case of Algeria, the travel agencies and content creators reflected their role in decolonising the tourism sector. This was noticed during the interviews when we discussed their views and aspirations for Algeria's tourism. A few examples of such arguments were mentioned by participant D1; a female travel content creator said:

“Culture is important; our indigenous culture is attractive when we show the authentic side of it, the side that is purely Algerian and found mostly in rural towns that were not majorly influenced by outside cultures”.

Participant D3; a male travel content creator from the South commented:

“I try to avoid showing the colonial heritage ... it is part of our history and embedded in our livelihood, but not part of our culture”.

As for travel agencies, Agency 6 stated:

“Our colonial past has been dominating our lives for a long time and that is enough ... we cannot let a brutal past shape our future, and it is time to regain control of our true identity and celebrate it through travel”.

Through travel agencies and content creators, we can see the optimism in (re)shaping how the Algerian identity has been narrated and the desire to pursue a decolonisation framework to reflect an authentic image of Algeria's culture, people, and tourism. Despite the *Hybridity* that the Algerian identity is characterised of, there is a clear and strong desire to slowly attempt to move from a colonial French-dominant identity to a decolonised Algerian identity with hybrid characteristics inherited from past civilisations and (re)shaped to fit the Algerians' reflections of self and surrounding.

It is worth mentioning that the lengthy French colonial presence in Algeria instilled certain characteristics within the Algerian community, notably the French architecture that remained protected by the Algerian Ministry of Culture. Upon reviewing the colonial legacy

present within the streets of Algeria, Participant B4 mentioned, *“The French architecture is still predominantly present and preserved across Algeria”*. In order to explain this statement, it is important to note that colonial presence was settler colonialism. France worked to include Algeria in the French metropole, which was achieved until the 1962 independence referendum, and with settler colonialism, it was their goal to rebuild Algeria for European settlers, hence the strong French architectural presence. Generally speaking, France adopted the neo-Moorish style when constructing buildings across Algeria (Belakehal et al., 2015). With its attractiveness and modern stylistic tendency, French buildings were preserved during the colonial era as they were homes and administrative offices for the colonial power and later preserved as a symbol of liberation in postcolonial Algeria (Barbara & Molnár, 2019). The French architecture reflects a symbol of colonial legacy that was accepted and acquired by the Algerian government and community as part of their postcolonial identity. The neo-Moorish style indicates an Arab simple stylistic design with a touch of modernity. With the artistic alteration of adding Arabic writing and Koranic verses to architecture, ex-French buildings now reflect the postcolonial Algerian identity based on Islam and Arabic heritage.

Participant B8 made an interesting point regarding the language choice in digital practices when she stated, *“Almost all offers I have seen by travel agencies or posts of content creators are written in French”*. The statement indicates the assimilation policy's strong effect on today's Algerian community. Despite being a free nation for over 60 years, language seems still rooted within the community, administration, and even political speech (Benrabah, 2013). This has been reflected through Figures 6.1, 7.5, and 7.6. where travel agencies' offers are communicated using French, while customers responding to these offers posted on Instagram communicate using French or French/Algerian Arabic code-switching pattern.

The language issue has been debated among Algerian sociolinguists who study the Arabisation process and language planning and policy. French is still predominantly intertwined within Algerian speech. The phenomenon of code-switching clearly indicates how language setting is, to some extent, rich, however deemed impure, especially as most Arab nations struggle to comprehend the Algerian dialect because of its heavy implementation of French. Belfarhi (2019, p.53) refers to the code-switching pattern in Algerian speech as the result of “a contact of cultures rather than a contact with the French people”. To a certain degree, the Algerian way of speaking is a concoction of French and Arabic terms, used

alternatively or in conjunction for reasons of familiarity, vocabulary richness, or lack thereof, or even interdependence between the two systems due to the long period they have been used together. Ibrahimi (1995, p.117) noted in this regard that:

We see how the elements of the French language are mixed with the elements of the Arabic language: we can even say that they can be integrated into the system of the language. The French verbs are conjugated in the same way as the Arabic verbs.

The decolonisation process in Algeria and the pursuit of replacing the French language with Arabic presented a complex and contentious issue deeply rooted in the country's colonial history and struggle for liberation. With the French colonial policy of erasing the Algerian identity and promoting French language and culture, French "became the language of instruction in schools, administration, and public life, while Arabic and Berber languages were marginalised", as Djamila Saidi noted in her book *The Algerian Uprising* (1962). As *Arabisation* policy was set in post-colonial Algeria, there was a core focus established to replace French with Arabic as the official language as Arabization was considered as a means of reassuring Algeria's Arab-Muslim identity to break with the colonial past (Pargeter, 2008).

In tourism context, the continued prominence of the French language in Algerian tourism promotion is seen by some as undermining the country's decolonisation efforts and the Arabisation policy. Alistair Preston notes in *The Compact Compendium of the World's Languages* (Campbell & King, 2020) that the French language is still considered as an important lingua franca in various sectors such as tourism because of its historical legacy, and in the case of Algeria, the language became deeply rooted within the Algerians' day-to-day glossary. This issue of reliance on the French language especially in the tourism sector has drawn criticism from advocates of Arabisation. Karima Slimani-Direche, a French Algerian historian mentions in *The Berber Question; Linguistic and language politics* (Lafkioui, 2013) that the persistence of French in various can be regarded as failure to fully decolonize and promote national language, which undermines the purpose of the Arabisation policy. This asserts that the policy failed in Algeria, to a certain extent, in fully replacing French with Arabic. However, this does not prevail from taking into consideration the fact that French heritage is part of the Algerian identity. Madjid Haddad, the author of *Language Planning in Algeria* (2011), notes that economic considerations and practicality should be prioritised over ideological stances. Haddad states that despite the Arabisation's importance for the identity

restoration, it is also significant to prioritise effective marketing efforts with whichever language to communicate the industry's aspirations.

French architecture and language are visible throughout travel agencies and content creators' digital branding practices. This glorification and somewhat appreciation of colonial legacy may receive a certain rejection from Algerian nationals who categorically refuse anything concerning France. Participant B6 stated:

"I am from the South; we only use Algerian Arabic, which is something that I saw different in Northern cities ... I do not like how French is still present in our dialect ... it is not part of our identity as Algerians",

While participant B4 (an Amazigh) asserted:

"I appreciate the diversity we have within our country, and even more that we still have historical monuments that reminds and narrates our country's struggle with colonialism, but I do not want only to see history, I want to see us, I want to see our culture and identity".

To a certain extent, both statements reflect the importance of communicating the national identity when branding instead of endorsing a colonial legacy. Of course, discussing and presenting indications of a country's historical struggle with self-determination is important as it is, in a way, a narration of the past; however, the present identity should also be celebrated. Participant D6 (a travel content creator) affirms the importance of identity in branding:

"I appreciate seeing a culture and people's celebration of such culture in their own way; that is something I want to capture and share as an experience through social media ... Saharan destinations are great in representing their identity and customs, regardless of what can be historically intrusive".

This statement can reflect how host communities in Southern destinations strive to represent their Algerian identity and cultural practices. Additionally, as per the statement of B6 above, the Southern communities resisted change, yet they still indicated signs of *Hybridity* as they faced colonialism and its repercussions.

7.6. Summary

The practice of posting on social media about a destination, its culture, people, and unique characteristics contributes to the overall aims of encouraging mobility and tourism. The portrayed image of cultural destinations narrates the authentic story of the place and contributes to (re)shaping the perception of identity and pursuits of decolonising tourism. Throughout this chapter, I went through an analysis and discussion of data that were gathered from Algerian travel agencies and travel content creators to demonstrate how Algeria's culture and identity are digitally (re)presented to (re)shape and (re)construct the Algerian postcolonial hybrid identity. With illustrations from social media platforms of Algeria destinations, it has been enlightening to investigate and interpret the digital practices of Algerian travel agencies and travel content creators in decolonising the Algerian identity and attempting to lessen the celebration of French legacy and heritage surrounding the Algerian people daily.

The following chapter will present and summarise the findings of this research and connect these findings with the literature concerning postcolonial tourism, national identity, and Algerian postcolonial studies. In addition, I will conclude with the practical and theoretical contributions of the present study to the tourism field and postcolonial studies, along with recommendations for future studies, a personal reflection on my PhD journey, and the study's limitations.

CHAPTER EIGHT: CONCLUSIONS

8.1. Introduction

Throughout the interpretation and analysis presented in the previous two chapters, I have been able to demonstrate the process in which tourists' experiences and their postcolonial identity are closely and continuously fusing and colliding to construct a decolonised narrative to tourism practices, and the extent to which the characteristics of the Algerian national identity take account of tourism practices and digital consumption of tourism-related content. This guide to identifying and recognising the gaps in which tourists' experiences are studied, especially from a postcolonial perspective. In a more nuanced conclusion, this study attests to the importance of tourism practices and activities to (re)shape, (re)construct, and (re)interpret the postcolonial identity tourists are in constant search of, which in retrospect, reflects the decolonising processes underlying their crucial role in ideally (re)presenting the Algerian postcolonial hybrid identity.

This chapter provides an account to summarise and conclude the thesis. First, I present the key findings of the study and how participants' views and interpretations of their postcolonial identity and tourism practices are brought together through decolonisation processes to tourism narratives and hybrid identity. Second, I explain the theoretical and practical contributions of the study in terms of postcolonial studies of tourists' experience in domestic contexts to uncover the postcolonial identity, and how it manifests through tourism practices. Third, I provide recommendations for future research concerning postcolonial identity in Algeria and tourism implications in decolonising national identity. Lastly, I conclude this thesis with a personal reflection in which I recapitulate my research journey and how I developed this work through my own process of conceptualising and understanding my postcolonial identity.

8.2. Key findings

In a postcolonial setting, national identity is viewed as a hybrid space where it can be challenging to illustrate and properly deliver in words. Bhabha's *Third Space* and Said's *Orientalism* and *Othering* concepts are key theories to comprehend where one can locate their

identity, and what makes them who they are in their social and cultural positioning. My research questions that shaped the process of investigating identity are:

1. To what extent is the postcolonial identity of Algerian tourists influencing their experiences in domestic tourism practices?
2. How are domestic tourism trends featured and communicated on social platforms to influence and reshape the Algerian tourists' experiences and their postcolonial identity?

As I explained previously in **Chapter Two** and **Three**, this research is relying on concepts of postcolonialism, tourism practices and postcolonial national identity. This thesis was primarily concerned with uncovering Algerians' identity through exploring the notions of *Hybridity* and *Third Space* in tourists' experiences. My data collection process was conducted online and was in three different settings, focus group discussions, interviews, and visuals documented on social media platforms. While interpreting my data through a TA model, I focused on delivering what the participants interpret as their worldviews and understanding of tourism digital practices and experiences in (re)shaping their national identity.

In **Chapter Four**, I described and reported the theoretical framework that highlights key theories that this research constitutes of. The focus was primarily on Bhabha's *Hybridity* and *Third Space* theory, Said's *Orientalism* underpinnings, and Spivak's *Otherness* in matters of Algerians' position as colonised subjects. These theories were closely connected to the field of postcolonial tourism to demystify the concept of identity among Algerian tourists in their pursuits of (re)constructing and uncovering their national identity.

The key findings that I discussed and presented in **Chapter Six** and **Seven** are stemming from the five main themes found through applying TA model; (1) encountering identity, (2) challenging postcolonial identity, (3) reconstructing cultural disparity, (4) decolonising identity, and (5) experiencing decolonised identity. The key findings are synthesised in this concluding chapter to gain insights into tourists' postcolonial identity and experiences with digital branding practices, and to answer the aforementioned research questions under the following results:

- Algerians' national identity is unstable and in constant alteration within a *Third Space*;
- The digital practices of travel agencies and content creators are significantly (re)shaping how tourists perceive their identity, and positively contributing to the overall influence on tourists' decision-making processes and their experiences as visitors of the promoted domestic destination;

- The postcolonial complexes (namely trauma, safety concerns, and poverty) are limiting tourists from exploring their full potentials to travel to domestic destinations.

The above results are to be explained and summarised in the following sections entitled:

- Locating Algerians' national identity ;
- Digital practices to decolonise tourism for domestic tourists;
- Postcolonial complexes to tourists' experiences.

8.2.1. Locating Algerians' National Identity

Our modern world is uniquely characterised with a compression of time-space and a significant advancement in communication and transportation (Cresswell, 2006). Tourism and mobility are in the core of defining one's experience. This study focuses on the external influences that are existing within the realm of the Algerian tourists' understanding and interpretation of their national identity. In this section of the chapter, I am summarising the findings that reflect how an Algerian tourist interpret, locate, and (re)construct the postcolonial national identity in the *Third Space* framework.

From the data analysis in **Chapter 6** (See 6.2 and 6.3), we noticed how the tourist is in a constant search to locate the national identity of the Algerian indigenous people. Throughout this process of fitting within an identity framework, Algerian tourists are facing the difficulty of knowing what constitute the complex ideology of being an Algerian. Consequently, they locate various characteristics of their identity; being an Arab, being a Muslim, being an Amazigh, which were all confirming the colonial separation of ethnic, national, and self-identity. Unlike in the era when Arab nationalism movement was vouching for an Arab-Islamic national identity, today the national identity is mostly limited to the term "Algerian", which may be an indication of the strong bond the Algerians have with their land; a land their grandparents and ancestors fought to regain for over a decade.

The state of the national identity of Algerians is altered and fused with different cultures that came in contact with Algerians at a certain time in history. Historical presence of civilisations and foreign cultures has been influential on the development and (re)construction of today's postcolonial identity of Algerians. To put it in a postcolonial theoretical perspective, the *Hybridity* of Algeria's national identity presents a unique space that features various ideologies, cultures, and visual representation. As previously mentioned in Sections **6.2,7.27.5,**

language as a mode of communication served the *Hybridity* aspect to which a new jargon has emerged, combining multiple codes to switch interchangeably while an Algerian is having a day-to-day conversation. Music as a constituent of culture was also influenced with the adaptation of Andalusian folk music from the Iberian Peninsula, and became a folk musical style that is widely chanted among small towns and conservative parts of Northern Algeria. National traditional costumes were surprisingly preserved, and kept their originality and authenticity throughout colonial and postcolonial era. Yet, architecture is significantly accepted and celebrated through portraying colonial heritage on social media platforms.

The ongoing influence of external factors and characteristics of other identities is contributing to a continuous state of reconstruction to the identity of Algerians. This process is reflected to everyday interactions with people from the same community, and with the outside world. Adding to that, the practice of tourism and mobility can be a contributing factor in triggering the reconstruction process since mobility “captures the gist of people’s progression in time and space” (Theodoropoulou, 2015, p.65). In these lines, the process of uncovering the identity is illustrated below:

Figure 8.1. an illustrative diagram of participants’ process of locating their identity

The figure above reflects the continuous cycle of locating and (re)constructing the hybrid identity the participants belong to and identify with throughout their lives. These

processes are showing a simultaneous occurrence when tourists interact with their identity through their approach to understand and locate themselves from a postcolonial perspective. While this can be reflective to any individual seeking to understand their national identity, Botta (2021) presented an excellent example in her autobiography. Botta (2021) narrates her personal experience as a migrant showcasing the process of deconstructing and reconstructing of her identity within an *Other* community. Her autobiographical account of the lived experiences is a testament to the simultaneous and continuous process of locating oneself, deconstructing what is already known through personal worldviews, and proceeding in reconstructing new hybrid identities to understand one's position within the socio-cultural contexts of a community.

8.2.2. Digital Practices to Decolonise Tourism for Domestic Tourists

Mobility and tourism are considered to be the physical movement of people from one place to another. This phenomenon existed for centuries that today it is displaying its characteristics through technological development and ICTs (Urry, 2007). In our modern world, the technological advancement serves as a fast online opportunity to maintain contact and awareness in regard to tourism practices. This contributes to foster and expose the fluid, complex and diverse experiences of other tourists in terms of (re)presenting the identity.

In recent years, social media witnessed a significant growth of users and content across all spectrums, areas, and topics of interest. Tourism being linked to visual acceptance and motivation, is also prevailing on social media as people are more prone to share their travel and motivated to visualise their destinations. Many content creators share their travel with their audience and influence them in pursuing similar tourism practices (Jansen et al., 2009; Knoll, 2016; Lai et al., 2018). Travel agencies are now viewing content creators as facilitators to advertise their offers to larger audiences, and sought collaborations to delve into digital marketing. As per Nanji's work (2017), marketers and travel agencies are leaning more towards hiring influencers in their marketing for 5 main reasons; (1) to improve the brand advocacy, (2) to expand the brand awareness, (3) to reach new customers and targeted audience, (4) to increase the share of voice and exposure percentage in comparison to competitors in the field, and (5) to improve the sales conversion.

The digital practices that I noticed throughout my investigation has shown significant focus on the culture of the destination been advertised. Interviews conducted with travel agencies and content creators indicate the importance of using culture as a tool to widely influence social media users, and spread knowledge about these cultures and the richness of each domestic destination. Additionally, I concluded that the five reasons for content creators' marketing tool are implemented by the Algerian travel agencies. These are as follows: (1) to improve the brand advocacy, (2) to expand the brand awareness, (3) to reach new customers and targeted audiences, (4) to increase the share of voice and exposure percentage, and (5) to improve the sales conversion.

Through social platforms where Algeria's tourism is promoted, content creators are seemingly improving the brand advocacy and awareness. The follow-up interviews with Algerian tourists have reflected how the said tourists are now more aware of newer destinations and newer activities to shape their experiences in uncovering their national identity. The digital marketing practices are also reaching to new customers. Data also reflect that Algerian tourists are exposed to travel agencies' offers and willing to take part in new experiences to learn about the host communities and their respective culture and identity. As for travel agencies that are active on social media, and collaboratively working with travel content creators, their offers are more likely to be far more reaching to customers, especially young tourists who actively use social media for their pre-purchase stage. This comes in contrast as a positive attribute for travel agencies who are up to date with ICTs and are aware of the importance of digital branding at times of globalisation and social media widespread, in comparison to the travel agencies who are still using traditional branding methods to promote and sell their offers. As for the fifth reason; to improve the sales conversion, this is reflected in travel agencies' strategic branding plan when opting for content creators' marketing. The travel agencies I interviewed showed that they always aim to work with content creators that are allocated within the niche of travel. The following graph illustrates and summarises the Algerian travel agencies' process to brand through content creators' platforms with excerpts from data:

Figure 8.2. A summary of Algerian travel agencies' process to advertise through content creators' platforms

Travel agencies agreed on the importance of pursuing both traditional marketing; through national exhibitions and fairs, and the modern digital marketing; through social media platforms and content creators. The diversification of marketing strategies is considered to be profitable in terms of helping tourists shape their decision-making process, and positively

influencing their experiences once they conduct a trip to promoted domestic destinations. Additionally, travel agencies emphasised on the crucial role of digital marketing especially during the global pandemic of COVID-19 and closure of their offices. The ban on public gathering in close spaces encouraged travel agencies to give up on traditional marketing that they long have been using, and pursue digital marketing through social media platforms and visual incentives to encourage Algerians to purchase their offers.

Despite the efforts being conducted on social media for the sake of improving tourism sector, agencies and content creators agreed on the role of political and economic conduct on improving services, and providing further tourism facilities for a positive tourist experience. Adding to that, the travel agencies and travel content creators are playing a significant role in the decolonisation process of tourism. This is indicated in their destination choices that reflect the Algerian national identity, the Arab/Islamic significant locations, activities, and practices. Added to this, there is a certain pattern I concluded throughout my observation which is that travel agencies and content creators are leaning more towards advertising places that are deemed traditional, comfortable to see and visit, and simple to integrate with the host communities. An example of this is the Oued Souf destination. This Southeastern Saharan city is a traditional haven for those seeking the experience of living a simpler life, and partake in activities such as pottery and traditional rug making. In destinations like Oued Souf, the postcolonial Algerian culture is the main component in all activities. It is reflecting elements of *Hybridity* as all Algerians went through a postcolonial identity crisis post-independence, however, such destinations especially where the host community is involved within the destination planning process, continues to protect and represent its postcolonial culture and identity.

Throughout the advertising strategies implemented by Algerian travel agencies and content creators, it is resulted that their overarching aim is to decolonise the tourism narrative. Algeria's tourism promotion is focused on reflecting the cultural constituents and features of the society. Despite the apparent influences of colonial legacy (such as language dominance and code-switching patterns, and restored French architecture), there is a distinct pattern that travel agencies and content creators follow to reflect the Algerian identity that is hybrid in contexts of being a new space, a *Third Space*, in which past civilisations that once settled in

Algeria are concocted to produce a unique identity, with features that reflect the historical legacy of these civilisations in an “Algerian way”.

8.2.3. Postcolonial Complexes to Tourists’ Experiences

The Algerian tourist faces various complexes effecting the experience they seek to live. Some of these complexes discussed through Section 6.5 are of socio-economic origins. Poverty is an indicative economic issue that immensely influence tourists’ experience. The poverty complex limits the tourist experience, and causes the tourist to reconsider how to travel to a chosen destination, along with every aspect of the foreseen trip. Additionally, with a high poverty rate in Algeria, along with economic limitations to the sector of tourism, affordability of services is hardly reached by an Algerian from the middle class. As seen in participants’ responses during the data collection, tourists are reluctant to book hotel stays and are more likely to pursue a one-day trip or visit family and friends in their destination. Along the lines of poverty concerns, the issue of safety is also highly regarded and considered very crucial in a poor postcolonial society, especially by female travellers. The notion of safety is an indicative of the overall quality of the services provided. It reflects an important element to reach a positive experience. Additionally, it is a clear testament to the society’s overall perceived identity. The lack of safety can cause detrimental outcomes to the whole sector of tourism, and can prevent people from traveling. The third social complex to tourists’ experiences is the collective colonial trauma. As a postcolonial nation, with an extensively long history of battling settler colonialism, it is understandable how history can cause an inherited trauma effecting individuals in pursuing somewhat of “normal” upbringing, and healthy wellbeing.

The colonial trauma affected the psychology of the Algerians and put them in a constant state of fear, despite the freedom and comfort they are currently living in. Arguably, a psychological evaluation and consideration is ought to be widely performed to help Algerians comprehend and cope with their experiences and perception of their world. Such trauma is reflected through the writings of Frantz Fanon such as in *The Wretched of the Earth* (1961), *Black Skin, White Masks* (1952), and *A Dying Colonialism* (1959), in which he discussed the traumatising psychological warfare on the Algerian indigenous subjects. In his book *A Dying Colonialism* (1959), Fanon explained that the Algerian revolution was a transformative process that created ‘new souls’, to which I comment that it created a hybrid identity, a hybrid presence, and a hybrid personality of resilience and fear, challenges, and trauma. Fanon (1959) concluded

his book by a statement that is quite resonating to all Algerians, when he said “The revolution ... changes man and renews society, has reached an advanced stage. This oxygen which creates and shapes a new humanity -this, too, is the Algerian revolution”. Fanon was also concerned about the state of the Algerian society post-independence. According to Alice Cherki (2016), a close acquaintance to Fanon;

Fanon worried about the shape of the new society that would emerge in post-independence Algeria; the prospects were dim -a new bourgeoisie ready to pick up where the others had left off, or a power struggle between different clans or a religious movement that would succeed in determining the nature of the State.

This statement reflects as a grounded concern in his book *The Wretched of the Earth* in which he reported how the FLN is a multi-class compound that will potentially play a retrograde role upon raising to power after the Independence. Evidently, the FLN rise to power caused significant impact as the new state was attempting to decentralise politics and shift from national and nationalism to social and communist consciousness, which eventually will hinder the process of national independence and, according to Fanon, cannot be achieved since the majority of Algerians were peasants coming from colonial domination. Along these lines, Bhabha’s work *Framing Fanon* (2004) presents a reflection on the dynamics of decolonisation and nationalistic challenges in the globalisation era. Bhabha (2004, p. x) wrote:

Fanon’s best hopes for the Algerian revolution were taken hostage, and summarily executed, first by bureaucratized military rule ..., and then by the rise of fundamentalist groups like the Islamic Salvation Front.

Going back to the topic of tourism amidst these postcolonial complexes and challenge, the Algerian tourist is faced with an abundant weight of trauma when devouring the practice of tourism. Poverty, safety, and colonial trauma are all said to be major factors in directing the Algerian tourist experience in Algeria. As found in the data (See Section 6.5), Algerian tourists may fear travelling alone. This fear can stem from the idea that safety is not guaranteed, especially for female travellers, and as a sole resort, Algerian female travellers are more likely to opt for travel agencies’ offers. Algerian tourists are also reluctant to visit places that are known for higher poverty rate which may be challenging to their safety. Additionally, the Algerian tourists are challenged with the high expenses of travelling to domestic destinations due to financial reasons, which may lead these tourists to opt for alternative solutions, such as

visiting friends and relatives, travel for a same-day trip, and many options based on their flexibility, finances, and preferences.

These postcolonial complexes that are hindering the Algerian tourist from exploring their ‘land’ to the full potentials, are stemming from Said’s Orientalism work that indicated the process of constructing identities, alterities, and the tourist experience itself (Edensor, 1998; Boukhris & Peyvel, 2019). The outcome that is driving such postcolonial complexes, namely safety and trauma, is possibly deployed from the notion of the inconsistency in drawing significant lines during the decolonial stages of the Algerian state, and the inability to solve societal issues that can be a limitation to locating and (re)shaping the Algerian hybrid identity.

8.3. Research Contribution

Based on the findings presented and outlined in **Chapters Six and Seven**, this thesis gives a valuable contribution to two fields of research: (1) the tourist’s hybrid identity, and (2) postcolonial identity in Algeria.

The hybrid tourist experience contributes theoretically to the advancement in literature about the postcolonial tourist experience and identity understanding. The Algerian case in particular has certain dimensions to approach investigating settler colonial implications to identity, and this contributed to (re) shaping and drastically altering how identity is perceived by the Indigenous people of Algeria.

8.3.1. Theoretical Contribution

The study of Algerian tourists’ postcolonial identity contributes to the broader theoretical understanding of how colonial histories and power dynamics continue to shape contemporary tourism practices. A postcolonial theoretical lens allows for an examination of how Algerian tourists navigate and (re)construct their national and cultural identities in the context of a tourism industry that was largely shaped by French colonial rule (Pritchard & Morgan, 2000).

Postcolonial theory focuses on studying how postcolonial societies resist, negotiate, reformulate their identities, as well as the lens they perceive themselves from (Bhabha, 1994; Said, 1978). Bhabha’s notion of *Third Space* is highly relevant to this study’s theoretical scope

and the focus on Algerian tourists' identity understanding. The conceptualisation of the *Third Space* emphasises the in-betweenness, hybrid spaces where colonial and postcolonial identities, narratives, and power dynamics intersect and are (re)negotiated. When projecting this theory on the tourism context, the *Third Space* perspective suggests that Algerian tourists occupy a transitional position, navigating between their national/cultural identities and the touristic spaces, interactions, and (re)presentations that have been heavily influenced by the colonial past (Hollinshead, 1998; Wearing et al., 2010). Rather than simply accepting/absorbing or rejecting colonial-era tourism vision, Algerian tourists are more likely to engage in a process of cultural translation and hybridisation, creatively (re)constructing their identities through tourism experiences and within this ambiguous, in-between space.

Bhabha's scope to *Hybridity* and *Third Space* has shown the complexity of investigating a postcolonial national and cultural identity. The French colonial legacy created a "new space" where Algerians were subject to encountering newness and consequently mixing and "hybridising" their identity with the coloniser's. The cultural blend and syncretism are notably visible through Algerian tourists' behaviour, but vaguely worded in the sense of feelings of loss and Algerians' inability to clearly communicate and locate their national identity. This is also contributed to explaining how identity is flexible, fluid, and constantly changing, be it from a region to another, or from a person to another. However, the Algerian hybrid identity was found to have certain characteristics that are shared among all Algerian community. These characteristics can be linguistic, cultural, social, and historically inherited from colonial presence, but they are all pertaining within a *Third Space* in which these characteristics are a manifestation of the intercultural and social interaction between Algerian, Ottoman, Arab, and French cultures through history. The scholarship emerging from this investigation denotes that the case of Algeria is an interesting environment to investigate the socio-cultural interaction of civilisations that brought what we can locate today in Bhabha's *Third Space* theory.

Tourism has been found to serve a crucial element in uncovering and (re)shaping the hybrid identity. The aspect of mobility and travelling to domestic destinations contribute to providing a newer insight into how hybrid identities can be investigated. The present study enriches postcolonial tourism studies by providing empirical insights into how Algerian tourists engage with and make meaning of touristic spaces, interactions, and narratives in ways

that reflect their complex, multifaceted identities as simultaneously Algerian and postcolonial subjects (Wearing et al., 2009; Wearing & McDonald, 2002). This also adds to theories of tourist identity and behaviour by displaying how the colonial past is continuously shaping tourist motivations, experiences, and identities (Weaver, 2010). Additionally, the study's focus on Algerian tourists' identity expands the geographical scope of postcolonial tourism research, which tends to concentrate on former European colonies in the Global South, however with less focus on Algeria as a case study and an interesting sphere of postcoloniality and tourism intersection. Many scholars (such as Hollinshead, 1998; Hall & Tucker, 2004; Salazar, 2012; Hottola, 2009; Scheyvens, 2011) agree on the point that expanding the geographical scope of postcolonial tourism studies is important to capture the diverse ways colonial legacies manifest in tourism across different regional settings. This denotes that there is a need to emphasise on understudied contexts, such as Algeria which has received relatively less attention in postcolonial tourism studies, to broaden theoretical understandings of the intersections between tourism, colonialism, and identity, and exploring various tourism dynamics from the postcolonial nations' perspective. Furthermore, a focus on the case of Algeria can expand the theoretical application of Bhabha's theory beyond the more extensively researched former European colonies in the Global South. By examining the *Third Space* dynamics in the Algerian landscape, valuable comparative insights can emerge which might contribute to a more holistic, multifaceted theorisation of how colonial legacies and postcolonial identities intersect with and are (re)produced and manifested through tourism practices and experiences.

Overall, this study's theoretical contribution lies in its application of postcolonial theory to enhance the conceptual understanding of how tourist identities, behaviours, and experiences are fundamentally shaped by the enduring impacts of colonialism, even in the contemporary, supposedly "postcolonial" era.

8.3.2. Contributions to Tourism Sector

Examining the postcolonial identity of Algerian tourists carries several important contributions to the tourism field. The investigation provides valuable insights into how the legacy of French colonial rule continues to shape tourism practices, experiences, and (re)presentations in today's Algeria. By understanding how Algerian tourists navigate and (re)construct their national/cultural identities within a tourism landscape that was profoundly influenced by the colonial era, tourism stakeholders can develop more culturally sensitive and

inclusive approaches to tourism development and promotion. This was evident as discussions held with travel agencies reflected their motivation into including culture as demand grew for domestic destinations with cultural components and experiences.

Moreover, examining the postcolonial identity among Algerian tourists can shed light on the ways in which they resist, negotiate, and (re)direct tourism narratives and (re)presentations that may perpetuate colonial dominance and power structures (Bhabha, 1994). This collective knowledge can inform and instigate the development of tourism products, services, and marketing strategies that better align with the values, preferences, and self-perceptions of Algerian tourists as post-colonial subjects (Wearing et al., 2010). Upon my investigation of the digital practices performed by travel agencies and travel content creators, this study found that digital branding contributes immensely to the advancement and wider reach of tourism offers. Examining the digital representation of the Algeria identity, and how travel content creators show the cultural and national identity of Algeria through images reflects the way Algerians are taking the initiative to (re)present, and somewhat (re)shape the narrative around their identity. These practices can also be viewed from a broader societal perspective as they contribute to discussions around national identity, cultural sovereignty, and decolonial practices in the post-independence era (Hollinshead, 1998). They prompt attempts to decolonise the identity from the French colonial legacy that can be still reflected within the Algerian community through language and architectural infrastructure. Algerian tourists, along with Algerian content creators, are often engaged in a tendency to mix and match between their Arab Islamic heritage, the French colonial legacy, and the indigenous Amazigh attributes in ways that deem the culture and the identity as unstable and flexible (Bhabha, 1994; 2004). With employing Bhabha's notion of *Hybridity*, we may open newer perspectives in investigating discourse surrounding matters of "Other presentation" and "foreign-ness" (Hollinshead, 1998).

The study's findings can also provide valuable insights for policymakers, tourism marketers and organisations seeking to promote more equitable and empowering forms of tourism development in Algeria. The interest in uncovering and understanding the postcolonial identities of Algerian tourists can challenge the dominant colonial narratives and representations, and contribute to making changes to the broader societal discussions around identity (re)presentation and cultural inclusivity, leading to decolonising the tourism sector and properly showcasing the postcolonial Algerian identities.

With advancement in the ICTs in this era of globalisation, media is considered as a powerful tool to build and connect communities together. The digital marketing can be a contributor towards the process of conceptualising a nation and nationalism (Imran, 2017). Additionally, the growing interest and tendencies among tourists and consumers of tourism products towards visual stimulants and easy access to plans, recommendations, and solutions to their decision-making processes, tourism marketers can benefit from this point when creating their offers and meet consumer demand. In doing so, Anholt's competitive identity (2008) can be a significant approach to help brand the Algerian hybrid identity through the process of advertising their brand to represent the nation's distinct and unique value among national tourists, and later implement a wider aim to attract international audiences.

8.4. Recommendations for Future Research

The present study provided a valuable implication to the field of postcolonial research and postcolonial tourist experiences especially in the case of Algeria. The literature investigating Algerian tourism is mostly, but not limited to, researching tourism development perspectives and consumers' demands (Zeraib et al., 2022; Taibi, 2016; Louardi et al., 2018; Meftah et al., 2022); postcolonial heritage management and decision-making process to maintain sustainable tourism policies (Coslett, 2020; Aouchal et al., 2022); and cultural heritage sites' protection and sustainability (Rahal et al., 2020; Pirzada, 2019; Berbache & Hadjab, 2020). However, the impact of Algeria's colonial history and postcolonial consequences on tourists' perception of their national identity lacks investigation. The interdisciplinarity of postcolonialism and tourists' pursuits for national identity within the domestic realm carries a wider implication to discuss the perception and communication of identity, along with experiences associated with understanding the said identity with influence of digital practices on social platforms. Literature on Algerian identity is mostly sought from a sociological perspective (Scagnetti, 2003), or through postcolonial theoretical framework (Barclay et al., 2018; Brown, 2018). The lack of interdisciplinary investigation of Algerian identity and *Hybridity*, and postcolonial tourism was a driving force to address this gap and contribute to knowledge with a study that will potentially be a start to a new field that approaches and prioritises the Algerian experience with hybrid identity understanding through the act of tourism and domestic travel.

Despite the enlightening data and discussions this thesis produced, I do not consider my work as concluding research to investigating Algerian tourists' experiences and postcolonial identity. There are certain limitations that I encountered and can prompt future research in the field of postcolonial tourism. One of the limitations that this study faced was the lack of investigation on the Algerians' tourist experience and identity from a postcolonial perspective. Scholars investigating the case of Algeria either emphasise on researching the tourism sector from the perspective of top-bottom angle; that is to say, tourism literature is more focused on tourism planning and policies to advance the sector (Aouchel et al., 2022; Abada & Foura, 2019; Aouinane, 2014; Adala & Benyamina, 2013), or studying identity from a social science and postcolonial perspective, with certain emphasis on arts, language and literature (Sajed, 2023; Laroussi, 2016; Benrabah, 2004; 2014). However, the intersectionality between both disciplines lacks investigation, especially from a bottom-up perspective and an emphasis on the tourists' narrative and interpretation of identity.

Another limitation that can be further addressed in future research is the lack of clear guidelines and foreseeable goals in terms of the marketing environment among the Algerian travel agencies and tourism marketers in general. The study was driven through emphasising on digital marketing that is widely spread in the era of globalisation and ICTs, where social media and the electronic Word-of-Mouth are significantly contributing to consumers' decision-making processes and availability of different options, recommendations, and opinions. In turns, travel marketers and tourism scholars can establish guidelines to the branding segments of tourism products, and facilitate the process of categorising and demystifying the new generation to marketing. Additionally, the developments noticed in ICTs and social media platforms can present an additional and positive contribution to investigating Algerian tourists' behaviour and experiences with digital tourism content. As I previously explained in **Chapter 7**, there is still a discrepancy when it comes to trusting digital advertising as many Algerians are more interested in traditional approaches to tourism marketing. However, it is imperative to further highlight the growing interest of young tourists' digital interaction and perception of tourism products on social media. As a suggestion, further research can implement qualitative and quantitative approaches to investigating and focusing on younger generation's digital responses and practices of exploring culture and identity through tourism.

8.5. Personal Reflection

Conducting postgraduate research as an international student has been an invaluable opportunity that changed the course of my life. Throughout the five years of this PhD journey, I learnt plenty of academic and personal skills that shaped my personality and way of thinking, and contributed significantly to my personal growth as a woman from the Global South in the West. I have learnt how to be autonomous, developed my critical thinking, and understood what it takes to persevere and be ambitious to achieve my dreams and goals. Looking back and reflecting on my PhD journey made me realise how far I got as a researcher. Although this PhD journey was filled with growth and rewarding moments, it encountered several challenges along the way which made it very hard for me to tackle them and have a life-work balance.

In 2020, nine months after I started my PhD, the world was faced with a global pandemic that halted mobility and caused risky and unprecedented decisions to be taken. As an international student living alone in a Western country, I was undecided onto what to do amidst the global pandemic, and took a decision to travel back home during the first lockdown of March 2020. I spent 5 months sheltered among my family and had to work remotely on my thesis, as the rest of the world would do during these circumstances. When returning to the UK, the global pandemic has not subsidised yet and I found myself alone again, but this time I was not even able to meet friends at the library or for long walks across the streets of Paisley. This complete isolation from the outside world was of great negative impact on my mental health; I was hopeless for some sort of normality, even a glimpse of social interaction with people and fellow students. Additionally, as an international student who is multilingual, I did not have the opportunity to sharpen my English-speaking skills, or socialise with fellow international students in the halls of UWS. It also prevented me from defeating my fear of public speaking. However, this critical situation has taught me to be resilient, enjoy the company of myself through reading books as a coping mechanism, and step out of my comfort zone to build my self-esteem.

Being a female Muslim woman from the Global South living in the UK has also taught me a lot about diversity, and mobility. Drawing from personal experiences, I had the chance to learn from a culture that is completely different from mine, and grew an outmost respect to fellow international students in the UWS community. I lived with international students from

Belarus, China, France, and Germany, and learnt a lot about their cultures throughout our daily encounters in our flat, to whom I am forever grateful.

In terms of my academic development as a researcher, I must reflect with subjectivity on how my research evolved my perception of self and identity. My study was developed from an attempt to investigate and interpret domestic tourists' personal experiences while partaking in tourism practices and postcolonial identity exploration. Throughout this development, my own identity as a researcher exponentially grew, not only how to conduct this research, but also how to perceive and interpret experiences of my participants. As a researcher, it is often communicated that my role is to investigate without immersing myself so deeply with the participants or feeling the need to pause and reconsider how I can relate to them and their worldviews, despite knowing the importance of reflexivity when approaching a phenomenon.

The more I engaged in discussions with my participants and investigated the phenomena, the more I became aware of how similar to them I was. I realised that I took part in such phenomenon too, I realised that I made statements similar to theirs when thinking about my postcolonial identity and position as a tourist. These realisations came as I was nearing the end of this PhD journey as I tried so hard from the beginning to be somewhat of an outsider when investigating a phenomenon that is too familiar for me and that I needed to compartmentalise myself away from it in order to give it justice and recognition it requires, and provides the least biases that could interfere with their interpretation of the phenomenon and mine. Hence, my attempts to defamiliarise myself with the investigated phenomenon contributed to how I perceived it the way it occurred and developed in the field, and how I was communicating with the participants in a way that positioned me as a dependent on their interpretations with more trajectory to an insider positioning.

The insider/outsider positioning was prevalent from the start of this investigation as I continuously debated whether I'm being an insider or an outsider. As I progressed with the research, I wonder if I had really been an outsider all along this journey. From my understanding, the criteria of an outsider are one that does not belong to the same group as the participants, and is objective and free from any personal bias that might carry certain inaccuracies. Being a member of the Algerian society as my participants, it would be difficult to carry on an objective stand to limit personal biases and reflexivity, however, I came to the

realisation that the way I am interpreting my participants' views and experiences was interconnected with how I analyse and alter my own views on identity along this journey.

The internal dilemma of my position and reflexivity was also contributing to exploring my own identity as a researcher, as a tourist, and as an Algerian woman. The overwhelming realisation that I was also embarking upon a journey to uncover and reconstruct my postcolonial identity along the way was essential to this work. As an Algerian woman who took part in tourism practices and constantly attempting to understand her identity, it was exponentially enlightening to discuss these concerns with my participants who are also going through the same identity crisis and manifesting a newer approach to (re)construct and (re)shape it in a way that collectively makes sense to us Algerians. Taking part in tourism practices in a domestic setting is not only a leisure activity, but also an opportunity to learn about the cultural and national heritage. These practices when taken for the purpose of uncovering one's identity can be a learning experience, especially for postcolonial society's members to be aware of their position and familiar with their identity's complexity and hybridity. Having discussions with Algerian tourists about identity opened wider expectations and interpretations to how hybrid identities should be looked at especially from a tourism perspective and how such a practice can be detrimental to fully grasp the reality of the postcolonial hybrid identity found within the Algerian community. As a concluding statement, I must acknowledge the significance of this research to my personal and academic views on identity. This journey allowed me to view the complex process to demystify and compartmentalise the Algerian identity within a *Third Space* and how to express and justify the socio-cultural and historical influences that (re)constructed the perception of *Hybridity*, thus recognising the diverse reality that is operating within postcolonial societies.

REFERENCES

Abada, R.E.A. and Foura, S. (2019) 'Le tourisme en Algérie un choix ou une évidence?', *International Journal of Human Settlements*, 3(2), pp. 3–17.

Abadeer, C. and Noh, Y. (2018) 'Politics and education in post-war Algeria', *Belfer Center for Science and International Affairs*, pp. 81–85.

Abbas, F. (1931) *De la colonie vers la province: Le jeune algérien*. Aux Éditions de la Jeune Parque.

Abidin, C. (2016) 'Visibility labour: Engaging with Influencers' fashion brands and #OOTD advertorial campaigns on Instagram', *Media International Australia*, 161(1), pp. 86–100. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1329878X16665177>.

Abrams, D. and Hogg, M.A. (1988): *A Social Psychology of Intergroup Relations and Group Processes*. London: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203135457>.

Abrams, D. and Hogg, M.A. (1998) 'Prospects for Research in Group Processes and Intergroup Relations', *Group Processes & Intergroup Relations*, 1(1), pp. 7–20. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1368430298011002>.

ABTA (2016) *Holiday Habits Report 2016*. Available at: <https://www.abta.com/industry-zone/reports-and-publications/abta-holiday-habits-reports/holiday-habits-report-2016> (Accessed: 26 August 2023).

Achi, A. (2005) *Reservoir Simulation Study of Ben Kahla Field, Algeria*. University of Oklahoma.

Adala, L. and Benyamina, K. (2013) 'Reality of Tourism Sector in Algeria', 12, pp. 1–12.

Adder, F.Z. and Bagui, H. (2020) 'Promoting Students' Intercultural Communicative Competence through English Literary Texts: Students' Attitudes and Teachers' Challenges', *Arab World English Journal*, 11(2), p. 9. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3649236>.

Aguiar, M. (2011) *Tracking Modernity: India's Railway and the Culture of Mobility*. U of Minnesota Press.

Aidi, H. (2016) *Tamazight as official language in Algeria*. Available at: <https://www.aljazeera.com/opinions/2016/2/16/algerias-berbers-cautiously-optimistic-about-reforms> (Accessed: 26 June 2023).

Ait Bara, A. (2022) 'Tourisme à Chétaïbi : Des potentialités à valoriser à Sidi Akacha', *Le Provincial*.

Ait Hamou (2020) 'Violence against women in times of confinement in Algeria'. Available at: <https://mena.fes.de/blog/e/violence-against-women-in-times-of-confinement-in-algeria> (Accessed: 25 August 2023).

Ait-Chaalal, A. (2002) 'L'Algérie depuis 1962 : retour sur une histoire contrastée', *Revue internationale et stratégique*, 46(2), pp. 61–72. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3917/ris.046.0061>.

Albanesi, C. (2014) 'Focus Groups', in A.C. Michalos (ed.) *Encyclopedia of Quality of Life and Well-Being Research*. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, pp. 2310–2313. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-0753-5_1066.

von Albertini, R. (1971) 'Decolonization, the Administration and Future of the Colonies, 1919–1960.', in *American Political Science Review*. Cambridge University Press, pp. 667–669. Available at: <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/american-political-science-review/article/abs/decolonization-the-administration-and-future-of-the-colonies-19191960-by-rudolf-von-albertini-garden-city-n-y-doubleday-company-inc-1971-pp-680-1295/59D254EEFDDDB2A6DB7D60D88486837F0> (Accessed: 23 August 2023).

Alegre, J. and Garau, J. (2010) 'TOURIST SATISFACTION AND DISSATISFACTION', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 37(1), pp. 52–73. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2009.07.001>.

‘Algeria’ (2021) *United States Department of State*. Available at: <https://www.state.gov/reports/2020-report-on-international-religious-freedom/algeria/> (Accessed: 2 May 2023).

Algeria: social media with most users 2022 (2022) *Statista*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1284853/number-of-social-media-users-in-algeria-by-platform/> (Accessed: 1 April 2023).

Algérie : Brèves culturelles de juillet (2012) *AgendaCulturel*. Available at: <https://www.agendaculturel.com/article/POD-Algerie-Breves-culturelles-de-juillet> (Accessed: 10 January 2023).

AlKroud, E.A.A. (2018) *Renarrating the Berbers in Three Amazigh Translations of the Holy Quran: Paratextual and Framing Strategies*. Manchester.

Amara, F. (2018) ‘Optimisation de la largeur en crête des petits barrages et retenues collinaires’.

Amoamo, M. (2007) ‘Māori tourism: Image and identity — a postcolonial perspective’, *Annals of Leisure Research*, 10(3–4), pp. 454–474. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/11745398.2007.9686776>.

Amoamo, M. (2011) ‘Tourism and hybridity: Re-visiting Bhabha’s third space’, *Annals of Tourism Research*, 38(4), pp. 1254–1273. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2011.04.002>.

Anderson, B.R.O. (1983) *Imagined communities: reflections on the origin and spread of nationalism*. Rev. ed. London; New York: Verso.

Anderson, B.R.O. (1991) *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*. Verso.

Anderson, B.R.O. (2006) *Imagined communities: reflections on the origin and spread of nationalism*. Rev. ed. London; New York: Verso.

d'Andrade, R.G. (1995) *The development of cognitive anthropology*. Cambridge University Press.

Andrews, J. (2018) *The Question of Painting*, Bloomsbury. Available at: <https://www.bloomsbury.com/uk/question-of-painting-9781472574282/> (Accessed: 22 May 2023).

Andrews, J. (2020) 'Interviewing Images: How Visual Research Using IPA (Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis) Can Illuminate the Change-Making Possibilities of Place, Space, and Dwelling', in *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Dwelling Form (IDWELL 2020)*. Atlantis Press, pp. 20–31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.201009.003>.

Anholt, S. (2007) 'What is Competitive Identity?', in S. Anholt (ed.) *Competitive Identity: The New Brand Management for Nations, Cities and Regions*. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, pp. 1–23. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230627727_1.

Anthropologists, E.A. of S. (2004) *Reframing Pilgrimage: Cultures in Motion*. Psychology Press.

Antonius, G. (1946) *The Arab Awakening: The Story of the Arab National Movement*. G. P. Putnam's Sons.

Aouchal, H., Boufenara, K. and Verdini, G. (2022) 'Heritage Exclusivism in Postcolonial Algeria: Assessing Local Heritageness in Annaba, Towards a Holistic and Participatory Approach to Urban Heritage Management', *The Historic Environment: Policy & Practice*, 0(0), pp. 1–27. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17567505.2022.2146236>.

Aouinane, A. (2013) 'السياحة في الجزائر الإمكانيات والمعوقات (2000-2025) في ظل SDAT2025'. الإستراتيجية السياحية الجديدة للمخطط التوجيهي للتهيئة السياحية.

Appiah, K.A. (2005) *The ethics of identity*. Princeton, NJ, US: Princeton University Press (The ethics of identity), pp. xviii, 358.

APS (2022) *New thinking to attract tourists and develop internal tourism*. Available at: <https://www.aps.dz/economie/145312-une-nouvelle-reflexion-pour-attirer-les-touristes-et-developper-le-tourisme-interne> (Accessed: 27 June 2023).

Arab, T.N. (2016) *Algerian Berbers rally for Amazigh recognition*, <https://english.alaraby.co.uk/>. The New Arab. Available at: <https://english.alaraby.co.uk/news/algerian-berbers-rally-amazigh-recognition> (Accessed: 17 August 2022).

Armes, R. (1987) *Third World Film Making and the West*. University of California Press.

Ashcroft, B. and Ahluwalia, D.P.S. (2001) *Edward Said*. Psychology Press.

Ashcroft, B., Griffiths, G. and Tiffin, H. (1989) *The Empire Writes Back*. 0 edn. Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203402627>.

Ashcroft, B., Griffiths, G. and Tiffin, H. (2000) 'Post-Colonial Studies: The Key Concepts, Second Edition', p. 305.

Ashcroft, B., Griffiths, G. and Tiffin, H. (eds) (2006) *The post-colonial studies reader*. 2nd ed. London; New York: Routledge.

Ashmore, R.D., Jussim, L.J. and Wilder, D. (2001) *Social Identity, Intergroup Conflict, and Conflict Reduction*. Oxford University Press.

Ateljevic, I. and Doorne, S. (2002) 'Representing New Zealand', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 29(3), pp. 648–667. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383\(01\)00077-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383(01)00077-9).

Ateljevic, I., Morgan, N. and Pritchard, A. (eds) (2012) *The critical turn in tourism studies: creating an academy of hope*. 1. publ. London: Routledge (Advances in tourism, 22).

Ayache, S. (2022) 'Dans le sud de l'Algérie, la pandémie de Covid-19 encourage un tourisme local', *Le Monde.fr*, 1 February. Available at: https://www.lemonde.fr/afrique/article/2022/02/01/algerie-dans-le-sud-du-pays-la-pandemie-de-covid-19-encourage-un-tourisme-local_6111852_3212.html (Accessed: 27 June 2023).

Ayikoru, M. (2009) 'Chapter 4. Epistemology, Ontology and Tourism', in J. Tribe (ed.) *Philosophical Issues in Tourism. Multilingual Matters*, pp. 62–79. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781845410988-005>.

Azada-Palacios, R.A. (2022) 'Hybridity and national identity in post-colonial schools', *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 54(9), pp. 1431–1441. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2021.1920393>.

Aziz, M.A. (2009) 'The Origins of Arab Nationalism'.

Azizi, N. and Bouacha, M. (2019) 'Analytical Study of Digital Marketing Applications in Algerian Hotels: A Case Study of 13 Hotels in Constantine Province', 6, pp. 47–61.

Azra, A. (2016) *Transformasi Politik Islam: Radikalisme, Khilafatisme, dan Demokrasi*. Kencana.

Babbie, E., Halley, F. and Zaino, J. (2007) *Adventures in Social Research: Data Analysis Using SPSS 14.0 and 15.0 for Windows*. Pine Forge Press.

Bailey, S. (2011) *professional practice reports*. Birmingham.

Baker, C., Wuest, J. and Stern, P.N. (1992) 'Method slurring: the grounded theory/phenomenology example', *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 17(11), pp. 1355–1360. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.1992.tb01859.x>.

Barbara, H. and Molnár, T. (2019) 'Towards understanding the colonial heritage in Algeria: The case of the Sheridan Villa', *Pollack Periodica*, 14(1), pp. 223–234. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1556/606.2019.14.1.22>.

Barclay, F., Chopin, C.A. and Evans, M. (2018) 'Introduction: settler colonialism and French Algeria', *Settler Colonial Studies*, 8(2), pp. 115–130. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/2201473X.2016.1273862>.

Barker, C. and Murray, S. (2010) 'Disabling Postcolonialism: Global Disability Cultures and Democratic Criticism', *Journal of Literary & Cultural Disability Studies*, 4(3), pp. 219–236.

Barnes, S., Mattsson, J. and Sørensen, F. (2014) 'Destination brand experience and visitor behavior: Testing a scale in the tourism context', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 48, pp. 121–139. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2014.06.002>.

Barthes, R. (1973) *Mythologies*. Granada.

Barthes, R. (1977) *Image-Music-Text*. Farrar, Straus and Giroux.

Beghoura, H. (no date) *Racontez-moi l'Algérie : 20 œuvres, 20 auteurs algériens*. Available at: <https://lepetitjournal.com/alger/racontez-moi-lalgerie-20-oeuvres-20-auteurs-algeriens-298252> (Accessed: 30 September 2022).

Beguïn, F. (1983) *Arabesances: Décor architectural et tracé urbain en Afrique du Nord, 1830-1930*. Paris: Bordas Dunod (Espace et architecture).

Béguin, F. *et al.* (1983) 'Arabesances : décor architectural et tracé urbain en Afrique du Nord, 1830-1950', in. Available at: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:160204739>.

Belakehal, A. *et al.* (2015) 'A MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE FRENCH COLONIAL ARCHITECTURE IN ALGERIA: THE FACADES OF BISKRA'. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/27891453/A_MORPHOLOGICAL_ANALYSIS_OF_THE_FRENCH_COLONIAL_ARCHITECTURE_IN_ALGERIA_THE_FACADES_OF_BISKRA (Accessed: 27 June 2023).

Belfarhi, K. (2019) 'English Adjectives in Online Comments of Algerian English Speakers', *Arab World English Journal*, 10(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3367578>.

Bell, P. (2023) 'The Handbook of Visual Analysis', in pages 10-34. London: SAGE Publications Ltd. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9780857020062>.

Benaïssa, F.T. *et al.* (2022) 'Desert tourism between the need for development and response to demand The case of the city of Béni Abbés - Algeria', *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 38, pp. 903–917. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v38i1.8358>.

Benchabib, M. (2022) *The strategy of developing the domestic tourism sector in Algeria in light of the Corona pandemic*. Available at: <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/114995/> (Accessed: 26 August 2023).

Benghadbane, F. and Khreis, S. (2019) 'The Role of Tourism Marketing in Enhancing Tourism Development: A Comparative Study between Constantine and Amman Cities', pp. 146–160.

Benrabah, M. (1999) *Langue et pouvoir en Algérie: histoire d'un traumatisme linguistique*. Paris: Séguier (Les colonnes d'Hercule).

Benrabah, M. (2004) 'Language and Politics in Algeria', *Nationalism and Ethnic Politics*, 10(1), pp. 59–78. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13537110490450773>.

Benrabah, M. (2013) *Language conflict in Algeria: from colonialism to post-independence*. Bristol: MULTILINGUAL MATTERS (Multilingual matters, 154).

Benrabah, M. (2014) 'Competition between four "world" languages in Algeria', *Journal of World Languages*, 1(1), pp. 38–59. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/21698252.2014.893676>.

BenTalbi, F., Jari, F. and Chellal, Z. (2018) 'Algeria's tourism sector: reality and challenges'.

Berbache, H. and Hadjab, M. (2020) 'OASIAN CITIES: A TOURIST HERITAGE THREATENED BY THE INVASION OF URBAN EXPANSION, CASE OF THE OASIS OF BOUSSAADA, ALGERIA', *GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 31(3), pp. 1119–1125. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.30892/gtg.31325-548>.

Berdún, M.M.G. (1996) *Nationalisms: The Nation-state and Nationalism in the Twentieth Century*. Polity Press.

Berdún, M.M.G. (2007) *The identity of nations*. Cambridge: Polity. Available at: <http://bvbr.bib-bvb.de:8991/F?func=service&doc library=BVB01&local base=BVB01&doc number=0164>

29156&line number=0001&func code=DB RECORDS&service type=MEDIA (Accessed: 24 August 2023).

Berdychevsky, L. (2016) 'Antecedents of Young Women's Sexual Risk Taking in Tourist Experiences', *The Journal of Sex Research*, 53(8), pp. 927–941. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224499.2015.1069783>.

Berg, B.L. (2009) *Qualitative Research Methods for the Social Sciences*. Allyn & Bacon.

Berger, M.T. (2003) 'Decolonisation, Modernisation and Nation-Building: Political Development Theory and the Appeal of Communism in Southeast Asia, 1945–1975', *Journal of Southeast Asian Studies*, 34(3), pp. 421–448. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022463403000419>.

Berque, J. (1956) 'L'ALGÉRIE OU LES FAUX DILEMMES', *Politique étrangère*, 21(6), pp. 703–710.

Betts, R. (1998) *Decolonization*. London: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203980859>.

Betts, R.F. (2004) *Decolonization*. 2nd ed. New York: Routledge (The making of the contemporary world).

Bhabha, H.K. (1983) 'The Other Question...', *Screen*, 24(6), pp. 18–36. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/screen/24.6.18>.

Bhabha, H.K. (1994) *The location of culture*. London; New York: Routledge (Routledge classics).

Bhabha, H.K. (2012) *The Location of Culture*. 2nd edn. Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203820551>.

Bhabha, J. (1993) 'Legal problems of women refugees', *Women: a cultural review*, 4(3), pp. 240–249. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09574049308578166>.

Bhambra, G.K. (2014) 'Postcolonial and decolonial dialogues', *Postcolonial Studies*, 17(2), pp. 115–121. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13688790.2014.966414>.

Bhandari, K. (2017) 'Understanding Nepali Nationalism', *Studies in Ethnicity and Nationalism*, 16(3), pp. 416–436. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/sena.12208>.

Bienvenue en Algérie coloniale! (no date). Available at: <https://www.lhistoire.fr/bienvenue-en-algerie-coloniale> (Accessed: 30 August 2022).

Bissell, D. (2010) 'Passenger Mobilities: Affective Atmospheres and the Sociality of Public Transport', *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space*, 28(2), pp. 270–289. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1068/d3909>.

Bitsch, V. (2005) 'Qualitative Research: A Grounded Theory Example and Evaluation Criteria'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.22004/AG.ECON.59612>.

Blackwell, C. (1997) 'Tourism and Cultural Tourism: Some Basic Facts', *Preservation Issues*, 7(3).

Blench, R. (2021) 'Reconstructing the history of Berber music', *Approches pour l'histoire de la langue berbère : Mise en perspective d'une langue à travers les âges* [Preprint]. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/61777326/Reconstructing_the_history_of_Berber_music (Accessed: 2 May 2023).

Block, D. (2006) *Multilingual Identities in a Global City*. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230501393>.

Block, D. (2007) 'The Rise of Identity in SLA Research, Post Firth and Wagner (1997)', *The Modern Language Journal*, 91, pp. 863–876. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.2007.00674.x>.

Board, I.T. (1988) *Inventory of Cultural Tourism Resources in the Member States and Assessment of Methods Used to Promote Them*. Commission of the European Communities.

Boehmer, E. (2005) *Stories of Women: Gender and Narrative in the Postcolonial Nation*. Manchester University Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt155j4ws>.

Bossut, C.A. (2016) *Arabization in Algeria: language ideology in elite discourse, 1962-1991*. Thesis. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15781/T2X05XH9K>.

Botta, M. (2021) 'Deconstructing and Reconstructing Identity: A Transformational Transcontinental Journey', in A.K. Giri (ed.) *Cross-Fertilizing Roots and Routes*. Singapore: Palgrave Macmillan, pp. 95–107. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-7118-3_8.

Bouadam, D.K. (2011) 'The national strategy of tourism development in Algeria: issues, opportunities, and limitations', (2), pp. 23–37.

Boudraa, N. and Krause, J. (eds) (2007) *North African mosaic: a cultural reappraisal of ethnic and religious minorities*. Newcastle, UK: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.

Boufelih, T. (2010) *A comparative study of the reality of the tourism sector in North African countries*. Faculty of Economics, Bouira University.

Boukhris, L. and Peyvel, E. (2019) 'Tourism in the context of postcolonial and decolonial paradigms', *Via. Tourism Review* [Preprint]. Translated by M. Giroux-Aubin and N. Graburn, (16). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4000/viatourism.4119>.

Boulhila, S. *et al.* (2022) 'Towards a development model of local cultural tourism through the involvement of local actors (Province of Constantine, Algeria)', *Geojournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 40(1), pp. 9–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.30892/gtg.40101-797>.

Bowen, H.E., Daniels, M.J. and Ingram, L. (2006) 'Hybrid Analysis in Tourism Research', *Tourism Recreation Research*, 31(2), pp. 59–66. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2006.11081262>.

Bowen, J.T. (1998) 'Market segmentation in hospitality research: no longer a sequential process', *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 10(7), pp. 289–296. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596119810240924>.

Boyd, D.M. and Ellison, N.B. (2007) 'Social network sites: Definition, history, and scholarship', *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13(1), pp. 210–230. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2007.00393.x>.

Bradley, H. (2015) *Fractured Identities: Changing Patterns of Inequality*. John Wiley & Sons.

Bradshaw, A. (1997) 'Restoration of mined lands—using natural processes', *Ecological Engineering*, 8(4), pp. 255–269. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-8574\(97\)00022-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-8574(97)00022-0).

Braginsky, V.I. (1997) 'Rediscovering the "Oriental" in the Orient and Europe: new books on the East-West cultural interface: a review article', *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies*, 60, pp. 511–532.

Branchik, B.J. and Chowdhury, T.G. (2017) 'Men Seeing Stars: Celebrity Endorsers, Race, and The Male Consumer', *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*, 25(3), pp. 305–322. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10696679.2017.1311216>.

Brand, C.P. (2011) *Italy and the English Romantics: The Italianate Fashion in Early Nineteenth-Century England*. Cambridge University Press.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) 'Using thematic analysis in psychology', *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77–101. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2012) 'Thematic analysis.', in H. Cooper et al. (eds) *APA handbook of research methods in psychology, Vol 2: Research designs: Quantitative, qualitative, neuropsychological, and biological*. Washington: American Psychological Association, pp. 57–71. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/13620-004>.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2013) *Successful qualitative research: a practical guide for beginners*. First published. Los Angeles London New Delhi: SAGE.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2021a) 'Can I use TA? Should I use TA? Should I *not* use TA? Comparing reflexive thematic analysis and other pattern-based qualitative analytic

approaches’, *Counselling and Psychotherapy Research*, 21(1), pp. 37–47. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/capr.12360>.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2021b) ‘One size fits all? What counts as quality practice in (reflexive) thematic analysis?’, *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 18(3), pp. 328–352. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14780887.2020.1769238>.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2021c) ‘To saturate or not to saturate? Questioning data saturation as a useful concept for thematic analysis and sample-size rationales’, *Qualitative Research in Sport, Exercise and Health*, 13(2), pp. 201–216. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/2159676X.2019.1704846>.

Bravi, M. and Gasca, E. (2014) ‘Preferences Evaluation With a Choice Experiment on Cultural Heritage Tourism’, *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 23(4), pp. 406–423. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19368623.2013.822339>.

Brett, M. (1997) *The Berbers*. 1. publ. in paperback. (The peoples of Africa).

Brett, M. and Fentress, E. (1996) *The Berbers: Michael Brett and Elizabeth Fentress*. Blackwell.

Brocki, J.M. and Wearden, A.J. (2006) ‘A critical evaluation of the use of interpretative phenomenological analysis (IPA) in health psychology’, *Psychology & Health*, 21(1), pp. 87–108. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14768320500230185>.

Brown, G. (1992) ‘Tourism and symbolic consumption.’, *Tourism and symbolic consumption.*, pp. 57–71.

Brown, H. (2018) *French Colonialism in Algeria: War, Legacy, and Memory*.

Bryman, A. (2012) *Social research methods*. 4th ed. Oxford; New York: Oxford University Press.

Bucholtz, M. (2003) ‘Sociolinguistic nostalgia and the authentication of identity’, *Journal of Sociolinguistics*, 7(3), pp. 398–416. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9481.00232>.

Bunten, A.C. and Graburn, N.H.H. (2018) *Indigenous Tourism Movements*. University of Toronto Press.

Burney, S. (2012) 'CHAPTER ONE: Orientalism: The Making of the Other', *Counterpoints*, 417, pp. 23–39.

Burns, P. and Novelli, M. (2006) 'Tourism and social identities: global frameworks and local realities', in. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Tourism-and-social-identities-%3A-global-frameworks-Burns-Novelli/795ef15345973835fb60715f2f9594a31ecb0479> (Accessed: 27 May 2023).

Burton, R. (1995) 'Tourism and the environment.', *Travel geography.*, (Ed. 2), pp. 5–146.

Bustard, J.R.T. *et al.* (2019) 'The emerging smart event experience: an interpretative phenomenological analysis', *Tourism Review*, 74(1), pp. 116–128. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/TR-10-2017-0156>.

Butler, R. and Hinch, T. (2007) *Tourism and indigenous peoples: Issues and implications*. Routledge.

Butowski, L. *et al.* (2021) 'Social constructionism as a tool to maintain an advantage in tourism research', *Tourism Geographies*, 23(1–2), pp. 53–74. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616688.2019.1654537>.

Buzard, J. (2002) 'The Grand Tour and after (1660-1840)', in P. Hulme and T. Youngs (eds) *The Cambridge Companion to Travel Writing*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press (Cambridge Companions to Literature), pp. 37–52. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CCOL052178140X.003>.

Byrne, J.J. (2009) 'Our Own Special Brand of Socialism: Algeria and $\frac{1}{2}$ the Contest of Modernities in the 1960s', *Diplomatic History*, 33(3), pp. 427–447. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-7709.2009.00779.x>.

Bywater, M. (1993) 'The Market for Cultural Tourism in Europe'.

Calmein, M. (1975) *L'ALGERIANISTE, N° SPECIAL 1975, BULLETIN D'IDE... - COLLECTIF - Cercle Algérieniste*. Available at: <https://www.leslibraires.fr/livre/3181550-1-algerianiste-n-special-1975-bulletin-d-ide--collectif-cercle-algerianiste> (Accessed: 23 May 2023).

Camilleri, M.A. (2017) 'Market Segmentation, Targeting and Positioning', p. 17.

Campbell, A. and Coulson, D. (2010) 'Big Hippo Site, Oued Afar, Algeria', (21), pp. 81–92.

Canavan, B. (2016) 'Tourism culture: Nexus, characteristics, context and sustainability', *Tourism Management*, 53, pp. 229–243. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2015.10.002>.

Canavan, B. and McCamley, C. (2021) 'Negotiating authenticity: Three modernities', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 88, p. 103185. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2021.103185>.

Caprara, G.V., Barbaranelli, C. and Guido, G. (2001) 'Brand personality: How to make the metaphor fit?', *Journal of Economic Psychology*, 22(3), pp. 377–395. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-4870\(01\)00039-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-4870(01)00039-3).

Carcary, M. (2021) 'The Research Audit Trail: Methodological Guidance for Application in Practice', *Electronic Journal of Business Research Methods*, 18(2). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.34190/JBRM.18.2.008>.

Carfora, A., Pansini, R.V. and Scandurra, G. (2021) 'The role of environmental taxes and public policies in supporting RES investments in EU countries: Barriers and mimicking effects', *Energy Policy*, 149, p. 112044. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2020.112044>.

Carrigan, A. (2010) *Postcolonial Tourism: Literature, Culture, and Environment*. New York: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203832097>.

Čerović, S., Vukadinović, P. and Knežević, M. (2015) 'THE INFLUENCE OF GLOBALIZATION ON TOURISM AND IMPACT OF TOURISM ON OTHER

ACTIVITIES WITH AN EMPHASIS ON GREENFIELD INVESTMENTS IN TOURISM’, in *Proceedings of the Singidunum International Tourism Conference - Sitcon 2015*. Sitcon 2015, Belgrade, Serbia: Singidunum University, pp. 47–52. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.15308/sitcon-2015-47-52>.

Chafik, M. (2005) *A Brief Survey of Thirty-three Centuries of Amazigh History*. El Maarif Al-Jadida.

Chakraborty, A.R. (2016) *Liminality in post-colonial theory: A journey from Arnold van Gennep to Homi K. Bhabha*. Available at: http://scholar.googleusercontent.com/scholar?q=cache:EBYAr3VqiUoJ:scholar.google.com/+postcolonial+studies+focus+on+hybrid+identity&hl=en&as_sdt=0,5&as_vis=1 (Accessed: 12 July 2023).

Chalabi, A. and Lazri, Y. (2021) ‘Image and Signification of the Neo-Moorish Architecture in Algeria Case Study: The Big Post Office in Algiers’, *Civil Engineering and Architecture*. Edited by G. Taylor, 9, pp. 1246–1256. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.13189/cea.2021.090426>.

Chambers, D. (2007) ‘An Agenda for Cutting-Edge Research in Tourism’, in *Developments in Tourism Research*. Routledge.

Chambers, D. and Buzinde, C. (2015) ‘Tourism and decolonisation: Locating research and self’, *Annals of Tourism Research*, 51, pp. 1–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2014.12.002>.

Chan, B. (2006) ‘Virtual Communities and Chinese National Identity’, *Journal of Chinese Overseas*, 2(1), pp. 1–32. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1163/179325406788639093>.

Chaney, E. (2013) *The Evolution of the Grand Tour: Anglo-Italian Cultural Relations since the Renaissance*. London: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315870762>.

Charai, Z. (2014) *Les effets du tourisme sur l’identité culturelle : le cas de la médina de Fès*. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/reader/52778010> (Accessed: 19 July 2023).

Chatzigeorgiou, C. (2017) 'Modelling The Impact Of Social Media Influencers On Behavioural Intentions Of Millennials: The Case Of Tourism In Rural Areas In Greece'. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.1209125>.

Cherfaoui, A. (2015) *Tourism in Algeria; between National Economy Demands and International Economic Variables*. Algiers 3 University. Available at: <https://www.univ-bouira.dz/ar/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/%D8%AF%D9%83%D8%AA%D9%88%D8%B1%D8%A7%D9%87-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3%D9%8A%D8%A7%D8%AD%D8%A9-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AC%D8%B2%D8%A7%D8%A6%D8%B1%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D8%A8%D9%8A%D9%86-%D9%85%D8%AA%D8%B7%D9%84%D8%A8%D8%A7%D8%AA-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A7%D9%82%D8%AA%D8%B5%D8%A7%D8%AF-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%88%D8%B7%D9%86%D9%8A-%D9%88%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85%D8%AA%D8%BA%D9%8A%D8%B1%D8%A7%D8%AA-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A7%D9%82%D8%AA%D8%B5%D8%A7%D8%AF%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AF%D9%88%D9%84%D9%8A%D8%A9-%D8%B4%D8%B1%D9%81%D8%A7%D9%88%D9%8A-%D8%B9%D8%A7%D8%A6%D8%B4%D8%A9.pdf> (Accessed: 25 September 2022).

Cherki, A. (2016) *Frantz Fanon*. Nantes, France: POINTS. Available at: <https://www.abebooks.co.uk/book-search/title/frantz-fanon/author/cherki-alice/> (Accessed: 27 August 2023).

Chirot, D. (2008) 'Book Review: Kiernan, B. (2007). *Blood and Soil: A World History of Genocide and Extermination from Sparta to Darfur*. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press', *Comparative Political Studies*, 41(10), pp. 1432–1435. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0010414008315866>.

Clark-Ibáñez, M. (2004) *Framing the Social World With Photo-Elicitation Interviews*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764204266236>.

Clawson, M. and Knetsch, J.L. (1966) *Economics of Outdoor Recreation*. Resources for the Future.

Clifford, J. (1988) *The Predicament of Culture: Twentieth-Century Ethnography, Literature, and Art*. Harvard University Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctvjf9x0h>.

Cobo, J.M. (1986) *indigenous peoples* | *UNEP Law and Environment Assistance Platform*. Available at: <https://leap.unep.org/knowledge/glossary/indigenous-peoples> (Accessed: 15 August 2023).

Cohen, E. (1972) 'TOWARD A SOCIOLOGY OF INTERNATIONAL TOURISM', *Social Research*, 39(1), pp. 164–182.

Cohen, E. (1979) 'A Phenomenology of Tourist Experiences', *Sociology*, 13(2), pp. 179–201. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/003803857901300203>.

Cohen, E. (1984) 'The Sociology of Tourism: Approaches, Issues, and Findings', *Annual Review of Sociology*, 10(1), pp. 373–392. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.so.10.080184.002105>.

Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2007) *Research methods in education*. 6th ed. London; New York: Routledge.

Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2011) *Research Methods in Education*. 7th edn. London: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203720967>.

Cohen, L., Manion, L. and Morrison, K. (2017) *Research Methods in Education*. 8th edn. Eighth edition. | New York: Routledge, 2018.: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315456539>.

Coleman, S. and Crang, M. (eds) (2002) *Tourism: between place and performance*. New York: Berghahn Books.

Coles, T. and Hall, M. (2006) 'Editorial: The Geography of Tourism is Dead. Long Live Geographies of Tourism and Mobility', *Current Issues in Tourism*, 9(4–5), pp. 289–292. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500608668250>.

Colletta, L. (2015) *The Legacy of the Grand Tour: New Essays on Travel, Literature, and Culture*. Rowman & Littlefield.

Collier, J. and Collier, M. (1986) *Visual Anthropology* - Google Books. Available at: https://www.google.co.uk/books/edition/Visual_Anthropology/fDn8CrH8gRoC?hl=en&gbpv=1&dq=collier+%26+collier+1986&pg=PR11&printsec=frontcover (Accessed: 22 May 2023).

Collot, C. and Henry, J.R. (1978) 'Le mouvement national algérien: textes, 1912-1954', in.

'Common-Sense and Scientific Interpretation of Human Action' (1962) in Schutz, A., *Collected Papers I*. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands (Phaenomenologica), pp. 3–47. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-010-2851-6_1.

Connelly, L.M. (2016) 'Trustworthiness in Qualitative Research', *Medsurg Nursing: Official Journal of the Academy of Medical-Surgical Nurses*, 25(6), pp. 435–436.

Connor, W. (1994) *Ethnonationalism: The Quest for Understanding*. Princeton University Press. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv39x5s6> (Accessed: 24 August 2023).

Cooper, C. *et al.* (1993) *Tourism: principles and practice*. London: Pitman Publ.

Cooper, F. (1989) 'Decolonization in Africa', *The International Journal of African Historical Studies*, 22(4), p. 715. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/219062>.

Cooper, F. (2019) *Africa since 1940: The Past of the Present*. Cambridge University Press.

Cornwell, G.H. and Atia, M. (2012) 'Imaginative geographies of Amazigh activism in Morocco', *Social & Cultural Geography*, 13(3), pp. 255–274. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14649365.2012.677471>.

Correia, A., Kozak, M. and Ferradeira, J. (2013) 'From tourist motivations to tourist satisfaction', *International Journal of Culture, Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 7(4), pp. 411–424. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCTHR-05-2012-0022>.

Coslett, D.E. (2020) 'Preservation and tourism in Tunisia: on the colonial past in the neocolonial present', *The Journal of North African Studies*, 25(5), pp. 727–752. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13629387.2019.1644900>.

Creswell, J.W. (2013) *Qualitative inquiry and research design: choosing among five approaches*. 3rd ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications.

Creswell, J.W. and Creswell, J.D. (2018) *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Fifth edition. Los Angeles London New Delhi Singapore Washington DC Melbourne: SAGE.

Croisy, S. (2008) 'Algerian History, Algerian Literature, and Critical Theories: An Interdisciplinary Perspective on Linguistic Trauma and Identity Reformation in Postcolonial Algeria', *Interdisciplinary Literary Studies*, 10(1), pp. 84–106.

Crompton, J.L. and Love, L.L. (1995) 'The Predictive Validity of Alternative Approaches to Evaluating Quality of a Festival', *Journal of Travel Research*, 34(1), pp. 11–24. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/004728759503400102>.

Crossan, F. (2003) 'Research philosophy: towards an understanding', *Nurse Researcher*, 11(1), pp. 46–55. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7748/nr2003.10.11.1.46.c5914>.

Crotty, M.J. (1998) 'The Foundations of Social Research: Meaning and Perspective in the Research Process', pp. 1–256.

Crouch, D. (2008) 'Surrounded by Place: Embodied Encounters', in *Tourism: Between Place and Performance*. 1st edn. Berghahn Books, pp. 207–218.

Crous-Costa, N. (2022) 'Self-Otherness in Tourism. A Semiotic Analysis of China Travel Posters', *Rhetoric and Communications*, (51), pp. 20–43. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.55206/GCKV8809>.

Csapo, J. (2012) 'The Role and Importance of Cultural Tourism in Modern Tourism Industry', in M. Kasimoglu (ed.) *Strategies for Tourism Industry - Micro and Macro Perspectives*. InTech. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5772/38693>.

Cutler, S.Q. and Carmichael, B.A. (2010) 'Chapter 1. The Dimensions of the Tourist Experience', in M. Morgan, P. Lugosi, and J.R.B. Ritchie (eds) *The Tourism and Leisure Experience. Multilingual Matters*, pp. 3–26. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781845411503-004>.

DaCosta, P.K. (2018) *CULTURAL IDENTITY AND HYBRIDITY IN "DIFFERENT SPACES": RECENT IMMIGRANT STUDENTS NEGOTIATING SETTLEMENT AND UNIVERSITY IN ONTARIO, CANADA*. University of Toronto. Available at: [https://tspace.library.utoronto.ca/bitstream/1807/91819/1/DaCosta Paula 201811 PhD thesis.pdf](https://tspace.library.utoronto.ca/bitstream/1807/91819/1/DaCosta%20Paula%20201811%20PhD%20thesis.pdf).

Dammak, A. (2015) 'RESEARCH PARADIGMS: METHODOLOGIES AND COMPATIBLE METHODS', in. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/RESEARCH-PARADIGMS-%3A-METHODOLOGIES-AND-COMPATIBLE-Dammak/2336000d567aa0e4fbd31d06020fc5b9e3bc7c01> (Accessed: 25 August 2023).

De Veirman, M., Cauberghe, V. and Hudders, L. (2017) 'Marketing through Instagram influencers: the impact of number of followers and product divergence on brand attitude', *International Journal of Advertising*, 36(5), pp. 798–828. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02650487.2017.1348035>.

Deci, E.L. and Ryan, R.M. (2000) 'The "What" and "Why" of Goal Pursuits: Human Needs and the Self-Determination of Behavior', *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), pp. 227–268. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01.

'DECRA' (no date). Available at: <https://www.transromanica.com/explore-transromanica/coop-projects/decra/> (Accessed: 29 August 2023).

Deluz, J.J. (1988) *L'urbanisme et l'architecture d'Alger: aperçu critique*. P. Mardaga.

Demirovic, D. *et al.* (2019) 'Exploration of tourist motivation and preferred activities in rural areas', *Journal of the Geographical Institute Jovan Cvijic, SASA*, 69(1), pp. 29–37. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2298/IJGI1901029D>.

Denzin, N.K. (1998) 'The landscape of qualitative research: Theories and issue', *Sage Publications* [Preprint].

Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (2000) 'The Discipline and Practice of Qualitative Research', *Handbook of Qualitative Research* [Preprint].

Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (2003) *Turning Points in Qualitative Research: Tying Knots in a Handkerchief*. Rowman Altamira.

Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (eds) (2018) *The SAGE handbook of qualitative research*. Fifth edition. Los Angeles London New Delhi Singapore Washington DC Melbourne: SAGE.

Dib, M. (1952) *La Grande Maison*.

Dib, M. (1954) *L'Incendie*.

Dib, M. (1957) *Le métier à tisser*.

Dickerson, V.C. and Zimmerman, J.L. (1996) 'Myths, Misconceptions, and a Word or Two About Politics', *Journal of Systemic Therapies*, 15(1), pp. 79–88. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1521/jsyt.1996.15.1.79>.

Dirlik, A. (1997) *The postcolonial aura: Third World criticism in the age of global capitalism*. Nachdr. Boulder, Colo.: Westview Press.

Dizayi, S.A. (2019) 'Locating Identity Crisis in Postcolonial Theory: Fanon And Said', *Journal of Advanced Research in Social Sciences*, 2(1), pp. 79–86. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.33422/JARSS.2019.05.06>.

Dizayi, S.A.H. (2015) 'THE CRISIS OF IDENTITY IN POSTCOLONIAL NOVEL', in, pp. 999–1007. Available at: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:33109617>.

Djerbi, A. and Safi, A. (2003) 'Teaching the History of Architecture in Algeria, Tunisia, and Morocco: Colonialism, Independence, and Globalization', *Journal of the Society of Architectural Historians*, 62(1), pp. 102–109. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/3655087>.

Dodman, T. (2018) 'De l'utopie à la nostalgie en Algérie française', *Conserveries mémorielles. Revue transdisciplinaire* [Preprint], (#22). Available at: <https://journals.openedition.org/cm/2885> (Accessed: 30 August 2022).

Donze, M.G. (2017) (PDF) *Edward Saïd: Orientalism*. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313360730_Edward_Saïd_Orientalism?_sg%5B0%5D=2O8sh0a-51aMaf_wKFvU2Egb1tPZ44yYVxNxqgIsBs7sVZj5WgZpKbLpyHgO3C2dGRCIRLjEmnmKZP_0Ty4ap-vfUvMTUE9mXnzd85c3.fWgwZQ1tMutL_W3Psx1trAd0hLrmbcM03meUi4tdhbXWVzF4gSQGc9HjJUw5rZp9e6ZQZTiGYAijHW5T3d7fAA&_tp=eyJjb250ZXh0Ijp7ImZpcnN0UGFnZSI6InByb2ZpbGUlLCJwYWdlIjoicHJvZmlsZSI6InByZXZpb3VzUGFnZSI6InByb2ZpbGUlfiX0 (Accessed: 22 August 2023).

Drideche, H. (2017) 'Importance of Social Sciences in Understanding and Building the Society', *Journal of Horizons of Sociology*, (13), pp. 190–198.

Drideche, Y. (2017) *Activating Tourism for Local Sustainability, the case of Msila, Algeria*. Msila University.

Dubé-Rioux, L., Schmitt, B.H. and Leclerc, F. (1989) 'Consumers' Reactions to Waiting: When Delays Affect the Perception of Service Quality', *Advances in Consumer Research*, 16(1), p. 59.

Duval, D.T. (2004) *Trends and circumstances in Caribbean tourism, Tourism in the Caribbean*. Routledge, pp. 19–38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203402696-6>.

Eagly, A.H. and Chaiken, S. (1993) *The psychology of attitudes*. Orlando, FL, US: Harcourt Brace Jovanovich College Publishers (The psychology of attitudes), pp. xxii, 794.

Ebejer, J. (2015) *TOURIST EXPERIENCES OF URBAN HISTORIC AREAS*.

Echtner, C.M. and Prasad, P. (2003) ‘The context of third world tourism marketing’, *Annals of Tourism Research*, 30(3), pp. 660–682. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383\(03\)00045-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383(03)00045-8).

Edensor, T. (1998) *Tourists at the Taj: Performance and Meaning at a Symbolic Site*. Psychology Press.

Edmunds, J. and Turner, B.S. (2005) ‘Global generations: social change in the twentieth century’, *The British Journal of Sociology*, 56(4), pp. 559–577.

Eisenhardt, K.M. (1989) ‘Building Theories from Case Study Research’, *The Academy of Management Review*, 14(4), p. 532. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/258557>.

El Azzaoui, I., Carnicelli, S. and Khodadadi, M. (2022) ‘Tourism Development in Algeria and the Horizon 2025 Plan’, *Tourism Cases*, 2022, p. tourism20220001. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1079/tourism.2022.0001>.

Ellis, T.J. and Levy, Y. (2009) ‘Towards a Guide for Novice Researchers on Research Methodology: Review and Proposed Methods’, 6.

Elmarsafy, Z., Bernard, A. and Attwell, D. (eds) (2013) *Debating Orientalism*. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137341112>.

Elo, S. *et al.* (2014) ‘Qualitative Content Analysis: A Focus on Trustworthiness’, *SAGE Open*, 4(1), p. 215824401452263. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244014522633>.

Enloe, C. *et al.* (2018) 'Our Fighting Sisters: nation, memory and gender in Algeria, 1954–2012', *Women's History Review*, 27(1), pp. 120–129. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09612025.2017.1384129>.

Ennaji, M. (2005) *Multilingualism, Cultural Identity, and Education in Morocco*. New York: Springer-Verlag. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/b104063>.

Ennaji, M. (ed.) (2014) *Multiculturalism and democracy in North Africa: aftermath of the Arab spring*. New York: Routledge (Routledge studies in middle eastern politics).

Euromonitor International (2020) *Passport: Travel in Algeria*.

Falk, J.H. (2011) 'Contextualizing Falk's Identity-Related Visitor Motivation Model', *Visitor Studies*, 14(2), pp. 141–157. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10645578.2011.608002>.

Fanon, F. (1952) *Black skin, white masks*. Repr. London: Pluto Press (Pluto classics).

Fanon, F. (1959) *A dying colonialism*. Nachdr. New York, NY: Grove Press.

Fanon, F. (1961) *Les damnés de la terre*. Available at: <https://www.edition-originale.com/fr/litterature/editions-originales/fanon-les-damnes-de-la-terre-1961-56095> (Accessed: 22 August 2023).

Fanon, F. (1963) *The wretched of the earth*. New York: Grove Press.

Fanon, F. (1966) *The wretched of the earth*. Translated by Constance Farrington. New York: Grove Press.

Farmer, H.G. (1978) *Historical Facts for the Arabian Musical Influence*. Arno Press.

Favret, J. (1972) *Traditionalism through Ultra-Modernism in Arabs and Berbers: From Tribe to Nation in North Africa*. Ernest Gellner and Charles Micaud. Washington: Lexington Books.

Fechit, H. and Hedibi, S. (2020) 'Tourism and sustainable development in Algeria - an analytical study.', *Management and Development Journal for Research and Studies*, 9(2), pp. 202–221.

Fenwick, C. (2008) 'Archaeology and the Search for Authenticity: Colonialist, Nationalist, and Berberist Visions of an Algerian Past', *Theoretical Roman Archaeology Journal*, 0(2007), p. 75. Available at: https://doi.org/10.16995/TRAC2007_75_88.

Ferguson, G. (2003) 'Classroom code-switching in post-colonial contexts: Functions, attitudes, and policies', *AILA Review*, 16, pp. 38–51. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1075/aila.16.05fer>.

Fernandes, C. (2013) 'The impact of cultural tourism on host communities.', *Cultural tourism*, pp. 26–38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1079/9781845939236.0026>.

Fill, C. (2009) *Marketing Communications: Interactivity, Communities and Content*. Pearson Education.

Fladmark, J.M. (1998) *n search of heritage: as pilgrim or tourist?*

Florence, P.S. (1934) 'The Tourist Movement: An Economic Study. by F. W. Ogilvie', *The Economic Journal*, 44(175), pp. 475–477. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2225409>.

Fluehr-Lobban, C. (2003) *Ethics and the Profession of Anthropology: Dialogue for Ethically Conscious Practice*. Rowman Altamira.

Fois, M. (2017) 'Algerian Nationalism: From the Origins to Algerian War of Independence', *Oriente Moderno*, 97(1), pp. 89–110.

Folkestad, H. (2000) 'Getting the picture: Photo-assisted conversations as interviews', *Scandinavian Journal of Disability Research*, 2(2), pp. 3–21. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15017410009510757>.

Ford, B. (1981) 'The Grand Tour', *Apollo: The international magazine of arts*, (238 (December 1981)), pp. 390–400.

Forrester, M. (ed.) (2010) *Doing qualitative research in psychology: a practical guide*. Repr. Los Angeles: Sage.

Forstag, B. (2009) 'Berber Identity and the Crisis of Algerian Nationalism', in.

Fougère, M. and Moulettes, A. (2012) 'Disclaimers, dichotomies and disappearances in international business textbooks: A postcolonial deconstruction', *Management Learning*, 43(1), pp. 5–24. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1350507611407139>.

Foura-Bouchair, Y. and Foura, M. (2011) 'La patrimonialisation des tissus néomauresque et art déco à-foura', *calameo.com* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://www.calameo.com/read/00089986924a0f7628685> (Accessed: 27 August 2023).

Freberg, K. *et al.* (2011) 'Who are the social media influencers? A study of public perceptions of personality', *Public Relations Review*, 37(1), pp. 90–92. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2010.11.001>.

Frochot, I. and Morrison, A.M. (2000) 'Benefit Segmentation: A Review of Its Applications to Travel and Tourism Research', *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 9(4), pp. 21–45. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1300/J073v09n04_02.

Fromentin, E. (1887) *Sahara et Sahel*. Plon.

Galal, S. (2023) *Algeria: contribution value of tourism to GDP 2021*, *Statista*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1277068/contribution-value-of-tourism-to-gdp-in-algeria/> (Accessed: 18 May 2023).

Galbin, A. (2014) 'An introduction to social constructionism', *Social Research Reports*, 6(26), pp. 82–92.

Gall, M.D., Gall, J.P. and Borg, W.R. (2003) *Educational Research: An Introduction*. Allyn and Bacon.

Gallois, W. (2008) *The Administration of Sickness*. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230582606>.

Gao, Q. *et al.* (2022) 'Does Health Crises Effect Tourism: Role of Financial Inclusion for Green Financial Development', *Frontiers in Public Health*, 10, p. 896894. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2022.896894>.

García-Moreno, L. and Pfeiffer, P.C. (1996) *Text and nation: cross-disciplinary essays on cultural and national identities / edited by Laura García-Moreno and Peter C. Pfeiffer.*, *Text and nation: cross-disciplinary essays on cultural and national identities*. Columbia, SC: Camden House (The Quiason lecture series).

Geertz, C. (1973) *Deep Play*.

Gellner, E. (1983) *Nations and Nationalism*. Cornell University Press.

Gergen, K.J. (1985) 'The social constructionist movement in modern psychology.', *American Psychologist*, 40(3), pp. 266–275. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.40.3.266>.

Gergen, K.J. (2011) 'The Self as Social Construction', *Psychological Studies*, 56(1), pp. 108–116. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12646-011-0066-1>.

Ghanem-Yazbeck, D. (2018) 'Legal Pluralism and Justice in Iraq after ISIL'.

Ghodbani, T. (2005) 'Rechgoun, un espace à protéger sur le littoral ouest de l'Algérie', *Méditerranée*, (105), pp. 87–94. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4000/mediterranee.350>.

Ghodbani, T., Kansab, O. and Kouti, A. (2016) 'Développement du tourisme balnéaire en Algérie face à la problématique de protection des espaces littoraux. Le cas des côtes mostaganemoises', *Études caribéennes* [Preprint], (33–34). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4000/etudescaribeennes.9305>.

Giddens, A. (1991) *Modernity and Self-Identity: Self and Society in the Late Modern Age*. Stanford: Stanford University Press.

Gioia, D.A., Corley, K.G. and Hamilton, A.L. (2013) 'Seeking Qualitative Rigor in Inductive Research: Notes on the Gioia Methodology', *Organizational Research Methods*, 16(1), pp. 15–31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1094428112452151>.

Giorgi, A. (2010) 'Phenomenology and the practice of science', *Existential Analysis*, 21(1), pp. 3–22.

Glissant, É. (1969) *L'intention poétique*. Seuil.

Gnoth, J. (1997) 'Tourism motivation and expectation formation', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 24(2), pp. 283–304. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383\(97\)80002-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383(97)80002-3).

Golafshani, N. (2003) 'Understanding Reliability and Validity in Qualitative Research', *The Qualitative Report* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2003.1870>.

Goldberg, D.T. (1996) 'Racial Formation in Contemporary American National Identity', *Social Identities*, 2(1), pp. 169–191. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504639652448>.

Goldsmith, R. and Clark, R. (2008) 'An analysis of factors affecting fashion leadership and fashion opinion seeking', *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*, 12, pp. 308–322. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/13612020810889272>.

Goleš, I.K. (2020a) 'Constructing identities in postcolonial theory', 14.

Goleš, I.K. (2020b) (PDF) *Constructing identities in postcolonial theory*. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339229595_Constructing_identities_in_postcolonial_theory?enrichId=rgreq-00c72c4401d72cf0ca28fb97a69a918b-XXX&enrichSource=Y292ZXJQYWdlOzMzOTIyOTU5NTtBUzo4NTgwMzgzMDI5NDExODZAMTU4MTU4MzY4MTYxMA%3D%3D&el=1_x_2&esc=publicationCoverPdf (Accessed: 26 June 2023).

Gonzalez, R. (2020) *Across the Maghreb, the Imazighen are pressing for rights and cultural recognition*, *Equal Times*. Available at: <https://www.equaltimes.org/across-the-maghreb-the-imazighen> (Accessed: 17 August 2022).

Goodall, B. (1988) 'How Tourists Choose Their Holidays: An Analytical Framework', in *Marketing in the Tourism Industry (RLE Tourism)*. Routledge.

Goodall, B. (1991) 'Understanding holiday choice.', *Understanding holiday choice.*, pp. 58–77.

Goodman, J. (2004) 'Reinterpreting the Berber spring: from rite of reversal to site of convergence', *The Journal of North African Studies*, 9(3), pp. 60–82. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1362938042000325813>.

Goodson, L. and Phillimore, J. (eds) (2004) 'Progress in Qualitative Research in Tourism', in *Qualitative Research in Tourism*. 1st edn. Taylor & Francis.

Goossens, C. (2000) 'Tourism information and pleasure motivation', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 27(2), pp. 301–321. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383\(99\)00067-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383(99)00067-5).

Graburn, N.H.H. and Barthel-Bouchier, D. (2001) 'Relocating the Tourist', *International Sociology*, 16(2), pp. 147–158. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0268580901016002001>.

Graham, B., Ashworth, G. and Tunbridge, J. (2016) *Geography of Heritage*.

Green, N. (2002) 'On the Move: Technology, Mobility, and the Mediation of Social Time and Space', *The Information Society*, 18(4), pp. 281–292. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01972240290075129>.

Greene, M. (2017) *Morocco's Amazigh: The long road to recognition - Qantara.de*, *Qantara.de - Dialogue with the Islamic World*. Available at: <https://en.qantara.de/content/morocco-amazigh-the-long-road-to-recognition> (Accessed: 17 August 2022).

Grosfoguel, R. (2007) 'THE EPISTEMIC DECOLONIAL TURN', *Cultural Studies*, 21(2–3), pp. 211–223. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09502380601162514>.

Guba, E.G. and Lincoln, Y.S. (2005) 'Paradigmatic Controversies, Contradictions, and Emerging Confluences', in *The Sage handbook of qualitative research, 3rd ed.* Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications Ltd, pp. 191–215.

Guede, J.R.S., Curiel, J. de E. and Antonovica, A. (2020) 'Increase the influence of the travel video bloggers by using YouTube to sell trips indirectly through relationship marketing and service quality online', in.

Guibernau, M. (2001) *Understanding nationalism*. Oxford: Polity Press. Available at: <http://www.waterstones.com/waterstonesweb/advancedSearch.do?buttonClicked=2&isbn=0745624022> (Accessed: 24 August 2023).

Guibernau, M. (2004) *Catalan Nationalism: Francoism, Transition and Democracy*. Routledge.

Hacking, I. (2001) *The social construction of what?* 7. print. Cambridge, Mass.: Harvard Univ. Press.

Hagelstein, R. (2008) 'Explaining the Violence Pattern of the Algerian Civil War'. Available at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20170812005527/http://hicn.org/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2012/06/wp43.pdf> (Accessed: 17 April 2023).

Haggett, P. (2001) *Geography: a Global Synthesis*. Pearson Education.

Haim, S.G. (1962) 'Arab Nationalism: An Anthology.', *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 345(1), p. 255. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/000271626334500156>.

Halcomb, E.J. *et al.* (2007) 'Literature review: considerations in undertaking focus group research with culturally and linguistically diverse groups', *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 16(6), pp. 1000–1011. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2702.2006.01760.x>.

Halewood, C. and Hannam, K. (2001) 'Viking heritage tourism', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 28(3), pp. 565–580. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383\(00\)00076-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383(00)00076-1).

Hall, C.M. and McArthur, S. (1993) *Heritage management in New Zealand and Australia: visitor management, interpretation, and marketing*.

Hall, C.M. and Tucker, H. (2005) *Tourism and Postcolonialism: Contested Discourses, Identities and Representations*. New York; Florence: Routledge Taylor & Francis Group

[distributor. Available at:
<http://VH7QX3XE2P.search.serialssolutions.com/?V=1.0&L=VH7QX3XE2P&S=JCs&C=T C0000311715&T=marc&tab=BOOKS> (Accessed: 6 June 2022).

Hall, C.M. and Tucker, H. (eds) (2014) *Tourism and postcolonialism: contested discourses, identities, and representations*. 1. issued in paperback. London: Routledge (Contemporary geographies of leisure, tourism, and mobility, 3).

Hall, C.M. and Zeppel, H. (1990) 'History, Architecture, Environment: Cultural Heritage and Tourism', *Journal of Travel Research*, 29(2), pp. 54–55. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/004728759002900212>.

Hall, M.C. and Tucker, H. (2004) *Tourism and Postcolonialism: Contested Discourses, Identities and Representations*. Routledge.

Hall, S. (1989) 'Ethnicity: Identity and Difference', *Radical America*, pp. 9–20.

Hall, S. (1997) 'Cultural Identity and Diaspora', p. 16.

Halpern, M. (1963) *The politics of social change in the Middle East and North Africa / by Manfred Halpern., Wellcome Collection*. Available at: <https://wellcomecollection.org/works/abeff9ju> (Accessed: 24 August 2023).

Hamadouche, L.D.-A. and Zoubir, Y.H. (2009) 'Pouvoir et opposition en Algérie : vers une transition prolongée?', *L'Année du Maghreb*, (V), pp. 111–127. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4000/anneemaghreb.535>.

Hammond, R.A. and Axelrod, R. (2006) 'The Evolution of Ethnocentrism', *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 50(6), pp. 926–936. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022002706293470>.

Hamour, D. (2022) 'Chapitre I : fêtes, festivals, patrimoine et développement local'.

Hannam, K., Butler, G. and Paris, C. (2013) 'Developments and Key Issues in Tourism Mobilities', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 44. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2013.09.010>.

- Hargreaves, J.D. (2014) *Decolonization in Africa*. Routledge.
- Harper, D. (1988) 'Visual sociology: Expanding sociological vision', *The American Sociologist*, 19(1), pp. 54–70. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02692374>.
- Harper, D. (2002) 'Talking about pictures: A case for photo elicitation', *Visual Studies*, 17(1), pp. 13–26. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14725860220137345>.
- Haug, S., Braveboy-Wagner, J. and Maihold, G. (2021) 'The "Global South" in the study of world politics: examining a meta category', *Third World Quarterly*, 42(9), pp. 1923–1944. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2021.1948831>.
- Hawthorn, G. (1991): 'Comparing Third World Politics 1', in *Rethinking Third-World Politics*. Routledge.
- Heddir, A.K. (2006) *The Reality of Tourism in Algeria, and Future Aspirations*. Algiers University. Available at: <https://www.ccdz.cerist.dz/admin/notice.php?id=0000000000000000191288000000> (Accessed: 25 July 2023).
- Hedges, P. (2015) 'Islamism, Radical Islam, Jihadism: The Problem of Language and Islamophobia'. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/10186000/Islamism_Radical_Islam_Jihadism_The_Problem_of_Language_and_Islamophobia (Accessed: 25 August 2023).
- Hedir, A. (2016) 'Tourism in Algeria', *Economic Studies*, 10(3), pp. 279–292.
- Hefferon, K. and Gil-Rodriguez, E. (2011) 'Interpretative phenomenological analysis', *The Psychologist*, 24(10), pp. 756–759.
- Heigham, J. and Crocker, R.A. (2009) *Qualitative research in applied linguistics: a practical introduction*. Nachdr. Basingstoke Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Helfront, S. (no date) *Post-Colonial States and the Struggle for Identity in the Middle East since World War Two - Foreign Policy Research Institute*. Available at:

<https://www.fpri.org/article/2015/10/post-colonial-states-and-the-struggle-for-identity-in-the-middle-east-since-world-war-two/> (Accessed: 1 October 2022).

Herbst, J. (2000) 'Economic incentives, natural resources and conflict in Africa', *Journal of African Economics*, 9(3), pp. 270–294. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/jae/9.3.270>.

Hewison, R. (2023) *The Heritage Industry: Britain in a climate of decline*. Routledge.

Hibbert, J.F. (2013) *Understanding the role of the tourists' identity in travel*.

Higgins-Desbiolles, F. and Whyte, K.P. (2013) 'No high hopes for hopeful tourism: A critical comment', *Annals of Tourism Research*, Complete (40), pp. 428–433. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2012.07.005>.

Hill, J.N.C. (2006) 'Identity and instability in postcolonial Algeria', *The Journal of North African Studies*, 11(1), pp. 1–16. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13629380500409735>.

Hinch, T.D. and Prentice, R. (2004) 'Indigenous People and Tourism', in A.A. Lew, C.M. Hall, and A.M. Williams (eds) *A Companion to Tourism*. Malden, MA, USA: Blackwell Publishing Ltd, pp. 246–261. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470752272.ch20>.

Hitchcock, M. (1999) 'Tourism and ethnicity: situational perspectives', *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 1(1), pp. 17–32. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1522-1970\(199901/02\)1:1<17::AID-JTR145>3.0.CO;2-L](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1522-1970(199901/02)1:1<17::AID-JTR145>3.0.CO;2-L).

Hitchcock, M. *et al.* (eds) (2010) *Heritage tourism in Southeast Asia*. Copenhagen: NIAS Press.

Hobsbawm, E.J. (1992) *Nations and Nationalism since 1780: Programme, Myth, Reality*. 2nd edn. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press (Canto). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CCOL0521439612>.

Hoffman, K.E. (2010) 'Internal Fractures in the Berber-Arab Distinction: from Colonial Practice to Post-National Preoccupations', in K.E. Hoffman and S.G. Miller (eds) *Berbers and*

Others: Beyond Tribe and Nation in the Maghrib. Bloomington, IN: Indiana University Press, pp. 39–61.

Holland, D. *et al.* (1998) *Identity and agency in cultural worlds*. Cambridge, MA, US: Harvard University Press (Identity and agency in cultural worlds.), pp. ix, 349.

Hollinshead, K. (1992) ‘“White” gaze, “red” people — Shadow visions: the disidentification of “Indians” in cultural tourism’, *Leisure Studies*, 11(1), pp. 43–64. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02614369100390301>.

Hollinshead, K. (1998) ‘Tourism, Hybridity, and Ambiguity: the Relevance of Bhabha’s “Third Space” Cultures’, *Journal of Leisure Research*, 30(1), pp. 121–156. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222216.1998.11949822>.

Hollinshead, K. (2006) ‘The Shift to Constructivism in Social Inquiry: Some Pointers for Tourism Studies’, *Tourism Recreation Research*, 31(2), pp. 43–58. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2006.11081261>.

Hollinshead, K. (2011) ‘The under-conceptualisations of tourism studies: The case for postdisciplinary knowing’, in *The Critical Turn in Tourism Studies*. Routledge.

Holloway, J.C. (1989) *The Business of Tourism*. Pitman.

Hołowiecka, B., Grzelak-Kostulska, E. and Kwiatkowski, G. (2011) ‘Impacts of Globalization on Tourist Preferences and Activity’, pp. 55–62.

Hoogvelt, A. (1997) *Globalisation and the Postcolonial World*. London: Macmillan Education UK. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-25671-6>.

Hottola, P. (ed.) (2009) *Tourism strategies and local responses in southern Africa*. Wallingford, UK; Cambridge, MA: CABI.

Howe, J. (1992) ‘The Crisis of Algerian Nationalism and the Rise of Islamic Integralism’, *New Left Review*, (I/196), pp. 85–100.

Huddart, D. (2006) *Homi K. Bhabha*. London; New York: Routledge (Routledge critical thinkers).

Hudson, S. and Thal, K. (2013) 'The Impact of Social Media on the Consumer Decision Process: Implications for Tourism Marketing', *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 30(1–2), pp. 156–160. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10548408.2013.751276>.

Hughes, K. (1991) 'Tourist satisfaction: A guided "cultural" tour in north Queensland', *Australian Psychologist*, 26(3), pp. 166–171. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00050069108257243>.

Humphrey, J. (1976) "NATIONALISM" AND THE COLONIAL SITUATION IN ALGERIA UNDER FRENCH RULE 1830-1962'.

Hutchinson, J. and Smith, A.D. (1994) *Nationalism*. Oxford University Press.

Hutt, G. (2019) *North Africa*. Imray, Laurie, Norie and Wilson Ltd.

Hutton, E.M. (1937) *The Grand Tour in Italy in the sixteenth, seventeenth, and eighteenth centuries*. Ph.D. University of Cambridge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.31154>.

Hyde, K.F. and Lawson, R. (2003) 'The Nature of Independent Travel', *Journal of Travel Research*, 42(1), pp. 13–23. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287503253944>.

Hysa, B., Karasek, A. and Zdonek, I. (2021) 'Social Media Usage by Different Generations as a Tool for Sustainable Tourism Marketing in Society 5.0 Idea', *Sustainability*, 13(3), p. 1018. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13031018>.

Ibn Khaldun (1377) *مقدمة ابن خلدون*. Available at: <https://foulabook.com/ar/book/%D9%85%D9%82%D8%AF%D9%85%D8%A9-%D8%A7%D8%A8%D9%86-%D8%AE%D9%84%D8%AF%D9%88%D9%86-pdf> (Accessed: 25 May 2023).

Ibn Khaldun (2020) *The Muqaddimah: An Introduction to History - Abridged Edition*. Princeton University Press.

Ibrahimi, K.T. (1995) *Les Algériens et leur(s) langue(s): éléments pour une approche sociolinguistique de la société algérienne*. Editions el Hikma.

Imran, S. (2017) 'Strengthening the National Identity through Brands', *Advances in Economics and Business*, 5(2), pp. 76–82. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.13189/aeb.2017.050204>.

Ingham, R. (1986) 'Psychological contributions to the study of leisure—Part one', *Leisure Studies*, 5(3), pp. 255–279. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02614368600390201>.

Instagram monthly active users 2021 (no date) *Statista*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/253577/number-of-monthly-active-instagram-users/> (Accessed: 6 August 2022).

Iso-Ahola, S.E. (1983) 'Towards a social psychology of recreational travel', *Leisure Studies*, 2(1), pp. 45–56. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02614368300390041>.

Ivanovic, M. (2008) *Cultural tourism*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.4522.6323>.

Jackson, G. and Morpeth, N. (1999) 'Local Agenda 21 and Community Participation in Tourism Policy and Planning: Future or Fallacy', *Current Issues in Tourism*, 2(1), pp. 1–38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683509908667841>.

Jalilvand, M.R. *et al.* (2017) 'Factors influencing word of mouth behaviour in the restaurant industry', *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 35, pp. 81–110. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/MIP-02-2016-0024>.

Jamal, T. and Hollinshead, K. (2001) 'Tourism and the forbidden zone: the underserved power of qualitative inquiry', *Tourism Management*, 22(1), pp. 63–82. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177\(00\)00020-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177(00)00020-0).

Jamal, T. and Kim, H. (2005) 'Bridging the interdisciplinary divide: Towards an integrated framework for heritage tourism research', *Tourist Studies*, 5(1), pp. 55–83. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468797605062715>.

Jansen, B.J. *et al.* (2009) 'Twitter power: Tweets as electronic word of mouth', *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 60(11), pp. 2169–2188. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.21149>.

Javed, M., and Awan, T.M. (2022) 'The young tourist's co-creation nexus: market mavens and existential authenticity as driving forces of intentions to revisit and recommend', *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 6(2), pp. 716–734. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-12-2020-0240>.

Jaya, I.P.G.I.T. and Prianthara, I.B.T. (2020) 'Role of Social Media Influencers in Tourism Destination Image: How Does Digital Marketing Affect Purchase Intention?', in *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Vocational Higher Education (ICVHE 2018)*. 3rd International Conference on Vocational Higher Education (ICVHE 2018), Batam, Indonesia: Atlantis Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.200331.114>.

Jebari, I. (2018) 'Therapeutic History and the Enduring Memories of Violence in Algeria and Morocco', *Middle East - Topics & Arguments*, 11, pp. 108–119. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.17192/meta.2018.11.7808>.

Jenkins, O. (2003) 'Photography and travel brochures: The circle of representation', *Tourism Geographies*, 5(3), pp. 305–328. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616680309715>.

Jenkins, R. (2014) *Social Identity*. 4th edn. London: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315887104>.

Jewitt, C. and Oyama, R. (2023) 'The Handbook of Visual Analysis', in pages 134-156, . London: SAGE Publications Ltd. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9780857020062>.

Jones, C.M. and Hardy, J.M. (1988) 'From Colonialism to Community: Religion and Culture in Charles H. Long's Significations', *Callaloo*, (36), p. 582. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2931543>.

Jones, E. (1968) 'The Decolonization of African Literature'.

Julien, C.A. (1952) *L'Afrique du Nord en marche: nationalismes musulmans et souveraineté française*. R. Julliard.

Kaddache, M. (1981) *Histoire du nationalisme algérien: question nationale et politique algérienne, 1919-1951. 2ème. ed. 2 vols.* Available at: <https://www.degruyter.com/database/IABO/entry/iab19822743/html?lang=en> (Accessed: 25 August 2023).

Kadri, B. (2021) 'Vocabulary of Tourism Discourse with the help of Marie La Place, Alain A Grenier and Yann, R.'

Kalia, R. (2004) *Gandhinagar: Building National Identity in Postcolonial India*. Univ of South Carolina Press.

Kapitan, S. and Silvera, D.H. (2016) 'From digital media influencers to celebrity endorsers: Attributions drive endorser effectiveness', *Marketing Letters: A Journal of Research in Marketing*, 27(3), pp. 553–567. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11002-015-9363-0>.

Karacaoğlu, S. (2021) 'Impact of Electronic Word of Mouth Communication and Destination Image on Behavioural Intentions: The Case of Eskişehir Turkey', *Gastoria: Journal of Gastronomy And Travel Research*, 5(3), pp. 420–446. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.32958/gastoria.986606>.

Karayilan, E. and Cetin, G. (2016) 'Tourism Destination: Design of Experiences', in M. Sotiriadis and D. Gursoy (eds) *The Handbook of Managing and Marketing Tourism Experiences*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited, pp. 65–83. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-78635-290-320161004>.

Kardooni, R., Yusoff, S.B. and Kari, F.B. (2015) 'Barriers to Renewable Energy Development: Five Fuel Policy in Malaysia', *Energy & Environment*, 26(8), pp. 1353–1361. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1260/0958-305X.26.8.1353>.

Karim, K. (2016) 'Cultural Tourism Role for Domestic Tourism Development', *Journal of Administration and Development*, 5(1), pp. 311–332.

Kastarlak, B.I. and Barber, B. (2013) *Fundamentals of Planning and Developing Tourism: Pearson New International Edition*. Pearson Higher Ed.

Kateb, Y. (1956) *Nedjma*. Paris: Le Seuil.

Kavoura, A. (2007) 'Advertising of National Identity and Tourism Bureaucracy', *Current Issues in Tourism*, 10(5), pp. 397–414. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2167/cit276.0>.

Kedourie, E. (1960) *Nationalism*. Hutchinson.

Kelly, L.R. (2000) *Motivations and experiences of tourists at English cathedrals*. Ph.D. University of Liverpool. Available at: <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?did=3&uin=uk.bl.ethos.250377> (Accessed: 24 August 2023).

Kelner, S. (2010) *Tours That Bind: Diaspora, Pilgrimage, and Israeli Birthright Tourism*. NYU Press. Available at: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt9qfdrc> (Accessed: 27 August 2023).

Kerstetter, D., Confer, J. and Bricker, K. (1998) 'Industrial Heritage Attractions: Types and Tourists', *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 7(2), pp. 91–104. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1300/J073v07n02_05.

Khalidi, R. (1991) 'Arab Nationalism: Historical Problems in the Literature'.

Kherroubi, Y. (2016) 'Tourism culture and its role in stimulating the tourism market in Algeria: the case of Jijel', *Economic Visions Journal*, 6(2). Available at: <http://dspace.univ-eloued.dz:80/xmlui/handle/123456789/5904> (Accessed: 27 August 2023).

Kherrou, L. *et al.* (2020) 'ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITES AND TOURISM: PROTECTION AND VALORIZATION, CASE OF TIMGAD (BATNA) ALGERIA', *GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 28(1), pp. 289–302. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.30892/gtg.28123-470>.

Kiely, R. *et al.* (2001) 'The Markers and Rules of Scottish National Identity', *The Sociological Review*, 49(1), pp. 33–55. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-954X.00243>.

Kiernan, B. (2007) *Blood and soil: a world history of genocide and extermination from Sparta to Darfur*. New Haven: Yale University Press.

Kiernan, B. (2008) 'Blood and Soil: A World History of Genocide and Extermination from Sparta to Darfur. New Haven, CT: Yale University Press', *Comparative Political Studies*, 41(10), pp. 1432–1435. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0010414008315866>.

Kiger, M.E. and Varpio, L. (2020) 'Thematic analysis of qualitative data: AMEE Guide No. 131', *Medical Teacher*, 42(8), pp. 846–854. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/0142159X.2020.1755030>.

Kim, J.-H. (2018) 'The Impact of Memorable Tourism Experiences on Loyalty Behaviors: The Mediating Effects of Destination Image and Satisfaction', *Journal of Travel Research*, 57(7), pp. 856–870. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287517721369>.

Kim, J.-H., Ritchie, J. and McCormick, B. (2012) 'Development of a Scale to Measure Memorable Tourism Experiences', *Journal of Travel Research*, 51, pp. 12–25. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287510385467>.

Kiráľová, A. and Pavlíčka, A. (2015a) 'Development of Social Media Strategies in Tourism Destination', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 175, pp. 358–366. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.1211>.

Kiráľová, A. and Pavlíčka, A. (2015b) 'Development of Social Media Strategies in Tourism Destination', *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 175, pp. 358–366. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.1211>.

Kitiarsa, P. (2010) 'Buddha-izing a Global City-State: Transnational Religious Mobilities, Spiritual Marketplace, and Thai Migrant Monks in Singapore', *Mobilities*, 5(2), pp. 257–275. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17450101003665184>.

Knobloch, U., Robertson, K. and Aitken, R. (2017) 'Experience, Emotion, and Eudaimonia: A Consideration of Tourist Experiences and Well-being', *Journal of Travel Research*, 56(5), pp. 651–662. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287516650937>.

Knoll, J. (2016) 'Advertising in social media: A review of empirical evidence', *International Journal of Advertising*, 35, pp. 266–300. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02650487.2015.1021898>.

Korstjens, I. and Moser, A. (2018) 'Series: Practical guidance to qualitative research. Part 4: Trustworthiness and publishing', *European Journal of General Practice*, 24(1), pp. 120–124. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13814788.2017.1375092>.

Kotler, P., Bowen, J.T. and Makens, J.C. (1999) *Marketing for Hospitality and Tourism*. Prentice Hall.

Kracht, J. and Wang, Y. (2010) 'Examining the tourism distribution channel: Evolution and transformation', *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 22. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596111011053837>.

Kraidy, M.M. (2002) 'Hybridity in Cultural Globalization', *Communication Theory*, 12(3), pp. 316–339. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2885.2002.tb00272.x>.

Krais, J. (2019) 'MUSCULAR MUSLIMS: SCOUTING IN LATE COLONIAL ALGERIA BETWEEN NATIONALISM AND RELIGION', *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, 51(4), pp. 567–585. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0020743819000679>.

Krueger, R.A. (1994) *Focus Groups: A Practical Guide for Applied Research*. 2nd ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.

Krueger, R.A. and Casey, M.A. (2000a) 'A practical guide for applied research.' *A practical guide for applied research*.

Krueger, R.A. and Casey, M.A. (2000b) *Focus Groups: A Practical Guide for Applied Research*. SAGE.

Kuortti, J. and Nyman, J. (2007) *Reconstructing Hybridity: Post-colonial Studies in Transition*. Rodopi.

Kurun, İ. (2017) ‘Arab Nationalism from a Historical Perspective: A Gradual Demise?’, in. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Arab-Nationalism-from-a-Historical-Perspective-%3A-A-Kurun/71cb8f60880bed7c4c9f25cf29ff66bf87baf41a> (Accessed: 20 June 2023).

Ladjal, T. and Bensaid, B. (2012) ‘The French colonial occupation and the Algerian national identity: alienation or assimilation?’, *Journal: Int. J. of Arab Culture, Management and Sustainable Development*, 2, pp. 142–152. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJACMSD.2012.049124>.

Laesser, C., Beritelli, P. and Bieger, T. (2009) ‘Solo travel: Explorative insights from a mature market (Switzerland)’, *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 15(3), pp. 217–227. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356766709104268>.

Lafkioui, M. (2013) ‘La Question Berbère; politiques Linguistiques et Pratiques langagières.’, pp. 3–4.

Laframboise, N. *et al.* (1998) *Algeria: Stabilization and Transition to Market*. Washington, D.C.: International Monetary Fund (Occasional Papers). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781557756916.084>.

Lai, I. *et al.* (2018) ‘The Influence of Word of Mouth on Tourism Destination Choice: Tourist–Resident Relationship and Safety Perception among Mainland Chinese Tourists Visiting Macau’, *Sustainability*, 10(7), p. 2114. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10072114>.

Lambert, S.D. and Loiselle, C.G. (2008) ‘Combining individual interviews and focus groups to enhance data richness’, *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 62(2), pp. 228–237. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.2007.04559.x>.

Lanfant, M.-F., Allcock, J.B. and Bruner, E.M. (1995) *International Tourism: Identity and Change*. SAGE.

Larkin, M., Watts, S. and Clifton, E. (2006) 'Giving voice and making sense in interpretative phenomenological analysis', *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 102–120. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp062oa>.

Laroussi, F. (2016) *Postcolonial Counterpoint: Orientalism, France, and the Maghreb*. University of Toronto Press.

Larsen, J. (2001) 'Tourism Mobilities and the Travel Glance: Experiences of Being on the Move', *Scandinavian Journal of Hospitality and Tourism*, 1(2), pp. 80–98. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/150222501317244010>.

Layachi, A. (2005) 'The Berbers in Algeria: Politicized ethnicity and ethnicized politics', in, pp. 195–228.

Lazali, K. (2021) *Colonial Trauma: A Study of the Psychic and Political Consequences of Colonial Oppression in Algeria*. John Wiley & Sons.

Lazarus, N. (ed.) (2004) *The Cambridge Companion to Postcolonial Literary Studies*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press (Cambridge Companions to Literature). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CCOL0521826942>.

van Leeuwen, T. (2011) *The Language of Colour: An Introduction*. Routledge.

van Leeuwen, T. (2023) 'The Handbook of Visual Analysis', in pages 92-118, London: SAGE Publications Ltd. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9780857020062>.

Legg, C.A. (2021) *The New White Race*. University of Nebraska Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv1kbgsvg>.

Lengkeek, J. (2001) 'Leisure Experience and Imagination: Rethinking Cohen's Modes of Tourist Experience', *International Sociology*, 16(2), pp. 173–184. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0268580901016002003>.

Lester, A. (1998) "'Otherness" and the frontiers of empire: the Eastern Cape Colony, 1806–c.1850', *Journal of Historical Geography*, 24(1), pp. 2–19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1006/jhge.1997.0073>.

Leung, L. (2015) 'Validity, reliability, and generalizability in qualitative research', *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 4(3), p. 324. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4103/2249-4863.161306>.

Levers, M.-J.D. (2013) 'Philosophical Paradigms, Grounded Theory, and Perspectives on Emergence', *SAGE Open*, 3(4), p. 2158244013517243. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244013517243>.

Light, D. (2000) 'Gazing on Communism: Heritage Tourism and Post-Communist Identities in Germany, Hungary and Romania', *Tourism Geographies*, 2, pp. 157–176. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616680050027879>.

Lincoln, Y.S. and Guba, E.G. (1985) *Naturalistic inquiry*. Nachdr. Newbury Park, Calif.: Sage.

Lincoln, Y.S. and Guba, E.G. (2011) 'PARADIGMATIC CONTROVERSIES/ CONTRADICTIONS/ AND EMERGING CONFLUENCES'.

Literacy, training and employment for women, Algeria | UIL (2015). Available at: <https://uil.unesco.org/case-study/effective-practices-database-litbase-0/literacy-training-and-employment-women-algeria> (Accessed: 31 December 2022).

Litosseliti, L. (2003) *Using Focus Groups in Research*. A&C Black.

Little, R. (2006) 'Interpreting Colonialism', *French Studies*, 60(4), pp. 517–518. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/fs/knl128>.

Liu, M.J. *et al.* (2015) 'Authenticity Perceptions in the Chinese Marketplace', *Journal of Business Research*, 68(1), pp. 27–33. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2014.05.011>.

Löfgren, O. (2008) 'Motion and Emotion: Learning to be a Railway Traveller', *Mobilities*, 3(3), pp. 331–351. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17450100802376696>.

Louardi, K., Mohamed A., R. and Sofiane, H. (2018) 'REHABILITATION OF GEOGRAPHICAL AREAS FOR A TOURIST DEVELOPMENT THE CASE OF BATNA

REGION'S MOUNTAINS (ALGERIA)', *GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 22(1), p. 455. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.30892/gtg.22215-302>.

Mack, N. *et al.* (2005) 'Qualitative Research Methods: A Data Collector's Field Guide', *Family Health International* [Preprint].

Madani, A. *et al.* (2020) 'The Impact of Covid-19 Outbreak on the Tourism Needs of the Algerian Population', *Sustainability*, 12(21), p. 8856. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12218856>.

Maddison, S. (2012) 'Postcolonial guilt and national identity: historical injustice and the Australian settler state', *Social Identities*, 18(6), pp. 695–709. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504630.2012.709000>.

Maddy-Weitzman, B. (2011a) *The Berber Identity Movement and the Challenge to North African States*. University of Texas Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7560/725874>.

Maddy-Weitzman, B. (2011b) 'The Berber Identity Movement and the Challenge to North African States.' Available at: https://www.academia.edu/29836394/The_Berber_Identity_Movement_and_the_Challenge_to_North_African_States_Bruce_Maddy_Weitzman_pdf (Accessed: 25 August 2023).

Madison, D.S. (2012) *Critical ethnography: method, ethics, and performance*. 2. ed. Los Angeles, Calif. : SAGE.

Madouche, H. (2003) *Le tourisme en Algérie : jeu et enjeux, point de vue sur les préoccupations actuelles*. Alger: Editions distribution Houma.

Madoui, A. and Hakim, B. (2021) 'Reality of E-Tourism in Algeria and its Role in Promoting Tourism Products', 24, pp. 1311–1327.

Magno, F. and Cassia, F. (2018) 'The impact of social media influencers in tourism', *Anatolia*, 29(2), pp. 288–290. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13032917.2018.1476981>.

Mahé, A. (2001) 'II. - La Grande Kabylie au début du XIXe siècle', in *Histoire de la Grande Kabylie XIXe-XXe siècles*. Saint-Denis: Éditions Bouchène (Histoire du Maghreb), pp.

38–142. Available at: <https://www.cairn.info/histoire-de-la-grande-kabylie-xixe-xxe-siecles--2912946123-p-38.htm> (Accessed: 25 August 2023).

Majid, A. (1996) ‘Can the Postcolonial Critic Speak? Orientalism and the Rushdie Affair’, *Cultural Critique*, (32), pp. 5–42. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1354529>.

Makimoto, T. and Manners, D. (1997) *Digital nomad*. New York: Wiley.

Malinowski, B. (1931) ‘Descriptive Sociology or Groups of Sociological Facts classified and arranged by Herbert Spencer’, *Nature*, 127(3209), pp. 655–657. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/127655a0>.

Malone, S., McCabe, S. and Smith, A.P. (2014) ‘The role of hedonism in ethical tourism’, *Annals of Tourism Research*, 44, pp. 241–254. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2013.10.005>.

Malterud, K. (2001) ‘Qualitative research: standards, challenges, and guidelines’, *The Lancet*, 358(9280), pp. 483–488. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(01\)05627-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(01)05627-6).

Mammeri, M. (1965) *L’opium et le bâton: roman*. Paris: la Découverte.

Manai, A. (2020) ‘North Africa in the Tourist Guidebooks of the 19th and Early 20th Centuries’, *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 11(3), p. 63. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.36941/mjss-2020-0030>.

Mann, G. (2009) ‘What Was the “Indigénat”? The “Empire of Law” in French West Africa’, *The Journal of African History*, 50(3), pp. 331–353.

Mannell, R.C., Zuzanek, J. and Larson, R. (1988) ‘Leisure States and “Flow” Experiences: Testing Perceived Freedom and Intrinsic Motivation Hypotheses’, *Journal of Leisure Research*, 20(4), pp. 289–304. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222216.1988.11969782>.

Marinescu, R.-E. (2007) ‘Postcolonial Identities. British-South-Asian Novelists’, *Synergy*, (2), pp. 88–101.

Markowitz, M. (2021) 'Coinage of Ancient Numidia', *CoinWeek.com* [Preprint]. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/45107089/Coinage_of_Ancient_Numidia (Accessed: 24 August 2023).

Mascheroni, G. (2007) 'Global Nomads' Network and Mobile Sociality: Exploring New Media Uses on the Move', *Information, Communication & Society*, 10(4), pp. 527–546. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13691180701560077>.

Mateu, G. (2021) *Frontera sur: voces y relatos en los márgenes*. Primera edición. Edited by M. del Carmen. Somonte\$Cenero\$Gijón, Asturias, España: Ediciones Trea (Historia de la cultura).

Mawby, S. (2010) 'Orientalism and the Failure of British Policy in the Middle East: The Case of Aden', *History*, 95(3 (319)), pp. 332–353.

Maxwell, J.A. (2020) 'The Value of Qualitative Inquiry for Public Policy', *Qualitative Inquiry*, 26(2), pp. 177–186. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077800419857093>.

Mazouz, F. (2015) 'Le renouvellement du patrimoine bâti vétuste en Algérie. Le cas du centre-ville d'Oran', *Droit et société*, 89(1), pp. 151–170. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3917/drs.089.0151>.

McCabe, S. (2009) 'Chapter 2. Who is a Tourist? Conceptual and Theoretical Developments', in *Chapter 2. Who is a Tourist? Conceptual and Theoretical Developments*. Channel View Publications, pp. 25–42. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781845410988-003>.

McDougall, J. (2006) *History and the Culture of Nationalism in Algeria*. Cambridge University Press.

McDougall, J. (2017) 'A History of Algeria', *A History of Algeria*, p. xvii.

McKay, V. (1946) 'The Arab League in World Politics, Foreign Policy Reports'.

McKercher, B. and Decosta, P.L. (2007) 'Research Report: The Lingering Effect of Colonialism on Tourist Movements', *Tourism Economics*, 13(3), pp. 453–474. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5367/000000007781497746>.

McKercher, B. and Du Cros, H. (2003) 'Testing a cultural tourism typology', *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 5(1), pp. 45–58. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/jtr.417>.

McLeod, J. (1994) 'Postmodernism and Postcolonialism', in *Postmodern Surroundings*. BRILL, pp. 167–178. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1163/9789004647268>.

McNamara, C. (2009) *General Guidelines for Conducting Research Interviews - Management Library*. Available at: <https://management.org/businessresearch/interviews.htm> (Accessed: 13 January 2023).

Meade, R.D. and Whittaker, J.O. (1967) 'A Cross-Cultural Study of Authoritarianism', *The Journal of Social Psychology*, 72(1), pp. 3–7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00224545.1967.9922293>.

Meethan, K. (2003) 'Mobile Cultures? Hybridity, Tourism and Cultural Change', *Journal of Tourism and Cultural Change*, 1(1), pp. 11–28. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14766820308668157>.

Meftah, S., Bouchama, O. and Bouzid, H. (2022) 'THE POSSIBILITY OF EXPLOITING THE TOURISM POTENTIALS IN BISKRA PROVINCE (SOUTH-EASTERN ALGERIA)', *GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 42(2 supplement), pp. 718–726. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.30892/gtg.422spl10-881>.

Mellah, S. (2004) *Les massacres en Algérie, 1992-2004*. Justice Commission for Algeria.

Memmi, A. (2006) *Decolonization and the Decolonized*. U of Minnesota Press.

Meng, F., Tepanon, Y. and Uysal, M. (2008) 'Measuring tourist satisfaction by attribute and motivation: The case of a nature-based resort', *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 14(1), pp. 41–56. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356766707084218>.

Meo, A.I. (2010) 'Picturing Students' Habitus: The Advantages and Limitations of Photo-Elicitation Interviewing in a Qualitative Study in the City of Buenos Aires', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 9(2), pp. 149–171. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/160940691000900203>.

Merbah, T.Y., Yahiaoui, A. and Aissat, F.Z. (2020) 'Tourism awareness and its developmental relationship to the tourism sector in Algeria', *Economic studies*, 14(3), pp. 226–239.

Meredith, aul (1998) 'Hybridity in the Third Space: Rethinking Bi-cultural Politics in Aotearoa/New Zealand', p. 7.

Merriam, S.B. (1998) *Qualitative research and case study applications in education*. Rev. and expanded. San Francisco, Calif: Jossey-Bass Publishers (A joint publication of the Jossey-Bass education series and the Jossey-Bass higher and adult education series).

Merri Catherine (2018) 'Huey P. Newton's Interview with The Movement Magazine (1968)', *Medium*, 21 February. Available at: <https://medium.com/@merricatherine/huey-p-newtons-interview-with-the-movement-magazine-1968-a328e6b78c32> (Accessed: 19 June 2023).

Merriman, N. (1989) *Museum Visiting as a Cultural Phenomenon*. P Vergo. Towebridge: The New Museology.

Metz, H.C. (ed.) (1994) *Algeria: a country study*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C: Federal Research Division, Library of Congress: For sale by the Supt. of Docs., U.S. G.P.O (Area handbook series, 550–44).

Mezhoud, S. (2020) 'The Ethics of Dealing with the Other, in the Thought of Prince El-Amir Abdelkader Al-Jazairi', *Milev Journal of Research and Studies*, 6(2), pp. 60–77. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.58205/mjrs.v6i2.387>.

Mignolo, W.D. (2007) 'Delinking; The Rhetoric of Modernity, the Logic of Coloniality and the Grammar of De-coloniality', *Cultural Studies*, 21(2–3), pp. 449–514. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09502380601162647>.

Mignolo, W.D. (2010) 'Introduction: Coloniality of power and de-colonial thinking', in *Globalization and the Decolonial Option*. Routledge.

Millar, S. (no date) 'ICOMOS International Cultural Tourism Charters'.

Miller, E.R. and Kubota, R. (2013) 'Second language identity construction', in J. Herschensohn and M. Young-Scholten (eds) *The Cambridge Handbook of Second Language Acquisition*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press (Cambridge Handbooks in Language and Linguistics), pp. 230–250. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781139051729.015>.

Miller, J. (1997) 'Cultural tourism worthy of note.', *Hotel & Motel Management*, 212(15), p. 7.

Milostivaya, A. *et al.* (2018) 'Sociocultural and Linguistic Reflections on Post-colonial Studies of H.K. Bhabha', *SHS Web of Conferences*. Edited by S. Cindori *et al.*, 50, p. 01107. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/20185001107>.

Milostivaya, A., Nazarenko Ekaterina, E. and Makhova, I. (2017) 'Post-colonial Theory of Homi K. Bhabha: Translator's and Translatologist's Reflection', in *Proceedings of the 7th International Scientific and Practical Conference 'Current issues of linguistics and didactics: The interdisciplinary approach in humanities' (CILDIAH 2017)*. 7th International Scientific and Practical Conference 'Current issues of linguistics and didactics: The interdisciplinary approach in humanities' (CILDIAH 2017), Volgograd, Russia: Atlantis Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2991/cildiah-17.2017.31>.

Mkono, M. (2016) 'The reflexive tourist', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 57, pp. 206–219. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2016.01.004>.

Mobilities, tourism and travel behavior: contexts and boundaries (2018). Rijeka, Croatia: InTech.

Modood, T. and Werbner, P. (1997) *Debating Cultural Hybridity*. Zed Books.

Molz, J.G. (2012) *Travel Connections: Tourism, Technology, and Togetherness in a Mobile World*. Routledge.

Monod, T. (1932) 'Général Meynier et Capitaine Nabal. — Guide pratique du tourisme au Sahara. — Paris, Société d'éditions géographiques, maritimes et coloniales, 1931', *Revue d'Écologie (La Terre et La Vie)*, 2(3), pp. 184–184.

Moon, K. *et al.* (2016) 'A guideline to improve qualitative social science publishing in ecology and conservation journals', *Ecology and Society*, 21(3). Available at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26269983> (Accessed: 24 April 2024).

Moore, K. *et al.* (2021) 'Authenticity in tourism theory and experience. Practically indispensable and theoretically mischievous?', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 89, p. 103208. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2021.103208>.

Moore, L. (2008) *Arab, Muslim, woman: voice and vision in postcolonial literature and film*. London; New York: Routledge (Transformations).

Moran, A. (2011) 'Multiculturalism as nation-building in Australia: Inclusive national identity and the embrace of diversity', *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 34(12), pp. 2153–2172. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870.2011.573081>.

Morgan, A. (2004) 'MATOUB LOUNES – A lifetime dancing with death – Andy Morgan Writes'. Available at: <https://www.andymorganwrites.com/matoub-lounes-a-life-that-danced-with-death/> (Accessed: 24 August 2023).

Morgan, D.L. (1996) 'Focus Groups', *Annual Review of Sociology*, 22(1), pp. 129–152. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.soc.22.1.129>.

Morgan, N.J., Pritchard, A. and Piggott, R. (2003) 'Destination branding and the role of the stakeholders: The case of New Zealand', *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 9(3), pp. 285–299. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/135676670300900307>.

Morse, J.M. (2000) 'Determining Sample Size', *Qualitative Health Research*, 10(1), pp. 3–5. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/104973200129118183>.

Moscardo, G. (2006) 'Backpackers and Other Younger Travellers to the Great Barrier Reef: An Exploration of Changes in Characteristics and Behaviours Over Time', *Tourism*

Recreation Research, 31(3), pp. 29–37. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/02508281.2006.11081503>.

Mossberg, L. (2007) 'A Marketing Approach to the Tourist Experience', *Scandinavian Journal of Hospitality and Tourism*, 7(1), pp. 59–74. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/15022250701231915>.

MTA (2022) *Ministère du Tourisme, de l'Artisanat et de l'Economie Sociale et Solidaire*. Available at: <https://mtaess.gov.ma/fr/> (Accessed: 26 August 2023).

Murairwa, D.S. (2015) 'VOLUNTARY SAMPLING DESIGN', 4(2).

Murdock, G. and Pink, S. (2005) 'Ethnography Bytes Back: Digitalising Visual Anthropology', *Media International Australia*, 116(1), pp. 10–23. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1329878X0511600104>.

Murray, S.J. and Holmes, D. (2014) 'Interpretive Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) and the Ethics of Body and Place: Critical Methodological Reflections', *Human Studies*, 37(1), pp. 15–30.

Musso, M. (2017) 'Oil will set us free?: the hydrocarbon industry and the Algerian decolonization process', in. UCL Press, pp. 62–84. Available at: <http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:kth:diva-285835> (Accessed: 10 January 2023).

Nanji, A. (2017) 'The Most Popular Social Network With Micro-Influencers', *Marketing Profs*. Available at: <https://www.marketingprofs.com/charts/2017/31676/the-most-popular-social-network-with-micro-influencers> (Accessed: 6 August 2022).

Nasser, R. (2019) 'Identity beyond borders: national identity and the post-colonial alternative', *Social Semiotics*, 29(2), pp. 145–171. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10350330.2018.1425317>.

Nedeljković, O., Jovanović, R. and Đokić, M. (2013) 'Trendovi razvoja i uticaj globalizacije na turizam', *EMC Review - Časopis za ekonomiju - APEIRON*, 5(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7251/EMC1301073N>.

Newton, H.P. (1968) *Huey P. Newton's Interview with The Movement (1968) | by Merri Catherine | Medium*. Available at: <https://medium.com/@merricatherine/huey-p-newtons-interview-with-the-movement-magazine-1968-a328e6b78c32> (Accessed: 24 August 2023).

Ngũgĩ, wa T. (1986) *Decolonising the mind: the politics of language in African literature*. London: Portsmouth, N.H: Pearson Education Limited.

Nickerson, N.P. (2005) 'Some Reflections on Quality Tourism Experiences', in *Quality Tourism Experiences*. Routledge.

Nielsen (2013) *Global Trust in Advertising and Brand Messages*. Available at: <https://www.nielsen.com/insights/2013/global-trust-in-advertising-and-brand-messages/> (Accessed: 26 October 2022).

Nkomo, S.M. (2011) 'A postcolonial and anti-colonial reading of "African" leadership and management in organization studies: tensions, contradictions and possibilities', *Organization*, 18(3), pp. 365–386. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1350508411398731>.

Noonan, H. (2019) *Personal Identity*. 3rd edn. London: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315107240>.

Nowell, L.S. *et al.* (2017) 'Thematic Analysis: Striving to Meet the Trustworthiness Criteria', *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 16(1), p. 160940691773384. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406917733847>.

Noy, C. (2007) 'The language (s) of the tourist experience: An autoethnography of the poetic tourist', *The critical turn in tourism studies*, pp. 349–370.

Nwaubani, E. (2003) 'The United States and the Liquidation of European Colonial Rule in Tropical Africa, 1941-1963', *Cahiers d'études africaines*, 171(3), pp. 505–551. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4000/etudesafricaines.214>.

Oelofsen, R. (2015) 'Decolonisation of the African mind and intellectual landscape', *Phronimon*, 16, pp. 130–146.

Office of International Religious Freedom (2022) *2021 Report on International Religious Freedom*. Available at: <https://www.state.gov/reports/2021-report-on-international-religious-freedom/> (Accessed: 26 August 2023).

Okazaki, E. (2008) 'A Community-Based Tourism Model: Its Conception and Use', *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 16(5), pp. 511–529. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669580802159594>.

Olsen, D.H. (2012) 'Negotiating identity at religious sites: a management perspective', *Journal of Heritage Tourism*, 7(4), pp. 359–366. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/1743873X.2012.722642>.

Olsson, M. (2010) 'Colonial Legacies -Ambivalence, mimicry and hybridity in Chinua Achebe's Things Fall Apart and Louise Erdrich's Tracks'.

O.Nyumba, T. *et al.* (2018) 'The use of focus group discussion methodology: Insights from two decades of application in conservation', *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*. Edited by D. Geneletti, 9(1), pp. 20–32. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12860>.

OPEC (2019) *OPEC Annual Statistics Bulletin 2019*. Available at: https://www.opec.org/opec_web/static_files_project/media/downloads/publications/ASB_2019.pdf (Accessed: 20 October 2021).

OPEC (2022) *Data download*. Available at: https://asb.opec.org/data/ASB_Data.php (Accessed: 18 May 2023).

O'Reilly, T. (2005) *What Is Web 2.0*. Available at: <https://oreilly.com{file}> (Accessed: 25 August 2023).

Otto, J.E. and Ritchie, J.R.B. (1996) 'The service experience in tourism', *Tourism Management*, 17(3), pp. 165–174. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0261-5177\(96\)00003-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0261-5177(96)00003-9).

Ouazani, M. (2012) *Sustainable Tourism, Reality and Challenges in Algeria, Case Study of Saida city, Hammam Rabi*. Abou Bakr Belkaid. Available at: <https://www.theses-algerie.com> (Accessed: 25 July 2023).

Page, S. (1995) *Urban Tourism (Routledge Topics in Tourism)*. London: Cengage Learning Emea. Available at: <https://www.biblio.com/book/urban-tourism-routledge-topics-tourism-page/d/1376023664> (Accessed: 28 August 2023).

Palomino-Schalscha, M.A. (no date) 'INDIGENEITY, AUTONOMY AND NEW CULTURAL SPACES: THE DECOLONISATION OF PRACTICES, BEING AND PLACE THROUGH TOURISM IN ALTO BÍO-BÍO, CHILE', p. 332.

Papastergiadis, N. (2013) *Cosmopolitanism and Culture*. John Wiley & Sons.

Paris, C.M. and Teye, V. (2010) 'Backpacker Motivations: A Travel Career Approach', *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 19(3), pp. 244–259. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19368621003591350>.

Pashaki, A.M.N., Shahri, A.R.H. and Seedighi, K. (2016) 'Semiotics in Haroun Hashem Rashid Lyrics Relying on the Theory of Pierce', *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 6(7), p. 31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijel.v6n7p31>.

Patton, M.Q. (2015) *Qualitative research & evaluation methods: integrating theory and practice*. Fourth edition. Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications, Inc.

Pearce, P.L. (1993) 'Fundamentals of tourist motivation', *Tourism research: Critiques and challenges*, pp. 113–134.

Pennington-Gray, L. *et al.* (2011) 'Crisis Planning and Preparedness in the United States Tourism Industry', *Cornell Hospitality Quarterly*, 52(3), pp. 312–320. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1938965511410866>.

Percy, L. (2008) *Strategic Integrated Marketing Communications*. London: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780080878294>.

Perkins (1896) *South Africa, Wellcome Collection*. Available at: <https://wellcomecollection.org/works/bmxn4wbn> (Accessed: 24 August 2023).

Perkins, K.J. (2007) 'History and the Culture of Nationalism in Algeria: James McDougall', *Digest of Middle East Studies*, 16(1), pp. 155–158. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1949-3606.2007.tb00082.x>.

Pernecky, T. (2012) 'Constructionism', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 39(2), pp. 1116–1137. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2011.12.010>.

Phillips, J. (2008) 'Female Sex Tourism in Barbados: A Postcolonial Perspective', *Brown Journal of World Affairs*, 14, p. 201.

Phillips, N.L., Adams, G. and Salter, P.S. (2015) 'Beyond Adaptation: Decolonizing Approaches to Coping With Oppression', *Journal of Social and Political Psychology*, 3(1), pp. 365–387. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5964/jspp.v3i1.310>.

Piessé, L. (1862) *Itinéraire historique et descriptif de l'Algérie, comprenant le Tell et le Sahara*. Hachette.

Pietkiewicz, I. and Smith, J.A. (2012) 'A Practical Guide to using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis in Qualitative Research Psychology'.

Pink, S. (2009) *Doing Sensory Ethnography*. 1 Oliver's Yard, 55 City Road, London EC1Y 1SP United Kingdom: SAGE Publications Ltd. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446249383>.

Pink, S. (2013) *Doing Visual Ethnography*. SAGE Publications.

Pirzada, K. (2019) 'Sustainable Tourism Development a Basic Factor for Preserving Urban Heritage in Algeria: An Applied Study on the Casbah of Algiers', *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*, 8(1).

Pizam, A., Reichel, A. and Uriely, N. (2001) 'Sensation Seeking and Tourist Behavior', *Journal of Hospitality & Leisure Marketing*, 9(3–4), pp. 17–33. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1300/J150v09n03_03.

Platenkamp, V. and Botterill, D. (2013) 'Critical realism, rationality and tourism knowledge', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 41, pp. 110–129. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2012.12.006>.

Pop, R.-A. *et al.* (2022) 'The impact of social media influencers on travel decisions: the role of trust in consumer decision journey', *Current Issues in Tourism*, 25(5), pp. 823–843. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2021.1895729>.

Porter, B.W. and Salazar, N.B. (2005) 'Heritage tourism, conflict, and the public interest: An introduction', 11(5), pp. 361–370.

Potter, E. (2003) 'Canada and the New Public Diplomacy', *International Journal*, 58(1), pp. 43–64. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/002070200305800103>.

Powell, R.A. and Single, H.M. (1996) 'Focus Groups', *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 8(5), pp. 499–504. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/8.5.499>.

Prashad, V. (2007) *The darker nations: a people's history of the third world*. New York: New Press: Distributed by W.W. Norton (A New Press people's history).

Prendergast, G., Tsang, A. and Chan, C. (2010) 'The interactive influence of country of origin of brand and product involvement on purchase intention', *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 27, pp. 180–188. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/07363761011027277>.

Prentice, R.C., Witt, S.F. and Hamer, C. (1998) 'Tourism as experience: The case of heritage parks', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 25(1), pp. 1–24. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383\(98\)00084-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383(98)00084-X).

Pritchard, A. and Morgan, N. (2007) *De-centring Tourism's Intellectual Universe, or Traversing the Dialogue Between Change and Tradition, The Critical Turn in Tourism Studies*. Routledge, pp. 11–28. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780080470986-3>.

Prochaska, D. (1990) 'Making Algeria French and Unmaking French Algeria', *Journal of Historical Sociology*, 3(4), pp. 305–328. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6443.1990.tb00109.x>.

Prunty, R. (2021) 'The Impact of French Algeria's Participation during the First and Second World Wars on the Algerian Nationalist Movement', 2(1).

Quandt, W.B. (2001) *Between Ballots and Bullets: Algeria's Transition from Authoritarianism*. Brookings Institution Press.

Quinlan Cutler, S. and Carmichael, B. (2010) 'The dimensions of the tourist experience', in *The Tourism and Leisure Experience*, pp. 3–26. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781845411503-004>.

Rabiee, F. (2004) 'Focus-group interview and data analysis', *Proceedings of the Nutrition Society*, 63(4), pp. 655–660. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS2004399>.

Rahal, W., Rezzaz, M.A. and Kherrou, L. (2020) 'THE PRESERVATION OF WORLD ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITES AND PROMOTION OF TOURISM: QALA'AT BANI HAMMAD (M'SILA) ALGERIA', *GeoJournal of Tourism and Geosites*, 33(4), pp. 1571–1578. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.30892/gtg.334spl19-610>.

Raina, A.K. and Agarwal, S.K. (2004) *The essence of tourism development: dynamics, philosophy, and strategies*. Sarup & Sons.

Rao, N. (2000) "'Neocolonialism" or "Globalization"?: Postcolonial Theory and the Demands of Political Economy', *Interdisciplinary Literary Studies*, 1(2), pp. 165–184.

Ravi, S. (2011) 'Engaging the Postcolonial: Terrorism, Tourism, and Literary Cosmopolitanism in the Twenty-First Century', *International Journal of Canadian Studies*, (44), p. 215. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7202/1010089ar>.

Rebhi, A. (2013) 'Sustainability in Algeria', *AlMi'yar*, 8.

Regan, P. (2010) *Unsettling the settler within: Indian residential schools, truth telling, and reconciliation in Canada*. Vancouver: UBC Press.

Rehman Khan, S.A.R. *et al.* (2017) 'Travel and tourism competitiveness index: The impact of air transportation, railways transportation, travel and transport services on

international inbound and outbound tourism’, *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 58, pp. 125–134. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jairtraman.2016.10.006>.

Reid, A.-M. *et al.* (2018) ‘Ethical dilemmas and reflexivity in qualitative research’, *Perspectives on Medical Education*, 7(2), pp. 69–75. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/S40037-018-0412-2>.

van Rensburg, M.J. (2014) ‘Relevance of travel agencies in the digital age’, 3.

Reyes, G.E. (2001) ‘Four main theories of development’: Available at: <http://localhost:8080/xmlui/handle/123456789/285> (Accessed: 23 August 2023).

Richards, G. (1996) ‘Cultural Tourism in Europe’, *CAB International* [Preprint].

Richards, G. (1999) ‘Culture, Cultural Tourism and Identity’, p. 12.

Richards, G. (2001) ‘The development of cultural tourism in Europe.’, in G. Richards (ed.) *Cultural attractions and European tourism*. 1st edn. UK: CABI Publishing, pp. 3–29. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1079/9780851994406.0003>.

Richards, G. (2018) ‘Cultural tourism: A review of recent research and trends’, *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 36, pp. 12–21. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhtm.2018.03.005>.

Richerson, P.J. and Boyd, R. (2005) *Not by genes alone: How culture transformed human evolution*. University of Chicago Press.

Rickly-Boyd, J.M. (2013) ‘Existential Authenticity: Place Matters’, *Tourism Geographies*, 15(4), pp. 680–686. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616688.2012.762691>.

Ritchie, J. *et al.* (2013) *Qualitative Research Practice: A Guide for Social Science Students and Researchers*. SAGE.

Rocherieux, J. (2001) ‘L’évolution de l’Algérie depuis l’indépendance’, *Sud/Nord*, 14(1), pp. 27–50. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3917/sn.014.0027>.

Rodney, W. (1974) 'Interviews: Walter Rodney', *The Black Scholar*, 6(3), pp. 38–47. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00064246.1974.11431475>.

Rolland, G. (1889) *La conquête du désert, Biskra - Touggourt, l'Oued Rir*. Challamel.

Roy, B.K. (2017) *Cultural Identity and Third Space: An Exploration of their Connection in a Title I School*.

Rukundwa, L.S. and Van Aarde, A.G. (2007) 'The formation of postcolonial theory', *HTS Teologiese Studies / Theological Studies*, 63(3), pp. 1171--1194. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v63i3.237>.

Rushdie, S. (1991) *Imaginary homelands: essays and criticism 1981-1991*. London: Vintage Books.

Rutherford, J. (1990) *Identity: Community, Culture, Difference*. London: Lawrence & Wishart. Available at: https://muse.jhu.edu/pub/248/edited_volume/book/34784 (Accessed: 22 August 2023).

Ryan, C. and Glendon, I. (1998) 'Application of leisure motivation scale to tourism', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 25(1), pp. 169–184. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383\(97\)00066-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383(97)00066-2).

Ryan, F., Coughlan, M. and Cronin, P. (2009) 'Interviewing in qualitative research: The one-to-one interview', *International Journal of Therapy and Rehabilitation*, 16(6), pp. 309–314. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/ijtr.2009.16.6.42433>.

Saad Allah, A.A. (2009) *Algeria's Cultural History Part Two*. Islamic West House. Available at: <https://www.noor-book.com/en/ebook--ابو-القاسم-ل-ال-الثاني-الجزء-الثقافي-الجزائر-التاريخ-الجزائر-الثقافي-الجزء-الثاني-ل-ابو-القاسم--pdf> (Accessed: 27 August 2023).

Sääksjärvi, M., Hellén, K. and Balabanis, G. (2016) 'Sometimes a celebrity holding a negative public image is the best product endorser', *European Journal of Marketing*, 50(3/4), pp. 421–441. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJM-06-2014-0346>.

Sabi, A. (2015) *Three Reasons behind Algeria's Stagnant Tourism Industry*. Available at: <https://globalriskinsights.com/2015/11/three-reasons-behind-algerias-stagnant-industry/>.

Sacks, J. (2021) 'Fanon's insurgence', *Postcolonial Studies*, 24(2), pp. 234–250. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13688790.2020.1752248>.

Sadaoui, F. and Kheniche, Y. (2019) 'Le Secteur Touristique en Algérie'

Sahel, M. (2017) 'The Algerian Post-Independence Linguistic Policy - a Recovery of National Identity', *European Journal of Language and Literature*, 8(1), p. 38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.26417/ejls.v8i1.p38-43>.

Sahlins, M. (1976) *Culture and Practical Reason*. University of Chicago Press.

Sahnouni, M. (1998) 'The Site of Ain Hanech Revisited: New Investigations at this Lower Pleistocene Site in Northern Algeria', (25), pp. 1083–1101.

Said, E. (1978) *Orientalism*. New York: Pantheon.

Said, E. (1999) 'The One-State Solution', *The New York Times*, 10 January. Available at: <https://www.nytimes.com/1999/01/10/magazine/the-one-state-solution.html> (Accessed: 27 August 2023).

Said, E.W. (2003) *Orientalism*. New preface edition. London: Penguin (Penguin classics).

Sajed, A. (2023) 'Between Algeria and the world: anticolonial connectivity, aporias of national liberation and postcolonial blues', *Postcolonial Studies*, 26(1), pp. 13–31. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13688790.2023.2127655>.

Salazar, N.B. (2012) 'Tourism Imaginaries: A Conceptual Approach', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 39(2), pp. 863–882. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2011.10.004>.

Salhi, H. (2007) 'History and the Culture of Nationalism in Algeria', *Middle East Policy*, 14(4), p. 186+.

Sattar, Z., Hannam, K. and Ali, N. (2013) 'Religious obligations to travel: first-generation Pakistani migrants from Newcastle-upon-Tyne', *Journal of Tourism and Cultural Change*, 11(1–2), pp. 61–72. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14766825.2013.795963>.

Scagnetti, J.-C. (2003) 'Identité ou personnalité algérienne? L'édification d'une algérianité (1962-1988)', *Cahiers de la Méditerranée*, (66), pp. 367–384. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4000/cdlm.113>.

Scheffel, R.L. and Wernert, S.J. (1980) *Reader's Digest natural wonders of the world*. Edited by Reader's Digest Association. Pleasantville, N.Y: Reader's Digest Association.

Schein, E.H. (1993) 'On dialogue, culture, and organizational learning', *Organizational Dynamics*, p. 40+.

Scheyvens, R. (2011) 'The challenge of sustainable tourism development in the Maldives: Understanding the social and political dimensions of sustainability: Tourism development in the Maldives', *Asia Pacific Viewpoint*, 52(2), pp. 148–164. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8373.2011.01447.x>.

Schnettler, B. and Raab, J. (2009) 'Interpretative Visual Analysis Developments: State of the Art and Pending Problems', *Historical Social Research / Historische Sozialforschung*, 34(2 (128)), pp. 265–295.

Schulhofer-Wohl, S. (2007) *Heterogeneity, Risk Sharing and the Welfare Costs of Risk*. 2007 Meeting Papers 926. Society for Economic Dynamics. Available at: <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:red:sed007:926>.

Schwartz, B. (1989) *Psychology of learning and behavior*, 3rd ed. New York, NY, US: W Norton & Co (Psychology of learning and behavior, 3rd ed), pp. xvii, 379.

Shaw, G. and Williams, A.M. (1994) 'Critical issues in tourism: a geographical perspective.', *Critical issues in tourism: a geographical perspective*. [Preprint]. Available at: <https://www.cabdirect.org/cabdirect/abstract/19941805547> (Accessed: 24 August 2023).

Shepard, T. (2013) 'Algerian Nationalism, Zionism, and French Laïcité: A History of Ethnoreligious Nationalisms and Decolonization', *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, 45(3), pp. 445–467.

Shifflet, D.K. (1999) 'Pennsylvania Heritage Tourism Study'.

Silberberg, T. (1995) 'Cultural tourism and business opportunities for museums and heritage sites', *Tourism Management*, 16(5), pp. 361–365. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0261-5177\(95\)00039-Q](https://doi.org/10.1016/0261-5177(95)00039-Q).

Silverstein, P. and Crawford, D. (2004) 'Amazigh Activism and the Moroccan State', *Middle East Report*, (233), pp. 44–48. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1559451>.

Sinamai, A. (2020) "'We are Still Here": African Heritage, Diversity and the Global Heritage Knowledge Templates', *Archaeologies*, 16(1), pp. 57–71. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11759-020-09389-5>.

Sinclair, J.M. (ed.) (1999) *Collins English dictionary*. 4th ed., repr. Glasgow: HarperCollins [u.a.].

Singh, A. and Schmidt, P. (2000) *Postcolonial Theory and the United States: Race, Ethnicity, and Literature*. Univ. Press of Mississippi.

Slemon, Stephen (1995) 'Afterword: the English side of the lawn - ProQuest', (56), pp. 274–286.

Slimani-Direche, K. (1997) *Histoire de l'émigration kabyle en France au XXe siècle: réalités culturelles et politiques et réappropriations identitaires*. Harmattan.

Smallwood, R. *et al.* (2021) 'Understanding the Impact of Historical Trauma Due to Colonization on the Health and Well-Being of Indigenous Young Peoples: A Systematic Scoping Review', *Journal of Transcultural Nursing*, 32(1), pp. 59–68. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1043659620935955>.

Smith, A.D. (1991) 'The Nation: Invented, Imagined, Reconstructed?', *Millennium: Journal of International Studies*, 20(3), pp. 353–368. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/03058298910200031001>.

Smith, A.D. (2005) 'Nationalism in Early Modern Europe', *History and Theory*. Edited by A.W. Marx, 44(3), pp. 404–415.

Smith, D. (2002) 'Framing the national question in Central and Eastern Europe: A quadratic nexus?', *Global Review of Ethnopolitics*, 2. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14718800208405119>.

Smith, E.M.J. (1985) 'Ethnic Minorities: Life Stress, Social Support, and Mental Health Issues', *The Counseling Psychologist*, 13(4), pp. 537–579. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0011000085134002>.

Smith, J.A. and Dunworth, F. (2003) 'Qualitative methods in the study of development', in. Available at: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Qualitative-methods-in-the-study-of-development-Smith-Dunworth/d551cff0778372edd91b4863d6fb9901cd1bdfd3> (Accessed: 25 August 2023).

Smith, J.A., Flowers, P. and Larkin, M. (2009) *Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis: Theory, Method, and Research*. SAGE.

Smith, J.A. and Osborn, M. (2008) 'Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis', *Qualitative Psychology* [Preprint].

Smith, M.K. and Richards, G. (eds) (2017) *The Routledge handbook of cultural tourism*. First issued in paperback. London New York: Routledge (Routledge handbooks).

Soares, J.C., Domareski Ruiz, T.C. and Ivars Baidal, J.A. (2021) 'Smart destinations: a new planning and management approach?', *Current Issues in Tourism*, 25(17), pp. 2717–2732. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2021.1991897>.

Solis, B. (2015) 'Why The Future of Influencer Marketing Starts With People And Relationships Not Popularity.'

Spencer-Oatey (2012) *What is culture? A compilation of quotations*. GlobalPAD Open House.

Spivak, G.C. (1988) 'Can the Subaltern Speak? (Marxism and the Interpretation of Culture)'. Available at: <https://kinasevych.ca/2015/02/15/spivak-1988-can-the-subaltern-speak-marxism-and-the-interpretation-of-culture/> (Accessed: 13 January 2023).

Spivak, G.C. (1992) 'Teaching for the Times', p. 11.

Spivak, G.C. (1995) 'Supplementing Marxism', in *Whither Marxism?* Available at: <https://www.routledge.com/Whither-Marxism-Global-Crises-in-International-Perspective/Magnus-Cullenberg/p/book/9780415910439> (Accessed: 22 August 2023).

Spivak, G.C. (2015) *Can the Subaltern Speak? Colonial Discourse and Post-Colonial Theory*. Routledge, pp. 66–111. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315656496-6>.

Spry, A., Pappu, R. and Bettina Cornwell, T. (2011) 'Celebrity endorsement, brand credibility and brand equity', *European Journal of Marketing*, 45(6), pp. 882–909. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/03090561111119958>.

Stamboulis, Y. and Skayannis, P. (2003) 'Innovation strategies and technology for experience-based tourism', *Tourism Management*, 24(1), pp. 35–43. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177\(02\)00047-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177(02)00047-X).

Starck, K. and Luyt, R. (2019) 'Political Masculinities, Crisis Tendencies, and Social Transition: Toward an Understanding of Change', *Men and Masculinities*, 22(3), pp. 431–443. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1097184X18782730>.

Statista (2022) *Algeria: social media with most users 2022*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1284853/number-of-social-media-users-in-algeria-by-platform/> (Accessed: 25 August 2023).

Stebbins, R.A. (1996) 'Cultural tourism as serious leisure', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 23(4), pp. 948–950. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-7383\(96\)00028-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0160-7383(96)00028-X).

Steele, R. (2017) 'Violence in Algeria: From Colony to Independent Nation', *Student Theses, Papers, and Projects (History)* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://digitalcommons.wou.edu/his/62>.

Stephenson, M.L. and Hughes, H.L. (2005) 'Racialised boundaries in tourism and travel: a case study of the UK black Caribbean community', *Leisure Studies*, 24(2), pp. 137–160. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/0261436052000308811>.

Stewart, E.J. *et al.* (1998) 'The "place" of interpretation: a new approach to the evaluation of interpretation', *Tourism Management*, 19(3), pp. 257–266. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177\(98\)00015-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0261-5177(98)00015-6).

Stock, F. (2009) 'Identity, image and brand: A conceptual framework', *Place Branding and Public Diplomacy*, 5(2), pp. 118–125. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1057/pb.2009.2>.

Stoll, P.-T. and von Hahn, A. (2004) 'Part II: indigenous peoples, indigenous knowledge and indigenous resources in international law', in *Indigenous heritage and intellectual property: genetic resources, traditional knowledge and folklore*. The Hague.

Stone, L.S. (no date) *The Tourist Gaze: Domestic versus International Tourists*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287518781890>.

Stone, L.S. and Nyaupane, G.P. (2019) 'The Tourist Gaze: Domestic versus International Tourists', *Journal of Travel Research*, 58(5), pp. 877–891. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287518781890>.

Stora, B. (1994) 'La guerre d'Algérie quarante ans après: Connaissances et reconnaissance', *Modern & Contemporary France*, 2(2), pp. 131–139. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09639489408456171>.

Stora, B. (2004) *Histoire de l'Algérie depuis l'indépendance - Benjamin Stora - Éditions La Découverte*. Available at: <https://www.editionsladecouverte.fr/histoire-de-l-algerie-depuis-l-independance-9782707144058> (Accessed: 26 December 2022).

Strielkowski, W., Riganti, P. and Wang, J. (2012) 'Tourism, cultural heritage and eservices: Using focus groups to assess consumer preferences', *Tourismos*, 7, pp. 41–59.

Suddaby, R. (2006) 'From the Editors: What Grounded Theory is Not', *Academy of Management Journal*, 49(4), pp. 633–642. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5465/amj.2006.22083020>.

Sullivan, C. and Forrester, M.A. (eds) (2019) *Doing qualitative research in psychology: a practical guide*. 2nd edition. Los Angeles London New Delhi Singapore: Sage.

Swarbrooke, J. (1995) *The Development and Management of Visitor Attractions*. Butterworth-Heinemann.

Sylvester, C. (1999) 'Development studies and postcolonial studies: Disparate tales of the "Third World"', *Third World Quarterly*, 20(4), pp. 703–721. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436599913514>.

Taibi, N.-E. (2016) 'Conflict Between Coastal Tourism Development and Sustainability: case of Mostaganem, Western Algeria', *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 5(4), pp. 13–13. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.14207/ejsd.2016.v5n4p13>.

Taylor, C. (1985) 'Interpretation and the Sciences of Man', *The Review of Metaphysics*, 25(1), pp. 3–51.

Taylor, J., Levi, R. and Dinovitzer, R. (2012) 'HOMELAND TOURISM, EMOTION, AND IDENTITY LABOR', *Du Bois Review: Social Science Research on Race*, 9(1), pp. 67–85. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1742058X12000069>.

Teeroovengadum, V. and Nunkoo, R. (2018) 'Sampling design in tourism and hospitality research', in Nunkoo, R., *Handbook of Research Methods for Tourism and Hospitality Management*. Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 477–488. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781785366284.00048>.

Teo, P. and Leong, S. (2006) 'A postcolonial analysis of backpacking', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 33(1), pp. 109–131. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2005.05.001>.

Terki, L. and Yahyaoui, S. (2019) *Le tourisme dans les espaces de montagne comme vecteur de développement territorial: illustration par une étude comparative entre le cas de Tikjda dans le Parc National du Djurdjura et le Courchevel dans les Alpes*. Mouloud Mammeri.

Thakur, Swati and Thakur, Santosh (2016) 'Reasons Spivak Cites When She says that Subaltern cannot Speak', 7.

The Berbers (no date). Available at: <https://web.archive.org/web/20130819165403/http://al-bab.com/arab/background/berber.htm> (Accessed: 2 May 2023).

The Concise Compendium of the World's Languages. Second Edition (2020). London; New York: Routledge.

The Role of the Tourist Milieu in the Social Construction of the Tourist Experience - ProQuest (no date). Available at: <https://www.proquest.com/openview/207c0f879dc78b2c5ade8ed072d54077/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=2030935> (Accessed: 19 December 2022).

The World Bank (2018) *The World Bank in Algeria*. Text/HTML. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/algeria> (Accessed: 26 August 2023).

Thieux, L. (2020) *Algeria in 2020: A Weakened Power facing a Multidimensional Crisis*.

Thomas, R. (2022) *Identity and Imperialism in Algeria*, Owlcation. Available at: <https://owlcation.com/humanities/Identity-and-Imperialism-in-Algeria> (Accessed: 23 March 2023).

Thomas-Meyer, M., Mytton, O. and Adams, J. (2017) 'Public responses to proposals for a tax on sugar-sweetened beverages: A thematic analysis of online reader comments posted on major UK news websites', *PLOS ONE*. Edited by H. Yi, 12(11), p. e0186750. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0186750>.

Thompson, A. and Fevre, R. (2001) 'The national question: sociological reflections on nation and nationalism', *Nations and Nationalism*, 7(3), pp. 297–315. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/1469-8219.00018>.

Tibi, B. (2009) 'Islam's Predicament with Modernity. Religious Reform and Cultural Change', pp. 1–407. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203881552>.

Tie, C., Holden, A. and Park, H. yu (2015) 'A "reality of return": The case of the Sarawakian-Chinese visiting China', *Tourism Management*, 47, pp. 206–212. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2014.09.021>.

Tilmatine, M. (2016) 'French and Spanish colonial policy in North Africa: revisiting the Kabyle and Berber myth', *International Journal of the Sociology of Language*, 2016(239). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijsl-2016-0006>.

Timothy, D. and Olsen, D. (2006) *Tourism, Religion and Spiritual Journeys*. Routledge.

Timothy, D.J. (1997) 'Tourism and the personal heritage experience', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 24(3), pp. 751–754. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383\(97\)00006-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383(97)00006-6).

Timothy, D.J. and Boyd, S.W. (2003) *Heritage Tourism*.

Tod, A. (2006) 'Interviewing', in K. Gerrish and A. Lacey (eds). Wiley-Blackwell, pp. 337–352. Available at: <http://eu.wiley.com> (Accessed: 25 August 2023).

Torkington, K., Stanford, D. and Guiver, J. (2020) 'Discourse(s) of growth and sustainability in national tourism policy documents', *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 28(7), pp. 1041–1062. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669582.2020.1720695>.

Tourism Set to Return to Pre-Pandemic Levels in Some Regions in 2023 (no date). Available at: <https://www.unwto.org/news/tourism-set-to-return-to-pre-pandemic-levels-in-some-regions-in-2023> (Accessed: 23 January 2023).

Tribe, J. (2009) *Philosophical Issues in Tourism*. Channel View Publications.

Tucker, H. (2016) 'Empathy and tourism: Limits and possibilities', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 57, pp. 31–43. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2015.12.001>.

Tucker, H. and Akama, J. (2009) 'Tourism as postcolonialism', pp. 504–520.

Tuffour, I. (2017) 'A Critical Overview of Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis: A Contemporary Qualitative Research Approach', *Journal of Healthcare Communications*, 02(04). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4172/2472-1654.100093>.

Tuladhar-Douglas, W. and Tuladhar-Douglas, B. (2018) 'Working Together to Carry Water: Research Ethics when One of Two Parents is Indigenous', *Ethnobiology Letters*, 9(1), pp. 44–58. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.14237/ebl.9.1.2018.1064>.

Tung, V.W.S. and Ritchie, J.R.B. (2011) 'Exploring the essence of memorable tourism experiences', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 38(4), pp. 1367–1386. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2011.03.009>.

Turner, D. (2010) 'Qualitative Interview Design: A Practical Guide for Novice Investigators', *The Qualitative Report* [Preprint]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2010.1178>.

Tussyadiah, I.P. and Fesenmaier, D.R. (2008) 'Marketing Places Through First-Person Stories—an Analysis of Pennsylvania Roadtripper Blog', *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 25(3–4), pp. 299–311. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10548400802508358>.

Uk, E.I.U. (1993) 'The market for cultural tourism in Europe.', *Travel & Tourism Analyst*, (No. 6), pp. 30–46.

Understanding the Impact of Historical Trauma Due to Colonization on the Health and Well-Being of Indigenous Young Peoples: A Systematic Scoping Review (no date). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1043659620935955>.

UNSD (2021) *UNSD — Demographic and Social Statistics*. Available at: <https://unstats.un.org/unsd/demographic-social/products/dyb/index.cshtml> (Accessed: 24 August 2023).

UNWTO (2021) *Glossary of tourism terms* | UNWTO. Available at: <https://www.unwto.org/glossary-tourism-terms> (Accessed: 27 July 2023).

Urry, J. (1990) *The Tourist Gaze: Leisure and Travel in Contemporary Societies*. Sage Publications.

Urry, J. (1992) 'The Tourist Gaze "Revisited"', *American Behavioral Scientist*, 36(2), pp. 172–186. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764292036002005>.

Urry, J. and Larsen, J. (2011) *The Tourist Gaze 3.0*. SAGE.

Van Raaij, W.F. (1987) 'Expectations, actual experience, and satisfaction a reply', 1(14), pp. 141–142.

Varisco, D.M. (2017) *Reading Orientalism: Said and the Unsaid*. University of Washington Press.

Veracini, L. (2015) 'Introduction: The Settler Colonial Present', in *The Settler Colonial Present*. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, pp. 1–12. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137372475_1.

Vignoles, V., Schwartz, S. and Luyckx, K. (2011) 'Introduction: Toward an Integrative View of Identity', in, pp. 1–27. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-7988-9_1.

Vignoles, V.L. (2017) 'Identity: Personal AND Social', in.

Vinney, C. *et al.* (2019) 'Development and validation of a measure of popular media fan identity and its relationship to well-being.', *Psychology of Popular Media Culture*, 8(3), pp. 296–307. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1037/ppm0000188>.

Vittersø, J. *et al.* (2000) 'Tourist experiences and attractions', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 27(2), pp. 432–450. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383\(99\)00087-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0160-7383(99)00087-0).

Voase, R. (1995) *Tourism: the human perspective*. London: Hodder & Stoughton.

Vukonić, B. (1996) *Tourism and religion*. 1st ed. New York: Pergamon (Tourism social science series).

Walzer, M. (1995) *Toward a Global Civil Society*. Berghahn Books.

Wanhill, S. (2013) 'THE NATURE AND DEVELOPMENT OF VISITOR ATTRACTIONS', in Tisdell, C. A., *Handbook of Tourism Economics*. WORLD SCIENTIFIC, pp. 259–279. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1142/9789814327084_0012.

Warfa, N. *et al.* (2007) 'Khat use and mental illness: A critical review', *Social Science & Medicine*, 65(2), pp. 309–318. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2007.04.038>.

Watkin, R.O. (2021) *Arthur John Arberry(1905-1969): A Critical Evaluation of an Orientalist*. doctoral. University of Wales Trinity Saint David. Available at: <https://repository.uwtsd.ac.uk/id/eprint/1692/> (Accessed: 22 August 2023).

Wearing, B. and Wearing, S. (1996) 'Refocussing the tourist experience: the flaneur and the choraster', *Leisure Studies*, 15(4), p. 229.

Wearing, S. and McDonald, M. (2002) 'The Development of Community-based Tourism: Re-thinking the Relationship Between Tour Operators and Development Agents as Intermediaries in Rural and Isolated Area Communities', *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 10(3), pp. 191–206. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669580208667162>.

Wearing, S., Stevenson, D. and Young, T. (2009) *Tourist Cultures: Identity, Place, and the Traveller*. SAGE.

Weaver, D. (2010) 'Indigenous tourism stages and their implications for sustainability', *Journal of Sustainable Tourism*, 18(1), pp. 43–60. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09669580903072001>.

Weeden, C. (2005) 'A qualitative approach to the ethical consumer: the use of focus groups for cognitive consumer research in tourism'. Available at: https://www.academia.edu/1365235/Weeden_C_2005_A_qualitative_approach_to_the_ethical_consumer_the_use_of_focus_groups_for_cognitive_consumer_research_in_tourism (Accessed: 25 August 2023).

White, N.R. and White, P.B. (2007) 'Home and away: Tourists in a Connected World', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 34(1), pp. 88–104. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2006.07.001>.

Wideman, J.E. (2008) *Fanon*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.

Williams, D. (1989) *Great expectations and the limits to satisfaction: A review of recreation and consumer satisfaction research, Outdoor Recreation Benchmark 1988: Proceedings of the National Outdoor Recreation Forum*.

Williams, R. and Irving, V. (1998) 'The Politics of Constructionism', *Sage Publications*, pp. 1–256.

Willig, C. (2008) *Introducing qualitative research in psychology: adventures in theory and method*. Second ed. Maidenhead: Open university press.

Willis, K.D. and Yeoh, B.S. (2012) '“Coming to China Changed My Life”: Gender Roles and Relations among Single British Migrants', in *Gender and family among transnational professionals*. Routledge, pp. 211–232.

Wilson, W.J. (1970) 'Revolutionary Nationalism “Versus” Cultural Nationalism Dimensions of the Black Power Movement', *Sociological Focus*, 3(3), pp. 43–51.

Winchester, H.P.M. (2013) *Landscapes: Ways of Imagining the World*. London: Routledge. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315842325>.

Wong, I.A., McKercher, B. and Li, X. (2016) 'East Meets West: Tourist Interest in Hybrid Culture at Postcolonial Destinations', *Journal of Travel Research*, 55(5), pp. 628–642. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047287514563984>.

Woodward, K. (2002) 'Understanding Identity'.

Yansané, A.Y. (ed.) (1980) *Decolonization and dependency: problems of development of African societies*. Westport, Conn: Greenwood Press (Contributions in Afro-American and African studies, no. 48).

Yardley, L. (2000) 'Dilemmas in qualitative health research', *Psychology & Health*, 15(2), pp. 215–228. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08870440008400302>.

Yin, R.K. (2018) *Case study research and applications: design and methods*. Sixth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE.

Yoon, Y. and Uysal, M. (2005). "An examination of the effects of motivation and satisfaction on destination loyalty: a structural model", 26(1), pp. 45–56.

Young, R.J.C. (2005) *Colonial desire: hybridity in theory, culture, and race*. Repr. London: Routledge.

Young, R.J.C. (2016) *Postcolonialism: An Historical Introduction*. John Wiley & Sons.

Young, R.J.C. (2020) *Postcolonialism: A Very Short Introduction*. Oxford University Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/actrade/9780198856832.001.0001>.

Zaei, Mansour and Zaei, Ma (2013) 'The Impacts of Tourism Industry on Host Community', 1, pp. 12–21.

Zeraib, S., Kouba, Y. and Berghout, B. (2022) 'The Influence of Tourism Development Strategies on the Attractiveness of Mountainous Destinations: A Case Study of the Aures Mountains in Algeria', *Sustainability*, 14(20), p. 13045. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142013045>.

Zeraoulia, F. (2020) 'The Memory of the Civil War in Algeria: Lessons from the Past with Reference to the Algerian Hirak', *Contemporary Review of the Middle East*, 7(1), pp. 25–53. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/2347798919889781>.

Zhang, C.X. *et al.* (2019) 'National identity and cultural festivals in postcolonial destinations', *Tourism Management*, 73, pp. 94–104. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2019.01.013>.

Zhang, C.X., L'Espoir Decosta, P. and McKercher, B. (2015) 'Politics and tourism promotion: Hong Kong's myth making', *Annals of Tourism Research*, 54, pp. 156–171. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2015.07.003>.

Zhang, S.-N., Ruan, W.-Q. and Yang, T.-T. (2021) 'National Identity Construction in Cultural and Creative Tourism: The Double Mediators of Implicit Cultural Memory and Explicit Cultural Learning', *SAGE Open*, 11(3), p. 21582440211040789. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211040789>.

Zohra ADDER, F. and Bagui, H. (2020) 'English - Algerian Arabic Code-switching in EFL Classroom: Case of EFL Teachers and Students in the Department of English at Tlemcen University, Algeria', *Arab World English Journal*, 11(4), pp. 144–162. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol11no4.10>.

Zytnicki, C. (2013) '« Faire l'Algérie agréable ». Tourisme et colonisation en Algérie des années 1870 à 1962', *Le Mouvement Social*, 242(1), pp. 97–114. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3917/lms.242.0097>.

Zytnicki, C. (2016) *L'Algérie, terre de tourisme: histoire d'un loisir colonial*. Paris: Vendémiaire (Collection Empires).

'وزارة السياحة والصناعة التقليدية' (no date). Available at: <https://www.mta.gov.dz/> (Accessed: 27 June 2023).

APPENDICES

Appendix.1

Survey posted on Facebook to recruit participants (in Arabic)

دراسة استقصائية

مرحبا ، اسمي ليمان العزوي ، طالبة دكتوراه في جامعة غرب اسكتلندا ببريطانيا. أنا أجري دراسة تركز على السيادة الثقافية في الجزائر وشعبيتها بين السياح الجزائريين. هذه الدراسة هي محاولة أولية لتدعيم اسمك في كلمة المشاركين في مجموعة سياح جزائريين قاطنين لمنطقة ألتيز و آراء حول تجاربكم الشخصية في الاستشف و التحول داخل الوطن. المشاركة سوف تكون عبر منصة Microsoft Teams أو Zoom. ستكون لك كل الحرية في تكميل خصية الصوت و الصورة أو الصوت فقط بمجرد أن تعتزكم مرشحا مثليا . سترسل اليك عبر الايميل استمارة الموافقة واستمارة المعلومات للمشاركة حتى تتمكن من فهم ما تكون حوله هذه الدراسة . وما هو دورك كمشارك.

لکم منی خالص عبارات الشکر و التقدير.

elazzaouimene@gmail.com [Changer de compte](#)

*Obligatoire

Adresse e-mail *

Votre adresse e-mail

الإسم الكامل *

Votre réponse

العمر *

Votre réponse

* أي منصة تفضل استعمالها؟

Microsoft Teams

Zoom

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQL5fW096D-5kxk-jpgCjwUuE27me9PpCOu4mLacQFh071Nw/viewform>

1/3

* هل سالت إلى موقع تراث ثقافي في الجزائر؟ (على سبيل المثال : القصبة ، الالة بني حماد ، جميلة ، تيمقاد)

نعم

لا

* هل ترغب في المشاركة في اجتماع/مناظرة على الإنترنت مع مجموعة من السياح الجزائريين؟

نعم

لا

* إذا أجابت بنعم على السؤال السابق ، الماخذ سيتصل بك عبر البريد الإلكتروني

موافق

غير موافق

Envoyer

Effacer le formulaire

N'envoyez jamais de mots de passe via Google Forms.

Ce contenu n'est ni rédigé, ni cautionné par Google. [Signaler un cas d'utilisation abusive](#) · [Conditions d'utilisation](#) · [Règles de confidentialité](#)

Google Forms

Appendix.2

Participants Information Sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Name of school: School of Business and Creative Industries

Name of Degree: Ph.D. Research

Title of the Project: Rebranding the Culture for Domestic Market; Algeria's Approach to Nation Branding for Tourism.

You are being invited to take part in a research project. Before you decide it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with the researcher if you wish. Ask the researcher if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

Thank you for reading this.

My name is Imene El ~~Azzaoui~~ Azzaoui. I am a Ph.D. student at the University of the West of Scotland. I am currently undertaking a study about the Algerian tourism sector and the authority's use of cultural heritage to promote domestic market.

What is the purpose of the study?

The study aims at collecting information, analysing and interpreting experiences of Algerian tourists previously engaged in a cultural trip within Algeria to understand the emerging trend of domestic tourism, and to investigate the authorities' role in activating the nation branding strategy.

Why should I consider participating?

The participation is voluntary. You are welcomed to participate if you are open to share your opinion and experience of travelling to a cultural site.

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. You can withdraw during the focus group discussion at any time and without giving a reason. The researcher, therefore, will remove any data collected about you from the study. Once the focus group discussions have finished you can still withdraw your data up to the point where the data has been analysed and has become anonymous, so your identity cannot be determined.

Why am I invited to take part?

You have been chosen to take part because you are a local resident and/or a business owner involved in cultural tourism domestically.

What would taking part involve?

Taking part of the investigation will involve answering questions related to tourism situation in Algeria, strategies implied by the tourism sector and opinions regarding cultural tourism. Personal experiences will be asked to be included in the discussion to understand more about your position as a consumer of Destination Marketing Organisation's offers.

What are the advantages and possible disadvantages or risks of taking part?

Recruited participants will not face any disadvantages or danger when contributing in this study. The researcher is abiding confidentiality and ethical considerations to ensure the safety of the participant's self and information.

What type of information will be sought from me and why is the collection of this information relevant for achieving the research project's objectives?

The information sought from you, and all participants, is purely related to your analysis, perspective and opinion regarding the topic under investigation. As this investigation is a

social phenomenon and requires members from the selected case study to take part in, the collection of data from you will help immensely in understanding the cultural tourism aspect directly from the domestic tourist, as you are considered as a consumer of offers provided by the DMO's.

Where the participation is taking place? And for how long?

The participation will be taking place online, via Zoom or Teams (according to your preference). The participation will be for about 1h to 1h30 to allow all recruited participants to discuss and engage in debates and opinions sharing.

Will I be recorded, and how will the recorded media be used?

For research purposes, you will be recorded. The audio recordings of your speech made during this research will be used solely for analysis and the transcription of the recording(s) for illustration in the researcher's dissertation. No other use will be made of them without your written permission, and no one outside the project will be allowed access to the original recordings.

How will my information be kept?

All the information to be collected about you during the focus group discussions will be kept strictly in accordance with UWS ethics and regulations. You will not be identified in any reports or publications without your specific consent. Your identity will be anonymised immediately after the data collection.

Only the researcher, and the supervisory team (Dr. Sandro Carnicelli and Dr. Masood Khodadadi), will have access to your data that will be used in accordance with ethical considerations of UWS. Personal data will be stored solely and securely at the possession of the researcher, and will be destroyed immediately after the dissertation final results.

Contact for further information

If you have any questions or would like further information, please contact the researcher

If you have any complaint about the researcher's behaviour, a misconduct of questions, or an issue to raise when conducting the focus group/interview, feel free to contact the researcher's supervisor via email;

Finally

If you decide to take part, you will be given a copy of the consent form signed by the researcher as a record.

Thank you.

Appendix.3

Consent form

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST of SCOTLAND

Participant Consent Form

Title of the Study: Rebranding the culture for domestic market; Algeria's approach to nation branding for tourism.

Researcher's contact details: Imene El Azzaoui
University of the West of Scotland

- I..... voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.
- I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.
- I understand that I can withdraw permission to use data from my interview within two weeks after the interview, in which case the material will be deleted.
- I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.
- I understand that participation involves providing personal details and experiences.
- I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research.
- I agree to my interview being audio-recorded.
- I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.
- I understand that in any report on the results of this research my identity will remain anonymous. This will be done by changing my name and disguising any details of my interview which may reveal my identity or the identity of people I speak about.
- I understand that disguised extracts from my interview may be quoted in the researcher's dissertation.
- I understand that if I inform the researcher that myself or someone else is at risk of harm, they may have to report this to the relevant authorities - they will discuss this with me first but may be required to report with or without my permission.

- I understand that signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be retained with the researcher's possession until the exam board confirms the results of their dissertation.
- I understand that a transcript of my interview in which all identifying information has been removed will be retained for two years from the date of the exam board.
- I understand that under freedom of information legislation I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.
- I understand that I am free to contact any of the people involved in the research to seek further clarification and information.

Signature of research participant

Signature of participant Date

Signature of researcher

I believe the participant is giving informed consent to participate in this study

Signature of researcher Date

Appendix.4

A screenshot of the message sent to one travel agency via Messenger for interview recruitment.

Appendix.5

Notes from Focus Group Discussions and follow-up interviews with Algerian tourists.

key points:

difficulty defining identity } all
participants

no clear boundaries to national identity

colonial legacy → within identity
↓
in tourism

Appendix.6

A sample of an interview transcript with notes

Interview #1

Question 1: as a travel agency taking part in the annual tourism exhibition, what are your thoughts regarding tourism in Algeria?

Answer1: it's a crucial sector that needs to be taken care of if we want more international exposure. We still have more to do to compete with neighbouring countries but we're on the way. Political reforms and issues have raised since the 2019 revolution. Many projects have been slowed down or postponed, a stage of instability emerged because of infinite flaws to the whole governmental system, and the pandemic that cost us agencies a significant financial harm. However, the infrastructure is promisingly growing, we witnessed the growth in the industry in the previous 10 years, more hotels were and are been built, leisure and attraction parks, public transportations and roads constructions, more interest to travel from locals...etc

Question 2: these constructions are based upon a nation branding strategy that was initiated in 2008, do you have an idea concerning such strategy?

Answer2: yes, I remember receiving a note from the tourism ministry regarding this strategy. I personally think it misses many important elements; the focus of the strategy is primarily on building the sector for international tourists, though it's a great initiative yet there's no focus on having representatives of the Algerian tourism sector abroad to promote the country, so how would the foreigners be interested in coming to Algeria if they do not know anything about it? For example, my agency is the first intermediate for Algerians wanting to travel within Algeria or travel abroad, but I don't bring foreign tourists to Algeria because we don't have the facility or way to do so. The Algerian tourism ministry have few representatives attending international conferences and exhibitions in Europe, but there is no clear construction or strategy to successfully represent the country.

Question 3: so according to you, these exhibitions are crucial spots to bring businesses together and collaborate?

Answer3: yes, and since the Algerian travel agencies cannot attend these conferences and exhibitions, the local exhibitions are our only way to introduce our services to the domestic market, and to collaborate with foreign agencies and businesses that are present. That's why I take part in the Annual Exhibition of Oran, and Tourism Exhibition in Algiers, and honestly, I

elazzaouiimene@gmail.com ... ✎ 📎
SLOW PROGRESS IN SECTOR DEVELOPMENT
Reply

elazzaouiimene@gmail.com ... ✎ 📎
OPINIONS REGARDING NATION BRANDING
REGULATIONS
LACK OF REPRESENTATION OF ALGERIA'S IMAGE
ABROAD
Reply

elazzaouiimene@gmail.com ... ✎ 📎
AGENCIES' ONLY OPPORTUNITY TO PROVIDE
OFFERS TO DOMESTIC MARKET IS THE EXHIBITIONS
Reply

managed to secure a well-established reputation among my clients and the exhibitions' visitors. I gained more exposure locally. I worked with few businesses from Morocco, Emirates, Tunisia and established deals with hotels and airlines with whom I create an offer for my clients.

Question4: through your participation as an exhibitor, how would you evaluate the visitors' perception of your offers?

Answer4: I would say mostly positive. I try to accommodate to the clients' needs and serve what they wish. It is important to provide offers for everyone. My agency is flexible, I take the visitors' opinions and preferences very seriously. If a client wants me to arrange a certain trip with specific conditions, I happily do it. As a result, most of my regular clients I initially met at the exhibitions and they continued to purchase my offers for years.

Question 5: which of your offers you noticed are preferred by the exhibitions' visitors? Do you receive requests for domestic or international travel?

Answer5: it depends on the clients and what they prefer. In the previous editions, visitors were more interested in travelling abroad specifically to Saudi Arabia during pilgrimage season, or Tunisia, Morocco and France for leisure and holidays. Mostly because of prices that were low and lack of services locally. But in the last 3 years, there has been a remarkable interest to domestic travel especially since international travel is banned at the moment. I had many requests for southern destinations during the cultural festivals of the new years and spring break. Currently I have 2 offers for the upcoming spring break to ~~QuesSouf~~ **QuesSouf** where the visit will focus on exploring the old city, visiting shops that create and sell traditional arts and crafts, tasting local dishes, camels' riding and driving quads in the desert, visiting oases...etc.

Question 6: I get from your answer that you are focusing on the cultural aspects of the destination to construct your offers?

Answer6: yes, all my domestic offers focus on including the destination's culture. It is rare that I get requests for hotels' booking only with no leisure or activities, and these requests come mostly from clients wanting to go to the destination for business purposes and not tourism.

Question7: how do you advertise for your domestic offers?

Appendix.7

Few questions prepared for the semi-structured interviews.

Appendix.8

Images used for Photo-Elicitation Interviewing

The Martyrs Monument (Picture taken by an Algerian travel content creator)

Santa Cruz Fort in Oran, Algeria. (Picture taken by an Algerian travel content creator)

Timgad Roman Ruins in Batna, Algeria. (Picture taken by an Algerian travel content creator)

Emir Abdelkader Mosque in Constantine, Algeria (Picture taken by a photographer)

Ketchaoua Mosque in Algiers, Algeria (Picture taken by a photographer)

La Grande Poste d'Alger in Algiers, Algeria (Picture taken by an Algerian travel content creator)

French residential building renovated by Algeria' Ministry of Culture in Oran, Algeria (Picture taken by a Algerian tourist and posted on an Instagram page)

.All content redacted due to copyright restrictions

Appendix.9

A timeline of chronological succession of civilisations' presence in Algeria

Appendix.10

A timeline of major nationalism dates in the MENA region

Appendix.11

A table indicating the emergence of themes from the data

Main themes	Subthemes	Initial codes
Encountering identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourists travel to learn about identity • Tourists search for their identity within local communities • Tourists learn about similarities and differences of their identity and host communities' • Tourists face difficulties describing their identity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traveling to local communities • Talk to locals about their culture • Similarities to host communities • Sense of loss • Difficulty understanding one's identity
Challenging postcolonial identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourists are aware of postcolonial effects on their identity • Tourists question the postcolonial influence on their identity • Tourists attempt to acknowledge their postcolonial identity • Tourists' ethnicity vs. identity dilemma • Tourists facing socio-economic challenges • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness • Questioning self • Debating postcolonialism • Complex barriers • Safety • Travelling comfortably
Reconstructing cultural disparity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourists recognise cultural diversity • Tourists learn about their identity through cultural diversity • Tourists celebrate cultural diversity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural divergence • Cultural recognition • Importance of culture • Domestic tourists' motivations • Tourists' embodiment
Decolonising identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agencies notice tourists preferences of culture • Agencies reflect postcolonial Algerian identity • Agencies and travel content creators decolonise their narrative through social media • Agencies and travel content creators celebrate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shifting from French to nationalist narrative • Culture is preferred • Promoting indigenous culture • French legacy • Prioritising originality

	indigeneity and postcolonial national identity	
Experiencing decolonised identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourists' experiences with social media travel content • Tourists positive experiences with decolonised identity • Tourists perception and thoughts about indigenous identity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decolonised identity on social media • Experiences with postcolonial Algerian identity • Hybridity • Recognition • satisfaction